

Selfie Numbers With Binomial Coefficients and Fibonacci Numbers

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

By *selfie numbers*, we understand that the numbers represented by their own digits by use of certain operations, such as, **basic operations, factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence, Triangular numbers**, etc. These are by use of single variable. In two variables, worked with **binomial coefficients type selfie numbers**. This paper brings combine results by use of **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers and Fibonacci sequence values**. This is done by use of **basic operations, factorial, and square-root**. The work is in **digit's order and in reverse order of digits**.

Contents

1 Introduction	2
1.1 Selfie Numbers with Factorial	2
1.2 Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root	3
1.3 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence	3
1.4 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients	4
2 Binomial Coefficients Fibonacci Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order	4
2.1 Basic Operations	5
2.1.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	5
2.1.2 Non Symmetric and Consecutive	7
2.2 Factorial	17
2.2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	17
2.2.2 Non Symmetric and Consecutive	22
2.3 Square-Root	51
2.3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	51
2.3.2 Non Symmetric and Consecutive	51
2.4 Factorial and Square-Root Together	58
2.4.1 Symmetric Representations	58
2.4.2 Non Symmetric Representations	59

¹Formerly, Professor of Mathematics, Universidade Federal de Santa Catarina, Florianópolis, SC, Brazil (1978-2012). Also worked at Delhi University, India (1976-1978).

E-mail: ijjtaneja@gmail.com; **Web-sites:** <http://inderjtaneja.com>;

Twitter: @IJTANEJA; **Instagram:** @crazynumbers.

3 Binomial Coefficients Fibonacci Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits	65
3.1 Basic Operations	65
3.1.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	65
3.2 Symmetric and Non Consecutive	67
3.2.1 Non Symmetric Representations	67
3.3 Factorial	79
3.3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	79
3.3.2 Non Symmetric Representations	84
3.4 Square-Root	116
3.4.1 Symmetric and Consecutive	116
3.5 Symmetric and Nonconsecutive	118
3.5.1 Non Symmetric Representations	118
3.6 Factorial and Square-Root Together	126
3.6.1 Symmetric Representations	127
3.6.2 Non Symmetric Representations	130
4 Summary: Selfie Numbers	134
4.1 Permutable Powers	135
4.2 Basic Operations	135
4.3 Factorial	136
4.4 Square-Root	137
4.5 Factorial and Square-Root	137
4.6 Fibonacci Sequence	138
4.7 Triangular Numbers	140
4.8 Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Numbers	140
4.9 Binomial Coefficients	142
4.10 S-gonal numbers	143
4.11 Centered Polygonal Numbers	144
4.12 Quadratic-Type Selfies	145
4.13 Cubic-Type Selfies	145

1 Introduction

Recently, author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4], i.e., the numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Subsections below give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **binomial coefficients**, etc. are also given.

1.1 Selfie Numbers with Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial. See below some examples:

$$145 := 1! + 4! + 5!$$

$$733 := 7 + 3!! + 3!$$

$$5177 := 5! + 17 + 7!$$

$$363239 := 36 + 323 + 9!$$

$$363269 := 363 + 26 + 9!$$

$$403199 := 40319 + 9!$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 1463 &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & 361469 &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9!. \\
 10077 &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7!. & 364292 &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2!. \\
 40585 &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5!. & 397584 &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4!. \\
 80518 &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8!. & 398173 &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3!. \\
 317489 &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9!. & 408937 &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7!. \\
 352797 &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7!. & 715799 &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9!. \\
 357592 &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2!. & 720599 &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9!. \\
 357941 &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1!. & &
 \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [17, 21, 28].

1.2 Selfie Numbers with Factorial and Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of factorial and/or square-root. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned}
 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! & = 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\
 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9/6} & = 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\
 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) & = (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\
 331779 &:= 3 + (31 - 7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} & = \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\
 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 & = -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\
 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 & = (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9}-5+7}. \\
 759381 &:= 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 & = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.
 \end{aligned}$$

Examples given above are with **factorial** and **square-root** [17, 21, 28]. First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**.

1.3 Selfie Numbers with Fibonacci Sequence

The examples given in subsections, 4.3 and 4.4 are with **factorial** and **square-root**. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Fibonacci sequence** values. See below:

$$\begin{aligned}
 235 &:= 2 + F(F(F(3) + 5)) & 63 &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 256 &:= 2^5 \times F(6) & 882 &:= 2 \times F(8) \times F(8) \\
 4427 &:= (F(4) + 4^2) \times F(F(7)) & 1631 &:= F(13) \times (6 + 1) \\
 46493 &:= F(4 \times 6) + (-4 + 9)^3. & 54128 &:= 8 \times (F(2) + F(1 \times 4 \times 5)).
 \end{aligned}$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [28, 29].

1.4 Selfie Numbers with Binomial Coefficients

The examples given in subsection 1.3 are with **Fibonacci sequence**. Still, one can have similar kind of examples, using **Binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order** and **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3+5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4}+6) \\ 15504 &:= C(15+5, 0!+4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\ 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05+24) \\ 54264 &:= C(5+4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4!-6/2, (\sqrt{4}+5)!) \\ 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4-6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3!+16, (-4+7)!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 12650 &:= C(-1+26, 5-0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\ 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7+0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\ 14950 &:= C(-1+4!+\sqrt{9}, 5-0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\ 18564 &:= C(18, (5-6+4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2+(0 \times 2)!) \\ 19448 &:= C(19-\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4}+8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8-4) \\ 26334 &:= C(2+C(6, 3), 3+\sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0!+0!) \\ 43758 &:= C(4!-3!, 7-5+8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7-0!-0!) \\ 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3!-0!) & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0!+0!)). \end{aligned}$$

The symbol C used for binomial coefficients is given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

For more details refer author's work [19, 20, 27]. Also refer [5, 13] for historical books on numbers. Some initial study on **selfie numbers** are given in [6, 7, 8, 9], and for extensions refer [2, 3, 4]. The last Section 4 is dedicated to the summary of **selfie numbers** done by author with different functions.

The aim of this paper is to bring **selfie numbers** by simultaneous use of **binomial coefficients** and **Fibonacci sequence** values. This we have done in three parts. One is by use of **basic operations**, second by use of **factorial** and third by use of **square-root**. Few results are also given when we have **factorial square-root** together. It is done in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**.

Remark 1.1. *Most of the selfie numbers appearing in sections below are with lot of extra brackets "...". These can be removed easily after making simplifications.*

2 Binomial Coefficients Fibonacci Type Selfie Numbers: Digit's Order

This section brings **selfie numbers** with **Binomial Coefficients** and **Fibonacci sequence** values simultaneously. Results are in terms of digit's order in four different situations. First only with **basic operations**. Secondly, with use of **factorial**. Thirdly, by use of **square-root**. Forth way is when **factorial square-root** are together. The results are up to 5-digits numbers.

Remark 2.1. *In some cases, we don't need to write in terms of "C". The numbers can be written directly. See below:*

$$C(n, 1) := n \times 1;$$

$$C(n, n) := n/n.$$

For example, $C(8, 1) = 8 \times 1$ and $C(5, 5) := 5/5$. We kept them as they appeared in calculations.

2.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers** just with basic operations. The results are in terms of digit's order. The work is up to 6 digits. This subsection is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10 or 100. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

2.1.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$33650 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 0$$

$$33651 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 1$$

$$33652 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 2$$

$$33653 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 3$$

$$33654 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 4$$

$$33655 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 5$$

$$33656 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 6$$

$$33657 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 7$$

$$33658 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 8$$

$$33659 := F(F(3)) + C(F(3) + F(F(6)), 5) + 9$$

$$38760 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 0$$

$$38761 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 1$$

$$38762 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 2$$

$$38763 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 3$$

$$38764 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 4$$

$$38765 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 5$$

$$38766 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 6$$

$$38767 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 7$$

$$38768 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 8$$

$$38769 := F(3) \times C(F(8), 7) / 6 + 9$$

$$48620 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 0$$

$$48621 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 1$$

$$48622 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 2$$

$$48623 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 3$$

$$48624 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 4$$

$$48625 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 5$$

$$48626 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 6$$

$$48627 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 7$$

$$48628 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 8$$

$$48629 := C(-4 + F(8), F(6)) \times 2 + 9$$

$$54730 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 0$$

$$54731 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 1$$

$$54732 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 2$$

$$54733 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 3$$

$$54734 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 4$$

$$54735 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 5$$

$$54736 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 6$$

$$54737 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 7$$

$$54738 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 8$$

$$54739 := C(5, 4) \times F(7 \times 3) + 9$$

$$54750 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 0$$

$$54751 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 1$$

$$54752 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 2$$

$$54753 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 3$$

$$54754 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 4$$

$$54755 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 5$$

$$54756 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 6$$

$$54757 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 7$$

$$54758 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 8$$

$$54759 := 5 \times (4 + F(C(7, 5))) + 9$$

$$65480 := -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 0$$

$$65481 := -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 1$$

$$65482 := -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 2$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65483 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 3 \\
 65484 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 4 \\
 65485 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 5 \\
 65486 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 6 \\
 65487 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 7 \\
 65488 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 7 \\
 65489 &:= -C(F(6), 5) + 4^8 + 9 \\
 \\
 65780 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 0 \\
 65781 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 1 \\
 65782 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 2 \\
 65783 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 3 \\
 65784 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 4 \\
 65785 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 5 \\
 65786 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 6 \\
 65787 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 7 \\
 65788 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 8 \\
 65789 &:= C(F(6) + 5 + F(7), F(8)) + 9 \\
 \\
 67830 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 0 \\
 67831 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 1 \\
 67832 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 2 \\
 67833 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 3 \\
 67834 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 4 \\
 67835 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 5 \\
 67836 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 6 \\
 67837 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 7 \\
 67838 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 8 \\
 67839 &:= C(F(6) + F(7), 8) / 3 + 9 \\
 \\
 74990 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 0 \\
 74991 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 1 \\
 74992 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 2 \\
 74993 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 3 \\
 74994 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 4 \\
 74995 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 5 \\
 74996 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 6 \\
 74997 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 7 \\
 74998 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 8 \\
 74999 &:= -C(7, 4) + F(F(9) - 9) + 9 \\
 \\
 76580 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 0 \\
 76581 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 1 \\
 \\
 76582 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 2 \\
 76583 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 3 \\
 76584 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 4 \\
 76585 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 5 \\
 76586 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 6 \\
 76587 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 7 \\
 76588 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 8 \\
 76589 &:= 7 \times (-C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) + 9 \\
 \\
 77520 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 0 \\
 77521 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 1 \\
 77522 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 2 \\
 77523 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 3 \\
 77524 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 4 \\
 77525 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 5 \\
 77526 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 6 \\
 77527 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 7 \\
 77528 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 8 \\
 77529 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5 + 2) + 9 \\
 \\
 83790 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 0 \\
 83791 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 1 \\
 83792 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 2 \\
 83793 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 3 \\
 83794 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 4 \\
 83795 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 5 \\
 83796 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 6 \\
 83797 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 7 \\
 83798 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 8 \\
 83799 &:= C(F(8), 3) \times 7 \times 9 + 9 \\
 \\
 87560 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 0 \\
 87561 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 1 \\
 87562 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 2 \\
 87563 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 3 \\
 87564 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 4 \\
 87565 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 5 \\
 87566 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 6 \\
 87567 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 7 \\
 87568 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 8 \\
 87569 &:= 8 \times F(C(7, 5)) - F(6) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

2.1.2 Non Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 715 &:= C(F(7), -1 + 5) & 6773 &:= F(6) + F(C(-7 + F(7), 3)) \\
 749 &:= C(F(7), 4) + F(9) & 6783 &:= C(F(F(6)), F(7) - 8) / 3 \\
 987 &:= F(C(9, 8) + 7) & 6799 &:= F(C(6, F(F(7) - 9))) + F(9) \\
 1165 &:= F(F(C(1, 1) + 6)) \times 5 & 6864 &:= C(-F(6) + F(8), 6) \times 4 \\
 1275 &:= -12 + C(F(7), 5) & 7464 &:= F(F(7)) \times F(4) + F(C(6, F(4))) \\
 1286 &:= -1 + C(F(-F(2) + 8), F(6)) & 7752 &:= C(F(7) + 7, 5) / 2 \\
 1288 &:= 1 + C(F(-F(2) + 8), 8) & 7848 &:= C(F(7), 8) + F(4)^8 \\
 1296 &:= F(12) \times C(9, F(6)) & 7922 &:= F(F(7)) \times (C(9, 2) - 2) \\
 1638 &:= C(F(1 + 6), F(3)) \times F(8) & 8834 &:= -F(8) + C(F(8) + F(3), 4) \\
 1715 &:= -1 + C(F(7), 1 + 5) & 9384 &:= F(9) \times C(3 \times 8, F(F(4))) \\
 1716 &:= C(F(1 \times 7), 1 \times 6) & 9724 &:= F(9) \times C(C(F(7), F(2)), F(4)) \\
 1717 &:= 1 + C(F(7), -1 + 7) & 9737 &:= F(9) \times C(F(7), 3) + F(7) \\
 2646 &:= C(F(2) + F(6), 4) \times F(F(6)) & 10485 &:= C(10, F(F(4))) \times F(8 + 5) \\
 2647 &:= 2 \times C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - F(7) & 10584 &:= C(10, 5) \times F(8) \times F(F(4)) \\
 3574 &:= -F(F(3)) + 5 \times C(F(7), 4) & 10666 &:= -10 \times C(F(6), 6) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 3654 &:= C(3 \times F(6) + 5, F(4)) & 10826 &:= -C(10, F(8/2)) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 3662 &:= F(3) + 6 \times F(C(6, 2)) & 10863 &:= -F(10) + F(F(8)) - C(F(6), F(3)) \\
 3663 &:= 3 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) & 10943 &:= F(F(10) - F(9)) - F(C(4, 3)) \\
 3759 &:= 3 \times (C(F(7), 5) - F(9)) & 10951 &:= F(F(10) - F(9)) + C(5, 1) \\
 3876 &:= C(-F(3) + F(8), 7 + F(6)) & 10956 &:= 10 + F(C(9, 5) / 6) \\
 3963 &:= 3 \times (-9 + C(F(F(6)), 3)) & 10965 &:= 10 + 9 + F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) \\
 3978 &:= C(F(3) \times 9, 7) / 8 & 10981 &:= 1 + F(09) + F(F(C(8, 1))) \\
 4359 &:= C(4^{F(3)}, 5) - 9 & 11276 &:= C(-1 + 12, 7) + F(F(F(6))) \\
 4365 &:= -F(4) + C(F(3) \times F(6), 5) & 11386 &:= C(11, F(3)) \times 8 + F(F(F(6))) \\
 4374 &:= F(C(4, 3))^7 \times F(F(4)) & 11439 &:= -1 + C(1 \times 4^{F(3)}, 9) \\
 4558 &:= C(4 \times 5, 5) - F(F(8)) & 11650 &:= F(F(C(1, 1) + 6)) \times 50 \\
 4758 &:= -C(4 + F(7), 5) + F(F(8)) & 11658 &:= F(11) \times F(C(6, 5)) + F(F(8)) \\
 4843 &:= C(-F(F(F(4))) + F(8), 4) - F(3) & 11946 &:= (C(1, 1) + 9)^{F(4)} + F(F(F(6))) \\
 4844 &:= -F(F(F(4))) + C(F(8) - F(F(F(4))), 4) & 12096 &:= F(12) \times C(09, 6) \\
 4845 &:= C(-F(F(4)) + F(8), F(4)) \times 5 & 12648 &:= -1 \times 2 + C(F(F(6)) + 4, F(8)) \\
 4984 &:= F(F(F(4)) + 9) \times C(8, F(4)) & 12858 &:= -12 + C(F(8) - 5, 8) \\
 5478 &:= F(5 \times 4) - C(F(7), 8) & 12865 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, F(6)) - 5 \\
 5984 &:= -F(F(F(-5 + 9))) + C(F(8), 4) & 12868 &:= -1 \times 2 + C(8 + F(6), 8) \\
 6456 &:= F(F(6)) + C(F(4) \times 5, F(6)) & 13456 &:= 1 + C(3^{F(4)}, 5) / 6 \\
 6469 &:= C(C(6, 4), F(6)) + F(9) & 13728 &:= C(13, 7) \times F(2) \times 8 \\
 6561 &:= (F(6) - 5)^{F(C(6, 1))} & 13736 &:= (C(13, 7) + F(F(3))) \times F(6) \\
 6764 &:= 6 - 7 + F(C(6, F(4))) & 14378 &:= C(1 + F(4 + 3), 7) + F(F(8)) \\
 6765 &:= F(F(6) + C(7, 6) + 5) & 14945 &:= C(-1 + F(4) \times 9, 4) - 5 \\
 6771 &:= 6 + F(F(7) + C(7, 1)) & 14964 &:= 14 + C(F(9) - F(6), 4)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 15659** := $1 \times 5^{C(6,5)} + F(9)$
15948 := $C(15,9) - F(4) + F(F(8))$
15951 := $C(15,9) + F(F(F(5+1)))$
15956 := $C(15,9) + 5 + F(F(F(6)))$
16367 := $(-1 + C(F(F(6)), F(3)) \times 6) \times F(7)$
16381 := $-1 \times C(F(F(6)), 3) + F(F(8) + 1)$
16382 := $1 - C(F(F(6)), 3) + F(F(8) + F(2))$
16443 := $(-1 + F(C(6,4))) \times F(4)^3$
16472 := $(1 + C(F(6), 4)) \times (F(F(7)) - F(2))$
16497 := $(1 + F(C(6,4))) \times (F(9) - 7)$
16964 := $(-1 + F(F(F(6)))) + F(9) + C(F(F(6)), 4)$
17136 := $C(17+1, 3) \times F(F(6))$
17263 := $-1 - F(7) \times (2 - C(F(F(6)), 3))$
17264 := $F(1 \times 7) \times (-2 + C(F(F(6)), F(4)))$
17424 := $(C(-1 + F(7), F(F(4))) \times 2)^{F(F(4))}$
17426 := $1 - C(F(7), F(4)) + F(F(2) + F(F(6)))$
17478 := $F(C(-1 + 7, F(4))) - F(F(7)) + F(F(8))$
17683 := $F(1 + F(7) + F(6)) - C(8, F(3))$
17699 := $1 - F(7) + F(F(F(6))) + C(9, 9)$
17712 := $1 + F(7 + C(7 - 1, 2))$
17744 := $-1 + F(7) \times C(F(7) + F(F(4)), 4)$
17765 := $F((-1 - F(F(7))) / F(7)) + C(F(F(6)), 5)$
17855 := $F(-1 + F(7)) + F(F(8) + C(5, 5))$
17864 := $(-1 + F(F(7))) \times (F(8) + C(F(6), F(4)))$
18173 := $-1 + F(F(8 - 1)) \times C(F(7), F(3))$
18426 := $C(F(-1 + 8), 4) + F(F(2) + F(F(6)))$
18480 := $C(1 + F(8), F(F(4))) \times 80$
18486 := $(C(18, 4) + F(8)) \times 6$
18562 := $C(F(-1 + 8) + 5, 6) - 2$
18563 := $C(F(-1 + 8) + 5, 6) - F(F(3))$
18564 := $C(18, 5 + F(6 - 4))$
18577 := $C(18, 5 + 7) + F(7)$
18619 := $C(18, 6) + F(1 + 9)$
18648 := $C(18, 6) + 4 \times F(8)$
18668 := $C(F(-1 + 8), F(6)) \times 6 + F(F(8))$
18777 := $F(-1 + F(8)) + C(F(7), 7) \times 7$
19339 := $(-1 + C(9, 3)) \times F(F(-F(3) + 9))$
19448 := $C(F(1 \times 9) / F(F(4)), F(F(4)) + 8)$
19467 := $(19 + C((-4) + F(F(6))), 7)$
19485 := $((-C(19, 4) - F(8)) \times (-5))$
19655 := $(-1) + (C((F(9) - (6)), 5) / 5)$
19844 := $((F(F(-((1 - 9)))) - C(F(8), 4)) \times 4)$
20329 := $F(20) \times C(3, 2) + F(9)$
20349 := $C(F(2^{03}), -4 + 9)$
20367 := $-F(20) + C(-F(3) + F(F(6)), F(7))$
20373 := $F(20) \times 3 + C(F(7), F(3))$
20474 := $-F(2) + C(04 \times 7, 4)$
21657 := $2 \times (-1 + F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) - F(F(7))$
21682 := $2 \times F(F(F(1 \times 6))) - C(F(8), 2)$
21684 := $2 \times (1 + F(F(F(6)))) - C(F(8), F(F(4)))$
21736 := $2 \times 1 \times (-C(F(7), F(3)) + F(F(F(6))))$
21738 := $2 \times (1 - C(F(7), F(3)) + F(F(8)))$
21836 := $F(21) - C(8, 3) + F(F(F(6)))$
21876 := $2 \times (-1 + F(F(8)) - C(7, 6))$
21877 := $2 \times (-1 + F(F(C(8, 7)))) - F(7)$
21888 := $2 \times (-1 + F(F(8)) - C(8, 8))$
21928 := $F(21) + C(9, 2) + F(F(8))$
22874 := $2 \times (C(2 \times 8, 7) - F(4))$
22896 := $2 \times (C(2 \times 8, 9) + F(6))$
23182 := $-2 + F(C(3, 1) \times 8) / 2$
23183 := $(-2 + F(C(3, 1) \times 8)) / F(3)$
23476 := $2 \times (C(3 \times 4, 7) + F(F(F(6))))$
23647 := $(-F(2) + C(F(3) \times F(6), 4)) \times F(7)$
23944 := $((-F(2) - C(F(F(-((3 - 9))))), 4)) \times (-4)$
24466 := $(2 \times (C(F((F(4) + (4))), F(6)) + F(F(F(6))))$
24746 := $(-2) \times (F(4) - C((F(7) + (4)), 6))$
24752 := $(2 \times (C((4 + F(7)), 5) \times 2))$
24754 := $(2 + (C((4 + F(7)), 5) \times 4))$
24768 := $(2 \times (C((4 + F(7)), 6) + 8))$
25287 := $((2 \times C((5^2), F(8))) - F(7))$
25346 := $((C((2 \times 5), 3)^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(F(6))))$
26326 := $(C((F(2) + F(F(6))), (3 + 2)) - F(6))$
26327 := $(C((F(2) + F(F(6))), (3 + 2)) - (7))$
26332 := $(C((F(2) + F(F(6))), (F(3) + 3)) - 2)$
26333 := $(C((F(2) + F(F(6))), (F(3) + 3)) - F(F(3)))$
26334 := $C((2 + C(6, 3)), (F(3) + F(4)))$
26335 := $(F(2) + C(((F(6) + 3) \times F(3)), 5))$
26336 := $(2 + C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), (-3) + F(6)))$
26347 := $(C((F(2) + F(F(6))), (F(3) + F(4))) + (F(7)))$
26356 := $(F(2) + (C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 5) + F(F(6))))$

- 26449** := $((F(2) + F(C(6, F(4)))) + ((F(4)^9)))$
26466 := $((F(2) + (C(F(F(6)), F(F(4))) \times F(F(6)))) \times 6)$
26567 := $(C((F(2) + F(F(6))), 5) + (F((6+7))))$
26586 := $((C(F((F(2) + (6))), 5) - (F(8))) \times F(F(6)))$
26633 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) - (C((F(6) \times 3), 3)))$
26893 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) + (F(8) \times (-C(9, 3))))$
27132 := $C((-2) + F((7+1)), (3 \times 2))$
27366 := $((F(2) + F(F(7))) + C((-F(3) + F(F(6))), 6))$
27367 := $((2 + F(F(7))) + C((-F(3) + F(F(6))), F(7)))$
27378 := $(C(27, F(3)) \times 78)$
27549 := $((F(2) + C((F(7) + (5)), 4)) \times 9)$
27636 := $(C((F(2) + (7)), 6) \times F((F(3) \times F(6))))$
27676 := $(-((F(2) - (C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(7)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
27678 := $((F(2) + (C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(7))) + F(F(8)))$
27684 := $(((-2) - C(F(7), 6)) + F(F(8))) \times F(4)$
27783 := $((2 + C(7, 7)) \times (F(8)^3))$
28336 := $((C((2 + F(8)), 3) \times F(3)) \times F(6))$
28373 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (F(3) - C(F(7), 3)))$
28374 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (-3) + C(F(7), F(4)))$
28448 := $((F(2) - C(F(8), F(F(4)))) + F((F(F(4)) + (F(8))))$
28494 := $((-2) + F(F(8))) + C((F(4) \times 9), 4)$
28527 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (-C(5, 2)) \times F(7))$
28532 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (5^{C(3,2)}))$
28537 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - C(C(5, 3), 7))$
28634 := $((-2) - F(8)) + F((C(6, 3) + F(4)))$
28636 := $(-((F(2) \times F(8))) + F((C(6, F(3)) + F(6))))$
28642 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - C(6, (4 - 2)))$
28648 := $(-((F(2) + 8) - F((C(6, 4) + 8))))$
28649 := $((F(2) + F((8 + C(6, 4)))) - 9)$
28651 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - C(C(6, 5), 1))$
28653 := $((-2) + F((C(8, 6) - 5))) - F(3)$
28654 := $((F(2) + F((C(8, 6) - 5))) - 4)$
28656 := $(-F(2)) + F(((F(8) - C(6, 5)) + F(6)))$
28663 := $((2 \times F(F(8))) + (6 + F(C(6, 3))))$
28664 := $(-((F(2) - 8)) + F((F(6) + C(6, 4))))$
28665 := $((F(2) \times 8) + F((C(F(6), 6) - (5))))$
28666 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (F(6) + C(6, 6)))$
28685 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C(F(6), F((8 - 5))))$
28713 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C((7 + 1), 3))$
28723 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C((F(7) - F(2)), F(3)))$
28761 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (F(7) \times F(C(6, 1))))$
28762 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (7 \times C(6, 2)))$
28847 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + (C(F(8), F(4)) / 7))$
28867 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C(F(8), (6 + F(7))))$
28943 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C((9 + 4), 3))$
28982 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C((F(9) - 8), 2))$
29357 := $(-F(2)) + (C(C(9, F(F(3))), 5) \times F(F(7)))$
29568 := $((-C((2 + 9), 5)) \times F(6)) \times (-8)$
29636 := $((F((2 + 9)) \times C(F(F(6)), F(3))) + F(F(F(6))))$
29925 := $(C(F(-((F(2) - 9))), (F(9) / 2)) \times 5)$
31558 := $(C((3 \times F((1 + 5))), 5) - F(F(8)))$
31746 := $(3 \times (-C((1 + F(7)), F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))$
31825 := $(F(F(3)) + (C(18, (2 + 5))))$
31826 := $(F(3) + C(18, (F(2) + (6))))$
32733 := $((F(F(F((3 \times 2)))) - C(7, 3)) \times 3)$
32775 := $(-3) \times (F((F(2) + (7))) - (F(C(7, 5))))$
32866 := $((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + C(F(6), 6))$
32871 := $3 \times (-2 + F(F(8))) + F(C(7, 1))$
32873 := $((3 \times F((F(2) \times F(8)))) + C(7, 3))$
33448 := $(F((C((3 + 3), 4) + 4)) \times 8)$
33537 := $(F(F((3 + 3))) \times F((C(5, 3) + 7)))$
33552 := $(F(3) + (F((3 \times 5)) \times F(C(5, 2))))$
33553 := $(3 + (F((3 \times 5)) \times F(C(5, 3))))$
33645 := $(-((F(3) + F(3))) + C((F(F(6)) + F(F(4))), 5))$
33646 := $(-3) + C((F(3) + F(F(6))), -(F(4) - F(6)))$
33648 := $(-((F(F(3)) - C((F(3) + F(F(6))), -(F(4) - 8))))$
33649 := $C((F(3) + F((F(3) + (6)))) - ((4 - 9)))$
33845 := $((F((-C(3, 3)) + F(8))) + (4)) \times 5$
33859 := $((F((-C(3, 3)) + F(8))) \times 5) + F(9)$
33864 := $(F(3) \times ((F(F(3)) + F(F(8))) + C(F(F(6)), 4)))$
33865 := $((F((-C(3, 3)) + F(8))) + F(6)) \times 5$
33866 := $(C((3^3), F(8)) - (F(6)^6))$
34296 := $(3 \times (C((4^2), 9) - F(6)))$
34398 := $(C((3^{F(4)}), F(3)) \times 98)$
34749 := $((3^{F(4)}) \times C(F(7), -(4 - 9)))$
34884 := $(3 \times C(-((F(F(4)) - (F(8)))) - (8 - F(4))))$
34983 := $((C(F((3 + 4)), 9) + F(F(8))) \times 3)$
36366 := $(3 \times ((C(F(6), 3) \times F(F(6))) + F(F(F(6))))$
36464 := $(((-3) \times F(C(6, 4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4$
36575 := $(C((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))), (5 + F(7))) \times 5)$

- 36576** := $(F((F(3) \times C(6,5))) \times (F(F(7)) + F(F(6))))$
36642 := $((F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + F(C(6,4))) \times 2)$
36675 := $(3 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(6) - C(F(7), 5))))$
36678 := $(F((3 \times F(6))) + (C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / (-F(8))))$
36686 := $((F(3) \times C((F(6) + F(6)), 8)) + F(F(F(6))))$
36786 := $-((F((F(F(3)) + F(F(6)))) - (F(F(7)) + (C(F(8), 6))))$
36828 := $(3 \times (C(F(F(6)), F(8/2))) + F(F(8)))$
36831 := $(3 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((C(F(8), 3) + 1)))$
36834 := $((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) + (C(F(8), 3))) \times F(4)$
36836 := $((3 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(8), 3)))) + F(6))$
36846 := $(3 \times (F(F(F(6))) + ((C(F(8), F(4)) + (6))))$
37446 := $((F(F(3)) + C(F(7), F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) \times 6)$
37629 := $(F(((3 \times C(7,6)) - 2)) \times 9)$
37826 := $((F(3)^7) \times C(F(8), 2)) + F(F(F(6)))$
38078 := $(C(-(F(3) - F(8))), F(07)) + F(F(8)))$
38447 := $(F(3) + (C((8 + F(4)), F(4)) \times F(F(7))))$
38464 := $((F(F(3)) \times C(F(8), F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-4)$
38479 := $(C((3 + 8), F(4)) \times F(F(7))) + F(9)$
38527 := $(C(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8))), (5 + F(2))) - F(F(7)))$
38586 := $(3 \times (C((F(8) - 5), 8) - F(6)))$
38613 := $((C((F(3) \times 8), F(6)) + 1) \times 3)$
38680 := $(C(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8))), 6) - (80))$
38692 := $(C(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8))), 6) + (F(9) \times (-2)))$
38697 := $(C(-(F(F(3)) - (F(8))), 6) - (9 \times 7))$
38738 := $((3 - C(F(8), 7)) / (-3)) - F(8)$
38747 := $(F(F(3)) \times ((C(F(8), 7) / F(4)) - F(7)))$
38749 := $-((F(3) - ((C(F(8), 7) / F(4)) - 9)))$
38758 := $-((F(3) + (C(F(8), 7) / (5 - 8))))$
38759 := $((-3) + C(F(8), 7)) / F(-((5 - 9)))$
38776 := $((F(3) \times 8) + C((F(7) + 7), 6))$
38784 := $((3 \times (F(F(8)) - (F(7)))) + (C(F(8), 4)))$
38823 := $((3 \times F(F(8))) + (C(F(8), (F(2) + 3))))$
38896 := $((C((-3) + F(8)), 8) / 9) \times F(6)$
39301 := $-3 + F(9)^{C(3,01)}$
39387 := $((3^9) \times F(3)) + F(C(8, 7))$
39596 := $((F((-3) + F(9)) - 5) / F(C(9, F(6))))$
39648 := $((-F(3)) - (-9) \times C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) \times F(8)$
39843 := $(F(F(-((F(3) - 9)))) \times C((F(8) - F(F(4))), F(3)))$
39936 := $((F(3)^9) \times (C(9, 3) - 6))$
40656 := $(F(F(4)) \times (C(F(F(06)), 5) - F(F(6))))$
42563 := $(F(4) + ((2^5) \times C(F(F(6)), 3)))$
42564 := $(4 + ((2^5) \times C(F(F(6)), F(4))))$
43448 := $(-4) \times (C((3 \times F(4)), F(4)) - F(F(8)))$
43472 := $(4 \times (F(F((F(3)^{F(4)}))) - (C(F(7), 2))))$
43668 := $(-4) \times ((F(F(3)) + C(F(6), 6)) - F(F(8)))$
43754 := $((F((F(4)^{F(3)})) \times C(F(7), 5)) - 4)$
43756 := $((-4) + F(3)) + C((F(7) + 5), F(6))$
43758 := $C((F(4) + ((3 + 7) + 5)), 8)$
43759 := $((4 - 3) + (C(F(7), 5) \times F(9)))$
43766 := $(C(((F(4) + F(3)) + F(7)), F(6)) + F(6))$
43771 := $((4 \times F((3 \times 7))) - F(C(7, 1)))$
43784 := $(C(4, 3) \times F(C(7, (8/4))))$
43788 := $(4 \times (F((3 \times 7)) + C(8, 8)))$
43818 := $((C(4, 3) \times F(F(8))) + F((1 + 8)))$
43819 := $((C(4, 3) \times F(F(8))) + (1 + F(9)))$
43839 := $((C(4, 3) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(F(3)) + 9)))$
43872 := $(4 \times (F(F(3)) + (F(8) + F(C(7, 2))))$
43873 := $((C(4, 3) \times F(F(8))) + F((F(7) - F(3))))$
43874 := $((-4) \times (-3) - F(F(8))) + C(F(7), F(F(4)))$
43884 := $((C(4, 3) + F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 4$
43987 := $((-4) + C((F(3) \times 9), 8)) + F(F(7))$
44264 := $((C((4 \times 4), 2) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 4)$
44288 := $(-4) \times ((-C(4, 2) \times F(8)) - F(F(8)))$
44624 := $((F(F((4 + 4))) + C(F(F(6)), 2)) \times 4)$
44626 := $(F(F(4)) + (4 \times (C(F(F(6)), 2) + F(F(F(6)))))$
44628 := $(4 + (4 \times (C(F(F(6)), 2) + F(F(8))))$
44648 := $(C(4, F(4)) \times ((6^{F(4)}) + F(F(8))))$
44649 := $((F(F((4 + 4))) - C(F(F(6)), 4)) \times 9)$
44854 := $(4 + (F(4) \times C((F(8) + 5), 4)))$
44864 := $((-4) + C((F(4) \times 8), 6)) / F(4)$
44876 := $(C(4, F(4)) \times (F(F(8)) + (F(7) \times F(F(6)))))$
44964 := $(-((4^4)) + (F(9) \times C(F(F(6)), F(4))))$
44982 := $(F(C(4, F(4))) \times (F(9) \times (F(8)^2)))$
45676 := $(4 \times (C((-5) + F(F(6))), 7) - F(F(6)))$
46228 := $(-4) \times (-((F(C(6, 2)) + F(2))) - F(F(8)))$
46236 := $(4 \times ((F(C(6, 2)) + 3) + F(F(F(6))))$
46248 := $-((C((F(F(4)) \times F(6)), 2) - F((F(4) \times 8)))$
46276 := $(4 \times ((F(C(6, 2)) + F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))))$
46334 := $(F((4 + C(6, 3))) - 34)$
46353 := $(F((4 + C(6, 3))) - (5 \times 3))$

- 46359** := $(F((C((4+6), 3)/5) - 9)$
46364 := $(- (4) + F(((6+3) + C(6, 4)))$
46365 := $(F((4 \times 6) - C(3, (6-5)))$
46366 := $(F((4 \times 6) - (3 - C(6, 6)))$
46368 := $F((4 \times ((C(6, 3) - 6) - 8))$
46369 := $(F((4 \times 6) + C((3+6), 9))$
46372 := $(4 + F(((6-3) + C(7, 2)))$
46381 := $(F((4 + C(6, 3))) + F((8-1)))$
46387 := $((F((4 \times 6) - F(3)) + F(C(8, 7)))$
46396 := $((F((4 + C(6, 3))) + F(9)) - (6))$
46398 := $((F((4 + C(6, 3))) + 9) + F(8))$
46424 := $(F((4 \times 6) + C((4 \times 2), F(4)))$
46427 := $((4 + (6^{C(4,2)})) - F(F(7)))$
46432 := $(F((4 \times 6) + (4^{C(3,2)}))$
46438 := $(C((F(F(4)) + (6)), 4) + F((3 \times 8)))$
46466 := $-((C(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6))))), F(F(4))) - (6^6)))$
46473 := $(F((4 \times 6) + (F(4) \times C(7, 3)))$
46475 := $(C(F((F(F(F(4))) + 6)), 4) \times (F(7) \times 5))$
46494 := $(F((4 + C(6, F(4)))) + (C(9, 4)))$
46583 := $((F((4 \times 6) + 5) + C(F(8), F(3)))$
46654 := $(F(4) + (((6^6) - C(5, 4)))$
46665 := $(F(4) + ((6^6) + C(6, 5)))$
46675 := $-((F(F(4)) - ((6^6) + C(7, 5)))$
46681 := $((4 + (6^6)) + F(C(8, 1)))$
46753 := $(F((4 \times 6) - (- (7) \times F(C(5, 3))))$
46776 := $((4 \times 6) \times (F(F(7)) + C(F(7), 6)))$
46844 := $((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) + C((F(8) - F(4)), 4))$
46863 := $(C((4 + F(6)), 8) + F((F(6) \times 3)))$
46978 := $(F((4 \times 6) + F((C(9, 7) - F(8))))$
47352 := $(- (F(4)) - (- (7) \times F((F(3) \times C(5, 2))))$
47353 := $-((F(F(4)) + (- (7) \times F((F(3) \times C(5, 3))))$
47354 := $-((F(F(F(4))) - (7 \times F((F(3) \times C(5, F(4))))$
47363 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (7 \times (F(F(3)) + (F(C(6, 3))))$
47364 := $(F(F(4)) + (7 \times (F(F(3)) + F(C(6, F(4))))$
47632 := $((- (4) + F(F(7))) \times (C(F(F(6)), F(3)) - 2)$
47646 := $-F(F(F(4))) - F(F(7)) + C(F(F(6)), 4) \times F(6)$
47647 := $((F(F(F(4))) + 7) \times C(F(F(6)), 4) - F(F(7)))$
47648 := $(F(F(F(4))) - ((F(F(7)) - (C(F(F(6)), 4) \times 8)))$
47693 := $((F(F(4)) + C(F(7), F(6))) \times (F(9) + 3))$
47762 := $(- (F(4)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), 2)))$
47763 := $-((F(F(4)) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), F(3))))$
47764 := $-F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), F(4)))$
47766 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), 6)))$
47846 := $-((F((- (4) + F(7))) - (C(F(8), 4) \times F(6)))$
47848 := $((4 - C((F(7) + 8), 4)) \times (-8))$
47864 := $(- ((F(4) + F(7))) + (8 \times C(F(F(6)), 4)))$
47884 := $(4 - ((F(7) - F(8)) \times C(F(8), 4)))$
48387 := $(C(-((F(4) - F(8))), (F(F(3)) + 8)) - F(F(7)))$
48450 := $(C(-((F(F(4)) - (F(8))))), F(4)) \times 50$
48464 := $(-F(F(4)) + C(F(8), F(F(4)))) \times F(F(F(F(6)) / F(4)))$
48468 := $((C((4 + F(8)), F(4)) + F(6)) \times F(8))$
48488 := $(- (4) \times (- ((C(8, F(4)) \times F(8)) - F(F(8))))$
48576 := $((C((F(4) \times 8), 5) / 7) \times F(6))$
48615 := $(C(-((F(4) - F(8))), (F(6) + 1)) - (5))$
48639 := $-((F(F(4)) - ((F(8) + (C((6 \times 3), 9))))$
48662 := $((- (C((- (4) + F(8)), F(6))) - F(F(6))) \times (-2))$
48664 := $((4 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(6) \times F(C(6, 4))))$
48739 := $(C((F(F(4)) + (F(8))), 7) - (F((3 \times 9)))$
48789 := $((4 \times F(F(8))) + (C((7 + 8), 9)))$
48968 := $(((- (4) - C(F(8), 9)) / (-6)) - F(8))$
48986 := $-((F(F(F(4))) - ((C(F(8), 9) - 8) / 6))$
48996 := $(F(F(4)) - ((C(F(8), 9) + F(9)) / (-6)))$
49163 := $(- (F((4 + 9))) \times (- (1) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))))$
49284 := $((F(4) + F(9)) \times (2 + C(F(8), F(4))))$
53163 := $((C(5, 3) + F((1 + F(F(6)))) \times 3)$
53646 := $((F((5 \times 3)) \times C(F(6), 4) + F(F(F(6))))$
53654 := $(C(F((5 + 3)), 6) - F((5 \times F(4))))$
53667 := $(- (F((5 \times 3))) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) + (F(7))))$
53823 := $(F(F((5 + F(3)))) \times C((F(8) + F(2)), F(3)))$
54256 := $(C(F((5 + F(4))), (F(2) + 5)) - F(6))$
54257 := $(C(F((5 + F(4))), (F(2) + 5)) - (7))$
54263 := $(C((5 + (4^2)), 6) - F(F(3)))$
54266 := $((5 - F(4)) + C(F((2 + 6)), 6))$
54269 := $(5 + C(F((4 \times 2)), (6 + 9)))$
54281 := $((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))^2) - C(8, 1))$
54283 := $((F(C(5, F(4))) \times F((2 \times 8))) - F(3))$
54285 := $(F(C(5, F(4))) \times F(((F(2) \times F(8)) - (5))))$
54286 := $((5 \times 4) + 2) + C(F(8), 6)$
54344 := $(F(C(5, F(4))) + (F(F((3 + 4)))^{F(F(4))})$
54366 := $((F((5 + 4)) \times 3) + C(F(F(6)), 6))$

- 54373** := $(C((5+4), 3) + (F(F(7))^{F(3)}))$
54386 := $(((5^{F(4)}) - 3) + C(F(8), 6))$
54465 := $((-((F(C(5, F(4))) - F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 5)$
54497 := $C(F(5 + F(4)), -F(4) + 9) + F(F(7))$
54646 := $((C(5, 4) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (-4) \times F(F(6)))$
54655 := $(((-5) \times F(4)) + F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) \times 5)$
54664 := $((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - F(F(F(6)))) - C(F(6), F(4)))$
54665 := $((C(5, 4) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (65))$
54666 := $((C(5, 4) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(6) \times F(6)))$
54672 := $((-5) \times (-4) - F(F(F(6)))) - (C(F(7), 2))$
54675 := $(-5) \times ((F(4) + F(6)) - F(C(7, 5)))$
54676 := $(F((5^{F(F(4))})) - (C(F(F(6)), (F(7) - F(6))))$
54691 := $((-5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(C(9, 1)))$
54693 := $((C(5, 4) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(9) + 3))$
54694 := $((C(5, 4) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (9 \times 4))$
54715 := $(-5) \times (F(4) - F(C(C(7, 1), 5)))$
54720 := $(-5) \times (F(F(4)) - (F((C(7, 2) + 0))))$
54721 := $((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(C(7, 2)))) + 1)$
54723 := $((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(C(7, 2)))) + 3)$
54725 := $((C(5, 4) \times F(C(7, 2))) - (5))$
54727 := $((-5) \times (F(F(4)) - (F(C(7, 2)))) + (7))$
54775 := $(-5) \times ((4 - F(7)) - F(C(7, 5)))$
54866 := $(F((5 \times F(4))) + (C(F(8), 6) - F(6)))$
54867 := $(F((5 \times F(4))) + ((C(F(8), 6) - (7))))$
54868 := $((5^4) + (C(F(8), 6) - F(8)))$
54869 := $((C(5, 4) \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) + F(9))$
54874 := $(F((5 \times F(4))) + C(F(8), (F(7) + F(F(4))))$
54885 := $((C(5, F(4)) + F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 5)$
54975 := $(-5) \times (-49) - F(C(7, 5))$
56446 := $((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) + (C(F((F(4) + (4))), 6)))$
57121 := $((5 + F(F(7))) + 1)^{C(2, 1)}$
57497 := $(5 - (F((F(7) + (4))) \times (-C(9, 7))))$
58649 := $(-5) - (C(F(8), F(6)) - (4^9))$
59319 := $(5 + F(9))^{C(3, 1^9)}$
59321 := $((5 + F(9))^3 + C(2, 1))$
59837 := $((5 \times 9) \times C(F(8), 3) - F(7))$
59845 := $((5 \times 9) \times C(F(8), F(4)) - (5))$
61776 := $(-6) \times (C(F((1 \times 7)), 7) \times (-6))$
62842 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (C(28, 4))) \times 2)$
63504 := $(C((F(6) + F(3)), 5)^{F(F(04))})$
63664 := $((C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(4))$
63667 := $(C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6) - F((F(6) + F(7))))$
63688 := $((C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6) + (F(8))) - F(F(8)))$
63726 := $((F(F(F(6))) - C((F(3) \times F(7)), 2)) \times 6)$
63840 := $(C(F(F(6)), 3) \times (8 + 40))$
63846 := $(6 \times (F(F(3)) + (C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(6))))$
64278 := $(-6) \times (F((C(4, 2) + 7)) - F(F(8)))$
64346 := $(-C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + ((F(3) + (4)) \times F(F(F(6))))$
64365 := $((F(C(6, 4)) + 3) \times F(F(6))) \times 5)$
64386 := $((F((6 \times 4)) \times (-3)) + C(F(8), F(6)))$
64467 := $C(F(F(6)) - F(F(4)), F(F(4)) \times F(F(F(6)) - 7)$
64536 := $((F(F(F(6))) - C((4 \times 5), F(3))) \times 6)$
64636 := $(C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), F(6)) - F(F((F(3) + (6))))$
64638 := $((C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), F(6)) + F(3)) - F(F(8)))$
64686 := $((C((F(6) + F(4)), F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-6))$
64766 := $(-((C(F(6), 4) \times F(7))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-6)))$
64778 := $(-C(C(6, F(4)), F(7))) - (-F(7) \times F(F(8)))$
64785 := $((F(C(6, 4)) + (7)) \times F(8)) \times 5)$
64792 := $((C(F(6), F(4)) \times F(7)) \times F((9 + 2)))$
64847 := $(C(6, F(4)) - ((F(8)^{F(4)}) \times (-7)))$
64848 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + (F(8))) \times 48)$
65364 := $(6 \times ((-F(C(5, 3))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4))$
65467 := $(-((C(F(6), 5) - ((4^{F(6)}) - F(7))))$
65472 := $(-6) \times (F((5 + 4)) - F(C(7, 2)))$
65542 := $((F(C(6, 5))^5 + F(4)) \times 2)$
65547 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), C(5, 4)) - F(F(7)))$
65564 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), 5) - ((6^{F(4)})))$
65576 := $(C(F(6), 5) \times ((5 \times F(F(7))) + (6)))$
65591 := $((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - F(C(9, 1)))$
65636 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F(6))) - F((F(3) \times 6)))$
65637 := $((C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (3 \times F(7)))$
65638 := $(-C(F(6), 5) + (-6) \times (-3) - F(F(8))))$
65639 := $((C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (3 + F(9)))$
65642 := $((C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(4)^2)))$
65643 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6 - F(C(4, 3)))$
65646 := $(-6) \times (5 - F((C(6, 4) + 6)))$
65649 := $((C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (F(4) \times 9))$
65651 := $((F(F(F(6))) - (5)) \times 6 + C(5, 1))$
65658 := $6 \times (5 - F(C(6, 5)) + F(F(8)))$
65663 := $((C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - F((F(6) - F(F(3))))$

- 65665** := $((C(6,5) \times F(F(F(6)))) - (6+5))$
65675 := $(-((6-5) + (6 \times F(C(7,5))))$
65676 := $(6 \times F(F((56/C(7,6))))$
65677 := $((C(6,5) \times F(F(F(6)))) + C(7,7))$
65679 := $((C(6,5) \times F(F(F(6)))) + F((F(7)-9)))$
65681 := $(C(6,5) + ((6 \times F(F(8))) - 1))$
65682 := $(- (6) \times ((5-6) - F(C(F(8), F(2))))$
65683 := $(C(6,5) + ((6 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(3))))$
65685 := $(- ((F(F(C(6,5))) - (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (5))))$
65687 := $((6+5) + (6 \times F(F(C(8,7))))$
65689 := $(- ((F(F(C(6,5))) - ((6 \times F(F(8))) + F(9))))$
65690 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F(6))) - (90))$
65693 := $((C(6,5) \times F(F(F(6)))) + (F(9)/F(3)))$
65696 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F(6))) - (C(9,6)))$
65697 := $(F(F(C(6,5))) + (6 \times F((F(9) - F(7))))$
65699 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F(6))) - ((9 \times 9)))$
65724 := $(- (6) \times ((- (5) - F(C(7,2))) - F(4)))$
65736 := $((F(F(F(6))) + C(5, F((7-3)))) \times 6)$
65767 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), (F(7) - F(6))) - (F(7)))$
65775 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F((-7) + F(7)))) - (5))$
65778 := $(- ((F((F(6) - (5))) - (C((F(7) + F(7)), F(8))))$
65835 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) + F((F(3) \times 5)))$
65844 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) + ((4^{F(4)}))$
65856 := $((C(F(6), 5) \times F(8)) \times 56)$
65864 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) - (F(F(6)) \times (-4)))$
65885 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) - (F(8) \times (-5)))$
65886 := $((C(F(6), 5) - F(8)) + F(F(8))) \times 6$
65897 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) - (-9) \times F(7))$
66248 := $((C((F(6) + (6)), 2)^{F(F(4))}) \times 8)$
66348 := $(- (6) \times ((C(F(6), F(3)) \times (-4)) - F(F(8))))$
66379 := $((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(3))) + (C(F(7), 9)))$
66636 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (F(6) \times C(6,3))) \times 6)$
66936 := $((F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)), F((9/3)))) \times 6)$
66972 := $((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) + ((C(9,7)^2))$
66996 := $((F(F(F(6))) + C((F(F(6)) - 9), 9)) \times 6)$
67257 := $(- ((F(F(F(6))) - ((C(F(7), 2) + (5^7))))$
67337 := $((C((6+7), 3) + 3) \times F(F(7)))$
67386 := $(- (6) + ((- (C(F(7), 3)) - F(F(8))) \times (-6)))$
67392 := $(F(6) \times ((F(F(7)) + F(F(3))) \times C(9,2)))$
67561 := $(- ((F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(7), 5) \times (-61))))$
67579 := $((F(F(F(6))) - C(F(7), 5)) \times 7) - F(9))$
67597 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / F(-((5-9)))) - F(F(7)))$
67627 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((C(F(7), F(6)) - 2))) \times 7)$
67683 := $((F(F(6)) \times (-7)) + (C(F(F(6)), 8) / 3)$
67754 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) - F(F(7))) + (5)) / F(4)$
67823 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) - (F(8))) / (F(2) + F(3)))$
67825 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / F((8/2))) - (5))$
67844 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) - (-F(8)) \times F(F(4))) / F(4))$
67864 := $(F(F(6)) + (F(7) + (C(F(8), F(6)) / F(4))))$
67893 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) + (F(8) \times 9)) / 3)$
67956 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) + (C((9+5), 6))))$
68276 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((C(F(8), 2) \times F(7)) \times F(F(6))))$
68376 := $((F(F(6)) - C((F(8) - 3), F(7))) \times (-F(6)))$
68537 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(8) \times F(C(5,3)))) \times 7)$
68576 := $(F(6) \times (-8) - (-5) \times C(F(7), 6))$
68640 := $(C(-((F(6) - F(8))), 6) \times 40)$
68646 := $(6 \times (F(F(8)) + (C((F(6) + (4)), F(6))))$
68676 := $(6 \times (C((8 + F(6)), 7) + (6)))$
68733 := $(F(F(6)) \times (C((F(8) + (7)), 3) - 3))$
68766 := $((C((F(6) + 8), 7) + F(F(6))) \times 6)$
68964 := $(F(F(6)) \times (8 + C((F(9) - (6)), F(4))))$
69279 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F((9 \times 2)) + C(F(7), 9)))$
69456 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (C(9,4) \times 5)) \times 6)$
69784 := $(- ((F(F(F(6))) - C((F(9) - (7)), (8 - F(4))))$
69966 := $((C(-((F(F(6)) - F(9))), 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6)$
71844 := $((F(7) - 1) \times (C(F(8), 4) + F(F(4))))$
72425 := $(- ((C((F(7) \times 2), F(4)) - F(25)))$
72545 := $(C((F(7) \times 2), 5) + F((4 \times 5)))$
72774 := $((F(F(7)) + F(2)) \times (F(F(7)) + C(F(7), F(F(4))))$
73216 := $(C(F(7), 3) \times (2^{F(1 \times 6)}))$
73626 := $(- ((F((F(7) + 3)) - C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), 6)))$
73791 := $((- (7) - (F(3)^{F(7)})) \times (-C(9,1)))$
74256 := $(C((F(7) + (4)), (F(2) + (5))) \times 6)$
74415 := $((7 + 4) \times F((C(4,1) \times 5)))$
74431 := $((7^{C(4, F(4))}) \times 31)$
74606 := $(- (7) + C((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))) , 06))$
74616 := $((7 - 4) + C((F(F(6)) + 1), 6))$
74626 := $(F(7) + C(((4 \times 6) - 2), 6))$
74627 := $((C(F(7), F(4)) - F(F(F(6)))) - F(2)) \times (-7)$
74638 := $((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + C(F(F(6)), -((3-8)))$

- 74646** := ((7 + 4) × (F(C(6, F(4))) + F(F(6))))
74648 := (- (7) × ((- (F(4)) - C(F(F(6)), F(4))) × 8))
74736 := ((C(F(7), F(4)) + F(F(7))) × F((F(3) × 6)))
74739 := (- (C(F(7), F(4)) + F((F(7) + (3 + 9))))
74746 := (- ((C(F(7), F(4)) - (7))) + F((4 + F(F(6))))
74764 := ((F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}) + C((7 + F(F(6))), 4))
74793 := (F(F(7)) × ((4 + F(F(7))) + (C(9, 3))))
74799 := (C(7, F(F(F(4)))) - (F(F(7)) - F((F(9) - 9))))
74846 := (F(F(7)) + C(((4 + F(8)) - F(4)), 6))
74858 := (- (7) × (C((F(F(4)) + 8), 5) - F(F(8))))
74947 := - ((C(F(7), F(F(4))) - F((9 + F(4)) + F(7))))
75012 := - ((F(7) - F((C(5, 01)²)))
75046 := (F((C(7, 5) + 04)) + F(F(6)))
75248 := ((F(F(7)) - C(5, 2)) + F((4 + F(8))))
75254 := ((F(F(7)) + F((C(5, F(2)) × 5))) - (4))
75271 := F(F(7)) + F(5²) + F(C(7, 1))
75286 := (F(F(7)) + (F((5²)) + C(8, 6)))
75376 := (7 × ((F(C(5, 3)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6))))
75454 := ((C(F(7), 5) / F(4)) + F((5^{F(F(4))})))
75466 := (F((C(7, 5) + 4)) + (F(F(6)) × F(F(6))))
75887 := (- (7) × ((5 × F(8)) - F(F(C(8, 7))))
75957 := ((F(C(7, 5)) - (95)) × 7)
76348 := (- (7) + (C(F(F(6)), 3) + F((4 + F(8))))
76355 := (C((F(7) + F(6)), 3) + F((5 × 5)))
76362 := ((- (C(F(7), 6)) × F((3 + F(6)))) / (-2))
76426 := (- (7) × (C(F(6), F(F(4))) - F(F((2 + 6))))
76489 := 7 × (C(6, 4) + F(F(8)) - F(9))
76494 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - (F(F(4)) + (C(9, 4))))
76495 := (((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(F(4)))) - (C(9, 5)))
76522 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - (C(5, 2)²))
76524 := (7 × (F(F(F(6))) - (C(5, 2) + 4)))
76544 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - C(F((5 + F(F(4))), F(F(4))))
76545 := (7 × (F(F(F(6))) - (F(C(5, F(4))) / 5)))
76546 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - (F(C(5, F(4))) + F(F(6))))
76552 := (7 × (F(F(F(6))) - C(5, (5 - 2))))
76557 := ((7 × F(F(F(C(6, 5)))))) + (- (5) × F(7))
76561 := ((7 × F(F(F(C(6, 5)))))) - 61
76572 := (((- (7) + F(F(F(C(6, 5)))))) × 7) - F(2))
76593 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - C((- (5) + F(9)), F(F(3))))
76596 := ((7 × F(F(F(C(6, 5)))))) - (F(9) - F(6))
76601 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(C(6, 01))))
76611 := ((C(7, 6) × F(F(F(6)))) - 11)
76612 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - C((6 - 1), 2))
76613 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - (C(6, 1) + 3))
76614 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - F(C(6, (1⁴))))
76619 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + ((C(6, 1) - 9)))
76621 := ((7 × F((6 + C(6, 2)))) - 1)
76623 := ((7 × F((6 + C(6, 2)))) + F(F(3)))
76624 := ((7 × F((6 + C(6, 2)))) + F(F(4)))
76631 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + C((6 + 3), 1))
76632 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (C(6, 3) / 2))
76643 := (7 × (F((6 + C(6, 4))) + 3))
76654 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (F(C(6, 5)) × 4))
76657 := (F(F(7)) × ((6 × C(F(6), 5)) - (7)))
76663 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (F(F(6)) + C(6, 3)))
76664 := (- (7) × (- (6) - F((6 + C(6, 4))))
76684 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (6 + C(8, F(4))))
76686 := ((C(7, 6) × (F(6) + F(F(8)))) + F(6))
76727 := (((7 + F(6)) + F(C(7, 2))) × 7)
76739 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (C(F(7), F(F(3))) × 9))
76741 := (C(F(7), 6) + F(((F(7) × F(F(4))) - 1)))
76748 := ((C(F(7), 6) + (7)) + F((4 + F(8))))
76752 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (F(7) × C(5, 2)))
76812 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + C((F(8) - 1), 2))
76826 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (C(F(8), 2) - (6)))
76831 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + (C(F(8), F(3)) - 1))
76833 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - (- (C(F(8), F(3))) - F(F(3))))
76855 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + F(F((8 - C(5, 5))))
76876 := (((C(7, 6) × F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + F(F(6)))
76986 := (C(F(7), F(- ((6 - 9)))) × F((8 + F(6))))
77287 := (C((F(7) + (7)), - ((F(2) - 8))) - F(F(7)))
77515 := ((C((F(7) + (7)), 5) - 1) × 5)
77535 := ((C((F(7) + (7)), 5) + 3) × 5)
77636 := (- (F(7)) × (F(7) - C(F(F(6)), - ((F(3) - (6))))))
77676 := (- (F(F(7))) + ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + C(F(7), F(6))))
77688 := ((- (7) × (- (C(F(7), 6)) - F(F(8)))) - F(F(8)))
77714 := (F(7) × (- (7) + C(F((7 + 1)), 4)))
77753 := (F(F(7)) + C((F(7) + (7)), (5 + F(3))))
77844 := (F(7) × (C((F(7) + 8), 4) + F(4)))
77896 := (F(7) × (7 + C(F(8), (9 + F(6))))

- 77974** := $(F(7) \times (F(7) + C((F(9) - F(7)), 4)))$
78288 := $(F(F(7)) \times (C(F(8), F(2)) \times (8 + 8)))$
78414 := $(7 \times (F(F(8)) + (C(4, 1)^4)))$
78415 := $((F(7) \times C(F(8), 4)) + F(15))$
78646 := $((7 \times F(F(8))) + C((6 \times 4), F(F(6))))$
79274 := $-((F(F(7)) - ((C(9, 2) + 7)^{F(4)})))$
79445 := $((F(7) + (C(9, 4)^{F(F(4))})) \times 5)$
79494 := $(-F(7) + ((C(9, F(F(F(4)))) + F(9))^{F(4)}))$
79617 := $((F(F(7)) \times 9) + C((F(F(6)) - 1), F(7)))$
79758 := $((7 \times 9) \times (C(F(7), 5) - F(8)))$
81467 := $(C((F(8) - 1), 4) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)))$
81848 := $(-8) \times (C(F(-(1 - 8)), 4) - F(F(8)))$
82368 := $((8^2) \times C(F((F(F(3)) + (6))), 8))$
83236 := $-((F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) - C(23, 6)))$
83298 := $((C(8, F(3)) \times F((2 \times 9))) + F(F(8)))$
83387 := $(F((F(8) - C(3, 3))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7)))$
83764 := $-((F(F(8)) + ((F(3) \times (-7)) \times F(C(6, F(4))))))$
83832 := $(F(8) \times ((3 \times C(F(8), 3)) + 2))$
83984 := $((C((F(8) - F(F(3))), 9) + 8) / F(F(4)))$
84645 := $((F(F(8)) - F(F(4))) + C(F(F(6)), 4)) \times 5$
84653 := $((-C(F(8), 4) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)) - F(3)$
84654 := $((-C(F(8), 4) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)) - F(F(F(4)))$
84655 := $((-C(F(8), 4) - F(F(F(C(6, 5)))))) \times (-5)$
84672 := $((C(8, F(F(4))) \times F(F(6))) \times F((F(7) - F(2))))$
84685 := $((-C(F(8), 4) + (6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-5)$
84749 := $(F((F(8) + (4))) + ((C(F(7), F(4)) \times F(9))))$
84887 := $((C(F(8), F(4)) \times (8 \times 8)) - F(F(7)))$
85272 := $(C((F(8) + F(F((5 - 2))))), 7) / 2$
85344 := $((C(F(8), 5) + F((F(3)^4))) \times 4)$
85888 := $((C(F(8), F(-(5 - 8))) - F(F(8))) \times (-8))$
86464 := $((-F(8) - C(F(F(6)), F(4))) \times (-64))$
86581 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - F((-5) + F(C(8, 1))))$
86628 := $((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times (-2)) - 8$
86632 := $((F(F(8)) - (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(3))) \times (-2))$
86633 := $((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times (-F(3))) - 3$
86634 := $((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times (-F(3))) - F(F(4))$
86636 := $-(((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times F(-(3 - 6))))$
86642 := $((F(F(8)) - (C(F(F(6)), 6) + F(4))) \times (-2))$
86728 := $((F(F(8)) - C((F(6) + (7)), 2)) \times 8)$
86846 := $(F(F(8)) - (-6) \times C((F(8) + (4)), F(F(6))))$
86856 := $((C(F(8), 6) + F(8)) / 5) \times F(6)$
86874 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) + ((F(8) - C(F(7), 4)))$
86896 := $((F(F(8)) \times F(6)) - (8 \times C(9, 6)))$
87176 := $((F(F(8)) - (C(7, 1) \times 7)) \times F(6))$
87263 := $-((F(F(8)) - ((F((C(7, 2) + 6)) / F(3))))$
87293 := $((8 \times (F(C(7, 2)) - F(9))) - 3)$
87294 := $((8 \times (F(C(7, 2)) - F(9))) - F(F(4)))$
87296 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 2))) - (F(9) \times F(6)))$
87526 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - (2 \times F(F(6))))$
87528 := $((F(F(C(8, 7))) - (5)) \times (F(2) \times 8))$
87534 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - 34)$
87536 := $(8 \times ((F(C(7, 5)) + F(3)) - (6)))$
87537 := $((8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) - 3)) - (7))$
87542 := $((8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) - F(4))) - 2)$
87543 := $((8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) - F(4))) - F(F(3)))$
87544 := $(8 \times (F(C(7, C(5, 4))) - F(4)))$
87546 := $((8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) - F(F(4)))) - (6))$
87547 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - (F(4) \times 7))$
87552 := $(8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) - F((5 - 2))))$
87553 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - (5 \times 3))$
87559 := $((8 \times F(F((7 + C(5, 5)))) - 9)$
87573 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + (7)) - F(3)$
87574 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + (7)) - F(F(F(4)))$
87576 := $((8 + F(C(7, 5))) - (7)) \times F(6)$
87581 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + F((8 - 1)))$
87584 := $(8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) + (8/4)))$
87589 := $((F(8) - F(C(7, 5))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))$
87596 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + F(9)) - (6)$
87598 := $((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + 9) + F(8)$
87616 := $(8 \times (F(C(7, (6 - 1))) + (6)))$
87623 := $(C(F(8), C(7, 6)) - F(23))$
87656 := $((F(F(C(8, 7))) + (6 + 5)) \times F(6))$
87671 := $((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times C(F(6), 7)) - 1$
87694 := $((8 \times F((F(7) + F(6)))) + (C(9, 4)))$
87724 := $((8 + F(F(7))) \times C((7 \times 2), F(4)))$
87736 := $((F(C(8, 7)) + F((7 \times 3))) \times F(6))$
87776 := $((F(F(C(8, 7))) + (F(7) + F(7))) \times F(6))$
87785 := $((F((F(8) - (7))) \times F(F(7))) - C(8, 5))$
87862 := $(F(8) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F((C(8, 6) / 2))))$
87882 := $((F(F(8)) + (F(7))) \times 8) + (C(F(8), 2))$

- 88384** := $((8 \times F(F(8))) + C((-3) + F(8), F(4)))$
88464 := $(8 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(F(4)) \times C(F(6), F(4))))$
88466 := $(F(F(8)) + C((F(8) - F(F(4))), (-F(6) + F(F(6))))$
88478 := $(-(((F(8) - C(F(8), 4)) \times F(7))) + F(F(8)))$
88528 := $((F(F(8)) + C((F(8) - 5), 2)) \times 8)$
88555 := $((F(F(8)) + F((F(8) - C(5, 5)))) \times 5)$
88647 := $(F(F(8)) + ((8 - C(F(F(6)), 4)) \times (-F(7))))$
88855 := $((8 \times F(F(8))) + (C((8 + 5), 5)))$
88876 := $((8 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8) + C(F(7), F(6))))$
88984 := $((-8) + F((8 + 9))) \times C(8, F(4))$
89248 := $((F(F(8)) + C((9 + F(2)), 4)) \times 8)$
89467 := $((C((-8) + F(9)), 4) \times 6) - F(F(7))$
89496 := $((C((-8) + F(9)), 4) - F(9)) \times 6$
89846 := $(C((8 + 9), 8) + (4^{F(6)}))$
89943 := $(-F(8)) \times ((F(9) \times (-C(9, 4))) + F(F(3)))$
89956 := $((F(8) \times F(9)) \times C(9, 5)) - F(6)$
89957 := $((F(8) \times F(9)) \times C(9, 5)) - 7$
89964 := $((F(8) \times F(9)) \times C(C(9, F(6)), 4))$
89986 := $(C((8 + 9), 9) + (F(F(8)) \times 6))$
92289 := $(-((F((9 + 2)) - C((-2) + F(8)), 9)))$
92369 := $(-9) + C((F(2) + ((3 \times 6))), 9)$
92389 := $((9 + 2) + C(-((F(3) - F(8))), 9))$
92736 := $((C(9, F(2)) - 7) \times F((3 \times F(6))))$
93312 := $((C(9, F(3))^3) \times (1 \times 2))$
93314 := $((C(9, F(3))^3 + 1) \times F(F(4)))$
93885 := $((9/3) \times (F(F(8)) + (C(F(8), 5))))$
94386 := $(-((9^4)) + C((F(3) + F(8)), 6))$
94647 := $((-9) + (F(F(4)) \times F(C(6, F(4)))) \times 7)$
94673 := $(F((9 \times F(4))) + (C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / (-F(3))))$
94773 := $((C((9 \times F(F(4))), 7) - F(F(7))) \times 3)$
94864 := $((9 + F(F(4))) \times C(8, 6))^{F(F(4))}$
95256 := $((C(9, 5))^{F(-2+5)}) \times 6$
95365 := $((-9) + F((5^{F(3)}))) + C(F(F(6)), 5)$
95634 := $(9 \times C(((5 + F(F(6))) - F(3)), 4))$
96327 := $(9 \times F(F(F(6))) - (C(3, 2)^7))$
96417 := $(9 \times (F((C(6, F(4)) + 1)) - F(F(7))))$
96534 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (F(C(5, 3)) \times 4)))$
96622 := $((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), 2)))) - 2)$
96623 := $((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), 2)))) - F(F(3)))$
96624 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - C((F(6) + 2), 4)))$
96633 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), F(3)) - F(F(3))))$
96637 := $((9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - C(F(F(6)), F(3)))) + F(7))$
96642 := $(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), F(F(4))) - 2))$
96798 := $(-((C((F(9) - F(F(6))), 7) + (-9) \times F(F(8))))$
96974 := $((9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (C((9 + F(7)), F(4))))$
97184 := $((9 \times F(F((7 + 1)))) - C(F(8), F(4)))$
97578 := $(9 \times (F(C(7, 5)) + (F(7) \times (-8))))$
97842 := $((-9) + (F(F(7)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))) \times 2)$
98246 := $(-F(9) + C(C(8, 2), -(F(4) - F(6))))$
98261 := $((9 \times (-C(8, 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) - 1)$
98262 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - C((2 + 6), 2)))$
98263 := $((9 \times (-C(8, 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))$
98264 := $((9 \times (-C(8, 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(4)))$
98271 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - C(27, 1)))$
98272 := $9 \times (F(F(8)) - F(2)) - F(C(F(7), F(2)))$
98283 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - C((F(2) + F(8)), F(3)))$
98314 := $(F(9) + C(C(8, F(3)), (1 + 4)))$
98334 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - C((3 + 3), F(4))))$
98394 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - C((F(F(3)) + 9), F(4)))$
98424 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - (C(4, 2) + 4)))$
98444 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - C((4 + 4), 4))$
98471 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 4)) - C(7, 1))$
98477 := $((9 \times (F(F(8)) - 4)) - C(7, 7))$
98482 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (4 + C(8, 2)))$
98483 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - (F(4) + C(8, F(3))))$
98504 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) - C(5, F(04)))$
98505 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) - C(5, 05)))$
98515 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + C(C(5, 1), 5))$
98519 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + C(5, (1^9)))$
98521 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + C((5 + 2), 1))$
98522 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(5, 2) - 2))$
98532 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5 - C(3, 2))))$
98534 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(5, F(F(3))) \times 4))$
98535 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + C((5 + F(3)), 5))$
98537 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(5, 3) + F(7)))$
98541 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) + F((C(5, 4) - 1))))$
98542 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + C((5 + F(4)), 2))$
98544 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(5, F(4)) \times F(4)))$
98568 := $(9 \times (F(F(8)) + (5 + C(F(6), 8))))$
98569 := $((9 \times F(F(8))) + C((5 + 6), 9))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98593 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - ((5 - C(9,3)))) \\
 98634 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + C((F(6) + F(3)), F(4))) \\
 98649 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(6,4) \times 9)) \\
 98658 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(C(6,5)) + 8))) \\
 98669 &:= (- (F(C(9,8))) + ((- (F(F(6))) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-9))) \\
 98679 &:= (9 + (C((F(8) + (6)), 7) / 9)) \\
 98682 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (6 \times C(8,2))) \\
 98724 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + C(C(7,2), F(F(4)))) \\
 98743 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - C(4,3)) \\
 98744 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - F(C(4, F(4)))) \\
 98747 &:= ((C(9,8) \times F((7 \times F(4)))) + F(F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98752 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + C(5, F(2))) \\
 98762 &:= (((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) + C(6,2)) \\
 98787 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + (F(7) \times F(C(8,7)))) \\
 98838 &:= (9 \times (F(F(8)) + (C(8, F(3)) + 8))) \\
 98844 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) + C((8 + F(4)), 4)) \\
 99387 &:= (9 \times ((C(9,3) + F(F(8))) + (F(7)))) \\
 99437 &:= ((F(9) \times C((9 \times F(4)), 3)) - F(7)) \\
 99445 &:= ((F(9) \times C((9 \times F(4)), F(4))) - (5)) \\
 99648 &:= (9 \times (C(C(9, F(6)), 4) + F(F(8))))
 \end{aligned}$$

2.2 Factorial

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with factorial**. The results are in terms of digit's order. The work is up to 6 digits. This subsection is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10 or 100. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

2.2.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 1330 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 0 \\
 1331 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 1 \\
 1332 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 2 \\
 1333 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 3 \\
 1334 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 4 \\
 1335 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 5 \\
 1336 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 6 \\
 1337 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 7 \\
 1338 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 8 \\
 1339 &:= C(F(F(1 \times 3!)), 3) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4270 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 0 \\
 4271 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 1 \\
 4272 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 2 \\
 4273 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 3 \\
 4274 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 4 \\
 4275 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 5 \\
 4276 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 6 \\
 4277 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 7 \\
 4278 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 8 \\
 4279 &:= F(C(F(4!), 2)) \times 7 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6370 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 0 \\
 6371 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 1 \\
 6372 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 2 \\
 6373 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 3 \\
 6374 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 4 \\
 6375 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 5 \\
 6376 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 6 \\
 6377 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 7 \\
 6378 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 8 \\
 6379 &:= C(F(F(6)), 3) + 7! + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 13420 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 0 \\
 13421 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 1 \\
 13422 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 2 \\
 13423 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 3 \\
 13424 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 4 \\
 13425 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 5 \\
 13426 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 6 \\
 13427 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 7 \\
 13428 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 8 \\
 13429 &:= (1 + F(F(3!))) \times F(C(F(4!), 2)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 14640 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 0 \\ 14641 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 1 \\ 14642 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 2 \\ 14643 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 3 \\ 14644 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 4 \\ 14645 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 5 \\ 14646 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 6 \\ 14647 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 7 \\ 14648 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 8 \\ 14649 &:= 1 \times 4! \times F(C(6,4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 20350 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 0 \\ 20351 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 1 \\ 20352 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 2 \\ 20353 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 3 \\ 20354 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 4 \\ 20355 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 5 \\ 20356 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 6 \\ 20357 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 7 \\ 20358 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 8 \\ 20359 &:= F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), 5) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25620 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 0 \\ 25621 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 1 \\ 25622 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 2 \\ 25623 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 3 \\ 25624 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 4 \\ 25625 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 5 \\ 25626 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 6 \\ 25627 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 7 \\ 25628 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 8 \\ 25629 &:= (2+5!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 0 \\ 25921 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 1 \\ 25922 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 2 \\ 25923 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 3 \\ 25924 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 4 \\ 25925 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 5 \\ 25926 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 6 \\ 25927 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 25928 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 8 \\ 25929 &:= (F(2)+5)! \times C(9,2) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 32940 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 0 \\ 32941 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 1 \\ 32942 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 2 \\ 32943 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 3 \\ 32944 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 4 \\ 32945 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 5 \\ 32946 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 6 \\ 32947 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 7 \\ 32948 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 8 \\ 32949 &:= F(C(3!,2)) \times 9 \times F(4)! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33250 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 0 \\ 33251 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 1 \\ 33252 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 2 \\ 33253 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 3 \\ 33254 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 4 \\ 33255 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 5 \\ 33256 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 6 \\ 33257 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 7 \\ 33258 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 8 \\ 33259 &:= C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times 25 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 33550 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 0 \\ 33551 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 1 \\ 33552 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 2 \\ 33553 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 3 \\ 33554 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 4 \\ 33555 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 5 \\ 33556 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 6 \\ 33557 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 7 \\ 33558 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 8 \\ 33559 &:= F(C(3!, F(3))) \times 55 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34670 &:= -F(C(3!,4)) + F(6)! - 7! + 0 \\ 34671 &:= -F(C(3!,4)) + F(6)! - 7! + 1 \\ 34672 &:= -F(C(3!,4)) + F(6)! - 7! + 2 \\ 34673 &:= -F(C(3!,4)) + F(6)! - 7! + 3 \\ 34674 &:= -F(C(3!,4)) + F(6)! - 7! + 4 \\ 34675 &:= -F(C(3!,4)) + F(6)! - 7! + 5 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 34676 &:= -F(C(3!, 4)) + F(6!) - 7! + 6 \\ 34677 &:= -F(C(3!, 4)) + F(6!) - 7! + 7 \\ 34678 &:= -F(C(3!, 4)) + F(6!) - 7! + 8 \\ 34679 &:= -F(C(3!, 4)) + F(6!) - 7! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 36330 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 0 \\ 36331 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 1 \\ 36332 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 2 \\ 36333 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 3 \\ 36334 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 4 \\ 36335 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 5 \\ 36336 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 6 \\ 36337 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 7 \\ 36338 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 8 \\ 36339 &:= F(3!) - C(F(F(6)), 3) \times 3 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38040 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 0 \\ 38041 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 1 \\ 38042 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 2 \\ 38043 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 3 \\ 38044 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 4 \\ 38045 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 5 \\ 38046 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 6 \\ 38047 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 7 \\ 38048 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 8 \\ 38049 &:= -3!! + C(F(8) - 0!, F(4)!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 0 \\ 38761 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 1 \\ 38762 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 2 \\ 38763 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 3 \\ 38764 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 4 \\ 38765 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 5 \\ 38766 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 6 \\ 38767 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 7 \\ 38768 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 8 \\ 38769 &:= C(3! + F(8) - 7, 6) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38990 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 0 \\ 38991 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 1 \\ 38992 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 2 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38993 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 3 \\ 38994 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 4 \\ 38995 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 5 \\ 38996 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 6 \\ 38997 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 7 \\ 38998 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 8 \\ 38999 &:= F(3!) - C(F(8), 9 + 9) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41460 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 0 \\ 41461 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 1 \\ 41462 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 2 \\ 41463 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 3 \\ 41464 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 4 \\ 41465 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 5 \\ 41466 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 6 \\ 41467 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 7 \\ 41468 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 8 \\ 41469 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) + F(6)! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 42700 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 0 \\ 42701 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 1 \\ 42702 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 2 \\ 42703 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 3 \\ 42704 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 4 \\ 42705 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 5 \\ 42706 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 6 \\ 42707 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 7 \\ 42708 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 8 \\ 42709 &:= F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \times 70 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 44100 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 0 \\ 44101 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 1 \\ 44102 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 2 \\ 44103 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 3 \\ 44104 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 4 \\ 44105 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 5 \\ 44106 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 6 \\ 44107 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 7 \\ 44108 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 8 \\ 44109 &:= C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^{1+0!} + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44270 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 0 \\
 44271 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 1 \\
 44272 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 2 \\
 44273 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 3 \\
 44274 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 4 \\
 44275 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 5 \\
 44276 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 6 \\
 44277 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 7 \\
 44278 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 8 \\
 44279 &:= C(4! - 4, 2) \times F(F(7)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44340 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 0 \\
 44341 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 1 \\
 44342 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 2 \\
 44343 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 3 \\
 44344 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 4 \\
 44345 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 5 \\
 44346 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 6 \\
 44347 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 7 \\
 44348 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 8 \\
 44349 &:= F(4!) - C(4!, 3) - 4 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47520 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 0 \\
 47521 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 1 \\
 47522 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 2 \\
 47523 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 3 \\
 47524 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 4 \\
 47525 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 5 \\
 47526 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 6 \\
 47527 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 7 \\
 47528 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 8 \\
 47529 &:= F(4)!! \times C(7 + 5, 2) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47650 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 0 \\
 47651 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 1 \\
 47652 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 2 \\
 47653 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 3 \\
 47654 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 4 \\
 47655 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 5 \\
 47656 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 6
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47657 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 7 \\
 47658 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 8 \\
 47659 &:= F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6)) - 5 + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53130 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 0 \\
 53131 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 1 \\
 53132 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 2 \\
 53133 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 3 \\
 53134 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 4 \\
 53135 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 5 \\
 53136 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 6 \\
 53137 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 7 \\
 53138 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 8 \\
 53139 &:= C(5^{F(3)}, -1 + 3!) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53450 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 0 \\
 53451 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 1 \\
 53452 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 2 \\
 53453 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 3 \\
 53454 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 4 \\
 53455 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 5 \\
 53456 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 6 \\
 53457 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 7 \\
 53458 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 8 \\
 53459 &:= F(F(5 + 3)) + C(4!, 5) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54360 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 0 \\
 54361 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 1 \\
 54362 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 2 \\
 54363 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 3 \\
 54364 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 4 \\
 54365 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 5 \\
 54366 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 6 \\
 54367 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 7 \\
 54368 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 8 \\
 54369 &:= 5! - 4! + C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54850 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 0 \\
 54851 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 1 \\
 54852 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 2 \\
 54853 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 3
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 54854 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 4 \\ 54855 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 5 \\ 54856 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 6 \\ 54857 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 7 \\ 54858 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 8 \\ 54859 &:= C(5, 4) \times F(F(8)) + 5! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 55440 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 0 \\ 55441 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 1 \\ 55442 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 2 \\ 55443 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 3 \\ 55444 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 4 \\ 55445 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 5 \\ 55446 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 6 \\ 55447 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 7 \\ 55448 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 8 \\ 55449 &:= 5! \times C(5 + F(4)!, F(4)!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63840 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 0 \\ 63841 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 1 \\ 63842 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 2 \\ 63843 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 3 \\ 63844 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 4 \\ 63845 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 5 \\ 63846 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 6 \\ 63847 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 7 \\ 63848 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 8 \\ 63849 &:= F(6) \times 3! \times C(F(8), F(4)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64350 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 0 \\ 64351 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 1 \\ 64352 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 2 \\ 64353 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 3 \\ 64354 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 4 \\ 64355 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 5 \\ 64356 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 6 \\ 64357 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 7 \\ 64358 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 8 \\ 64359 &:= C(-F(6) + 4!, F(3!)) \times 5 + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64630 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 0 \\ 64631 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 1 \\ 64632 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 2 \\ 64633 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 3 \\ 64634 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 4 \\ 64635 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 5 \\ 64636 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 6 \\ 64637 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 7 \\ 64638 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 8 \\ 64639 &:= F(6)! + C(-4 + F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65330 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 0 \\ 65331 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 1 \\ 65332 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 2 \\ 65333 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 3 \\ 65334 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 4 \\ 65335 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5 \\ 65336 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 6 \\ 65337 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 7 \\ 65338 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 8 \\ 65339 &:= F(F(F(6))) + 5! + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65340 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 0 \\ 65341 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 1 \\ 65342 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 2 \\ 65343 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 3 \\ 65344 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 4 \\ 65345 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 5 \\ 65346 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 6 \\ 65347 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 7 \\ 65348 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 8 \\ 65349 &:= (-C(F(6), 5) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4)! + 9 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 73840 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 0 \\ 73841 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 1 \\ 73842 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 2 \\ 73843 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 3 \\ 73844 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 4 \\ 73845 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 5 \\ 73846 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 6 \\ 73847 &:= (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$73848 := (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 8$$

$$73849 := (-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) \times F(F(4)!) + 9$$

$$73990 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 0$$

$$73991 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 1$$

$$73992 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 2$$

$$73993 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 3$$

$$73994 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 4$$

$$73995 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 5$$

$$73996 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 6$$

$$73997 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 7$$

$$73998 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 8$$

$$73999 := 7! - C(F(F(3!)), 9) + 9! + 9$$

$$74480 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 0$$

$$74481 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 1$$

$$74482 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 2$$

$$74483 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 3$$

$$74484 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 4$$

$$74485 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 5$$

$$74486 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 6$$

$$74487 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 7$$

$$74488 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 8$$

$$74489 := 7 \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8) + 9$$

$$84420 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 0$$

$$84421 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 1$$

$$84422 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 2$$

$$84423 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 3$$

$$84424 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 4$$

$$84425 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 5$$

$$84426 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 6$$

$$84427 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 7$$

$$84428 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 8$$

$$84429 := 8! + C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(F(4)))^2 + 9$$

2.2.2 Non Symmetric and Consecutive

$$364 := C((3! + F(6)), F(4))$$

$$444 := (((F(4)!)! - C(4!, F(F(4))))$$

$$448 := (C(F((F(4)!)), F(4)) \times 8)$$

$$610 := F(C(6, (1 + 0!)))$$

$$634 := (F(C(6, F(3))) + (4!))$$

$$664 := (6! - C(F(6), F(4)))$$

$$1329 := (- (1) + C(F(F(3!)), (2 \times 9)))$$

$$1353 := (F((- (1) + F(F(3!)))) / C(5, F(F(3))))$$

$$1364 := (- (1) + C((- (3!) + F(F(6))), 4)$$

$$1547 := ((- (1) + (C(5, 4)!) \times F(7))$$

$$1738 := (1 + (C(F(7), 3!) + F(8)))$$

$$1749 := (- (1) + (C(F(7), (F(4)!) + F(9)))$$

$$2024 := C(((2 + 02)!)!, F(4))$$

$$2044 := (20 + C(4!, F(4)))$$

$$2394 := ((- (2) + F(F(3!))) \times C(9, 4))$$

$$2436 := (C(F((F(2) + (F(4)!)!), 3!) + (6!))$$

$$2442 := (2 + (4 \times F(C((F(4)!)!, 2))))$$

$$2444 := ((F(2) + F(C((F(4)!)!, F(F(4)))))) \times 4$$

$$2732 := (2 + (F(7) \times C(F(F(3!)), 2)))$$

$$2934 := (C(29, 3) - ((F(4)!)!))$$

$$3003 := C((F((3! + 0!)) + 0!), 3!)$$

$$3284 := (F(3!) + (C(28, F(4))))$$

$$3354 := ((C(F(3!), F(3)) \times 5!) - (F(4)!))$$

$$3355 := ((C(F(3!), F(3)) \times 5!) - (5))$$

$$3360 := (C(F(3!), F(3)) \times ((6 - 0!)!))$$

$$3375 := ((C(3!, F(3)) \times F(F(7))) - 5!)$$

$$3393 := (F((3! + F(3!))) \times C(9, F(F(3))))$$

$$3427 := ((3! \times F(C((F(4)!)!, 2))) - F(F(7)))$$

$$3432 := (C(F((3 + 4)), 3!) \times 2)$$

$$3438 := (C((3! \times F(4)), F(3!)) - 8!)$$

$$3477 := -((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) - (7! - F(F(7))))$$

$$3624 := (-((3! - F(C(6, 2)))) \times (F(4)!)$$

$$3633 := (C((F(3!) + F(F(6))), 3) - F(F(3!)))$$

$$3646 := (C((F(3!) + F(F(6))), F(4)) - F(6))$$

$$3647 := ((3! \times F(C(6, 4))) - F(7))$$

$$3747 := (- (3!) - (C(F(7), F((F(4)!)!)) - (7!)))$$

$$4046 := (F(F(4)) \times (- (0!) + C(4!, F(F(6))))$$

$$4048 := ((F(4) - 0!) \times C(4!, F(8)))$$

- 4430** := $-(F(C((F(4))!), F(F(4)))) - ((3! + 0!)!)$
4431 := $(F(F((F(4))!)) \times (C(F(F((F(4))!)), F(3)) + 1))$
4544 := $((F(F((F(4))!)) \times 5!) + (C(4!, F(4))))$
4647 := $((F((F(4))!) \times F(C(6, 4))) - F(F(7)))$
4753 := $-(((F(4))!)! - ((F(C(7, 5)) / F(3))))$
4758 := $(- (C((4! - 7)), 5) + F(F(8)))$
4824 := $-((F(F((F(4))!)) - (C((F(8) - F(2)), 4))))$
4827 := $-((F(4) + (C(F(8), 2) - 7!))$
4848 := $(4! \times (C(F(8), F(F(4))) - 8))$
4942 := $((F(4!) / 9) - C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$
5472 := $(- (5!) - (- (4!) \times F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
5844 := $(- ((5! - C(F(8), 4)) - F(F((F(4))!)))$
5964 := $-((F(F((F(-((5-9))))!)) - (C(F(F(6)), 4))))$
6344 := $((6! \times 3!) + C(4!, F(4)))$
6427 := $(- (F(6)) + C(C((F(4))!), 2), 7))$
6433 := $(C(C(6, 4), F(3!)) - F(3))$
6434 := $(C(C(6, 4), F(3!)) - F(F(F(4))))$
6443 := $(F(6) + C(C((F(4))!), F(F(4))), F(3!))$
6493 := $(F(C(6, F(4))) + (- (F(9)) \times F(3!))$
6498 := $((6! + F(F(4))) \times C(9, 8))$
6543 := $((C(F(F(6)), 5) - ((F(4))!)! / 3)$
6664 := $((F(6))! / 6) - C(F(6), F(4))$
6684 := $((6! - F(F(6))) + C(F(8), 4))$
6733 := $((F(6))! + (C(F(7), F(3)))) / 3!$
6777 := $(F(F(6)) + (C(F(7), 7) + 7!))$
6833 := $(68 + F(C(3!, 3)))$
7237 := $((C(F(7), F(2))^3 + 7!)$
7476 := $(C(F(7), (F(4))!) + (7! + 6!))$
7480 := $(C(F(7), 4) + F((F(8) - 0!))$
7764 := $((7 + C(F(7), F(6))) \times (F(4))!)$
8424 := $(C((F(8) + (F(4))!), 2) \times 4!)$
9044 := $(C(F((9 - 0!)), (F(4))!) / (F(4))!)$
10326 := $((- (10) - F(C(3!, 2))) + F(F(F(6))))$
10338 := $((1 + 0!) - F(C(3!, F(3)))) + F(F(8))$
10346 := $((10 - F(C(3!, 4))) + F(F(F(6))))$
10436 := $((C(10, 4) - 3!) + F(F(F(6))))$
10633 := $(1 + ((- (0!) + C(F(F(6)), 3)) \times F(3!))$
10638 := $((- (1) - 0!) - (C(F(F(6)), 3) \times (-8))$
10644 := $((10 + F(6)) + C(4!, 4))$
10736 := $((F(10) + C(F(7), F(3!))) \times F(6))$
10982 := $((1 + 0!) + F(9)) + F(C(F(8), F(2)))$
11384 := $((C(11, 3!) + F(F(8))) - (4!))$
11408 := $(C(11, (F(4))!) + F(F(08)))$
11440 := $C(((1 + 1)^4), ((F(4))! + 0!))$
11556 := $(F(F(F((C(1, 1) + 5)))) + F((5! / F(6))))$
11576 := $(F(F(F((C(1, 1) + 5)))) + (7! / F(6)))$
11665 := $((- (1) + F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + (C(6, 5)!))$
11933 := $(F(F(-((C(1, 1) - 9)))) + F((F(3) \times F(3!))))$
12144 := $((1 + 2)! \times C(((1 \times 4))!, F(4)))$
12233 := $(F(F(F(((1 + 2))!))) + C(F((F(2) + 3!)), F(3!))$
12368 := $(C((1 + (2 \times F(3!))), 6) - 8)$
12387 := $(1 + ((2 \times 3!) + F(F(C(8, 7))))$
12626 := $((F(((1 + 2))!) \times C(F(F(6)), 2)) + F(F(F(6))))$
12637 := $(C(((1 \times 2) \times F(6)), F(3!)) - F(F(7)))$
12642 := $(F(F(((1 + 2))!)) \times (- (F(6)) + F(C((F(4))!), 2)))$
12644 := $(C(-((1 - 26)), 4) - (F(4))!)$
12663 := $((1 + C(F((F(2) + 6))), 6) + F(F(F(3!))))$
12671 := $(F((1 + F((2 + 6)))) - (C(7, 1)!))$
12848 := $(- (1) + (C((2 \times 8), F((F(4))!) - (F(8))))$
12863 := $(- (1) + (C((2 \times 8), F(6)) - 3!))$
12864 := $(C(((1 \times 2) \times 8), F(6)) - (F(4))!)$
12869 := $(- (1) + C((2 \times 8), F(-((6 - 9))))!))$
13047 := $(- (1) + (C(F(3!), F(04)) \times F(F(7))))$
13233 := $((1 + (C(F(F(3!)), 2) \times F(F(3!)))) \times 3)$
13244 := $(1 + ((F(C(F(3!), 2)) + F(F((F(4))!))) / 4!))$
13246 := $(C(((1 + 3!)^2), F(4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
13310 := $((- (1) - C(F(F(3!)), 3)) \times (-10))$
13346 := $((((- (1) + 3!)! \times C(3!, F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))$
13364 := $(C((- (1) + (3 \times 3!)), F(6)) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
13384 := $((F(13) + 3!) \times C(8, F(4)))$
13385 := $(1 + (((F(3!))! / 3) - C(8, 5)))$
13454 := $(- (1) + (C((3 + 4!), 5) / (F(4))!))$
13461 := $(((- (1) \times (F(3!))!) / (-F(4))) + F(F(C(6, 1))))$
13484 := $((- (1) + F(C(3!, F(4)))) + (8! / (F(4))!))$
13486 := $((1 + F(C(3!, F(4)))) + (8! / 6))$
13633 := $((- (1) + F(F(F(3!)))) + ((F(6))! / C(3!, F(3))))$
13636 := $(- ((F(13) - 6!) \times C(F(3!), 6))$
13637 := $(1 + (C(F(3!), 6) \times (3! - F(F(7))))$
13664 := $((C(13, 6) - F(6)) \times F((F(4))!))$
13727 := $(- (1) + (F(3!) \times C(C(F(7), F(2)), 7)))$

- 13729** := $(1 + (F(3!) \times C(F(7), -(2-9))))$
13730 := $(1 + ((F(3!) \times C(F(7), 3!)) + 0!))$
13733 := $(-1 + ((F(3!) \times C(F(7), 3!)) + 3!))$
13734 := $((F(((1 \times 3)!)) \times C(F(7), 3!)) + (F(4)!))$
13736 := $((1 + C((3! + 7)), 3!)) \times F(6)$
13743 := $(-1 - ((-F(3)) - C(F(7), (F(4)!)) \times F(3!)))$
13744 := $(F(((1 \times 3)!)) \times (C(F(7), (F(4)!)) + F(F(4))))$
13768 := $(((-1) + 3!) + C(F(7), 6)) \times 8$
13934 := $(((-1) - (F(3!)!) - 9) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!))$
13936 := $((1 - (F(3!)!) - 9) + C(F(F(3!)), 6))$
13943 := $(-1 + (C(F(F(3!)), (9 - F(4))) - (F(3!)!))$
14168 := $(C((-1) + 4!), (-1 + F(F(6)))) \times 8$
14327 := $(-1 - (-4!) \times (F(C(3!, 2)) - F(7)))$
14328 := $((1 - F(C((F(4)!), 3))) / (-2)) + F(F(8)))$
14344 := $((((1 + 4)!^{F(3)}) - C(F((F(4)!), F(4))))$
14352 := $(C(((1 \times 4)!), F(3)) \times 52)$
14355 := $((5! \times 5!) - F(F(3!))) - (C(4, 1)!)$
14356 := $(F((1 + 4!)) - (C(F(F(3!)), 5) + (F(6)!))$
14391 := $((((1 + 4)!^{F(3)}) - C(9, 1))$
14399 := $((((1 + 4)!^{F(3)}) - C(9, 9))$
14534 := $(-1 + (F(4) \times C((5!/3!), 4)))$
14536 := $(1 + (C(F(F((F(4)!)), (5 + F(3))) / F(6)))$
14627 := $((((1 \times 4)! \times F(C(6, 2))) - F(7))$
14633 := $(1 + ((4! \times F(C(6, F(3)))) - F(3!))$
14635 := $((((1 \times 4)! \times F(C(6, F(3)))) - (5))$
14653 := $(C((-1) + 4!), F(F(6))) + (5!^{F(3)})$
14663 := $((-1) + ((F(4)!!) - (((F(6)! - C(F(F(6)), 3!))))$
14708 := $(F((1 + F(F((F(4)!)))) - C((F(7) + 0!), 8))$
14743 := $(-((F(14) - (7! \times F(C(4, 3))))$
14767 := $(-1) + ((C(F(F((F(4)!)), 7) / F(6)) + F(F(7)))$
14832 := $((1 \times 4)! \times (8 + F(C(3!, 2))))$
14837 := $(C((1 + 4!), F(8)) + (3^7))$
14844 := $(((-1) \times ((F(4)!!) \times (-F(8))) - C(4!, F(F(4))))$
14931 := $((((F((1 \times 4)!))! - 9) \times F(F((C(3, 1)!)))$
14944 := $(C((-1) + (F(4) \times 9)), 4) - (F(4)!)$
14950 := $C((-1) + (F(4) \times 9)), (5 - 0!)$
14951 := $(1 + C(-((F((F(4)!)) - F(9))), (5 - 1)))$
15361 := $((1 + 5!)^{F(3)} + (C(6, 1)!)$
15385 := $((1 - 5!) + C(-((F(F(3)) - (F(8))))), 5)$
15455 := $((F((-((1 - 5)))!) / F(4)) - C(5, 5))$
15494 := $((C(15, F(4)) \times F(9)) + 4!)$
15653 := $(C(F((1 + 5)), 6) + (5^{3!}))$
15943 := $((C(15, 9) - F((F(4)!)) + F(F(F(3!))))$
15946 := $((1 - 5!) \times (-C(9, 4) - F(6)))$
16380 := $(-1) - (C(F(F(6)), 3) - F((F(8) + 0!)))$
16436 := $((1 + F(6)) \times F(C((F(4)!), F(3)))) + F(F(F(6)))$
16443 := $((-1) + F(C(6, 4))) \times (4! + 3)$
16545 := $((1 + F(6))^5 - C(4!, 5))$
16730 := $((F((1 + 6)) \times C(F(7), F(3!))) - 0!)$
16731 := $(F((1 + 6)) \times C(F(7), (3! - 1)))$
16732 := $((F((1 + 6)) \times C(F(7), F(3!))) + F(2))$
16733 := $((F((1 + 6)) \times C(F(7), F(3!))) + F(3))$
16734 := $((F((1 + 6)) \times C(F(7), F(3!))) + F(4))$
16737 := $((1 \times 6) + (C(F(7), F(3!)) \times F(7)))$
16747 := $(16 + (C(F(7), F((F(4)!)) \times F(7)))$
17134 := $(C(17, (-1) + 3!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))$
17184 := $((1 + C(F(7), (1 + 8))) \times 4!)$
17346 := $(C((-1) + F(7)), F(3)) + (4! \times 6!)$
17416 := $(C(17, (F(4)!)) + ((1 + 6)!))$
17417 := $(C(17, (F(4)!)) + (1 + 7!))$
17661 := $((1 + (7!/6)) \times F(F(C(6, 1))))$
17844 := $(-(((1 - 7)))! - C((F(8) - F(4)), (F(4)!)))$
17931 := $(C((-1) + F(7)), 9) + F((F(F(3!)) + 1))$
17994 := $((C((1 + F(7)), 9) \times 9) - 4!)$
17996 := $((1 + C(F(7), 9)) - (-9!) / F(F(6)))$
18320 := $((F((1 + F(8))) + F(C(3!, 2))) - 0!)$
18321 := $(F((1 + F(8))) + F(C(3!, C(2, 1))))$
18323 := $((F((1 + F(8))) + F(C(3!, 2))) + F(3))$
18324 := $((F((1 + F(8))) + F(C(3!, 2))) + F(4))$
18331 := $(C(18, 3!) - F(F((3! + 1)))$
18333 := $((C(18, F(3)) + 3!) \times F(F(3!))$
18337 := $((C(18, 3!) + 3!) - F(F(7)))$
18342 := $((F((1 + F(8))) + F(F(3!))) + F(C((F(4)!), 2)))$
18354 := $((C(18, F(3)) \times 5!) - (F(4)!)$
18355 := $((C(18, F(3)) \times 5!) - (5))$
18360 := $(C(18, F(3)) \times ((6 - 0!)!)$
18438 := $(C(18, (F(4)!)) - ((3! \times F(8))))$
18445 := $(1 + (C((F(8) - F(4)), (F(4)!)) - 5!))$
18457 := $(C(18, (F(4)!)) - ((5! - F(7))))$
18465 := $((C(18, (F(4)!)) + F(F(6))) - 5!)$

- 18485** := $((- (F(18)) + ((F(4))!)!) + (C(F(8), 5)))$
18494 := $((- (1) - C(F(8), 4)) - (- (F(9)) \times ((F(4))!)!))$
18562 := $(C(18, ((- (5) + F(6))!)!) - 2)$
18573 := $((1 + 8) + C((5 + F(7)), 3!))$
18634 := $(C(18, 6) + C(F(3!), 4))$
18653 := $(C(18, 6) + F((5 + 3!)))$
18684 := $(C(18, 6) + ((8 - F(4))!))$
18765 := $((- ((- (1 - 8)))! - C(F(7), F(6))) \times 5)$
18767 := $((- (1) - ((- (8) \times C(F(7), 6)) - 7!))$
18768 := $((- ((1 - 8))!) + (C(F(7), 6) \times 8))$
18797 := $(C(18, (F((F(7) - 9))!)) + F(F(7)))$
19380 := $(C(19, 3) \times (F(8) - 0!))$
20132 := $(((((2 + 0!)!)! - 1) \times C(F(3!), 2))$
20244 := $(C(F(((2 + 0!)!)!), 2) \times (F(4) + ((F(4))!)!))$
20285 := $-(((2^{0!+2!}) - (C(F(8), 5))))$
20341 := $-((F(((2 + 0!)!) - C(F(F(3!)), (4 + 1))))$
20345 := $((2 - (03)!) + C(F(F((F(4))!)), 5))$
20346 := $((- (2) - 0!) + C(F(F(3!)), -((F(4) - F(6))))$
20348 := $((- (F(2)) + C(F(F((03)!)!), -((F(4) - 8))))$
20365 := $((2^{0!+3}) + C(F(F(6)), 5))$
20385 := $((((2 + 0!)!)^{F(3)} + (C(F(8), 5)))$
20544 := $(C(20, 5) + ((F(4) + (4))!))$
20547 := $((C(20, 5) + F(4)) + 7!)$
20574 := $(C(F(F(((2 + 0!)!)), 5) + (F(F(7)) - F((F(4))!)))$
20576 := $(C(F(F(((2 + 0!)!)), 5) + ((F(F(7)) - 6)))$
20582 := $(C(F(F(((2 + 0!)!)), 5) + F(F((8 - F(2))))$
20636 := $((C(F(F(((2 + 0!)!)), F(6)) / F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(6))))$
20878 := $(C(((- (2) - 0!) + F(8)), 7) - F(F(8)))$
20995 := $(C(20, 9) / F((F(9 - 5))!))$
21244 := $-((F(((2 + 1))!) - (2 \times C(4!, 4)))$
21254 := $(2 \times (1 + C((- ((F(2) - (5))))!, 4)))$
21282 := $-((F(C(((2 + 1))!, 2)) + (F(F(8)) \times (-2)))$
21342 := $(2 \times ((1 + F(F(F(3!)))) - (C(4!, 2)))$
21652 := $((F(F((C(2, 1) + 6))) - 5!) \times 2)$
21734 := $(2 \times ((- (1) - C(F(7), F(3))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
21756 := $((F(((2 + 1))!)!) - C((F(7) + (5)), 6))$
22176 := $((2 + 2)! \times C((- (1) + F(7)), 6))$
22434 := $((C(((2 + 2))!, (F(4))!) + F(3!)) / (F(4)!))$
22444 := $(2 \times (F(F((2 \times 4))) + C(4!, F(F(4))))$
22446 := $(2 \times ((F(2) + C(4!, F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))$
22448 := $(2 \times (2 + (C(4!, F(F(4))) + F(F(8))))$
22665 := $((- (F(22)) + (F(6))!) + (C(F(6), 5)))$
22693 := $((- (F(22)) + (F(6))!) + C(9, 3))$
22745 := $((F(22) + 7!) - C((F(4))!, 5))$
22751 := $(F(22) + (C(7, (5 + 1))))$
22772 := $((F(22) + 7!) + (C(7, 2)))$
22935 := $((2 + F((2 \times 9))) + C(F(F(3!)), 5))$
23178 := $((2 \times F(F(F(3!))) - (1 - C(F(7), 8)))$
23252 := $(2 \times (C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 5) - 2))$
23253 := $((2 \times C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 5)) - 3)$
23254 := $(2 \times (C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 5) - F(F(F(4))))$
23255 := $((- (F(2)) + (C(F(F(3!)), (2 + 5)) / 5))$
23377 := $((2 \times (F(C(3!, 3)) + (7!)) - F(F(7)))$
23436 := $((C(((F(2) + 3))!, 4) \times 3!) - (F(6))!)$
23473 := $((- (2) - F(C(3!, F(4)))) + (7! \times 3!))$
23474 := $((- (F(2)) - F(C(3!, F(4)))) + (7! \times (F(4))!))$
23476 := $((F(2) - F(C(3!, F(4)))) + (7! \times 6))$
23637 := $((F(23) + C(6, 3)) - 7!)$
23698 := $((- (23) + 6!) \times F(C(9, 8)))$
23733 := $(((- (2) + F(F(3!))) \times C(F(7), F(3!))) - (3!))$
23743 := $(C(((2 \times F(3!)) + F(7)), 4) - F(3!))$
23751 := $C(((2 \times F(3!)) + F(7)), (5 - 1))$
23816 := $(C((2 \times F(3!)), 8) + F(F(F((1 \times 6))))$
23827 := $(F(23) + (C(F(8), 2) - 7!))$
23844 := $((F(2) + 3) \times (C(F(8), 4) - 4!))$
23944 := $((F(2) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(9) / F(F(4)))) \times 4)$
24024 := $(C((2^4), ((0! + 2))!) \times F(4))$
24225 := $(C((- (F(2)) + F(F((F(4))!))), (2 + 2)) \times 5)$
24249 := $((- (C((- (2) + 4!), 2)) - (((F(4))!)! \times (-F(9))))$
24254 := $((- (F(2)) + ((F(F((F(4))!)^2) \times F(C(5, F(4))))$
24269 := $((- (F(2)) - (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2) - ((6! \times F(9))))$
24287 := $((- (F(2)) + (((4!)! \times 2) / (F(C(8, 7))!))$
24309 := $-((F(2) - C(((4! - 3!) - 0!), 9))$
24356 := $((2 \times F(C((F(4))!, 3))) - 5!) + F(F(F(6)))$
24375 := $(C((2 + 4!), F(3)) \times 75)$
24427 := $((F(2) - F(F((F(4))!))) - (F(C(F((F(4))!), 2)) / (-F(7)))$
24437 := $((- (2) - F((F(4))!)) + (F(C(F((F(4))!), F(3))) / F(7)))$
24440 := $((F(2) + F(C((F(4))!, F(F(4)))) \times 40)$
24472 := $(2 \times (C(4!, (F(4))!) / (F(7) - 2)))$
24479 := $((- (F(2)) + ((- ((C(4, 4) - 7))!) \times F(9)))$

- 24514** := ((F(2) + ((F(4))!)) × F((C(5, 1) + 4)))
24528 := (- (2) + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 5) + F((- (2) + F(8))))
24535 := (F((- (2) + F(F((F(4))!))) - (- (5) - C(F(F(3!)), 5)))
24637 := (F((F(2) + 4!)) - C((F(F(6)) - F(3)), 7))
24736 := (2 × (C((4! - 7)), 3!) - F(6))
24746 := (- (2) × (F(4) - C((- (7) + 4!), 6)))
24815 := ((- (F(2)) + F((F(4))!)) - (C((F(8) - 1), 5)))
24842 := (2 + (((F(4))!)/8) × C(4!, 2))
24933 := (- (F((2⁴))) + (C(9, F(3)) × 3!))
25082 := (2 - (5! × (0! - C(F(8), 2)))
25255 := ((5 × ((5 + 2))!) + F(C(5, 2)))
25257 := ((2 + F(C(5, 2))) - (- (5) × 7!))
25284 := (2 × (C((5²), F(8)) - F((F(4))!)))
25300 := (C(25, F(F(3!))) × (0! + 0!))
25302 := ((C(25, F(F(3!))) + 0!) × 2)
25320 := ((F(2) × 5!) × (C(F(F(3!)), 2) + 0!))
25321 := (F(2) + (5! × (C(F(F(3!)), 2) + 1)))
25322 := (2 - (- (5!) × (C(F(F(3!)), 2) + F(2)))
25324 := ((C(25, F(F(3!))) × 2) + (4!))
25357 := (- ((2⁵)) + (C(F(F(3!)), 5) + (7!)))
25374 := (- (F(2)) + ((5 + 3!) × C(7, 4)))
25392 := (C((- ((F(2) - 5)))!, F(3)) × 92)
25436 := (- (((2 + (C(5, 4))!)^{F(3)})) + (F(6))!)
25442 := (2 + (5! × (C(F(F((F(4))!)), F(F(4))) + 2)))
25454 := (C(F((2 + 5)), F(4)) × F((5 + (F(4))!)))
25458 := (- (2) + (C((5 + F(F((F(4))!))), 5) - 8!))
25464 := (((- (2) × (5!^{F(F(4))})) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!))
25475 := ((F((2 × C(5, 4))) + 7!) × 5)
25644 := (((2 + 5!) × C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) + (4!))
25734 := ((- (2) + (5 × C(F(7), 3!))) × F(4))
25738 := (- (2) - ((5! × C(F(7), 3!)) / (-8)))
25743 := ((F(2) + (5 × C(F(7), (F(4))!))) × 3)
25933 := (F((2 + 5)) + (C(9, F(3)) × 3!))
25985 := (F((- ((F(2) - 5)))!) - (F(9) + C(F(8), 5)))
25992 := ((2 + ((F(- ((5 - 9)))!)) × C(9, 2))
26313 := (C((F(2) + F(F(6))), (3! - 1)) - F(F(3!)))
26315 := ((2 - F(F(6))) + C((F(F(3!)) + 1), 5))
26325 := (- ((F(2) + F(6))) + C((F(F(3!)) + F(2)), 5))
26344 := (((F(2) + F(C(6, 3))) × 4) - ((F(4))!))
26346 := ((F((- (2) + F(F(6)))) + C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4)))) × 6)
26368 := ((2 × (F(6))!) - (C(F(F(3!)), 6) + 8))
26373 := ((F((- (2) + F(F(6)))) × 3!) + (C(F(7), F(3!))))
26376 := ((2 × (F(6))!) - C((3 × 7), 6))
26384 := (F((F(2) + F(6))) × (3! + C(8, F(4))))
26412 := (C((- (2) + F(F(6))), (F(4))!) - (((1 + 2))!))
26413 := ((C((- (2) + F(F(6))), (F(4))!) + 1) - 3!))
26455 := (F(2) + (C((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4))))), 5) + 5!))
26565 := ((C((- ((2 - 6))!), 5) / (-F(6))) × (-5))
26573 := ((C((F(2) + F(F(6))), 5) + F(F(7))) + 3!))
26574 := (C((F(2) + F(F(6))), 5) + (7! / F(F((F(4))!))))
26733 := ((F((2 × F(6))) + (C(F(7), 3))) × F(F(3!)))
26736 := (((2 × F(6)) × C(F(7), 3!)) - 6!))
26796 := (F((- ((2 - 6))!) - (F(F(7)) × C(9, 6)))
27026 := (- (F(2)) - (C(F(7), F(((0! + 2))!)) × (-F(F(6))))
27028 := (F(2) - (C(F(7), F(((0! + 2))!)) × (-F(8)))
27048 := ((F(2) + C(F(7), (0! + 4))) × F(8))
27054 := (C((F(2) + F((7 + 0!))), 5) + ((F(4))!))
27131 := (C((- (2) + F((7 + 1))), 3!) - 1)
27133 := (F(2) + C((F(7) + ((1 × 3))!), 3!))
27134 := (C((- (2) + F((7 + 1))), 3!) + F(F(4)))
27345 := (((C((- (2) + F(7)), 3)^{F(F(4))}) + 5!))
27384 := (((2 - F(F(7))) + 3!) × C(8, F(4)))
27424 := (((- (2) + C(F(7), (F(4))!)) × (2⁴))
27454 := (- (2) + (C(F(7), F(4)) × (5! - 4!)))
27464 := (2 × ((C(F(7), (F(4))!) × F(6)) + 4))
27466 := (- (2) + ((C(F(7), F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(6)))) × F(F(6))))
27475 := ((C((2 + F(7)), F(4)) + 7!) × 5)
27594 := (((- (2) + F(F(7))) × 5!) - C(9, 4))
27648 := (((2 × C(F(7), 6)) + 4!) × 8)
27649 := (- ((F(2) - 7!) - (C(F(F(6)), F((F(4))!)) / (-9)))
27791 := ((2 × 7!) + F((F(7) + C(9, 1))))
27814 := - ((F(F((F(2) + 7))) - (C((F(8) - 1), (F(4))!))))
27937 := - (((- ((F(2) - 7)))! - F((C(9, F(3)) - F(7))))
27940 := ((- (2) - C(F(7), 9)) + F((4! - 0!)))
27941 := (- ((F(2) + C(F(7), 9))) + F((4! - 1)))
27942 := (- (C((F(2) × F(7)), 9)) + F((4! - F(2))))
27944 := (((F(2) + 7))! - C((F(9) / F(F(4))), (F(4))!))
28244 := (- (F(2)) + (C((F(8) + F(2)), (F(4))!) - F(4!)))
28327 := ((2 × F(F(8))) + C(C(3!, 2), 7))
28342 := (F((2 + F(8))) - (F(F(3!)) × C((F(4))!, 2)))

$$\begin{aligned}
 28349 &:= (-((F(2) - 8!)) + (C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) \times (-9))) \\
 28432 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (C((F(4)!), F(3))^2)) \\
 28444 &:= (2 \times (F(F(8)) + (C((4! + 4), F(4)))) \\
 28465 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (4! \times F(C(6, 5)))) \\
 28536 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5! + C(3!, 6))) \\
 28541 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (5! - C(4, 1))) \\
 28630 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) - (C(F(6), F(3)) - 0!)) \\
 28652 &:= ((- (2) - F(F(8))) + (6! \times F(C(5, 2)))) \\
 28653 &:= ((2 + F((C(8, 6) - 5))) - 3!) \\
 28797 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (7!/C(9, 7))) \\
 28837 &:= -((F(F(-((F(2) - 8)))) + (C(F(8), F(3!)) / (-7))) \\
 28942 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + (9 + C(4!, 2))) \\
 29254 &:= (-((F(C(-((2 - 9)), 2)) + 5!)) + (F((F(4)!)))! \\
 29361 &:= ((- (F(-((2 - 9)))) + (F(3!))! - F(F(F(C(6, 1)))) \\
 29372 &:= ((- (2) + (F((9 - 3)))! - (F(C(7, 2)))) \\
 30373 &:= (F(((3 + 0)! - F(F(3)))) + C(F(7), 3!)) \\
 30645 &:= (3! - (C(F(F(06)), 4) \times (-5)) \\
 30675 &:= (- (3) \times ((0! + 6!) - F(C(7, 5))) \\
 30681 &:= (3 \times ((0! - 6!) + F(F(C(8, 1)))) \\
 30888 &:= (((3 + 0)! \times C((- (8) + F(8)), 8)) \\
 31295 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + C((12 + 9), 5)) \\
 31344 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), (1 \times 3)) - (4!)) \times 4! \\
 31444 &:= (((F(3!))! - C((- (1) + 4!), 4)) - F(F((F(4)!))) \\
 31549 &:= ((C(((3 + 1)!), 5) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - 9) \\
 31553 &:= ((C(((3 + 1)!), 5) - (5)) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 31554 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - (C((- ((1 - 5)))!, 5) - 4)) \\
 31556 &:= ((- (F(3)) + C((- ((1 - 5)))!, 5)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 31558 &:= (C(((3 + (1^5)))!, 5) - F(F(8))) \\
 31564 &:= ((C(((3 + 1)!), 5) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4)!)) \\
 31566 &:= ((C(((3 + 1)!), 5) + F(6)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 31577 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) - C(15, 7)) \times 7) \\
 31735 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((1 + C(F(7), 3!)) \times 5)) \\
 31745 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((- (1) + C(F(7), (F(4)!)) \times (-5))) \\
 31786 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), (- (1) + F(7))) - (8^6)) \\
 31803 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - (C(18, (0! + 3!)))) \\
 31816 &:= -((F(3!) - (C(18, (1 + 6)))) \\
 31823 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (C(18, (F(2) + 3!)))) \\
 31832 &:= (F(3!) + (C(18, (3! + F(2)))) \\
 31837 &:= (F((3! + 1)) + C((F(8) - 3), 7)) \\
 31845 &:= (F(F(3!)) + (C(18, ((F(4)! + (5))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 31879 &:= (F(F(3!)) - (- (C(18, 7)) - F(9))) \\
 32064 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), (2 + 0!)) + 6) \times 4! \\
 32228 &:= -((F(C(3!, 2)) - (F((2 + 2)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 32234 &:= (- (F(C(3!, 2))) + ((2 + F(F(F(3!)))) \times F(4))) \\
 32235 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (C(22, 3) - 5)) \\
 32296 &:= ((F(C(3!, 2)) \times (F(2) + F(9))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 32312 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((2 \times F(3!)), ((1 + 2)!))) \\
 32313 &:= (- ((C((F(3!) \times 2), 3!) - 1)) + (F(3!))! \\
 32313 &:= ((F(3!))! + (1 - C((F(3!) \times 2), 3!))) \\
 32333 &:= (((F(3!))! - (C((2 \times F(3!)), 3!))) + F(F(3!))) \\
 32333 &:= (((F(3!))! + F(F(3!))) - C((F(3!) \times 2), 3!)) \\
 32334 &:= ((C((F(F(3!)) + F(2)), 3) \times F(F(3!))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 32338 &:= (- (F(3)) + (C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), 3) \times F(8))) \\
 32340 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F((4 + 0))) \\
 32341 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4))) + 1) \\
 32342 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4))) + 2) \\
 32343 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) \times F(4)) - C((3! \times 2), F(3!))) \\
 32343 &:= (3 + (C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4)) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 32345 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4))) + (5)) \\
 32346 &:= (3! + (C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 32347 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4))) + 7) \\
 32348 &:= (F(3!) + (C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4)) \times F(8))) \\
 32349 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4))) + 9) \\
 32355 &:= (C((5 + 5), F(3)) \times (- (F(2)) + 3!)) \\
 32366 &:= ((F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2)) - (3! - C(F(F(6)), 6))) \\
 32383 &:= (- (C(C(3!, 2), 3)) + (F(F(8)) \times 3)) \\
 32384 &:= (F(3!) \times (2 \times C((3 \times 8), F(4)))) \\
 32403 &:= (((- (C(3!, 2)) \times ((F(4)!))! - 0!) \times (-3)) \\
 32448 &:= (F(3!) \times ((2 \times C(4!, F(4))) + 8)) \\
 32463 &:= ((F(C(3!, 2)) - (4^{F(6)})) / (-F(3))) \\
 32604 &:= ((F(F(3!)) - 2) \times C(F((F(6) - 0!)), (F(4)!)) \\
 32628 &:= -((C(F(F(3!)), 2) - ((6/2) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 32636 &:= -((C(F(F(3!)), 2) - ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3) + F(6))) \\
 32648 &:= ((C(3!, 2) - (F(6)^4)) \times (-8)) \\
 32676 &:= (((C(F(3!), 2) \times F(F(6))) \times (-F(7))) + (F(6)!)) \\
 32733 &:= ((3 \times F(F(F(3!))) - C((F(7) + 2), F(3))) \\
 32735 &:= ((F(3!) - (F(27))) / (-C(3!, 5))) \\
 32773 &:= (((F(C(3, 2)) + 7!) \times F(7)) / F(3)) \\
 32793 &:= ((- (C(3!, 2)) + F(-((F(7) - F(9)))) \times 3) \\
 32813 &:= -((C(F(3!), 2) - ((F(F(8)) + 1) \times 3))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 32883** := $((C(3!, 2) + F(F(8))) \times F((8/F(3))))$
32893 := $(C(F(3!), 2) + ((F(F(8)) + 9) \times 3))$
32934 := $((F(C(3!, 2)) \times 9) - F(F(3))) \times (F(4)!)$
32935 := $((F(C(3!, 2)) \times (9 \times 3!)) - (5))$
32964 := $((F(C(3!, 2)) \times (9 \times 6)) + (4!))$
33005 := $((F(3!))! - C((F(F(3!)) + 0!), -((0! - (5))))$
33044 := $((F(3!)^{3!-0!}) + C(4!, F(F(4))))$
33048 := $(3 \times (C(F(3!), 04) + F(F(8))))$
33071 := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + F(F(C(07, 1))))$
33072 := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (0! + F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
33093 := $(3 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (0! + (C(9, 3))))$
33154 := $-F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), F(F(-1+5)))^{F(F(4))}$
33178 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) + F((1 + F(7)))) - 8!))$
33224 := $(F(3!) \times (-C(F(3!), 2) + F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!))))))$
33225 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) - F(2)) \times 25)$
33238 := $((C(3!, 3)^2) + (3 \times F(F(8))))$
33245 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times (F(2) + 4!)) - (5))$
33264 := $((3! \times C((3! \times 2), 6)) \times (F(4)!)$
33271 := $((3!! + (F(F(F(3!))) / (-2))) \times (-C(7, 1)))$
33288 := $((-C(3!, 3) + F((-2) + F(8))) \times 8)$
33325 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 3) \times 25)$
33328 := $(F(3!) \times (-C(3!, F(3)) + F((-2) + F(8))))$
33333 := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + C((F(3) \times 3!), F(3!)))$
33333 := $((3 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + C((F(3) \times 3!), F(3!)))$
33344 := $((F(3)^{C(3!, F(3))}) + (4! \times 4!))$
33354 := $(F(C(3!, F(3))) + ((F(3!)^5) - (4!)))$
33355 := $((F(3!))! - C((F(3) + F(F(3!))), 5)) \times 5)$
33355 := $(-5) \times ((-5) \times C(F(F(3!)), 3) - F(F(3!)))$
33376 := $((C(F(3!), 3)^{F(3)} + (7! \times 6))$
33378 := $((F(3)^{C(3!, F(3))}) + F((7 + 8)))$
33427 := $((F(3!))! - (F(C(3!, F(4))) + (2^7)))$
33428 := $(-C(3!, 3) + (F((F(4)!)) \times F((-2) + F(8))))$
33433 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) + (4^{F(3!)})) / F(3))$
33433 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) + (4^{F(3!)})) / F(3))$
33435 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - ((4!/3)!) + 5!))$
33462 := $(3 \times ((C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 2))$
33463 := $(C(3!, F(3)) + (F((F(4)!)) \times F((F(F(6)) - F(3))))$
33464 := $((F(3)^{C(3!, 4)}) + (6! - 4!))$
33466 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) + F((F(4) + F(6)))) - (F(6)!))$
33468 := $(3 \times (C((3! + 4), 6) + F(F(8))))$
33535 := $(C((F(3) + F(F(3!))), 5) + ((3! - 5!))$
33542 := $(-F(3!)) + (F((F(3) \times 5)) \times F(C((F(4)!), 2)))$
33544 := $((F(C(3!, F(3))) \times F(C(5, F(4)))) - (F(4)!)$
33545 := $((F(C(3!, F(3))) \times F(C(5, F(4)))) - (5))$
33560 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) - (5)) - (F(6)!)) \times (-0!))$
33561 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - (5)) - (F(6)!)) - 1))$
33562 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - (5)) - (F(6)!)) - 2))$
33563 := $(F(3!) + (((3 + 5)! - F(C(6, 3))))$
33565 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - (5)) - (F(6)!)) - (5))$
33569 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - (5)) - (F(6)!)) - 9))$
33591 := $((F(3!)/3!) \times 5) - C(9, 1)$
33599 := $((F(3!)/3!) \times 5) - C(9, 9)$
33600 := $(C(F(3!), 3) \times 600)$
33610 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - (F(6)!)) - (F(10))))$
33625 := $((F(3!) \times (-3)) + C((F(F(6)) + 2), 5))$
33628 := $((F(3!)/(-3!)) + ((C(F(6), 2) + 8!))$
33635 := $((-3!) - F(3!)) + C((F(F(6)) + F(3)), 5)$
33641 := $-((F(3!) - C((F(3) + F(F(6))), (4 + 1))))$
33643 := $((C(((F(3) + F(3!))!), 6) / 4) - 3!)$
33649 := $C((C(3!, F(3)) + F(6)), -(4 - 9))$
33650 := $(C((C(3!, F(3)) + F(6)), 5) + 0!)$
33684 := $((F(C(3!, F(3))) - 6) \times (-F(8))) + F(4!)$
33745 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) - (F(7) + F(4))) \times 5)$
33754 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) - F(7)) \times 5) - (F(4)!)$
33755 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) - F(7)) \times 5) - (5))$
33755 := $(-5) + (-5) \times (F(7) - F(C(3!, 3)))$
33760 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) - F(7)) \times (6 - 0!))$
33764 := $-(((F(C(3!, 3)) - F(F(7))) - (F(6)!)) + (4!))$
33765 := $((-C(C(3!, F(3)), 7) + (F(6)!)) - 5!)$
33766 := $-(((3^{F(3!)} - C(7, 6)) - (F(6)!))$
33788 := $-(((C(F(3!), F(3)) \times F(F(7))) + (8 - 8!))$
33833 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) \times (8 - 3)) + F(3!))$
33833 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) \times (8 - 3)) + F(3!))$
33845 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) + (8 - 4)) \times 5)$
33855 := $((3! + F(C(3!, (8 - 5)))) \times 5)$
33855 := $(5 \times ((-((5 - 8)!)) + F(C(3!, 3))))$
33877 := $((F(3!))! - (F(3!) + C((8 + 7), 7)))$
33878 := $-(((C(C(3!, F(3)), 8) + (7)) - 8!))$
33883 := $-(((C(C(3!, F(3)), 8) - 8!) + F(3!))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33884 &:= (-((C(C(3!, F(3)), 8) - 8!)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 33886 &:= (F(F(3)) - (C(-((3! - F(8))), 8) - (F(6)!)) \\
 33888 &:= (3 - (C(-((3! - F(8))), 8) - 8!)) \\
 33896 &:= (C(F(3!), 3) + (8! + (-9) \times 6!)) \\
 33913 &:= (- (F(3)) + (C(F(-((1 - 9))), F(3!)) / 3!)) \\
 33915 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), F(3!)) / (((9 - 1) - 5)!)) \\
 33916 &:= (F(F(3)) - (C(F(F(3!)), (9 - 1)) / (-6)) \\
 33923 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), -((F(2) - 9))) / 3! + F(3!)) \\
 33949 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F(3!)) / (9 - F(4))) + F(9)) \\
 33957 &:= -((F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(3!)) - (C(9, 5) \times F(7)))) \\
 33965 &:= ((F(C(3!, 3)) + (F(9) - (6))) \times 5) \\
 34035 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F((F(4)!)) / (03!) + 5!)) \\
 34123 &:= -F(C(F(3!), 2)) + (1 + F(F(4)!)) - F(F(F(3!))) \\
 34154 &:= ((C(F(3!), F(4)) \times F(15)) - (F(4)!)) \\
 34155 &:= ((C(F(3!), F(4)) \times F(15)) - (5)) \\
 34160 &:= (C(F(3!), F(4)) \times F((16 - 0!)) \\
 34215 &:= -(((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(((2 + 1)!))!)) + 5!)) \\
 34216 &:= (((F(3!))! \times (F(C((F(4)!), 2)) + 1)) / 6!)) \\
 34248 &:= ((- (3) \times C(4!, F((2 \times 4)))) + 8!)) \\
 34274 &:= ((3! \times (4! \times 2)) - (C(F(7), F(4)))) \\
 34279 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((C((F(4)!), 2) - (7!)) \times (-9)))) \\
 34307 &:= (C((F(3!) + (F(4)!)), F(3)) \times F((0! + F(7)))) \\
 34313 &:= -(((C(F(F(3!)), 4) + F(F(3!))) + 1) - (F(3!))!) \\
 34314 &:= -F(3!) + F(F(F(4)!)) + C(F(F(3!) + 1, F(4)!)) \\
 34320 &:= (C(F((3 + 4)), 3!) \times 20) \\
 34323 &:= -(((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))! + (2 \times 3!)) \\
 34323 &:= ((3! \times (-2)) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))!)) \\
 34325 &:= -(((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))! + (2 \times 5)) \\
 34328 &:= -((C(F(F(3!)), 4) + ((3! + F(2)) - 8!)) \\
 34329 &:= (3 \times (F(4) + C((F(3!) \times 2), 9))) \\
 34330 &:= -(((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))! + (3! - 0!)) \\
 34331 &:= (((F(3!))! - 4) - C(F(F(3!)), (3 + 1))) \\
 34332 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), 4) + 3) - (F(3!))! \times (-F(2))) \\
 34333 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), 4) \times (-F(F(3)))) + (F(3!))! - F(3)) \\
 34333 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C(F(F((3 + 3))), 4) + F(3))) \\
 34334 &:= (((F(3!))! - F(F(F(4)))) - (C(F(F((3 + 3))), 4)) \\
 34339 &:= (((F(3!))! + 4) - C(F(F(3!)), (F(3!) + 9))) \\
 34340 &:= (((F(3!))! + 4) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - 0!)) \\
 34341 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))! - (F(4)!)) \times (-1)) \\
 34342 &:= (((F(3!))! + (F(4)!)) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - F(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34343 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((4! - 3), 4) - F(3!))) \\
 34343 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((4! - 3), 4) - F(3!))) \\
 34346 &:= ((F(3!) \times C((4! + 3), 4!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 34348 &:= (3! + ((C(4!, 3!) / 4) - F(8))) \\
 34354 &:= -(((F(3!) - C((4! + 3), 5)) + F(4!)) \\
 34359 &:= (((F(3!))! + (4!)) - C(F(F(3!)), -((5 - 9)))) \\
 34365 &:= (F((C(3!, 4) + F(3))) + (F(6)^5)) \\
 34372 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) - F(3!)) \times (F(7) \times 2)) \\
 34374 &:= ((F(3) - C(4!, 3)) \times (7 - 4!)) \\
 34390 &:= -(((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))! - F((9 + 0!)))) \\
 34394 &:= ((- (C(3!, F(4))) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (-9!) / F((F(4)!))) \\
 34398 &:= (C((3 + 4!), F(3)) \times 98) \\
 34424 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) - (F(4)!)) \times (2 + 4!)) \\
 34426 &:= (-(((3! - F(4!)) + C(4!, 2))) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 34429 &:= (F(F(3!)) + ((C(4!, F(4)) / 2) \times F(9))) \\
 34442 &:= ((F(F(3!)) - 4) \times (C(4!, F(4)) + 2)) \\
 34458 &:= -((C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (((F(4) + 5!) + 8!))) \\
 34468 &:= -((C(F(3!), F(4)) - ((F(4!) / (-F(6))) + 8!)) \\
 34482 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4))) - ((F(4!) + (8! \times (-2)))) \\
 34543 &:= (((F(C(3!, F(4))) \times 5) - F(F(4))) + 3!) \\
 34543 &:= (((F(C(3!, F(4))) \times 5) - F(F(4))) + 3!) \\
 34563 &:= (((F(3) \times (C(6, 5)!)) \times 4!) + 3) \\
 34580 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) \times (5 + F((8 + 0)))) \\
 34588 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) \times (5 + F(8))) + 8) \\
 34595 &:= ((F(C(3!, F(4))) + (5! + F(9))) \times 5) \\
 34635 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F((F(4)!)) / 6) + (3! \times 5!)) \\
 34636 &:= (3! + (((F(4)! + C(F(F(6)), F(3!))) / 6)) \\
 34642 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + F(((6 \times 4) - F(2)))) \\
 34643 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), F((F(4)!)) / 6) + F((F(4)!)) + (3!)) \\
 34643 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), F((F(4)!)) / 6) + F((F(4)!)) + (3!)) \\
 34646 &:= ((- (C(F(3!), F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(4!) - (6!)) \\
 34664 &:= (C(C(3!, F(4)), 6) - (F(6)^4)) \\
 34702 &:= -(((3! - F(4!)) + F(C(7, 02)))) \\
 34725 &:= F(C(3!, F(4))) + F(F(7)) \times F(2) \times 5! \\
 34731 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - C(3, 1))) \\
 34743 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - C((F(4)!), F(3)))) \\
 34743 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((4! \times F(F(7))) - C((F(4)!), F(3)))) \\
 34748 &:= (C(3!, F(4)) + ((F(F(7)) \times (-4!)) + 8!)) \\
 34749 &:= ((3 + 4!) \times C(F(7), -((4 - 9)))) \\
 34750 &:= (((3 + 4!) \times C(F(7), 5)) + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 34757 &:= (((F(C(3!, F(4)))) + F(F(7))) \times 5) - F(F(7))) \\
 34759 &:= (F(C(3!, F(4))) - ((F(F(7)) \times (-5!)) - F(9))) \\
 34770 &:= (F(C(3!, 4)) \times (- (F(7) - 70))) \\
 34777 &:= (((C(F(3!), 4) - (7!)) \times (-7)) - F(7)) \\
 34778 &:= (((F(C(3!, F(4))) - F(F(7))) \times 7) - F(F(8))) \\
 34785 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + ((7!/F(8)) \times 5!)) \\
 34788 &:= (3! \times ((-4) \times C(F(7), 8)) + F(F(8))) \\
 34848 &:= ((3!! + (F(4)!)) \times (C(8, F(4)) - 8)) \\
 34934 &:= (-((C((F(3!)^4), 9) - 3!)) + F(4!)) \\
 34935 &:= ((F(C(3!, F(4))) - (9!/F(3!))) / (-5)) \\
 34937 &:= ((C(3!, 4) + F(9)) \times (3!! - 7)) \\
 34947 &:= (-3) + ((4! + (C(9, 4))) \times F(F(7))) \\
 34964 &:= ((F(3!))! - (4 \times (9 + C(F(F(6)), F(4)))))) \\
 34998 &:= (3 \times (((4 - C(9, 9)))! + F(F(8)))) \\
 35184 &:= -(3! \times ((5! + 1) - C(F(8), 4))) \\
 35196 &:= (((F(3!))!/5) + C(19, 6)) \\
 35315 &:= (- (C((3 \times 5), 3!)) + (F((1 + 5)))!) \\
 35316 &:= (- ((C((3 \times 5), 3!) - 1)) + (F(6)))! \\
 35336 &:= (C(F(3!), 5) \times (3!! - F((3 + F(6)))))) \\
 35339 &:= (((F(3) \times 5!) + F(C(F(3!), F(3)))) / 9) \\
 35349 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((5 \times 3), (F(4)!)) - F(9))) \\
 35366 &:= (- ((C(F(3!), 5) - F((3 \times F(6)))) - F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 35419 &:= ((3!! \times F(C(5, F(4)))) - (F(19))) \\
 35442 &:= (F(3) \times (C(5, F(4)) + F((4! - 2)))) \\
 35463 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 5) - (((F(4))! - (F(F(6)) \times 3!)))) \\
 35470 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 5) + ((F(4) \times 7!) + 0!)) \\
 35473 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 5) + (4 + (7! \times 3))) \\
 35476 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(((F(4))! + F(7)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 35484 &:= (((C(F(3!), 5) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) + (F(4)!)) \\
 35486 &:= (((C(F(3!), 5) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) + F(6)) \\
 35548 &:= (((C(3!, 5) + 5!) + F(4!)) - F(F(8))) \\
 35662 &:= (F(3) \times (5! + F((-6) + C(F(6), 2)))) \\
 35676 &:= ((-3) \times 5!) + (F(F(6)) \times C(F(7), 6)) \\
 35744 &:= (((F(F(3!)) - 5) \times (-C(F(7), F(4)))) + (F((F(4))!))!) \\
 35763 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times ((-5) + C(F(7), 6)) - F(3!)) \\
 35793 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 5) - ((F(7))! / (-9!) - (F(3!))!)) \\
 35844 &:= (-(((3! + 5) - C(F(8), 4))) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 35904 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), -(5 - 9)) - 0!) \times (F(4)!)) \\
 35916 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), -(5 - 9)) + 1) \times 6) \\
 35928 &:= (((F(3) + 5!) \times (-C(9, 2))) + 8!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 35952 &:= (((F(3!))! / (-5!)) - (9! / (-C(5, 2)))) \\
 35968 &:= -(((F(3!) + 5!) \times F(C(9, F(6)))) - 8!) \\
 35973 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (- (F(-((5 - 9))) - C(F(7), 3!))) \\
 35992 &:= -((F(3!) - (5! \times C((F(9) - 9), 2)))) \\
 36032 &:= ((F(3) \times F((F(F(6)) + 0!)) + F(C(3!, 2))) \\
 36033 &:= (-3) + (F(F(6)) \times C(F((0! + 3!)), 3!)) \\
 36034 &:= (- (F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times C(F((0! + 3!)), (F(4)!)))) \\
 36036 &:= (C(((F(3) \times 6) + 0!), 3!) \times F(F(6))) \\
 36037 &:= (F(F(3)) + (F(F(6)) \times C(F((0! + 3!)), 7))) \\
 36038 &:= (F(3) + (C(F((F(6) - 0!)), 3!) \times F(8))) \\
 36044 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times C(F((F(6) - 0!)), (F(4)!)) + F((F(4))!)) \\
 36054 &:= (3! \times (C(F(F(6)), -(0! - 5))) + (4!)) \\
 36141 &:= ((3!! - F(F(F(6)))) + (-1 + F((C(4, 1))!)) \\
 36143 &:= ((3!! - F(F(F(6)))) - (-1 - F((C(4, 3))!)) \\
 36346 &:= ((C((F(3) \times 6), 3!) + F(4!)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 36352 &:= ((C(F(3!), 6)^3) + (5!^2)) \\
 36367 &:= -((F(F(F(3!))) - ((F(C(6, 3)) - (6)) \times 7))) \\
 36383 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + ((6 + C(F(F(3!)), 8)) / F(3!)) \\
 36427 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((6 \times F(C((F(4))!, 2))) + F(F(7)))) \\
 36433 &:= (F(F(3)) + (-6) \times (C(4!, 3) \times (-3))) \\
 36434 &:= (F(3) + (6 \times (C(4!, 3) \times F(4)))) \\
 36436 &:= -(((C((-F(3)) + F(F(6))), 4) + F(3!)) - (F(6))!) \\
 36442 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), 4) + 2)) \\
 36443 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), 4) + F(F(3)))) \\
 36444 &:= (3 \times ((6 \times C(4!, F(4))) + (4))) \\
 36446 &:= (F(3) - (C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), 4) - (F(6))!)) \\
 36454 &:= (((-F(3)) + (F(6))!) + C(4!, 5)) - F(4!) \\
 36455 &:= ((C((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))), 4) \times 5) - 5!) \\
 36499 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), F(6)) / (F(4)!)) + F((9 + 9))) \\
 36548 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), 6) - (5)) - F((F(F(4))) + (F(8)))) \\
 36553 &:= -((F(-((3 - (5 \times 5)))) - C(F(F(6)), 3!)) \\
 36553 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 6) - (F(((5 \times 5) - 3))) \\
 36630 &:= (3!! + (6 \times C(F(F(6)), (3 + 0!))) \\
 36642 &:= (3!! + (6 \times (C(F(F(6)), 4) + 2))) \\
 36645 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((6! + C(6, 4)) \times 5)) \\
 36662 &:= ((F(3) + (F(6))!) + (-6) \times F(C(6, 2))) \\
 36663 &:= ((-3) + (F(6))!) - C((F(6) + F(F(6))), 3) \\
 36663 &:= ((-3) + (F(6))!) - C((F(6) + F(F(6))), 3) \\
 36664 &:= ((-F(3)) + (F(6))!) - C((F(6) + F(F(6))), F(4)) \\
 36745 &:= (F(F(3)) - (((6! + 7!) - C(4!, 5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 36748** := $((3!! - F(6)) + (C(F(7), (F(4))!) \times F(8)))$
36749 := $-((F(F(3)) - (F(F(6)) \times (C(F(7), (F(4))!) + F(9))))$
36756 := $((C(F(3!), 6) \times C(F(7), 5)) + (6!))$
36771 := $((F(3!))! - (F(F(6)) \times (F(7) \times F(C(7, 1))))$
36847 := $-((F(3!) + ((6! - C(F(8), 4)) \times 7))$
36873 := $(((-3) \times 6!) + 8!) - C(F(7), F(3!))$
36879 := $((F(3!))! - (C((6+8), 7) + 9))$
36938 := $((F(3) + 6!) \times C(9, F(3))) + F(F(8))$
36982 := $(C(F(F(3!)), 6) - ((9!/F(8)) + 2))$
36983 := $(C(F(F(3!)), 6) + (-((9!/F(8))) - F(F(3))))$
37149 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (-F(F(7)) - (C(14, 9))))$
37184 := $((F(3!))! - ((C(7, 1) \times 8)^{F(F(4))}))$
37207 := $-(((F(3!))! - (7 + C(20, 7))))$
37224 := $(3!! + ((C(F(7), 2)^2) \times (F(4))!))$
37233 := $((F(3!))! - ((C(7, 2)^3) / 3))$
37258 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (F(7) \times C((-((F(2) - (5))))!, F(8))))$
37278 := $((-3) \times (C(F(7), 2) \times F(7))) + 8!$
37298 := $((3!! + (F((7 \times 2)))) \times F(C(9, 8)))$
37304 := $((F(3!))! - (7! - C(((3+0))!, F(4))))$
37316 := $(-((C((F(3) \times 7), 3!) + 1)) + (F(6))!)$
37317 := $-((C((F(3) \times 7), 3!) - ((1+7))!))$
37318 := $-(((C((F(3) \times 7), 3!) - 1) - 8!))$
37322 := $(- (C(F(F(3!)), F(7))) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-22)))$
37329 := $(3! + (C(F(7), F(3!)) \times 29))$
37335 := $((F(3!))! - ((-F(7)) + F(C(3!, F(3)))) \times 5))$
37343 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(F(7)) + 3!!) + (C(4!, 3))))$
37396 := $((F(3!) + (C(F(7), F(3)))) \times (-F(9))) + (F(6))!)$
37435 := $((3!! \times (F(7) \times C(4, 3))) - (5))$
37442 := $(F(3) + ((F(7) \times 4) \times (C(4, 2))!))$
37444 := $((3!! \times (F(7) \times 4)) + C(4, F(4)))$
37444 := $((3!! \times (F(7) \times 4)) + C(4, F(4)))$
37448 := $((3 + C(F(7), 4)) \times (-4)) + 8!$
37457 := $((3! - 7!) + (C(4!, 5) - F(7)))$
37462 := $-(((F(3) + 7!) - C(4!, (6 - F(2))))$
37465 := $(F(F(3)) - (7! - C((4 \times 6), 5)))$
37467 := $((3 - 7!) + C(4!, (6 + F(7))))$
37472 := $(F(3!) - (7! - C(4!, (7 - 2))))$
37476 := $((3 \times (-C(F(7), 4) - F(F(7)))) + (F(6))!)$
37483 := $(-((F(3) - (C(F(8), 4) \times F(7)))) - (F(3))!)$
37487 := $(-((C((F(3) \times F(7)), F(4)) - 8!)) - F(F(7)))$
37539 := $((F((3! + F(7))) - C(5, 3)) \times 9)$
37548 := $((-3) \times C((7+5), (F(4))!) + 8!)$
37634 := $((F(3!))! - ((F(7) + C(F(F(6)), 3)) \times F(F(4))))$
37681 := $((F(3!))! - (7 \times F(C((6+8), 1))))$
37708 := $-(((F(3) - C(F(7), 7)) \times (0! + F(8))))$
37720 := $((F(3!))! - C((F(7) + F(7)), (2 + 0!)))$
37723 := $((F(3!))! - (F(7) + F((C(7, 2) - 3))))$
37730 := $(-((F(F(3)) - C(F(7), 7)) \times (F(F(3!)) + 0!))$
37731 := $-((F(F(3!)) + (-C(F(7), 7)) \times (F(F(3!)) + 1)))$
37732 := $((F(3!))! - ((7 + C(F(7), F(3!))) \times 2))$
37753 := $((F(3!))! - (-7) + (C(F(7), 5) \times F(3)))$
37760 := $(F(3!) - (-C(F(7), 7)) \times (F(F(6)) + 0!))$
37773 := $-((F((3 + F(7))) - (C((F(7) + (7)), 3!)))$
37773 := $-((F((3 + F(7))) - (C((F(7) + (7)), 3!)))$
37824 := $(F(3!) \times (-((F(7) - C(F(8), 2)) \times 4!))$
37828 := $((F(-((F(3) - F(7)))) \times (-C(8, 2))) + 8!)$
37853 := $((F(F(3!)) \times C(F(7), 8)) - 5!) + F(F(F(3!)))$
37875 := $-(((3!^7) - F(C(8, (7-5))))$
37883 := $(-(((3!^7) - 8)) + F(C(8, F(3))))$
37927 := $((F(3!))! - (F(7) + C((F(9)/2), F(7))))$
37943 := $((F(3!))! - (C((F((F(4))!) + 9), F(7)) - 3))$
37944 := $((3!! \times F(7)) + C(9, 4)) \times 4$
37947 := $-(((3! - C((-7) + F(9)), 4!)) \times F(7))$
37963 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 7) + (-F(9) - (F(6))!)) / F(3))$
37973 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (-((F(7) - F(9))) \times C(F(7), F(3!))))$
37973 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (-((F(7) - F(9))) \times C(F(7), F(3!))))$
37974 := $(-3!) + ((F(F(7)) \times (-C(9, 7))) + F(4!))$
38034 := $-(((3!! - (C((F(8) - 0!), 3!)) + (F(4))!))$
38035 := $-(((3!! - ((C((F(8) - 0!), 3!) - (5))))$
38059 := $((F(3!))! - (C(F(8), 05) / 9))$
38064 := $-(((3!! - (C((F(8) - 0!), 6) + 4!))$
38078 := $(C(((3) + F(8)) + 0!), F(7)) + F(F(8)))$
38217 := $-((F(F(F(3!))) + (-((C(F(8), 2) + 1)) \times F(F(7))))$
38241 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (C((8 \times 2), 4) + 1))$
38278 := $(C(F(F(3!)), (8 - 2)) - (7! + F(F(8))))$
38346 := $((3! + C((8 \times F(3)), 4)) \times F(F(6)))$
38347 := $((-C((F(3) \times 8), 3!)) + F(4!)) - F(7)$
38377 := $((3! \times C((F(8) - 3!), 7)) - F(F(7)))$
38382 := $((F(3!))! - (C(F(8), 3!) / C(8, 2)))$
38391 := $((F(3!))! / (-F(8))) + (F(3!))! - C(9, 1)$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38425 &:= (((3 \times F(8)) \times F(C((F(4))!, 2))) - (5)) \\
 38431 &:= (((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))) + ((F(4))!)!) / (C(3, 1))!) \\
 38433 &:= (3 + ((F(8) \times F(4)) \times F(C(3!, F(3)))))) \\
 38483 &:= ((F(3!) + (F(8))) \times (- (F(4) - C(F(8), 3)))) \\
 38483 &:= ((F(3!) + (F(8))) \times (- (F(4) - C(F(8), 3)))) \\
 38484 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((C(8, 4) + F(F(8))) / (F(4))!)) \\
 38582 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (F((F(8) - (5))) \times C(8, 2))) \\
 38597 &:= ((C(-((3! - F(8))), 5) - F(9)) \times F(7)) \\
 38603 &:= -(((F(F(3)) - 8!) + C(F((F(6) - 0!)), 3!)) \\
 38604 &:= ((C(-((3! - F(8))), F(6)) - 0!) \times (F(4))!) \\
 38607 &:= ((3 + 8!) - C(F((F(6) - 0!)), 7)) \\
 38634 &:= ((C((F(3) \times 8), F(6)) \times 3) + 4!) \\
 38717 &:= -(((3! - (C(8, 7))!) + F(17))) \\
 38724 &:= (F(F(3)) + (8! - F((C(7, 2) - 4)))) \\
 38734 &:= (((3! - C(F(8), 7)) / (-3)) - 4!) \\
 38736 &:= (3! \times (F(8) + C((F(7) + F(3)), F(6)))) \\
 38740 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - ((C(F(8), 7) / F(4)) + 0!)) \\
 38744 &:= (F(3!) + ((C(F(8), 7) / F(4)) - 4!)) \\
 38745 &:= ((F(3!))! - (- (F(8)) + (C(F(7), (F(4))!) - 5!)) \\
 38746 &:= -((3! - ((C(F(8), 7) / F(4)) - F(6)))) \\
 38747 &:= -((3! - ((C(F(8), 7) / F(4)) - (7)))) \\
 38757 &:= ((-3) + (C(8, 7))!) - (5! \times F(7)) \\
 38773 &:= -((F(3!) - (F(8) + C((F(7) + (7)), 3!))) \\
 38774 &:= ((3! + 8) + C((F(7) + (7)), (F(4))!)) \\
 38784 &:= ((3! + (C(F(8), F(7)) / F(8))) \times 4) \\
 38823 &:= ((3 \times F(8)) + C((F(8) - F(2)), 3!)) \\
 38824 &:= (F(3!) \times (8 + C((F(8) - F(2)), 4))) \\
 38834 &:= (F(F(F(3!))) + (-((8! - C(F(8), 3!)) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 38837 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((-8) + F(8)), 3!) - F(F(7))) \\
 38847 &:= ((-3) + 8!) + (C(F(8), F(F(4))) \times (-7)) \\
 38848 &:= -((F(3) + ((F(8) \times C(8, 4)) - 8!)) \\
 38850 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F(8) \times C(8, (5 - 0)))) \\
 38882 &:= ((F(3) + 8!) + (8! / (-C(8, 2)))) \\
 38883 &:= ((3 + 8!) - (8! / C(8, F(3)))) \\
 38883 &:= ((3 + 8!) - (8! / C(8, F(3)))) \\
 38884 &:= ((F(3!) + F(F(8))) + ((F(8) \times C(F(8), F(4)))) \\
 38977 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C(F(8), F((-9) + F(7)))) + F(7)) \\
 38978 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(8) + F(9)) + C(F(7), 8))) \\
 38983 &:= (((F(3) + 8!) - 9) - C(F(8), 3)) \\
 38983 &:= (((F(3) + 8!) - 9) - C(F(8), 3))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 38984 &:= (((3 + 8!) - 9) - C(F(8), F(4))) \\
 39033 &:= ((F(3!))! - C(((9 + 0!) + 3), F(3!))) \\
 39165 &:= ((F(3!))! - (F((9 + 1)) \times F(F(C(6, 5)))) \\
 39195 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((9 \times (1 - C(9, 5)))) \\
 39310 &:= 3! + F(9)^{C(3,1)} + 0 \\
 39311 &:= (3! + ((F(9)^3) + C(1, 1))) \\
 39351 &:= ((F(3!))! - (9 + (F(3!) \times (C(5, 1))!)) \\
 39353 &:= -((3! - ((F(9)^3) + F(C(5, 3)))) \\
 39457 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((C(9, 4) \times 5) + F(F(7)))) \\
 39516 &:= -(((3! + C(9, (5 + 1))) - (F(6))!) \\
 39526 &:= -((C((3 + 9), 5) + 2) + (F(6))!) \\
 39533 &:= ((F(-((3 - 9)))^5) + F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 39598 &:= (((3! \times (-C(9, 5))) + F(9)) + 8!) \\
 39599 &:= (((F(3!))! - ((F((9 - 5))!)!) - C(9, 9)) \\
 39631 &:= (((-3) + F(9)) + (F(6))!) - ((C(3, 1))!)) \\
 39648 &:= ((F(3) \times (- (C(9, 6) \times 4))) + 8!) \\
 39686 &:= (((F(3) + (C(9, 6))) + 8!) - 6!) \\
 39732 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((-9) - F(7)) + F(C(3!, 2))) \\
 39735 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C((F(9) - (7)), 3) / 5)) \\
 39753 &:= ((F(3!))! - (9 \times (C(7, 5) \times 3))) \\
 39794 &:= ((F(3!))! - ((F(9) \times F(7)) + C(9, F(4)))) \\
 39825 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C(9, 8) \times F((2 \times 5)))) \\
 39826 &:= ((- (C((3 + 9), 8)) + F(2)) + (F(6))!) \\
 39852 &:= ((F(3!))! - (C(9, 8) \times 52)) \\
 39864 &:= -((((F(3)^9) - 8!) - C(F(6), F(4))) \\
 39876 &:= (-((F(3) + (F(C(9, 8)) \times F(7)))) + (F(6))!) \\
 39943 &:= ((F(3!))! - F(((9 + 9) - C(4, 3))) \\
 39987 &:= (((3 + F(9)) \times (-9)) + (C(8, 7))!) \\
 40034 &:= ((F((F(4))!)!) - C(F((0! + (03!)), F(4))) \\
 40036 &:= ((- (C(4!, (0! + 0!))) - F(3!)) + (F(6))!) \\
 40037 &:= ((- (C(4!, (0! + 0!))) + (F(3!))!) - 7) \\
 40042 &:= ((F((F(4))!)!) - ((0! + 0!) + C(4!, 2))) \\
 40043 &:= ((- (C(4!, (0! + 0!))) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(3!))!) \\
 40046 &:= ((- (C(4!, (0! + 0!))) + F(F(4))) + (F(6))!) \\
 40134 &:= -((C(F(F(F(4))!)), (0! + 1)) - (((F(3!))! + (4!)))) \\
 40185 &:= -((C((F(4))!, (0! + 1)) - (8! - 5!)) \\
 40241 &:= ((- (C(F(((F(4))! + 0!)), 2)) + (F((F(4))!)!) - 1) \\
 40242 &:= -((C(F(((F(4))! + 0!)), 2) - (((4 \times 2))!)) \\
 40250 &:= ((F((F(4))!)!) - C(F(((0! + 2))!), (5 - 0!)) \\
 40264 &:= (((4 \times 02))! - C(F(6), F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 40281** := $((-(40) + F(2)) + (C(8, 1))!)$
40291 := $((F((F(4))!))! - C(029, 1))$
40292 := $-((C(F((F(4))!), 02) - ((9 - F(2))!))!)$
40311 := $((F((F(4))! + 0!) - (F(3))!) \times (-C(1, 1)))$
40331 := $((4 + 0!) + 3!) + (F((C(3, 1))!))!$
40343 := $((4! - 0!) + ((F(3)^{F(C(4,3))}))!)$
40361 := $((40 + F(F(3))) + (F(C(6, 1))!))!$
40384 := $(F(4!) + (((0 \times 3)! - C(F(8), 4)))$
40389 := $(C(((F(4))! + 0!), 3) + (8! + F(9)))$
40390 := $(C(F((F(4))!), (0! + 3)) + (((9 - 0!)!))!$
40403 := $(C((F((F(4))! + 0!), F(4)) - 0!) + (F(3))!)$
40404 := $((F((F(4))!))! + C((0! + F((F(4))!)), F(04)))$
40404 := $((F((F(4))!))! + C((0! + F((F(4))!)), F(04)))$
40525 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C(F(F((0! + 5))))), 2) - (5))$
40526 := $(- (4) + (C(F(F((0! + 5))))), 2) + (F(6))!)$
40530 := $((F((F(4))!))! + C(F(F((0! + 5))), F((3 + 0)))$
40531 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C(F(F((0! + 5))), F(3)) + 1)$
40532 := $((F(F(4)) + (F((0! + 5))))! + C(F(F(3)), 2)$
40539 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C(F(F((0! + 5))))), F(3)) + 9)$
40572 := $((F(4!) / F((0! + 5))) \times C(7, F(2)))$
40652 := $((4! - 0!) - C(F(F(6)), 5) \times (-2)$
40761 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (F((0! + 7))) \times F(F(C(6, 1))))$
40932 := $((F(F(4)) + (-((0! - 9)))! + F(C(3!, 2)))$
40933 := $((F(4) + (-((0! - 9)))! + F(C(3!, F(3))))$
40934 := $((4 + (-((0! - 9)))! + F(C(3!, 4)))$
40945 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! - (C(9, 4))) \times (-5)))$
40955 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((0! + (C(9, 5))) \times 5))$
40963 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (-((0! - F(9))) + F(C(6, F(3))))$
41068 := $(C(F((F(4))!), (1 + 0!)) + (6! + 8!))$
41145 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C(11, F(4)) \times 5))$
41148 := $((C(4!, (1 + 1)) \times F(4)) + 8!)$
41184 := $(4! \times C(F(-((C(1, 1) - 8))), (F(4))!)$
41186 := $((F(4))! \times (-((C(1, 1) - 8)))! + F(F(F(6))))$
41236 := $-((F((F(4))!))! + (- (C(12, 3!) - (F(6))!))$
41237 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C(12, 3!) - (7)))$
41238 := $-(((F(4))! - (C(12, 3!) + 8!))$
41242 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C(12, (F(4))!) - 2))$
41243 := $-(((F(F(F(4))) - C(12, (F(4))!)) - (F(3))!))$
41244 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! + C((2 \times (F(4))!), (F(4))!))$
41246 := $(F(F(4)) + (C(12, (F(4))!) + (F(6))!))$
41248 := $(4 + (C(12, (F(4))!) + 8!))$
41273 := $((((C(4, 1) \times 2))! + F(F(7))) + 3!)$
41331 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!) + C(3, 1))$
41343 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!) + C((F(4))!, F(3)))$
41363 := $(F(4!) - (C(((1 + 3!) + F(6)), 3!))$
41364 := $((F(4!) + 1) - C((- (3!) + F(F(6))), (F(4))!))$
41375 := $(- (F((4! + 1))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 7) + 5!))$
41376 := $(4! \times (C(13, 7) + F(6)))$
41384 := $((F(4!) - ((1 + 3!)!) + C(8, F(4)))$
41399 := $((C(4!, F(((1 \times 3)!)) - 9!) / 9)$
41424 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! + (C(4!, 2) \times 4))$
41436 := $(- (4!) + (C((- (1) + F(F((F(4))!))), 3) + (F(6))!))$
41484 := $(- (C((4! + 1), F(4))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-4)))$
41494 := $((C((F(F((F(4))!)) - 1), F(4)) + F(9)) + (F((F(4))!))!$
41586 := $(C(F(((F(4))! + 1)), 5) - (- (8!) + F(F(6))))$
41598 := $(C(F(((F(4))! + 1)), 5) - (9 - 8!))$
41606 := $(C(F(((F(4))! + 1)), F(6)) - (0! - (F(6))!))$
41607 := $(C(F(((F(4))! + 1)), F(6)) + (((0! + 7))!))$
41608 := $(C(F(((F(4))! + 1)), F(6)) + (0! + 8!))$
41634 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (- (16) + C(F(F(3!)), F(4))))$
41637 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! + ((C(F(F(6)), 3) - F(7)))$
41644 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! + (C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - (F(4))!))$
41645 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! + (C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - (5)))$
41646 := $(- (4) + (C(F(F((1 \times 6))), F(4)) + (F(6))!))$
41648 := $(- (F((4 - 1))) + (C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + 8!))$
41650 := $((F(((4 - 1))!))! + (C(F(F(6)), F((5 - 0))))$
41651 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (1 + C(F(F(6)), F((5 - 1))))$
41663 := $(F(((F(4))! + 1)) + ((F(6))! + C(F(F(6)), 3)))$
41664 := $((4! + ((1 \times 6))!) \times C(F(6), F(4)))$
41667 := $-((C((F(F((F(4))!)) + 1), 6) - (C(F(F(6)), 7)))$
41745 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((1 - C(F(7), F(4))) \times (-5)))$
41748 := $(F(4!) - ((C((- (1) + F(7)), F(4)) \times F(8)))$
41775 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 17) \times 7) - 5!)$
41834 := $(F(F(F((F(4))!)) + (C(F(-((1 - 8))), F(3!)) \times 4!))$
41836 := $(- ((4! - C((1 + F(8)), 3))) + (F(6))!)$
41838 := $((C((4! - 1), F(8)) \times 3!) + 8!)$
41847 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C((1 + F(8)), F(4)) - F(7)))$
41883 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (F(F(-((1 - 8)))) + (C(F(8), 3))))$
41895 := $((F(4))! + 1) \times C(F(8), (9 - 5))$
41957 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (- (1) - (- (C(9, 5)) \times F(7)))$

- 41958** := $((F(((F(4))! + 1)) \times C(9, 5)) + 8!)$
41977 := $((C(F(F(((4 - 1))!)), 9) / 7) - F(7))$
41987 := $((C(F(F(((4 - 1))!)), 9) - (F(8))) / 7)$
42034 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (-2) + C(F((0! + 3!)), (F(4))!))$
42036 := $(C(((4!/2) + 0!), 3!) + (F(6))!)$
42047 := $(((((C(4, 2))! - 0!) + F(4)) - (7))!$
42063 := $((C(4!, (2 + 0!)) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(3!)))$
42145 := $(((((F(4))!)/(-2)) - (-1 - C(4!, 5)))$
42187 := $(F(4!) - F((-2) + F(C((1 \times 8), 7))))$
42338 := $((C(4!, F((2^3))) - 3!) + 8!)$
42343 := $(((((4 \times 2))! - F(F(3!))) + C(4!, 3!))$
42344 := $(C(4!, F((2^3))) + ((4 + 4))!)$
42364 := $(F(4!) - (C((2 \times F(3!)), 6) / F(F(4))))$
42384 := $(C(4!, (2 + 3)) - ((8 - F(4))!))$
42387 := $((C((4! + F(2)), 3) + 8!) - F(F(7)))$
42428 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2) - 4)^2) - 8)$
42434 := $(C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - C(F(3!), 4))$
42438 := $-((4! - ((-2) + C(4!, 3)) \times F(8)))$
42440 := $-(((F((F(4))!))^2) - (C(4!, (4 + 0!))))$
42445 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(2) - C(4!, 4)) / (-5)))$
42447 := $(((-C(4!, 2)) + F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \times 4) - F(F(7)))$
42449 := $(C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - F(-((4! - F(9))))$
42450 := $-((F((F(F(4))!)) + 2) - ((C(4!, 5) + 0!)))$
42452 := $(C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - 52)$
42457 := $-((F((F(4)^2)) - ((C(4!, 5) - F(7))))$
42458 := $-(((4! + F(2)) - (C(4!, 5) - F(8))))$
42459 := $(C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - (5 \times 9))$
42461 := $((F(F((F(4))!)) \times (-2) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) - 1)$
42462 := $(-42) + C(4!, (6 - F(2)))$
42463 := $((C(4!, 2) + F(4!)) - F((F(F(6)) - F(3))))$
42464 := $((C(F((F(4))!), 2)^{F(4)} - (6!)) \times F(F(4)))$
42466 := $(4 + ((-2) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \times F(F(6)))$
42476 := $((C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - (7)) - F(F(6)))$
42478 := $-(((4! + 2) - C(4!, (F(7) - 8)))$
42493 := $(C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - (9 + F(3)))$
42494 := $(C(4!, (F(2) + (4))) - (F(9) - 4!))$
42496 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), -((4 - 9))) - F(6))$
42497 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), -((4 - 9))) - (7))$
42502 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) - 02)$
42503 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) - ((0 \times 3))!)$
42504 := $C(C(4!, F(2)), C(5, 04))$
42505 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + ((0 \times 5))!)$
42512 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F(((1 + 2))!))$
42513 := $((C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + 1) + F(3!))$
42517 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F((1 \times 7)))$
42523 := $((C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) - 2) + F(F(3!)))$
42525 := $(F((4 \times 2)) + C(((5 - F(2))!), 5))$
42526 := $((C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F(2)) + F(F(6)))$
42532 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + C(F(3!), 2))$
42533 := $((C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F(3!)) + F(F(3!)))$
42534 := $((C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + 3!) + 4!)$
42538 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F((F(F(3)) + 8)))$
42539 := $((C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F(F(3))) + F(9))$
42545 := $((F(4))!^2) - (-5 - C(4!, 5))$
42546 := $((C(4!, -((2 - 5))) + F(F(4))) \times F(F(6)))$
42549 := $-((F(C(F((F(4))!), 2)) - ((-5!) \times F(F((F(4))!))) + 9!))$
42559 := $(F(F((F(4))!)) + (C((-((F(2) - 5))))!, 5) + F(9))$
42568 := $((C(4!, 2) + 5) \times F(6) + 8!)$
42584 := $(4! + ((2^5) \times C(F(8), F(4))))$
42593 := $(C(C(4!, F(2)), 5) + F((9 + F(3))))$
42625 := $(C(4!, -((F(2) - 6))) + ((F(2) + 5)!))$
42645 := $-(((F(4) - F((2 \times 6))) - C(4!, 5)))$
42673 := $(C(4!, -((F(2) - 6))) + ((F(7)^{F(3)})))$
42693 := $((C(4!, F((2 + 6))) + 9) \times F(F(3!)))$
42694 := $-((C(F(F((F(4))!), 2) - ((F(6))! + F((9 \times F(F(4)))))$
42733 := $(-(((F(C((F(4))!), 2) - (F(F(7))^{F(3)}))) - F(F(F(3!))))$
42737 := $(C(4!, -((2 - 7))) + F((3! + (7))))$
42745 := $((4 \times 2) + F(F(7))) + C(4!, 5)$
42775 := $((4! + F(2)) \times (C(F(7), 7) - 5))$
42795 := $(F(4!) - (-2) - (C(F(7), 9) \times (-5)))$
42804 := $((C(4!, 2) \times (8 + 0!)) + (F((F(4))!))!)$
42857 := $((C(4!, (-2) + F(8))) + 5!) + F(F(7))$
42872 := $((4! - F(2)) \times 8) \times F(C(F(7), F(2)))$
42903 := $(C(F((F(4))!), 2) + ((F(9) + 0!)^3))$
42928 := $((C(4!, F(2)) + F((9 \times 2))) + 8!)$
42932 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (F((2 \times 9)) + C(F(3!), 2)))$
42944 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!), 2) - F(F(F((9 - F(4))))) \times (-4))$
42945 := $((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(-((F(2) - 9)))) + C(4!, 5))$
42947 := $((F(4!) - (C(29, F(4)))) + F(F(7)))$
42972 := $((4 \times 2)! + (F(9) \times C(F(7), 2)))$

- 43038** := -(((F(4))!) - C((3 × (03)!), 8))
43069 := ((4 × F(F(F(3)))) - C(F((0! + (6))), 9))
43089 := -((F(F(F(4)!)) + ((C((F(F(3)) + 0!), 8) - 9!)))
43223 := ((C(4!, (3 + 2)) - F(2)) + 3!)
43225 := (F(F(F(4))) + (3!! + C(((2 + 2)!), 5)))
43232 := (F(4!) - (C(F((3 × 2)), 3)²))
43234 := -(((C(F((F(4))!), 3)²) + (-F(3) - F(4))))
43234 := -(((C(F((F(4))!), 3)²) + (-F(3) - F(4))))
43237 := ((C(4!, (3 + 2)) + 3!!) + F(7))
43262 := ((C(4!, (3! + F(2))) / F(6)) - F(2))
43263 := (C(4!, (3! + F(2))) / (6 + F(3)))
43265 := ((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(C(3!, 2)) - F(F(6))) × 5))
43266 := (((C(4!, 3) + 2) × F(F(6))) + (6!))
43281 := ((F(4) × F((F(3!) × 2))) + (C(8, 1)!))
43286 := -((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (-32) + C(F(8), 6)))
43312 := ((-((F(4))! - F(F(F(3)))) + (C(F(F(3!)), ((1 + 2)!)))
43313 := ((C(F(F(F(4))!), 3!) - F(F(F(3!)))) - (-1 + 3!))
43314 := ((-4) - F(F(F(3!))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F((1 × 4))!)))
43315 := (-F(4) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - F(F(F((1 + 5))))))
43317 := -((F(F(F(4))) - (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - (F(F((1 + 7))))))
43318 := (C((4! - 3), 3!) - F(F((1 × 8)))
43319 := (F(F(F(4))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - F(F(-((1 - 9))))))
43321 := (F(4) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - F(21)))
43323 := (C(((F(4))! + F(3!)), 3!) + ((2³)!))
43325 := ((F(F(4)) + (F(3!))!) + C(C(3!, 2), 5))
43329 := ((C(F(F(F(4))!), 3!) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (2 + 9))
43336 := -((C(4!, 3) - (((3 × 3)! / F(6))))
43344 := (F(4!) - (C((3 × 3), 4) × 4!))
43354 := (((F(4!) + (F(3!))!) / F(3)) + C(5, F(4)))
43356 := ((C(4!, F(3)) × (3! + (5))) + (F(6)!))
43358 := (C(F(F(F(4))!), 3!) - ((F(3!) × (-5)) + F(F(8))))
43363 := (F(4!) - (F(3) + C((3! + F(6)), 3!)))
43364 := ((F(4!) - F(F(3))) - C((3! + F(6)), (F(4))!))
43365 := (F(4!) - C(((3 × 3) + 6), 5))
43366 := ((F(4!) + F(F(3))) - C((3! + F(6)), F(6)))
43368 := (F(4!) - (-3) + C((3! + F(6)), 8))
43373 := ((F(4!) + F(3!)) - C((F(3) × 7), 3!))
43382 := ((C(F(F(F(4))!), 3!) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (8²))
43398 := (F(4!) - (3! × C((3 + 9), 8)))
43442 := (F(4!) - (C((3 + 4!), 4!) + F(2)))
- 43443** := (F(4!) - C((3 + 4!), F(C(4, 3)))
43444 := ((F(4!) + F(F(3))) - C((4! + F(4)), 4!))
43447 := ((C((4^{F(3)}), 4) × 4!) - F(F(7)))
43457 := (((F(4) × F(3))!) + C(4!, 5)) + F(F(7)))
43472 := (4 × (F((-3) + 4!) - (C(F(7), 2)))
43478 := ((C((4! + 3), 4!) + F(F(7))) + 8!)
43508 := (-C(4!, F(3)) + ((5 - 0!) × F(F(8))))
43558 := (C(F(F(F(4))!), 3!) - (-((5! + 5!)) + F(F(8))))
43571 := (((4! × F(3!)) - 5) × F(F(C(7, 1))))
43624 := -(((C(4!, 3) + 6!) - F(24)))
43629 := -(((F(F(4)) × 3!) + F(C(F(6), 2))) - 9!)
43635 := ((C((4! - 3!), F(6)) - 3) - 5!)
43638 := (C((4! - 3!), F(6)) - (-((3 - 8)!))
43668 := (C((4! - 3!), F(6)) + (6! / (-8)))
43672 := (-4) × (C(F(3!), 6) - (F(C(7, 2))))
43679 := (C((4! - 3!), F(6)) - 79)
43684 := ((-((4! + C(3!, 6))) + F(F(8))) × 4)
43691 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - C(9, 1))
43699 := ((-4) × (F(F(3!)) - F(F(F(6)))) - C(9, 9))
43722 := (F(4!) - (3! × (C(7, 2)²)))
43728 := (-4) × ((3! - F(C(7, 2))) + 8)
43743 := (F(4) + ((3⁷) × C((F(4))!, 3)))
43748 := (C(((F(4))! + F(3!)), 7) - (4 - 8!))
43749 := (C((4! - 3!), (F(7) - F(4))) - 9)
43751 := ((-4) × (F(3!) - (F(C(7, 5)))) - 1)
43752 := (-4) × ((3! - F(C(7, 5))) + 2))
43753 := (-((F(4) + F(3))) + C((F(7) + (5)), F(3!)))
43755 := ((-4) × (3! - F(C(7, 5)))) - (5)
43755 := (C(((5 × 5) - 7), F(3!)) - F(4))
43844 := ((C((F(4))!, F(3)) + F(F(8))) × C(4, F(4)))
43847 := (C((4! - 3!), 8) + F((4 + 7)))
43864 := ((C((F(4))!, 3) + F(F(8))) × (F(6) - (4)))
43876 := (C(4!, 3!) - (F(8) × (7! - 6!)))
43878 := (C((4! - 3!), 8) + ((F(7) - 8)!))
43888 := ((C((4! + F(3)), F(8)) - F(F(8))) - F(F(8)))
43894 := (C((4! - 3!), 8) + (F(9) × 4))
43928 := (F((4! - 3!)) × (C(9, F(2)) + 8))
43941 := (F(F(F(4))!) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + F(9)) × C(4, 1)))
43967 := (-((4! - C((F(3) × 9), F(6)))) + F(F(7)))
43978 := ((-C(4!, F(3))) × (F(9) - F(F(7)))) - F(F(8)))

- 43979** := $(F(4!) - (C((F(3!) + 9), F(7)) + 9))$
43987 := $((F(4!) - F(F(3))) - (C((9 + 8), F(7))))$
43998 := $((((F(4)!)! / 3) + C((9 + 9), 8))$
44034 := $((F(4)!) \times (4! + C((0! + F(F(3))), 4)))$
44038 := $(C(F(F((F(4)!)!)), (F(4)!) + (((03)!)! - F(F(8))))$
44044 := $(F(4!) - (C((4! + 0!), F(4)) + 4!))$
44044 := $(F(4!) - (C((4! + 0!), F(4)) + 4!))$
44073 := $((F((F(4)!)!) + (((F(4)!) + 0!)! - (C(F(7), F(3)))))$
44074 := $((4 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!)!))) + 0!) + C(F(7), F(4)))$
44098 := $((((F(4)!)^4 + 0!) \times F(C(9, 8)))$
44124 := $(4! + (C(F(F(((4 - 1)!)!)), 2)^{F(F(4))}))$
44160 := $(C(4!, F(F(4))) \times 160)$
44224 := $(((C(F(F((F(4)!)!)), F(F(4))) + 2)^2) - (((F(4)!)!))$
44245 := $(((F(4)!) - C((4! - F(2)), 4)) \times (-5))$
44249 := $(-C(F(F(F(4)!)!)), F(4)!) - F(2) + F(F(F(F(4)!)!)) \times 9$
44253 := $(F(4!) - (C((F(4)!)!, 2) \times (5! + F(F(3)))))$
44289 := $(((C(F((F(4)!)!), 4)^2) + (F(8))) \times 9)$
44309 := $(F(4!) - ((C(4!, 3) + 0!) + F(9)))$
44313 := $((F((F(4)!)!) + ((C(F(F((F(4)!)!)), 3) + 1) \times 3))$
44318 := $((F(4!) - ((F(4)!)!) - C(F(F(3)!), 18))$
44322 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 3) + (22)))$
44323 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 3) + F((2^3))))$
44328 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 3) + ((2 \times 8))))$
44331 := $((F(4!) - (C(4!, 3))) - F((3! + 1)))$
44332 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 3) + (3! \times 2)))$
44333 := $(((F(4!) - (C(4!, 3))) - F(3!)) - 3)$
44334 := $(F(4!) - ((C(4!, 3) + 3!) + (4)))$
44336 := $(F(4!) - (C((C(4, 3))!, 3) + F(6)))$
44337 := $(F(4!) - ((C(4!, 3) - 3!) + F(7)))$
44338 := $(-((C(4!, F(4)) + 3!) - F((3 \times 8))))$
44339 := $(F(4) + ((C(4!, 3) - 3!) \times F(9)))$
44350 := $(F(4!) - ((C(4!, 3) - (5)) - 0!))$
44354 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 3) - C(5, F(4))))$
44357 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, F((3 + 5))) - F(7)))$
44358 := $((F(F(4)) \times (C(4!, 3) - (5))) + 8!)$
44363 := $(((F(4!) - (C(4!, 3))) + F(F(6))) - F(3))$
44364 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 3) - C(6, F(4))))$
44365 := $((F(4!) - (C(4!, 3))) + F(F(C(6, 5))))$
44368 := $(-((C(4!, F(4)) \times (3! - F(6))) - 8!))$
44369 := $(F(4!) + ((F(4) - C((3! + F(6)), 9)))$
44376 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, F(3)) + C(F(7), 6)))$
44378 := $(F(4!) - ((C(4!, 3) - F(7)) - F(8)))$
44404 := $((C(F(F((F(4)!)!)), F(4) - 4!) \times F((0! + F((F(4)!)!)))$
44432 := $(F(4!) - (44^{F(C(3, 2))}))$
44436 := $((F(4!) / (-4!)) + (F((C(4, 3) \times 6))))$
44455 := $((C((5 \times 5), (F(4)!) + ((F(4)!)!)) / 4)$
44458 := $(F(C((F(4)!)!, F(F(4)))) + (F(4!) - (5! \times F(8))))$
44462 := $(F(4!) - (((F(4)!)^4) + (F(C(6, 2))))$
44465 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) - (C(4!, F(F(6))) - 5!))$
44472 := $(F(4!) - (4! + (4! \times C(F(7), 2))))$
44478 := $(F(4!) - (F(C(4, F(4))) \times (7! / 8)))$
44485 := $(F(4!) - ((C(4!, F(4)) - F(8)) - 5!))$
44495 := $(-(((F(4)!)!) + ((C(F(F((F(4)!)!)), F(4)) \times F(9)) - (5)))$
44521 := $((((F(4)!)^{F(4)} - (5))^{C(2, 1)})$
44528 := $(C(4!, F((F(4) + (5)))) \times (F(2) + F(8)))$
44543 := $((F(C((F(4)!)!, F(F(4)))) \times 5!) - F((4! - F(F(3))))$
44564 := $(F(4!) - (4 - (5! \times (-C(6, 4))))$
44583 := $(((C(4!, F(4)) + 5!) - F(8)) \times F(F(3)!))$
44585 := $((-((C(4!, F(4)) + (5))) + F(F(8))) \times 5)$
44597 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, 5) / ((-9) + F(7))!))$
44605 := $(((-C(4!, F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) - 0!) \times 5)$
44615 := $(((-C(4!, F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1) \times 5)$
44616 := $((F(F(4)) + (4!)) \times C(F((6 + 1), 6))$
44626 := $((4^{(F(4)!)}) + (C(F(F(6)), 2) + (F(6)!)!))$
44631 := $(-((C(4!, F(4)) - ((6^3) - 1)))$
44632 := $(-((C(4!, F(4)) - ((6^3)^2)))$
44633 := $(-((C(4!, F(4)) - (6^3))) + F(F(3)))$
44653 := $(F(F(F(4))) + (F(4!) - (C((F(6) + (5)), 3!)))$
44654 := $((F(4!) + F(F(4))) - C((F(6) + (5)), (F(4)!)!))$
44656 := $(F(4!) - (-4) + C((F(6) + (5)), 6))$
44676 := $((4! + F((4 \times 6))) - C(F(7), 6))$
44677 := $((F(4!) + 4) + F(F(6))) - C(F(7), 7))$
44682 := $((F(4!) - (F(4)!) - ((F(6) \times C(F(8), 2))))$
44683 := $((F((C(4, F(4))!) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F(8)^3))$
44684 := $((C(4!, 4) \times F(6)) - 8!) - (4)$
44728 := $((F(4!) - F(F(4))) - ((C(F(7), 2) \times F(8))))$
44736 := $((C(4!, 4) - 7!) + 3!) \times F(6)$
44765 := $((F(4!) - F((4! - (7)))) - C(6, 5))$
44800 := $(C(F((F(4)!)!, F(4)) \times 800)$

- 44804** := $(F(4!) - (4! + C((F(8) + 0!), F(4))))$
44822 := $((F(4)!)! + (F(F(4)) + ((C(F(8), 2^2))))$
44823 := $((F(4)!)! + (F(4) + (C(F(8), 2)^{F(3)})))$
44824 := $(F(4!) - (4 + C((F(8) + F(2)), F(4))))$
44829 := $((F(4)!)! / (-F(4)) - (F(C(8, 2)) - 9!))$
44856 := $(F(4!) - (C((4 + 8), 5) + 6!))$
44877 := $(C(4!, 4) + ((F(8) \times 7) \times F(F(7))))$
44884 := $((F(4)!)! + F((-4) + F(8))) \times C(8, F(F(4)))$
44893 := $-(((F(4)!)! - ((C(4!, F(8)) + 9!) / F(3!)))$
44914 := $((C(F(F(F(4)!)!), F(4)) - 9) \times F((1 + F((F(4)!)!)))$
44943 := $((C(4!, (F(4)!) + F((9 + 4))) / 3)$
44952 := $(4! \times (F(4) + (F(9) \times F(C(5, 2))))$
45033 := $((F(4!) - 5) - C(F(F((03)!), 3))$
45034 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(F((5 + 0!))), 3) + 4)$
45043 := $((F(4!) + 5) - C(F(F((F(04)!), 3))$
45044 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(F((5 + 0!))), F(4)) - (F(4)!)!))$
45046 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(F((5 + 0!))), F(4)) - F(6)))$
45063 := $(-((C(4!, 5) + 0!) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F(3!)))$
45073 := $((F(4!) - F((5 + 0!))) - C(F(7), F(3!)))$
45075 := $(F(4!) + ((-5) - 0!) - C(F(7), 5))$
45076 := $(F(4!) - (5 + C(F(07), F(6))))$
45078 := $((F(4!) - F((5 - 0!))) - C(F(7), 8))$
45086 := $((F(4!) + 5) - C(F(-((0! - 8))), F(6)))$
45212 := $(F(4!) - (F((C(5, 2) - 1)^2))$
45214 := $((F(F(F(4)!)!) \times (-F(C(5, 2)))) + (1 + F(4!)))$
45240 := $(F((4 + C(5, 2))) \times ((4 + 0!)!))$
45261 := $((F(4!) - 5!) - F((2 \times F(C(6, 1))))$
45288 := $(F(4!) - (5! \times C((F(2) + 8), 8)))$
45325 := $(C((F(4) \times 5), 3!) + (F((F(2) + (5))))!))$
45341 := $(-(((4^5) + 3)) + F((C(4, 1)!))$
45343 := $((-((4^5)) - F(F(3))) + F((C(4, 3)!))$
45381 := $(F(4!) - F(C(((5 - 3) \times 8), 1)))$
45416 := $(F(4!) - (((C(5, 4))! - 1) \times F(6)))$
45417 := $((C(F(F(4)!)!, 5) + (F(F(4)!)!)! + (1 + 7!))$
45418 := $((F(F(4)!)!^5) + (C((4! + 1), F(8))))$
45436 := $((F(4!) + F(C(5, F(4)))) - F((F(3) \times F(6))))$
45473 := $((F(4!) - F(C(5, F(4)))) - ((7! / 3!))$
45475 := $((F(F(4)!)!) + ((-C(5, 4) + 7!) + 5!))$
45477 := $((4 + C(5, 4)) \times (7! + F(7)))$
45480 := $((F(F(4)!)!) + ((C(5, 4))! + ((8 - 0!)!))$
45488 := $(F(4!) - (C(5, F(4)) \times 88))$
45492 := $((F(4!) - 5!) - ((F(4)!)! - C(9, 2))$
45554 := $(C(4!, 5) + (5 \times F((5 \times F(4))))$
45554 := $(C(4!, 5) + (5 \times F((5 \times F(4))))$
45629 := $(F(4!) - ((5! + F(C(6, 2))) + 9))$
45642 := $(F(4!) - ((5! \times 6) + C(4, 2)))$
45644 := $(F(4!) - ((5 + 6!) - C(4, 4)))$
45652 := $(F(4!) - ((-5) + (C(6, 5)! + F(2)))$
45653 := $(F(4!) - ((5 + F(6)) \times F(C(5, 3))))$
45656 := $(F(4!) - (F((5 + C(6, 5))) \times F(6)))$
45659 := $((F(4!) + 5) - (F(F(C(6, 5))) \times F(9)))$
45661 := $(F(4!) - ((-5) + 6!) - F(C(6, 1)))$
45663 := $(F(4!) - ((5 + 6!) - C(6, 3)))$
45675 := $(F(4) \times ((-5) - 6!) \times (-C(7, 5)))$
45704 := $(C(F(F(4)!)!, 5) - (((7 - 0!)! - F(4!)))$
45766 := $(C(4!, 5) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(6) + (6))))$
45773 := $(F(4!) + ((5! - C(F(7), (7 - 3))))$
45788 := $(F((4! - 5))) + (C(F(7), 8) + 8!))$
45808 := $(F(4!) - C((-5) + F(8)), F(-((0! - 8))))$
45834 := $((C((F(4)!)!, 5) \times (-F((8 + 3)))) + F(4!))$
45842 := $((F(4!) - 5!) - C((F(8) + F((F(4)!)!), 2))$
45848 := $(F(4!) + (((5 - C(8, 4)) \times 8)))$
45856 := $(F(4!) - ((5! - C(8, 5)) \times F(6)))$
45859 := $(F(4!) - (5 + (C(8, 5) \times 9)))$
45862 := $((C(4!, 5) - 8!) \times F(F(6))) - 2$
45863 := $((F(4!) - (-5) \times F(8)) - F(C(6, F(3))))$
45864 := $(C(4!, 5) + (8! / (F(6) + (4))))$
45884 := $(F(4!) - ((5! + C(8, 8)) \times 4))$
45893 := $(F(4!) - (-5) + (8! / C(9, 3)))$
45913 := $(F(4!) - C(((5 + 9) + 1), 3))$
45933 := $(F(4!) - (5 \times (C(9, 3) + 3)))$
45935 := $((F(4!) - (F((5 + 9)))) - C(F(3!), 5))$
45939 := $(F(4!) - ((5 \times C(9, 3)) + 9))$
45944 := $(F(4!) - ((5 \times C(9, F(4))) + (4)))$
45962 := $(F(4!) - C((-5) + F(9)), F((6/2)))$
45963 := $(F(4!) - (5 \times (C(9, 6) - 3)))$
45991 := $(F(4!) - F((5 + C(9, (9 - 1))))$
45993 := $(F(4!) + ((5 \times (9 - C(9, 3))))$
46043 := $(F(4!) - C((F(F(6)) + (0! + (4))), F(3)))$
46073 := $(F(4!) - ((F(6) + 0!) + C(F(7), 3)))$

- 46074** := $(F(4!) - (F(6) + C(F(07), F(4))))$
46092 := $(F(4!) - C(((- (6) + 0!) + 9)!, 2))$
46098 := $(F(4!) - (6 \times C((0! + 9), 8)))$
46107 := $((F(4!) - C(F(6), (1 + 0!))) - F(F(7)))$
46143 := $(F(4!) - (C(C(6, 1), 4)^{F(3)}))$
46163 := $((F(4!) - F(F((6 + 1)))) + C(F(6), F(3)))$
46198 := $(F(4!) - ((6 - 1) \times F(C(9, 8))))$
46203 := $(F(4!) - C(((F(6) + 2) + 0!), 3))$
46206 := $(F(4!) - ((C(F(6), 2) - 0!) \times 6))$
46216 := $(F(4!) - (F(6) + F((C(2, 1) \times 6))))$
46229 := $(F(4!) - (C(C(6, 2), 2) + F(9)))$
46263 := $(F(4!) - C(C(6, 2), (6/3)))$
46269 := $(F(4!) - ((C(6, 2) \times 6) + 9))$
46270 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(6), 2) + 70))$
46276 := $(F(4!) - (F(6) + (C((2 + 7), 6))))$
46306 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(6), 3) + 06))$
46311 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(6), 3) + C(1, 1)))$
46313 := $(F(4!) - F((6 + C((3 + 1), 3))))$
46323 := $(F((4 \times 6)) - (C(3!, 2) \times 3))$
46384 := $((F((4 + C(6, 3))) - 8) + 4!)$
46390 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(6), 3) - F((9 + 0))))$
46413 := $(F(4!) + (C(C(6, 4), 1) \times 3))$
46433 := $(F(4!) + (64 + C(3, 3)))$
46453 := $(F(4!) + ((6!/4!) + F(C(5, 3))))$
46479 := $(F(4!) + (C((6 + 4), 7) - 9))$
46484 := $(F(4!) + ((C(6, 4) \times 8) - 4))$
46486 := $(F(4!) + (6 + (4 \times C(8, 6))))$
46488 := $(F((4 \times 6)) + ((4 + C(8, 8))!))$
46495 := $(F(4!) + (F((6 - 4)) + (C(9, 5))))$
46528 := $(F(4!) + (C(6, (5 - 2)) \times 8))$
46532 := $(F(4!) + (C((6 + 5), 3) - F(2)))$
46547 := $(F(4!) + ((F(C(6, 5)) \times 4!) - F(7)))$
46557 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(6), 5) + 5!) + F(7)))$
46571 := $((F(4!) - (6 \times 5)) + F(F(C(7, 1))))$
46572 := $(F(4!) + (C(6, 5) \times F((7 + 2))))$
46575 := $((F(4!) - F(F(C(6, 5)))) + F(F(7))) - (5))$
46593 := $(F(4!) + (C(6, 5) + 9)^{F(3)})$
46623 := $((F(4!) - F(F(6))) + C(((6 - 2)!, F(3)))$
46641 := $((F(4!)!^6) - C(C(6, 4), 1))$
46642 := $(F(4!) + ((6 - F(6)) + C(4!, 2)))$
46677 := $((F(4!)!^6) + (C(F(6), 7) + F(7)))$
46719 := $((F(4!)!^6) + (C(7, 1) \times 9))$
46726 := $((F(4!)!^6) + (C(F(7), 2) - F(6)))$
46732 := $((F(4!) + F(F(6))) + (7^{C(3, 2)}))$
46741 := $((- (4) + F(F(F(6) - 7))) + F((C(4, 1))!))$
46752 := $(F(4!) + (F(6) \times (- (7) + F(C(5, 2))))$
46775 := $((F(4!)!^6) + (- (C(7, 7) + 5!))$
46776 := $(4! \times (F((6 + 7)) + C(F(7), 6)))$
46781 := $((C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(6)) / 7) + F((F(8) + 1)))$
46823 := $(F(4!) + C(C(6, (8/2)), 3))$
46827 := $((F(4!) + (6! - C(8, 2))) - F(F(7)))$
46832 := $(F(4!) + (F(6) \times (C(8, 3) + 2)))$
46833 := $(F(4!) + ((6! + C(F(8), F(3))) / F(3)))$
46836 := $(F(4!) + (6 + C((8 + 3), 6)))$
46881 := $((F(4)^{F(6)}) + (C(8, (8 - 1))!))$
46954 := $(F(4!) + (F(C(6, (9 - 5))) - 4!))$
46956 := $(F(4!) + (6! - (C(9, 5) + 6)))$
46962 := $(F(4!) + (6! - C(9, (6 - 2))))$
46963 := $(F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - C(6, F(3))))$
46971 := $(F(4!) + (F((6 + 9)) - C(7, 1)))$
46984 := $(F(4!) + ((6! - F(9)) - C(8, 4)))$
46986 := $(F(4!) + (F(6) + F((C(9, 8) + 6))))$
46998 := $(F(4!) + (((6 + C(9, 9))! / 8))$
47049 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(7), 04) - F(9)))$
47072 := $((F((F(4)!))! + (- (F(7)) + F(- ((0! - (C(7, 2)))))))$
47083 := $(F(4!) + C(F(7), (((0 \times 8))! + 3)))$
47088 := $(F(4!) + ((7 - C(08, 8))!))$
47122 := $(F(4!) + (F((C(7, 1) \times 2)) \times 2))$
47123 := $((F(4!) + C(7, (1 + 2))) + 3!)$
47144 := $((F(4)!))! + (C((7 + 1), F(4)) + F(4!))$
47154 := $((F(4!) + C((F(7) - 1), 5)) - (F(4)!))$
47155 := $(F(4!) + (C((F(7) - 1), 5) - (5)))$
47194 := $- (((C(4!, F(7)) - ((1 + 9))! / 4!))$
47227 := $(F(4!) - ((F((C(7, 2) - 2)) - 7!))$
47248 := $((4! \times F(C(7, 2))) / F(4)) - 8!$
47253 := $((F((F(4)!)) \times F(C(7, 2))) + (5)) - (F(3)!))$
47255 := $((5! - F(C(5, 2))) \times (7 + ((F(4)!))!))$
47257 := $(F(4!) + ((C(7, F(2)) + 5!) \times 7))$
47259 := $(F(4!) + ((- (C(7, 2)) + 5!) \times 9))$
47278 := $(F(4!) - ((F((7 \times 2)) - C(F(7), 8)))$

- 47286** := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), 2) \times F(8)) - 6!))$
47328 := $(4! \times (C(F(7), 3!) + (2^8)))$
47334 := $(F(4!) + (C((F(7) + 3!), 3) - F(4)))$
47337 := $(F(4!) + C((F(7) + 3!), (3 + F(7))))$
47340 := $-((F((F(4))!) - (7 \times (F(C(3!, F(4))) - 0!)))$
47343 := $(F(4!) + (C((F(7) \times F(3)), 4) \times 3))$
47348 := $(F(4!) + (C((7 \times F(3)), 4) - F(8)))$
47361 := $((F(4!) + F((F(7) + 3))) + C(6, 1))$
47367 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), 3) + 6!) - (7)))$
47383 := $((F(4!) + F((F(7) + 3))) + C(8, F(3)))$
47396 := $((- (4) - (F(F(7)) \times (-3!))) \times F(C(9, F(6))))$
47398 := $((F(4))! \times (C(F(7), 3) \times F(9))) - F(F(8)))$
47425 := $((F(4!) + 7) - (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2) \times (-5)))$
47431 := $((F(4!) + ((7^{F(4)}))) + ((C(3, 1))!))$
47474 := $((F(4!) - F((F(7) + F(F(4)))))) + C(F(7), (F(4))!))$
47474 := $((F(4!) - F((F(7) + F(F(4)))))) + C(F(7), (F(4))!))$
47498 := $((F(4))! \times F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4))) \times F(C(9, 8))$
47535 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(7), (5 + 3)) - 5!))$
47538 := $(F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (C(5, 3))!) / 8!))$
47543 := $((F(F(4)) + F(F(7))) \times 5) + F((C(4, 3))!))$
47627 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 7) - F(F(F(6)))) / 2) - (7!))$
47631 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) - ((3 + 1))!))$
47634 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + 3) - 4!))$
47643 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(7), F(6)) - (4 \times 3)))$
47646 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) - F(4)) - (6)))$
47649 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + F(4)) - 9))$
47660 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + (6)) - 0!))$
47661 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(7), F(6)) + C(6, 1)))$
47662 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + (6)) + F(2)))$
47663 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + (6)) + F(3)))$
47668 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) - F(6)) + F(8)))$
47673 := $((C(4!, 7) + (F(6))!) - (7!)) / F(3!))$
47674 := $((F(4))! + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + F(7)))) + F(4!))$
47674 := $((F(4))! + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + F(7)))) + F(4!))$
47676 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + F(7)) + F(6)))$
47679 := $((F(4!) + C(F(7), F(6))) + ((F(7) - 9))!)$
47683 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(7), F(6)) + C(8, F(3))))$
47684 := $((F(4!) + 7) - F(F(6))) + (C(F(8), F(4)))$
47689 := $(F(4!) + (C((7 + 6), 8) + F(9)))$
47690 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) + F(9)) + 0!))$
47691 := $(F(4!) + ((7 \times F(F(6))) \times C(9, 1)))$
47707 := $((F(4!) + C(F(7), 7)) - F((0! + F(7))))$
47733 := $(F(4!) + (F(7) \times (C(7, 3) \times 3)))$
47735 := $((F((F(4))!))! + ((F(F(7)) - C(F(7), 3!)) \times (-5)))$
47763 := $((F(4!) - (7!)) + C((7 + F(6)), F(3!)))$
47775 := $(F(4!) + (C(F(7), F((-7) + F(7)))) + 5!))$
47786 := $(F(F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(8, 6))))$
47803 := $((F(4!) + C(F(7), (8 + 0!))) + 3!))$
47824 := $(F(4!) + (F(7) \times (C(8, 2) \times 4)))$
47829 := $(F(4!) + ((7 \times C(F(8), 2)) - 9))$
47831 := $(F(4!) + (7 \times (C(F(8), F(3)) - 1)))$
47834 := $(F(4!) + ((7 \times C(F(8), F(3))) - (4)))$
47856 := $(4! \times (C((-7) + F(8), 5) - F(6)))$
47867 := $((F(4!) + C(F(7), 8)) - F(F(6))) + F(F(7)))$
47879 := $((F(4!) + C(F(7), 8)) + F(F(7))) - 9$
47880 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!)), F(7)) \times 8) / F((8 + 0!)))$
47888 := $((F(4!) + F(F(7))) + (C((-8) + F(8), 8)))$
47897 := $((F(4!) + ((C(F(7), 8) + 9))) + F(F(7)))$
47954 := $(F(4!) + (F(7) \times (C(9, 5) - 4)))$
47977 := $(-((C(4!, F(7)) / F(9))) + F((F(7) + F(7))))$
48024 := $((F(4!) / C(8, 02)) + F(4!))$
48048 := $-((4! \times ((F(8) + 0!) - C(4!, F(8))))$
48063 := $((F(4!) - (F(8))) + C(F((0! + (6))), 3!))$
48076 := $(F(4!) + (-8) + C(F(07), 6))$
48077 := $(F(4!) + ((-8) + 0!) + C(F(7), 7))$
48084 := $(F(4!) + C(F((8 - 0!)), (F((8 - 4))!))$
48084 := $(F(4!) + C(F((8 - 0!)), (F((8 - 4))!))$
48231 := $(-((F(4) - C(F(8), 2))) \times F(F((3! + 1))))$
48258 := $(F(4!) + ((C(F(8), 2) - 5!) \times F(8)))$
48294 := $((4 + C(F(8), 2)) \times 9) + F(4!))$
48306 := $((F(4))! \times (C(F(8), 3) + 0!)) + (F(6))!$
48324 := $((- (4) + 8!) + C((F(3!) \times 2), (F(4))!))$
48326 := $((C((4! - 8), 3!) - 2) + (F(6))!)$
48336 := $(F(4!) + (((8! / C(3!, F(3))) - 6!))$
48344 := $((4! + 8!) + (C(3!, F(4))^{F(4)}))$
48345 := $((F(4)^8 - 3!) + C(4!, 5))$
48349 := $((F(4!) - (F(8))) + C((F(3!) + (F(4))!), 9))$
48357 := $(F(4!) + (C((8 + 3!), 5) - F(7)))$
48364 := $((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - C(6, F(4))$
48371 := $((F(4!) - 8!) \times F(3!)) - F(C(7, 1))$

- 48375** := ((F(4!) + ((8 - F(3)))!) + C(F(7), 5))
48378 := (((F(4)!) × (C(F(8), 3) + F(7))) + 8!)
48386 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F((3 × 8))) - (6))
48392 := (C(4!, F(8)) + F(((3 + 9) × 2)))
48394 := (F(4!) + (C((8 + 3!), 9) + 4!))
48395 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + 3) + F(((9 - 5)!))
48400 := (C((4 + 8), F(4))^{0!+0!})
48413 := (F(4!) + (F(8) + C(4!, (1 × 3))))
48414 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F(F((F(4)!))) + (1 + F(4!)))
48424 := ((C((4 + 8), F(4))²) + 4!)
48426 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F(4!)) + F((F(2) + F(6))))
48434 := (((F(F(4)) × F(8)) + (C(4!, 3))) + F(4!))
48435 := (((C(4!, F(8)) × 4!) - F(F(3!))) - 5!)
48442 := -((F(F(F((F(4)!))) - ((8! - C(4!, 4)) × 2)))
48447 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F(4!)) + F((F(4) + (7))))
48448 := ((-4) × (-8 - C(4!, F(4)))) + 8!)
48451 := (((C(F(F((F(4)!)), 8) / F(F((F(4)!))) × 5) + 1)
48452 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F(4!)) + (5!/2))
48453 := (((C(4!, F(8)) × 4!) - 5!) - 3)
48455 := (((C(F(F((F(4)!)), 8) / F(F((F(4)!))) × 5) + (5))
48455 := (5 + (5 × (C(F(F((F(4)!)), 8) / F(F((F(4)!))))))
48457 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F(4!)) - (-5) × F(7))
48466 := (((F(4!) / (-8)) - F(F(4))) + C(F(F(6)), 6))
48488 := ((C(4!, F(8)) × 4!) - (88))
48494 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F(4!)) + (F(9) × F(4)))
48552 := (F(4!) + (C((F(8) - 5), 5) / 2))
48576 := (C(4!, F(8)) × (((5 - 7) + 6)!))
48607 := (C(-((F(4) - F(8))), (F(6) + 0!)) - F(7))
48614 := (C(-((F(4) - F(8))), (F(6) + 1)) - (F(4)!))
48624 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + F((6/2))) × 4!)
48632 := ((C((-4) + F(8)), F(6) + 3!) × 2)
48645 := (((C(4!, 8) × F(6)) - F(4!)) / 5!)
48649 := (F((F(4)!)) + (F(8) + C((-6) + 4!), 9)))
48667 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + ((6⁶))) - F(7))
48726 := (F(4!) + ((F(8) × C(F(7), 2)) + 6!))
48742 := (((C(4!, F(8)) + (7)) × 4!) - 2)
48743 := (((C(4!, F(8)) + (7)) × 4!) - F(F(3)))
48744 := ((F(4) × 8) × (7 + C(4!, F(4))))
48745 := (((C(4!, F(8)) + F(F(7))) + F(4!)) + 5!)
48756 := (((F((F(4)!))!) + C(F(8), F(7))) / 5) - 6)
- 48765** := (F(4) + ((-C(F(8), F(7))) - (F(6)!)) / (-5))
48783 := ((F(F((F(4)!)) × (-F(8))) - (7! - C(F(8), 3!)))
48824 := ((4 × F(F(8))) + ((C(8, 2) / 4)!))
48892 := (((F(4)!))! - C(8, 8)) × (F(9) × 2))
48944 := (F(4!) + (C((-8) + F(9)), F(4) - 4!))
48983 := (-4) + ((C(F(8), 9) - 8) / 3!)
48984 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + ((9 + 8))) × 4!)
48984 := ((C(4!, F(8)) + ((9 + 8))) × 4!)
48986 := (((F(4)! - ((C(F(8), 9) - 8))) / (-6))
48987 := ((F((F(4)!)) - C(F(8), 9)) / (-((F(8) / 7)!))
48993 := (((F(4)! - ((C(F(8), 9) + F(9)))) / (-3!))
48994 := ((4 × (C(F(8), 9) + F(9))) / 4!)
48999 := ((F((F(4)!))!) + ((C(F(8), 9) / F(9)) + F(9)))
49242 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9) / 2) - C((F(4)!), 2))
49252 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9) / 2) - C(5, F(2)))
49265 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9) / 2) + F(C(6, 5)))
49291 := (((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 9) / 2) + F(C(9, 1)))
49293 := (F(4!) + C((C(9, 2) - 9), 3))
49333 := ((C((F(4) × 9), 3!) / 3!) - F(3))
49334 := ((C((F(4) × 9), 3!) - 3!) / (F(4)!))
49335 := (C((F(4) × 9), 3!) / C(3!, 5))
49336 := ((C((F(4) × 9), 3!) + 3!) / 6)
49340 := (((F(4)!))! + C((9 × F(3)), (F((F(4)!)) + 0!)))
49343 := ((C((F(4) × 9), 3!) / (F(4)!)) + F(3!))
49344 := (4! × ((F(9) - F(3)) + C(4!, F(4))))
49349 := (((F(4)!))! + (9 + C((3! × F(4)), 9)))
49369 := ((C((F(4) × 9), 3!) / 6) + F(9))
49371 := (F(F((F(4)!)) × (F((9 × F(3))) - F(F(C(7, 1))))))
49392 := (F(4!) + (C(9, 3) × C(9, 2)))
49393 := (F(4!) + (C((9 + F(3)), 9)^{F(3)}))
49394 := (F(4!) - ((F(9) - C((F(3) × 9), 4)))
49394 := (F(4!) - ((F(9) - C((F(3) × 9), 4)))
49462 := (F(4!) + (F(9) × C(((F(4)! + F(6)), 2)))
49504 := (4 × C((9 + F((5 + 0!))), (F(4)!))
49568 := ((C((F((F(4)!)) + 9), 5) + F(6)) × 8)
49581 := ((F(F((F(4)!))^{F(9-5)}) + (C(8, 1)!))
49598 := (F(4!) + (95 × F(C(9, 8))))
49636 := (F(4!) + (C((F(9) - (6)), 3) - F(6)))
49637 := (F(4!) + (C((F(9) - (6)), 3) - (7)))
49642 := (F(4!) + (C((F(9) - (6)), F(4) - 2))

$$\begin{aligned}
 49643 &:= ((F(4!) + C((F(9) - (6)), F(4))), F(4))) - F(F(3)) \\
 49644 &:= (F(4!) + C((C(9,6) / F(4)), F(4))) \\
 49706 &:= (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + C(((F(9) - F(7)) - 0!), 6)) \\
 49826 &:= (((F(4) \times 9!) / C(8,2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 49863 &:= (F(4!) + (F((F(9) - F(8))) \times C(6, F(3)))) \\
 49944 &:= (((F(4)!))! + ((F(9) \times C(9, F(4))) + F(4)!)) \\
 50244 &:= (C((F(F(5 + 0!))) - 2), 4) + F(4!) \\
 50267 &:= (-((5! + 0!)) + C((-2) + F(F(6))), 7) \\
 50367 &:= -((F(F(5 + 0!))) - C((-F(3)) + F(F(6))), 7)) \\
 50387 &:= (-((5 \times 0)!) + C(-((F(3) - F(8))), 7) \\
 50546 &:= (((5 + 0!)! \times F(C(5, F(4)))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 50549 &:= (F(((5 - 0!)!)) + (F((C(5, F(4)) + 9)))) \\
 50874 &:= (((-5) - 0!) - C(F(8), F(7))) / (-4) \\
 50946 &:= (C((-((5 - 09)!)!, 4) + (F(6)!)) \\
 51238 &:= ((-C(F((5 + 1)), 2)) + (F(3)!))! + F(F(8))) \\
 51261 &:= ((-5) + (F(((1 + 2)!)!))! + F(F(F(C(6, 1)))) \\
 51265 &:= (F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - (F(2) - (F(C(6, 5)!))) \\
 51266 &:= (F((C((5 + 1), 2) + 6)) + (F(6)!)) \\
 51384 &:= (-((5! \times ((1 + 3)!)!)) + C(F(8), (F(4)!)) \\
 51387 &:= (F((C((5 - 1), 3)!) - ((F(8) - 7)!)) \\
 51475 &:= (-5) \times (1 - (F((F(4)!)) \times C(F(7), 5))) \\
 51953 &:= ((5 + C(19, 5)) + (F(3)!))! \\
 52274 &:= ((F(C((5 + 2), 2)) - 7!) + F(4!)) \\
 52353 &:= (F(((5 - F(2))!) + C(F(F(3!)), (5 - F(F(3)))) \\
 52374 &:= (F(((5 - F(2))!) + (F(F(3!)) \times C(F(7), F(4)))) \\
 52470 &:= (F(C(5, 2)) \times (((F(4)!))! + ((F(F(7)) + 0!))) \\
 52584 &:= (C(((5 - F(2))!)!, 5) - (8! / (-4))) \\
 52624 &:= (C(((5 - F(2))!)!, F(F(6))) \times (2 + 4!)) \\
 52696 &:= ((F(((5 - 2)!)!))! + (C((F(6) + 9), 6))) \\
 52730 &:= (C(5, 2) \times (F(F(7)) + ((3! + 0!))) \\
 52744 &:= (5! - ((-2) \times F(7)) \times C(4!, F(4))) \\
 52864 &:= (((5! - 2) \times 8) \times C(F(6), F(4))) \\
 52865 &:= (-F(C(5, 2))) + ((-F(8)) \times F(F(6))) \times (-5!)) \\
 53143 &:= (C(5, 3) - (F((1 + F(F((F(4)!)))))) \times (-3)) \\
 53184 &:= ((-5!) \times (F(3!) + 1)) + C(F(8), (F(4)!)) \\
 53304 &:= ((-5!) \times F(3!)) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(04)!)) \\
 53345 &:= (((-5) \times F(F(3!))) + F(F(F(3!))) + C(4!, 5)) \\
 53355 &:= (((-5) \times F(C(5, 3))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \times 5 \\
 53361 &:= (((5! + F(F(3))) \times F(F(3!))) \times F(F(C(6, 1)))) \\
 53364 &:= (-((5 \times 3!)^{F(3)})) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 53373 &:= (5 + (C(F(3!), 3) \times (F(F(7)) + 3!))) \\
 53397 &:= (5! + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - (F((9 + 7)))) \\
 53443 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - C(F((F(4) + (4))), F(3!))) \\
 53445 &:= ((-5) + F((-3) + 4!)) + C(4!, 5) \\
 53469 &:= ((-C((5 \times 3), (F(4)!)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9) \\
 53484 &:= (((5! / F(3)) - ((F(4)!))! + (C(F(8), (F(4)!))) \\
 53507 &:= (C((5^{F(3)}), 5) + F((0! + F(7)))) \\
 53534 &:= (-((5! + F((3 \times 5)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!)) \\
 53633 &:= (F((5 + 3!)) + (C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 3!)) \\
 53640 &:= (5! \times ((F(3!) \times C(F(6), F(4))) - 0!)) \\
 53662 &:= ((5! - 3!) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) - 2)) \\
 53663 &:= ((5! - F(F(3))) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) - 3!)) \\
 53666 &:= ((5! + F(3)) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) - (6!))) \\
 53734 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) - (C(F(7), 3!) - ((F(4)!))!)) \\
 53845 &:= ((-5) + 3!) + (C((F(8) + (4)), 5)) \\
 53849 &:= ((5 - F(F(3!))) - (C(F(8), 4) \times (-9))) \\
 53854 &:= (((C(5, 3))! / C(8, 5)) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\
 53855 &:= (((F(C(5, 3)) - F(F(8))) + 5!) \times (-5)) \\
 53904 &:= ((5! \times (-3)) + C(F((9 - 0!)), (F(4)!)) \\
 53964 &:= ((5! - F(F(3!))) - (-9) \times C(F(F(6)), 4)) \\
 53974 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F(3!)))) + (-C(9, 7) - ((F(4)!))!)) \\
 53984 &:= ((5! - F(F(3))) + (9 \times C(F(8), 4))) \\
 54036 &:= ((5 - F(F((F(4)! + 0!))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 6))) \\
 54064 &:= (-((5 \times 40)) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!)) \\
 54095 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!))) - (0! + (C(9, 5)))) \\
 54137 &:= (-5!) + (C(F(F((4 - 1)!)!))!, 3!) - 7) \\
 54142 &:= (-5!) + (C(F(F((4 - 1)!)!))!, (F(4)! - 2)) \\
 54157 &:= (-5!) + (C(F(F((F(4)!))!), (1 + 5)) + F(7)) \\
 54165 &:= ((F(C(5, F(4))) \times F(16)) - 5!) \\
 54166 &:= ((-5!) + F(F((F(4)!))) - (-1 - C(F(F(6)), 6))) \\
 54204 &:= (((-5!) / F(F(4))) + C(F(F((2 + 0!)!))!), (F(4)!)) \\
 54224 &:= (-((5! / F(4))) + C(F(F((F(2 + 2)!)!))!), (F(4)!)) \\
 54230 &:= (F(C(5, F(4))) \times (F((2 \times F(3!))) - 0!)) \\
 54233 &:= (((-5) - 4!) - 2) + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) \\
 54234 &:= ((5! / (-4)) + C(F((2^3)), (F(4)!)) \\
 54238 &:= (-5) + (C(F((4 \times 2)), 3!) - F(8)) \\
 54253 &:= ((-5) - (F(4)!)) + C(F(F((F(2) + (5))))!, 3!) \\
 54254 &:= (-C(5, F(4)) + C(F(F((F(2) + (5))))!), (F(4)!)) \\
 54259 &:= (-5) + C(F((4 \times 2)), (F(-((5 - 9)!)!)) \\
 54260 &:= (-5) + (C(F((4 \times 2)), 6) + 0!)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54263 &:= (5 + (C(F((4 \times 2)), 6) - 3!)) \\
 54270 &:= (5 + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), -(F(2) - (7)))) + 0!) \\
 54273 &:= ((5 + 4) + C(F((F(2) + (7))), 3!)) \\
 54274 &:= (C(5, F(4)) + C(F((F(2) + (7))), (F(4))!)) \\
 54278 &:= ((C((5 + 4!), 2) \times F(F(7))) - 8!) \\
 54283 &:= ((- (5) + 4!) + C((F(2) \times F(8)), 3!)) \\
 54303 &:= (5 + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 3!) + F((0! + F(3)))))) \\
 54319 &:= (C(F((5 + F(4))), 3!) + F((1 + 9))) \\
 54324 &:= ((5! / F(F(4))) + C(F(F((3 \times 2))), (F(4))!)) \\
 54329 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 3!) - F((F(2) + 9)))) \\
 54333 &:= ((5 + (4^3)) + C(F(F(3!)), 3!)) \\
 54334 &:= (C(F((5 + F(4))), 3!) + C(F(3!), 4)) \\
 54340 &:= (F(C(5, F(4))) \times (F((F(3)^4)) + 0!)) \\
 54345 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))))^{F(3)} + C(F((F(4))!), 5)) \\
 54345 &:= ((F(F((5 + F(F(4))))))^{F(3)} + C(F((F(4))!), 5)) \\
 54349 &:= ((5! - F(F(F(4)))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!) - F(9))) \\
 54353 &:= (F((- (5) + 4!)) \times (3 + C(5, 3))) \\
 54371 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 3!) - F(C(7, 1)))) \\
 54376 &:= ((5! - F((F(4))!)) + (C((3 \times 7), 6))) \\
 54378 &:= ((5! - (F(4))!) + C(F(F(3!)), (7 + 8))) \\
 54383 &:= ((5! - (4 - 3)) + C(F(8), 3!)) \\
 54384 &:= (C(F((5 + F(4))), 3!) + ((8 - F(4))!)) \\
 54386 &:= (((5! + (4)) - F(3)) + C(F(8), 6)) \\
 54396 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 3!) + (- (9) + F(F(6)))))) \\
 54404 &:= (5! + ((C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) - 0!) + F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 54405 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) + F(F((0! + (5)))))) \\
 54406 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) + (0! + F(F(6)))))) \\
 54418 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) + F((1 + 8)))) \\
 54419 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) + (1 + F(9)))) \\
 54444 &:= (((5 - C(4!, F(4))) \times (-4)) + F(4!)) \\
 54448 &:= ((- (5!) \times C(4!, F(F(4)))) + (F((F(4))!) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 54451 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - C(F((F(4))!), 5))) + 1) \\
 54452 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - C(F((F(4))!), 5))) + 2) \\
 54454 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!))) - C(4!, (5 - F(4)))) \\
 54463 &:= ((F((5 \times 4)) + F(4!)) + C(F(F(6)), 3)) \\
 54464 &:= (((5^{F(F(4))}) \times F((F(4))!)) + (C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!)) \\
 54474 &:= (C(F((5 + F(4))), (F(4))!) + (7! / 4!)) \\
 54481 &:= (((5! - F(F(F(4))))^{F(F(4))}) + (C(8, 1))!) \\
 54484 &:= ((5 \times 44) + C(F(8), (F(4))!)) \\
 54487 &:= (((C(5, 4))!^{F(F(4))}) + 8!) - F(F(7))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54488 &:= (((5 + F(F(4))) \times C(4!, F(8))) + 8!) \\
 54492 &:= (- (5) + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) + (F(F((9 - 2)))))) \\
 54495 &:= (5! + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), (F(4))!) - (9 - 5!)) \\
 54504 &:= ((5! \times F(F(4))) + C(F(F((5 + 0!))), (F(4))!)) \\
 54534 &:= ((54 \times 5) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!)) \\
 54554 &:= ((- (5!) - C(F((F(4))!), 5)) + (5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 54564 &:= (((5! / F(F(4))) \times 5) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!)) \\
 54610 &:= (- (5) \times (4! - F(F(F((C(6, 1) + 0)))))) \\
 54624 &:= ((5! \times F(4)) + C(F(F(6)), (2 + 4))) \\
 54631 &:= ((- (5) \times (4! - F(F(F(6)))) + F(F((C(3, 1)))))) \\
 54636 &:= ((- (5) + F((F(4))! + F(6))) + C(F(F(3!)), 6)) \\
 54637 &:= ((5! \times F(4)) + (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + F(7))) \\
 54643 &:= (- (5) + (((F(4))! + F(F(6))) \times C(4!, 3))) \\
 54648 &:= (((- (5) + 4!) + F(6)) \times C(4!, F(8))) \\
 54662 &:= ((- (5) \times (F((F(4))!) - F(F(F(6)))) - C(F(6), 2)) \\
 54663 &:= (((- (5) + 4!) \times F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)), 3!)) \\
 54664 &:= (((5^{F(F(4))}) + (F(6))!) - C(F(6), F(4))) \\
 54700 &:= (- (5) \times ((F(4))! - F(C(7, (0! + 0)))))) \\
 54720 &:= (- (5) \times ((F(4) - F(C(7, 2))) - 0!)) \\
 54754 &:= ((C(5, 4) \times F(C(7, 5))) + 4!) \\
 54784 &:= (((C(5, 4))! - F(7)) \times (8^{F(4)})) \\
 54874 &:= (F((5 \times F(4))) + C(F(8), ((7 - 4)!)) \\
 54875 &:= (((5 + 4!) + F(F(C(8, 7)))) \times 5) \\
 54927 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (- (C(9, 2)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 54972 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (9 + F(C(F(7), F(2)))))) \\
 54982 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!))) + (9 \times C(8, 2))) \\
 54984 &:= (((54 / 9)! + C(F(8), (F(4))!)) \\
 55344 &:= ((C((5 \times 5), 3) + (F(4))!) \times 4!) \\
 55434 &:= ((5! \times C((5 + (F(4))!), 3!)) - (F(4))!) \\
 55467 &:= - (((5! \times 5!) - C(4!, F(6))) / F(7)) \\
 55775 &:= (- (5!) - (- (5) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(C(7, 5)))))) \\
 55794 &:= (((5! + 5!) \times F(F(7))) - C(9, 4)) \\
 56264 &:= (((- (5) \times C(F(F(6)), 2)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(4!)) \\
 56328 &:= (- (5!) + (((F(6))! / C(3!, 2)) \times F(8))) \\
 56336 &:= ((C((- (5) + F(F(6))), 3!) \times F(3)) + (F(6))!) \\
 56443 &:= (- (5) - (((F(6))! / (-4)) - F((C(4, 3)))))) \\
 56472 &:= (((5! \times 6) + (4)) \times C(F(7), 2)) \\
 56476 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (F(4))!)) + C(F(7), 6)) \\
 56479 &:= ((- (5!) + F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4)! - (C(F(7), 9)))))) \\
 56664 &:= ((C((5 + F(6)), F(6)) \times F(6)) + F(4!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 56763 &:= ((F((-5) + F(F(6)))) + C(F(7), 6)) \times F(F(3!)) \\
 56784 &:= ((5! + (F(6) \times C(F(7), 8))) + F(4!)) \\
 56844 &:= (((5! - C(F(F(6)), 8)) / (-F(4))) - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \\
 56884 &:= -((F(F(F((-5) + F(6)!))) - (C(F(8), 8) / F(4))) \\
 57242 &:= (5! + ((C(F(7), F(2))^4) \times 2)) \\
 57248 &:= ((- (C((5 + 7), 2)) + F(4!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 57334 &:= (F(F((-5) + F(7))) - (- (C(3!, 3)) - F(4!))) \\
 57375 &:= (((5 \times C(F(7), F(3!))) + (7!)) \times 5) \\
 57375 &:= (((5 \times C(F(7), F(3!))) + (7!)) \times 5) \\
 57497 &:= (5 + (F((-7) + 4!)) \times C(9, 7)) \\
 57554 &:= (((5! + F(C(7, 5))) + 5!) + F(4!)) \\
 57794 &:= (((5 + C(F(7), 7)) \times F(9)) - ((F(4)!))!) \\
 57894 &:= ((-5) \times (C(F(7), 8) \times (-9))) - F(F((F(4)!))) \\
 58031 &:= (F(F((-5 - 8)!))! + F((0! + F(F(C(3, 1)!)))) \\
 58245 &:= (-5) \times (- (F(8) - C((-2) + F(F((F(4)!))), 5))) \\
 58332 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!)) + F(C(3, 2))) \\
 58333 &:= ((5 \times (F(F(8)) + 3!)) + C(3, F(3))) \\
 58339 &:= (-5) - (C(F((F(8) / 3)), 3!) \times (-F(9))) \\
 58344 &:= (C((5 + 8), 3!) \times F((F(4) \times F(4)))) \\
 58349 &:= (5 - (C(F((F(8) / 3)), (F(4)!)) \times (-F(9)))) \\
 58448 &:= (((-5!) - C(F(8), (F(4)!)) / (-F(4))) + 8!) \\
 58753 &:= (5 + ((8! - F(C(7, 5))) \times F(3))) \\
 58906 &:= (5! + (C(F(8), (9 + 0!)) / 6)) \\
 58935 &:= (5 - ((- (C(F(8), 9)) - 3!) / 5)) \\
 59238 &:= (F((-5 - 9)!)) + (C((2 \times F(3!)), 8)) \\
 59304 &:= (C(F(F(F(-5 - 9)!)), 3!) + ((0! + (F(4)!))!)) \\
 59334 &:= (((5 + F(9))^3) + C(3!, 4)) \\
 59343 &:= (((5 + F(9))^3) + (C(4, 3)!)) \\
 59387 &:= ((5! \times C((9 + 3), 8)) - F(7)) \\
 59520 &:= (5! \times ((9 \times F(C(5, 2))) + 0!)) \\
 59774 &:= (((-5 - 9)! - F(F(7))) \times (-C(F(7), F(4)))) \\
 59844 &:= (((5 \times 9) \times C(F(8), F(4))) - (F(4)!)) \\
 59850 &:= ((5 \times 9) \times C(F(8), F((5 - 0!)))) \\
 60434 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! - (C(4!, F(3)))) / (F(4)!)) \\
 60467 &:= ((C((F(6) + 0!), F(4)) \times 6!) - F(7)) \\
 60494 &:= ((C((F(6) + 0!), F(4)) + 9!) / (F(4)!)) \\
 60626 &:= -(((F(6)! + 0!) - C((F(F(6)) + 2), 6))) \\
 60635 &:= (((F(6)! - F((0! + F(6)))) + C(F(F(3!)), 5)) \\
 60656 &:= -((F(F(6) - 0!)) - (C(F(F(6)), 5) + (F(6)!))) \\
 60657 &:= (((F(6)! + 0!) + (C(F(F(6)), 5) - F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 60659 &:= (((F(6)! - 0!) + (C(F(F(6)), 5) - 9)) \\
 60663 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), -((0! - 6))) + (F(6)! - 3!)) \\
 60668 &:= (((F(6)! - 0!) + C(F(F(6)), (F(6) + 8))) \\
 60676 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), -((0! - 6))) + 7) + (F(6)!)) \\
 60696 &:= ((F(F(6)) - F((-0! + F(F(6)))) \times (-C(9, F(6)))) \\
 60766 &:= (((F(6) + 0!)! + C(F(7), 6)) / 6) \\
 60864 &:= (- (F(6)) \times (C(-((0! - F(8))), 6) - F(4!))) \\
 60879 &:= (-6) + (F(-((0! - F(C(8, 7)))) \times 9)) \\
 60891 &:= (6 + (F(-((0! - F(8))) \times C(9, 1))) \\
 60967 &:= ((6! \times 0! + (C(9, 6))) - F(F(7))) \\
 61584 &:= ((6! \times 5!) + C(F(8), (F(4)!)) \\
 61784 &:= (F(6) \times (1 - (- (C(F(7), 8)) \times (F(4)!))) \\
 62349 &:= -((F(C(F(6), 2)) + ((3! \times (-4!)) - 9!)) \\
 62434 &:= (F(C(6, 2)) - ((F(4!) / 3) \times (-4))) \\
 62444 &:= (F(F((F(6) - F(2)))) \times (C(4!, F(F(4))) - F((F(4)!))) \\
 62447 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(2) + C(4!, F(4)))) \times 7) \\
 62632 &:= ((F(6)! + (2 \times (F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(3!)), 2))) \\
 62730 &:= (C(6, 2) \times (F((F(7) + 3!) + 0!)) \\
 62744 &:= (((6 - 2)! + 7) \times C(4!, F(4))) \\
 62749 &:= ((C(6, 2) \times F((F(7) + (F(4)!))) + F(9)) \\
 63063 &:= (F(F(6)) \times C((3! + F(06)), 3!)) \\
 63071 &:= (((F(6)! + F((F(F(3!)) + 0!))) + (C(7, 1)!)) \\
 63308 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), 3!) / 3!) \times (- (0! - 8))) \\
 63388 &:= (C(F(6), F(3)) - (3! \times (-88))) \\
 63427 &:= (((F(6) \times F(C(3!, 4))) - F(2)) \times F(7)) \\
 63440 &:= ((F(6) \times F(C(3!, 4))) \times F(((F(4)! + 0!))) \\
 63478 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (4 \times 7!)) - F(F(8))) \\
 63546 &:= ((6! - 3!) \times F((C(5, 4) + 6))) \\
 63574 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), 3) / 5) \times (F(F(7)) + (F(4)!)) \\
 63613 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(3!)), (6 + 1))) / F(3)) \\
 63632 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(3!))) + (6! \times C(F(F(3!)), 2))) \\
 63637 &:= (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + ((6! + F(F(3))) \times F(7))) \\
 63645 &:= (((F(F(6))^3) + (C(F(F(6)), (F(4)! + 5!)) \\
 63726 &:= ((F(F(6)) + 3!) \times (C(F(7), 2) + F(6))) \\
 63783 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times C((F(3) \times 7), 8)) + 3!) \\
 63795 &:= -((F(C(6, 3)) - (7! \times (9 + 5))) \\
 63813 &:= ((6! - 3) \times F((C(8, 1) + 3))) \\
 63832 &:= (F(6) \times ((3! \times C(F(8), 3)) - F(2))) \\
 63834 &:= (-6) + (F(3) \times (C(F(8), 3) \times 4!)) \\
 63835 &:= (((F(6) \times 3!) \times C(F(8), 3)) - 5)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 63894** := (((C(F(F(6)), 3) × 8) + 9) × (F(4))!)
63996 := ((6! × F((F(3) + 9))) - C(9, 6))
64064 := (F(6) × C((4! - F(06)), (F(4))!))
64076 := (F(F(F(6))) + C((4! + 0!), (F(7) - F(6))))
64087 := ((F(6) + F(4!)) + F((0! + F(C(8, 7))))
64135 := -((F(F(F(6))) - (F((4! + 1)) + C(F(3!), 5))))
64177 := -((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + ((1 - 7!) × F(7)))
64225 := ((- (6!) × C((F(4))!, 2)) + F(25))
64245 := ((- (F(F(6))) + C((4²), F((F(4))!))) × 5)
64264 := (C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) + ((2 + F(6))⁴))
64308 := (C((6 × 4), F(3)) × F(F(-((0! - 8))))
64316 := (F(6) - (- (C(4!, F(3))) × F(F((1 + 6))))
64323 := ((C(F(F(6)), 4) × 3) + F(((F(2) + 3)!))
64326 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (C((F(4))!, F(3))²)) × 6)
64329 := (F(F(6)) + (C(4!, F(3)) × F(F(-((2 - 9))))))
64334 := (((F(F(F(6))) - F(F(4))) × 3!) - C(F(F(3!)), F(4)))
64335 := ((C(-((F(6) - 4!)), F(3!)) - 3) × 5)
64337 := (C((F(6) + (F(4))!), F(3)) × (3! - F(7)))
64338 := -(((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + F(3!)) - (3! × F(F(8))))
64340 := (- (C(F(F(6)), F(4))) + (3! × (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - 0!))
64342 := (C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) + (((F(3!))! / 4) - 2))
64343 := ((F(F(F(6))) × (F(4))!) - (C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) + 3))
64344 := (F(F(6)) × (C((4! - 3!), 4) + (4)))
64345 := ((C(-((F(6) - 4!)), F(3!)) - F(F(F(4)))) × 5)
64346 := -((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - (F((- (3) + 4!)) × 6))
64346 := -((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - (F((- (3) + 4!)) × 6))
64347 := ((6! + F(C(4, 3))) × F((4 + 7)))
64348 := -(((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - F(3)) - ((F(4))! × F(F(8))))
64364 := (((F(F(F(6))) + F(4)) × 3!) - C(F(F(6)), F(4)))
64395 := ((C(-((F(6) - 4!)), F(3!)) + 9) × 5)
64397 := ((F(6))! + (C((- (4) + F(F(3!))), 9) - F(F(7)))
64404 := (((F(6))! + C(4!, ((F(4))! + 0!))) / (F(4))!)
64416 := ((- (C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(((4 - 1)!)))) × 6)
64422 := (6 × (F(F(F((F(4))!))) - (C(F(F((F(4))!), 2) - F(2))))
64424 := F(6) + (F(F(F(F(4))!)) - C(F(F(F(4))!), 2)) × F(4)!
64436 := (F((F(6) + F(4))) × (C(4, 3) + 6!))
64439 := (- ((6! × 4!)) - (C(4!, F(3!)) / (-9))
64448 := (((F(6))! × F(F(4))) - (C(4!, F(4)) × 8))
64449 := (F(F(6)) × (C((F(4) × (F(4))!), 4) + 9))
64455 := (5 × (C((- (5) + F(F((F(4))!))), F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(6))))
64466 := ((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4))!)) - (4! - C(F(F(6)), 6)))
64476 := (6 × (C(4!, 4) + ((F(7) - F(6))!))
64478 := ((- (6) × C(4!, F(4))) - (- (7) × F(F(8))))
64484 := ((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4))!)) - ((F(4))! - C(F(8), (F(4))!)))
64485 := ((C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) - ((F(4))!)) + (F(F(8)) - (5)))
64486 := (((C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) - 4) + F(F(8))) - (6!))
64487 := (- (6) - ((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 4) - F(F(8))) × F(7)))
64490 := ((C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) - ((F(4))!)) + F(F((9 - 0!)))
64493 := ((F(F(F(6))) - C(F(F((F(4))!), 4)) × F((9 - F(3))))
64511 := (((- ((F(6))!) × F((F(4))!)) / (-5)) - C(1, 1))
64545 := ((F(6))! + ((C((4 × 5), 4) × 5))
64552 := (F(6) × (((F((F(4))!))! / 5) + C(5, F(2))))
64628 := (C((F(F(6)) - 4), F(6)) - (2 - 8!))
64684 := (((F(6) × C(4!, F(F(6)))) - (F(8))) × 4)
64855 := (5 + (5 × (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))))
64924 := ((- (F(6)) + F(4!)) + C((9 × 2), (F(4))!))
64926 := ((- (6) + F(4!)) + C((9 × 2), 6))
64965 := ((F(F(F(6))) × (F(4))!) - (- (9) + (C(6, 5)!))
64977 := ((C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) + F((F(9) - F(7)))) - F(F(7)))
65186 := (F(F(F(6))) - (((5 - 1)! - C(F(8), 6)))
65367 := ((C(F(F(6)), 5) × 3) - (6! - 7!))
65387 := (- (C(F(6), 5)) - ((- (3) × F(F(8))) + F(F(7))))
65431 := -F(F(6)) × 5 + 4^{F(C(3, 1)!)}
65507 := (((6 + C(5, 5))! - 0!) × F(7))
65548 := (- ((F(C(6, 5)) + 5!)) + ((F(4))! × F(F(8))))
65577 := -((F(C(6, 5)) - ((5 + 7!) × F(7)))
65614 := (- (C(F(6), 5)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - 1) × (F(4))!))
65620 := (- (C(F(6), 5)) + (F(F(F(6))) × ((2 + 0!)!))
65640 := ((F(6))! - (- (5!) × (C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)) + 0!)))
65654 := ((C((F(F(6)) + 5), F(F(6))) - 5!) - (F(4))!)
65655 := (C((F(F(6)) + 5), F(F(6))) + (- (5) - 5!))
65660 := (C((F(F(6)) + 5), F(F(6))) - ((6 - 0!)!))
65677 := ((F(F(F(6))) × ((- (5) + F(6))!)) + C(7, 7))
65682 := (6 + (((- (5) + F(6))! × F(C(F(8), F(2))))
65702 := (F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) + (((F(F(7)) + 0!)²))
65708 := (C(F(F(6)), 5) + (((7! - 0!) + 8!))
65709 := (C(F(F(6)), 5) - (7! × (0 - 9))
65754 := (((F(6) + 5) + F(C(7, 5))) × (F(4))!)
65764 := (((C(F(F(6)), 5) - F(F(7))) - (6!)) + F(4))
65774 := (C((F(F(6)) + 5), F(F((- (7) + F(7)))) - (F(4))!)

$$\begin{aligned}
 65793 &:= ((F(F(C(6,5))) + (7!)) \times F((9 - F(3)))) \\
 65802 &:= ((F(F(C(6,5))) + F(F(8))) \times ((0! + 2)!)) \\
 65804 &:= (C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) + (04!)) \\
 65808 &:= (C(6,5) \times (F(F(8)) + (0! + F(8)))) \\
 65814 &:= (C(6,5) \times (F(F(8)) + (-1 + 4!))) \\
 65843 &:= (((6 + 5) \times C(F(8), 4)) + F(3!)) \\
 65880 &:= (C(6,5) \times (F(F(8)) + F((8 + 0!)))) \\
 65894 &:= ((-6 + 5!) + C((-8 + F(9)), F(F((F(4))!)))) \\
 65948 &:= ((F(C(6,5)) \times F(9)) + ((F(4))! \times F(F(8)))) \\
 66072 &:= (6 \times (F(F(F(6)))) + C(-((0! - F(7))), 2)) \\
 66276 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((6! \times 2) + C(F(7), 6))) \\
 66334 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + F(6)) \times 3!) + F(C(3!, 4))) \\
 66368 &:= ((6! - C(F(6), F(3))) + (6 \times F(F(8)))) \\
 66375 &:= ((6! - F(F(6))) + (3! \times F(C(7, 5)))) \\
 66394 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(C(6, F(3)))) \times (-F(9))) + F(4!)) \\
 66408 &:= (C(F(F(6)), 6) - (((4!)! \times (-0!)) / (F(8))!)) \\
 66465 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (F(C(6, F(4))) - (6! \times 5))) \\
 66466 &:= ((6! + C(F(6), 4)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 6)) \\
 66466 &:= ((6! + C(F(6), 4)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 6)) \\
 66486 &:= (6! - (((-C(6, 4)) - F(F(8))) \times 6)) \\
 66633 &:= (-C(F(F(6)), 6) - ((F(F(6)) - (F(3))!) \times 3)) \\
 66645 &:= ((F(6))! + ((6! - C(F(F(6)), 4)) \times (-5))) \\
 66684 &:= (((C(F(6), 6) \times 6) + F(F(8))) \times (F(4))!) \\
 66694 &:= -((C(F(F(6)), 6) + ((6 - 9!) / F(4))) \\
 66696 &:= -((C(F(F(6)), 6) + ((F(6))! \times (-9 - 6)))) \\
 66843 &:= (-F((F(6) + F(6))) + (C(F(8), F((F(4))!)) / 3)) \\
 66849 &:= -((F(F(6)) + (C((6 + F(8)), (F(4))!)) - 9!)) \\
 66863 &:= (((6! \times 6!) - F(C(8, 6))) / 3) \\
 66939 &:= -((F(F(6)) - (6! \times (C(9, 3) + 9)))) \\
 66960 &:= (6! \times ((F(6) + (C(9, 6))) + 0!)) \\
 67106 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((C(F(7), (1 + 0!)) \times 6!)) \\
 67235 &:= (((F(6))! + C(7, 2)) / 3) \times 5) \\
 67262 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + ((C(F(7), 2) \times (6! + 2))) \\
 67326 &:= ((F(6))! + ((C(F(7), F(3!)) - F(2)) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 67333 &:= (F(F(6)) - (7 \times (C(F(F(3!)), 3) - F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 67343 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times C(F(7), F(3!))) - 4) + (F(3!))!) \\
 67347 &:= ((F(6))! + (C(F(7), F(3!)) \times (F(4) \times 7))) \\
 67358 &:= (6! + (C(F(7), 3) \times F((5 + 8)))) \\
 67368 &:= ((F(6))! + ((C(F(7), F(3!)) \times F(F(6))) + (F(8)))) \\
 67444 &:= (((F(6))! + C((F(7) + (F(4))!), (F(4))!)) - F((F(4))!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67446 &:= ((C((6 + F(7)), (F(4))!) - (F(4))!) + (F(6))!) \\
 67448 &:= (C((6 + F(7)), (F(4))!) - (4 - 8!)) \\
 67452 &:= ((F(6))! + C((F(7) + (F(4))!), ((5 - 2)!)) \\
 67475 &:= (((F(6) \times C(F(7), (F(4))!)) - F(F(7))) \times 5) \\
 67536 &:= (F(6) \times ((C(F(7), 5) \times 3!) + 6!)) \\
 67543 &:= ((6! + C(F(7), 5)) + (4^{F(3)})) \\
 67544 &:= ((F(6))! - ((7! \times (-5)) - C(4!, F(4)))) \\
 67613 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(7), F(6)))) \times (1 + 3!)) \\
 67776 &:= ((F(6))! + (C((7 + 7), 7) \times F(6))) \\
 67776 &:= ((F(6))! + (C((7 + 7), 7) \times F(6))) \\
 67843 &:= (((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) + (F(8))) / F(4)) + 3!) \\
 67854 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / (8 - 5)) + (4!)) \\
 67935 &:= (-F(F(6))) \times (-C(F(7), 9) + (F(F(3!)) \times (-5!))) \\
 68134 &:= (((F(6))! - F(F(8))) + C((-1 + F(F(3!))), (F(4))!)) \\
 68364 &:= (6 \times (F(F(8)) + (F(3!) \times C(F(6), F(4)))) \\
 68437 &:= (((F(6))! - C(F(8), 4)) \times F(3)) - F(F(7))) \\
 68439 &:= -((F((6 + 8)) - (C(4!, 3) \times F(9))) \\
 68444 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + C(F(8), 4)) \times 4) + ((F(4))!)) \\
 68479 &:= -((((6! - C(F(8), 4)) \times F(7)) - F(9))) \\
 68664 &:= (((6! \times F(8)) - 6!) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!)) \\
 68674 &:= -(((F(6))! + ((-C(F(8), 6) - F(F(7))) \times F(F(4)))) \\
 68726 &:= (((6! - C(F(8), 7)) / (-2)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 68745 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (8 \times C(F(7), (F(4))!))) \times 5) \\
 68929 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (C(F(8), 9))) \times (-F(2))) + 9!) \\
 68939 &:= -((F(6) + ((C(F(8), 9) + 3) - 9!)) \\
 68942 &:= (-((F(6) + C(F(8), 9))) + ((F(4)^2)!)) \\
 68944 &:= ((-6 - C(F(8), 9)) + ((F(4) \times F(4))!)) \\
 68949 &:= ((-C(F(F(6)), (F(8) - 9)) - F(F(F(4)))) + 9!) \\
 69434 &:= (6! + (F(9) \times (C(4!, 3) - F(4)))) \\
 69442 &:= (-F(F(F(6))) - ((-C(9, 4) + (F((F(4))!))! \times (-2))) \\
 69536 &:= (6! - (-F(9) \times C(((5 - F(F(3!)))!, F(F(6)))))) \\
 69568 &:= (((F(6))! - (C(9, 5))) + (F(6))! - F(F(8))) \\
 69644 &:= (((6! + 9!) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!)) / (F(4))! \\
 69649 &:= ((-((C(F(F(6)), 9) + F(F(6)))) + ((F(4))!)) + 9!) \\
 69670 &:= ((6! + 9!) - C(F(F(6)), (F(7) - 0!)) \\
 69694 &:= ((6! + 9!) - (C(F(F(6)), 9) - (4!)) \\
 69728 &:= ((F(6))! + (((F(9) - F(C(7, 2))) + 8!)) \\
 69734 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (-9) \times (F(F(7)) - F(C(3!, F(4)))))) \\
 69784 &:= ((6! \times 97) - C(8, F(4))) \\
 69937 &:= -(((C(F(F(6)), 9) - 9!) - F((3 + F(7))))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 69996** := ((6! + F(F((9 - C(9, 9)))))) × 6
70543 := (-((7! - 0!)) + C((-5) + 4!), F(3!))
70844 := (F(((7 × 0)! + F(8))) × C(4, F(4)))
71582 := (7 × (-((1 + 5)!)) + F(C(F(8), F(2))))
71844 := (((F(7) - 1) × C(F(8), 4)) + 4!)
72338 := (7 × ((-2) - F(C(3!, F(3)))) + F(F(8)))
72355 := (-5) + (5! × (F(C(3!, 2)) - 7))
72438 := (((F(C(7, 2)) × F(4)) - 3!) + 8!)
72441 := ((F(C(7, 2)) × 4) + F((4! - 1)))
72475 := (-7!) + (C((-F(2)) + F(F((F(4)!))), 7) - (5))
72480 := (-7!) + C((-F(2)) + F(F((F(4)!))), (8 - 0!))
72495 := -(((C(F(7), 2) + F(4)) + (9! / (-5))))
72567 := ((-C(7, 2) + 5!) × (6! + F(7)))
72764 := (-((7! + F(2))) + (F(7) × C(F(F(6)), 4)))
72774 := (C(F(7), 2) - (F(F(7)) × (-F(7) × 4!)))
72844 := (((7 × 2) × C(F(8), 4)) - F(F(F((F(4)!))))
72866 := (F(C(7, 2)) + (86 × 6!))
73213 := (F(7) + (F(C(3!, 2)) × ((-1) + 3!)))
73320 := (((7 - F(3))! × (F(C(3!, 2)) + 0!))
73326 := (-C(F(7), F(3!)) + C((F(F(3!)) + F(2)), 6))
73359 := (C(F(7), F(3!)) × (-F(3) - (59)))
73373 := ((C(F(7), 3) + F(F(3!))) × (F(F(7)) + 3!))
73386 := (((C(F(7), F(3!)) - F(3)) + F(F(8))) × 6)
73404 := (((C(F(7), F(3!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0!) × (F(4)!))
73416 := (((F(F(7)) × C(3!, 4)) + 1) × F(F(6)))
73425 := ((F(F(7)) - F(3!)) - (F(C((F(4)!), 2) × (-5!)))
73429 := (((F(F(7)) × F(F(3!))) × C((F(4)!), 2)) + F(9))
73433 := (F(F(7)) - ((F(C(3!, 4)) × 3!) / (-3!))
73434 := (((C(F(7), F(3)) + 4!) × 3!) - (F(4)!))
73435 := (((C(F(7), F(3)) + 4!) × 3!) - (5))
73437 := (((7! + F(C(3!, 4))) - F(F(3))) × F(7))
73437 := (((7! + F(C(3!, 4))) - F(F(3))) × F(7))
73464 := (((C(F(7), F(3)) + 4!) × 6!) + 4!)
73476 := (((C(F(7), F(3!)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + F(7)) × 6)
73486 := (7 × ((C(F(3!), F(4)) × (-8)) + F(F(F(6))))
73635 := ((C(F(7), F(3!)) + ((F(6)! / 3)) × 5)
73643 := (-F(7)) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + (C(F(F(6)), F(4)))) × 3!)
73644 := ((F(7) + 3!) × C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), 4))
73663 := (7 + (3! × (F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)), 3)))
73684 := (C((F(7) + 3), 6) + (F(F(8)) × (F(4)!))
73725 := -((C(F(7), F(3!)) + (F(7) - F(25))))
73773 := (-7!) + (F(F(3!)) × (7! - C(F(7), F(3!))))
73824 := ((C(F(7), 3!) × (8 × 2)) + F(4!))
73834 := (((-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) × F(3!)) - (F(4)!))
73835 := (((-C(F(7), 3!) + F(F(8))) × F(3!)) - (5))
73864 := (((C(F(7), 3!) - F(F(8))) × (-F(6))) + (4!))
73934 := (-((F(7) - (3⁹))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!))
73976 := ((7 × F(3!)) × (F(9) + C(F(7), F(6))))
73989 := ((7! - F(F(3))) + (9! - C(F(8), 9)))
74074 := (74 × C((0! + F(7)), 4))
74236 := -((F((7 × F(F(4)))) - C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), 6))
74244 := ((-7) + C(4!, 2)) × C(4!, F(F(4)))
74256 := (C((-7) + 4!), (F(2) + (5))) × 6
74304 := (-((C(F(7), 4) + 3!)) + F((0! + 4!))
74310 := (-C(F(7), 4) + F(((3 + 1)! + 0!))
74326 := (7 × (C(4!, (F(3) + 2)) - F(6)))
74340 := ((C(7, 4) - 3!) + F((4! + 0!))
74360 := ((C(F(7), 4) × F(3!)) × F((F(6) - 0!))
74367 := (-((F(7) - C((4! - F(3)), 6)) - F(F(7)))
74374 := (C(F(7), F(4)) + ((3! × 7)^{F(4)})
74381 := ((7 × C(4!, -((F(F(3)) - (F(8)))))) - 1)
74404 := (((7 × C(4!, 4) + 0!) + F(F((F(4)!)))
74409 := ((7 × (C(4!, 4) - 0!)) + F(9))
74416 := ((7 × C(4!, 4)) + F((1 + F(6))))
74434 := ((7 × (C(4!, 4) + F(3!))) - 4)
74436 := (((7 + 4) × F(C((F(4)!), 3))) + (F(F(6))))
74437 := (F(7) + ((C(4!, 4) + 3!) × 7))
74446 := ((7 × C(4!, 4)) + (F(F(4))⁶))
74447 := (F(F(7)) + ((C(4!, 4) - 4!) × 7))
74447 := (F(F(7)) + ((C(4!, 4) - 4!) × 7))
74468 := (F(F(7)) - ((C(F(F((F(4)!)), F((F(4)!)) / (-6)) - 8!))
74472 := ((7 × (C(4!, 4) + F(7))) - F(2))
74474 := ((7 × (C(4!, 4) + F(7))) + F(F(F(4))))
74598 := ((7 × F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - C((-((5 - 9))!), F(8)))
74603 := ((-7) - F(4)) + C((F(F(6)) + 0!), 3!))
74606 := (-7) + C(((F(F(4)) + F(F(6))) - 0!), 6))
74620 := (7 + C((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6))))), ((2 + 0)!))
74623 := ((F(7) - F(4)) + C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), 3!))
74673 := -(((C(F(7), F((F(4)!)) - (C(F(F(6)), 7))) + (F(3)!))
74737 := (((C(F(7), 4) + 7!) - 3!) × F(7))

- 74799 := ((C(7, (F(4))!) - F(F(7))) + F((F(9) - 9)))
 74823 := ((7!/4!) + C((F(8) + F(2)), 3!))
 74846 := (F(F(7)) + C((4! - (8/4)), 6))
 74861 := (C((F(7) + (F(4))!), 8) - ((6! + 1)))
 74862 := (C((F(7) + (F(4))!), 8) - ((6! × F(2))))
 74863 := ((C((F(7) + (F(4))!), 8) - (6!)) + F(F(3)))
 74864 := ((C((F(7) + (F(4))!), 8) - (6!)) + F(F(4)))
 74896 := (C((F(7) + (F(4))!), 8) + ((F(9) - 6!)))
 74929 := ((F(7)⁴) + F(((C(9, 2)/9)!))
 74969 := ((- (7) × F((F(4))!)) + F(- ((C(9, F(6)) - F(9))))
 74994 := ((- (7) - 4!) + F((C(9, 9) + 4!)))
 75004 := (- (C(7, 5)) + F((0! + (04)!)))
 75043 := ((F(7) + 5) + F((0! + (C(4, 3))!)))
 75046 := (C(7, 5) + F((0! + ((4 × 6))))
 75059 := (F(((C(7, 5) - 0!) + 5)) + F(9))
 75145 := (F((C(C(7, 5), 1) + 4) + 5!))
 75243 := ((F(F(7)) + F((5²))) - C((F(4))!, F(3)))
 75355 := (F((5 × 5) + C((3! + 5)), 7))
 75452 := (- (F(C(7, 5))) - (((F(4))!)! × (-5!) + 2))
 75454 := (- (F(C(7, 5))) + ((F(4))! × 5^{F(F(4))}))
 75456 := ((- (F(C(7, 5))) + F(F(4))) + (5! × 6!))
 75461 := (7 + ((5! × ((F(4))!)! - F(F(F(C(6, 1))))))
 75726 := (- (7) × ((5! - F(C(7, 2))) + F(6)))
 75733 := ((F(7) + 5!) + (7! × C(3!, F(3))))
 75753 := (- (C(F(7), 5)) + (- ((F(7) - 5!) × 3!))
 75754 := (- (7) × ((5! - F(C(7, 5))) + 4))
 75782 := (7 × (- (5!) + F(- ((7 - C(8, 2))))))
 75845 := ((F(F(7)) × C((5 + F(8)), 4!)) + 5!))
 75852 := (7 × ((- (5!) + F(F(8))) + C(5, 2)))
 75936 := (((7 - 5!) × (-C(9, 3))) × F(6))
 75943 := - ((F(F(7)) - (C((- ((5 - 9))!), F(F(4)))^{F(3)})))
 75947 := ((- (F(7)) - (F((F(- ((5 - 9))))!)) + (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 7)))
 75967 := ((7 - (F((F(- ((5 - 9))))!))! + (C(F(F(6)), 7)))
 75972 := (((7!/5) - F(9)) × C(F(7), 2))
 76245 := (F(7) × (C(F((6 + 2)), 4) - 5!))
 76302 := (C((F(7) + 6), F(3!)) + (((0! + 2))!))
 76303 := ((C((F(7) + 6), F(3!)) + 0!) + 3!))
 76304 := ((C(F(7), F(6)) - F(3!)) + F((0! + 4!)))
 76312 := (C(F(7), F(6)) + F(((3! - 1)²)))
 76314 := ((C(F(7), F(6)) + F(3)) + F((1 + 4!)))
 76337 := ((F((- (7) + F(F(6)))) - (F(3!))! + C(F(F(3!)), 7))
 76342 := (- (F(7)) + (C(F(F(6)), 3) + F((4! + F(2))))
 76343 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - (3 + C(4!, F(3))))
 76432 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - C(C((F(4))!, 3), 2))
 76455 := (C(5, 5) + ((- (4!) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7))
 76535 := ((- (7!) + (C(F(F(6)), 5) - F(3))) × 5)
 76553 := (((7! - C(F(F(6)), 5)) × (-5)) + F(3!))
 76567 := - ((F(F(7)) + (6! - C((5!/6), F(7))))
 76567 := - ((F(F(7)) + (6! - C((5!/6), F(7))))
 76585 := ((- (7!) + (C(F(F(6)), 5) + 8)) × 5)
 76602 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) - C(6, (0! + 2)))
 76650 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + C(F(6), (5 + 0!)))
 76667 := (((- (F(7)) - (F(6))!) + (6!)) + C(F(F(6)), 7))
 76667 := (((- (F(7)) - (F(6))!) + (6!)) + C(F(F(6)), 7))
 76673 := ((- (7) - (F(6))!) + (C(F(F(6)), 7) + 3!))
 76684 := ((C(7, 6) × (F(6) + F(F(8)))) + (F(4))!))
 76687 := ((7 - (F(6))!) + (6! + C(F(8), 7)))
 76700 := ((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + C(F(7), (0! + 0!)))
 76733 := (((F(7) + F(F(F(6)))) × 7) + C(3!, 3))
 76741 := (C((7 + 6), 7) + F((4! + 1)))
 76771 := (((7! - F(F(F(6)))) × (-F(7))) - C(7, 1))
 76807 := ((7 - 6!) + C((F(8) - 0!), F(7)))
 76824 := (((7 × F(F(F(6)))) + C(F(8), 2)) - F((F(4))!))
 76842 := ((7 × (- (F(6)) + F(F(8)))) + (C(4!, 2)))
 76887 := (((C(F(7), F(6)) + 8!) + 8!) - 7!))
 77232 := ((7 × F(C(7, 2))) + F(C(3!, 2)))
 77286 := ((7 × (F(C(7, 2)) - 8)) + 6!))
 77342 := ((7 × F((7 × 3))) + (C(4, 2))!))
 77507 := - ((F(7) - C((C(7, 5) - 0!), F(7))))
 77544 := - (((7! - (C(F(7), 5) × 4!)) × F(4)))
 77584 := ((F(F(7)) × C(F(7), - ((5 - 8))) + F(F(F((F(4))!))))
 77643 := ((7 × (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(C((F(4))!, F(3))))
 77664 := ((F(F(7)) + C((- (7) + F(F(6))), 6)) × 4!))
 77674 := (((- (C(F(7), 7)) + (F(6))!) + F(F(7))) × F(F(4)))
 77676 := (C(F(7), 7) + (C(F(F(6)), 7) - (F(6))!))
 77747 := ((C((F(7) + 7), F(7)) - (F(4))!) + F(F(7)))
 77774 := ((F(F(7)) + (C((F(7) + 7), F(7))) + F(F((F(4))!)))
 77805 := (F(7) × C((F(7) + 8), - ((0! - 5))))
 77896 := ((7! × F(7)) + (C((8 + 9), 6)))
 77944 := - ((7! + ((- (7) - F(9)) × C(4!, F(4))))

- 78064** := $((-((C(F(7), 8) + 0!)) + (F(6)!) \times F(F(4))))$
78092 := $(7 \times (F(F(8)) + C(F(-((0! - 9))), 2)))$
78448 := $(F(7) + (C((F(8) + F((F(4)!)), 4) - 8!))$
78473 := $(F(F(7)) + (C((F(8) - F(F(F(4))))), 7) + (3!)))$
78574 := $((F(F(7)) \times (8!/5!)) + (C(F(7), F(4))))$
78737 := $(-((F(7) + C(F(8), F(7)))) - ((F(3)!) \times (-7)))$
78744 := $(-(((F(F(7)) - 8! - C(F(7), 4))) \times F(F(4))))$
78763 := $((7 \times 8!) + F(7) - C(F(F(6)), F(3!)))$
78807 := $(C(F(7), 8) + C((F(8) - 0!), F(7)))$
78813 := $(-((C(F(7), 8) - ((8 - 1)!)) \times F(F(3!))))$
78988 := $((7 \times (8! + F(9))) - C(F(8), 8))$
79248 := $((7! + (-C(9, 2)) \times F(4!)) / (-F(8)))$
79365 := $(C(F(7), 9) \times (-((3 + 6) + 5!))$
79462 := $(- (F(F(7))) + ((-9!) + C(F(F((F(4)!)), F(6))) / (-2)))$
79464 := $(((-7) \times C(9, F(4))) + (F(6)!) \times F(F(4)))$
79474 := $(79 \times (((F(4)!)!) + (C(F(7), F(4))))$
79647 := $((C((F(7) + 9), 6) - (F(4)!) + (7!))$
79653 := $(7! + C(((9 + F(6)) + (5)), 3!))$
79776 := $((F(7) - 9)! \times (7! - C(F(7), 6)))$
79873 := $(F(7) + ((9! + C(F(8), 7)) / 3!))$
79883 := $(-((C(F(7), 9) - ((8! - F(8)) \times F(3))))$
79885 := $((7! - C(9, 8)) + F(F(8))) \times 5$
79889 := $(((-7) + 9!) + F(F(8))) - (C(F(8), 9))$
79935 := $((-((7! + C(9, 9))) - F(F(F(3)))) \times (-5))$
79943 := $(- (C(F(7), 9) - ((-9) - (F((F(4)!))!)) \times F(3)))$
79965 := $((C(F(7), 9) \times (-9)) + (6! \times 5!))$
80373 := $((C((F(8) + 0!), 3!) + 7!) + 3!))$
80465 := $(C((F(8) + 0!), 4) \times (6 + 5))$
80532 := $((8! + 0!) - F(C(5, 3))) \times 2$
80584 := $(-((C(8, (0! + (5))) - 8!)) \times F(F(4)))$
80661 := $((8! + (F(06)!) + F(F(C(6, 1))))$
80668 := $(8! + (C(F(06), 6) + 8!))$
80676 := $((8! + C((0! + F(6)), 7)) + (F(6)!)$
80730 := $C(((F(8) - 0!) + (7)), (3! - 0!))$
80754 := $(C(((F(8) - 0!) + (7)), 5) + 4!)$
80872 := $((8! - 0!) + 8! + F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
81333 := $(C((F(8) + 1), 3!) + ((F(3)!) / 3!))$
81396 := $((C(F(8), ((1 \times 3)!) \times (-9)) / (-6))$
81583 := $(- (C(F(8), -((1 - 5)))) + (F(F(8)) \times F(3!)))$
82356 := $((8! \times 2) + C(F((F(3) + (5))), 6))$
82376 := $(8 + ((2^3!) \times C(F(7), F(6))))$
82377 := $((8! \times 2) + F(F(3!)) + C(F(7), 7))$
82439 := $((8 - 2)! - (C(4!, F(3!)) / (-9)))$
82448 := $((F(F(8)) - (2 \times C(4!, 4))) \times (-8))$
82544 := $((8! \times 2) - 5! + C(4!, F(4)))$
82643 := $((8! \times 2) - F(F(6)) + (C(4!, 3)))$
82664 := $(C(((8/2)!)!, F(F(6))) + ((F(6)!) \times F(F(4))))$
82738 := $((C(F(8), 2) - 7!) + (F(3!) \times F(F(8))))$
82825 := $((8! + F(2)) + C(((8/2)!)!, 5))$
82845 := $((C(F(8), F(2)) + 8!) + C(4!, 5))$
83057 := $(8! + (C(((3 + 0)!)!, 5) + F(F(7))))$
83144 := $(- (8) \times (F(F((3! + 1))) - (C(4!, 4))))$
83264 := $(8! - ((C(F(F(3!)), 2) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 4))$
83300 := $((C(F(8), 3) + (F(3)!) \times (0! + 0!))$
83302 := $((C(F(8), 3) + (F(3)!) \times 0!) \times 2)$
83324 := $((C(F(8), 3) + (F(3)!) \times 2) + (4!))$
83342 := $((8! + F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), F(4))) \times 2$
83442 := $((F(F(8)) \times (-3)) + C(F(F((F(4)!)), ((F(4)!) + F(2))))$
83541 := $(F(8) + (3! \times (5! - C(4, 1))))$
83634 := $((- (F(F(8))) + (F(3)!) + ((C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4)))$
83636 := $(-(((F(F(8)) + F(3)) - (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (F(6)!))))$
83638 := $((C(F(8), 3!) + ((6 + F(3))!) - F(F(8)))$
83638 := $((C(F(8), 3!) + ((6 + F(3))!) - F(F(8)))$
83641 := $((C(F(8), 3!) + 6!) + F((4! - 1)))$
83644 := $((F((F(8) - F(3))) \times C(6, F(4))) + (4!))$
83646 := $((C(F(8), 3!) - (F(6)!) - F(4)) \times 6)$
83662 := $((C(F(8), 3!) - (F(6)!) \times 6) - 2)$
83663 := $((C(F(8), 3!) - (F(6)!) \times 6) - F(F(3)))$
83672 := $(8 \times ((- (3!)) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
83676 := $((C((F(8) - 3!), F(6)) \times F(7)) + F(F(6)))$
83775 := $((C((F(8) - 3!), 7) \times F(7)) + 5!)$
83937 := $((C(F(8), 3) \times 9) + F(F(3!))) \times 7$
83972 := $(- (8) - ((C(F(F(3!)), 9) / 7) \times (-2)))$
83974 := $(((- (F(8)) + C(F(F(3!)), 9)) / 7) \times F(F(4)))$
84072 := $((8! + C(F(((F(4)!) + 0!)), 7)) \times 2)$
84078 := $(8! + C(((4 + 0!) + F(7)), 8))$
84294 := $((8! \times F(F(4))) + (C(29, F(4))))$
84350 := $(- (C(F(8), F(4))) - (3! \times (- (5! - 0!))))$
84432 := $((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4)!) - (C(F((F(4)!)!, 3)^2)))$
84434 := $(8! - ((F(4)!) - (C(4!, 3!))) / F(F(4)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84446 &:= ((C((F(8) - F(F(4))), (F(4))!) + F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 84495 &:= (- (C(F(8), 4) - (((F(4))!) + F(9)) \times (-5!)) \\
 84544 &:= ((8! + F(4)) - (5! + C(4!, F(4)))) \\
 84565 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F((F(4))!)) - (C((5!/F(6)), 5))) \\
 84641 &:= ((- (C(F(8), F(4))) + F(F(F(6)))) + F((4! + 1))) \\
 84643 &:= (((- (F(8)) + F(4)) + (F(6))!) - (C(4!, 3))) \\
 84655 &:= (5 \times (C(F(F((-5) + F(6))), 4) + F(F(8)))) \\
 84669 &:= ((8! - ((F(4))!)!) - (F(C(F(6), 6) - 9!)) \\
 84737 &:= ((C(F(8), (F(4))!) + F(F(7))) + (3! \times 7!)) \\
 84821 &:= ((8! \times F(F(4))) + F((F(8) - C(2, 1)))) \\
 84843 &:= ((F(8)^{F(4)} + C((F(8) - F(F(4))), F(3!))) \\
 84848 &:= (8! + ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(8))) \times C(4!, F(8)))) \\
 84848 &:= (8! + ((F(F(F(4))) + (F(8))) \times C(4!, F(8)))) \\
 85008 &:= (8 \times C(((5 - 0)!), -((0! - F(8)))) \\
 85245 &:= (- ((F(8) \times F(C(5, 2)))) - (((F(4))!) \times (-5!)) \\
 85281 &:= (- (F(8)) \times (5! - F((-2) + F(C(8, 1)))) \\
 85389 &:= - (((F(C(8, (5 - 3))) - 8!) - 9!)) \\
 85461 &:= (F(8) + (5! \times (((F(4))!)! - F(C(6, 1)))) \\
 85467 &:= (- ((C(F(8), 5) + 4!) + (F(F(6)) \times 7!)) \\
 85470 &:= (- (C(F(8), 5) - (F(F((F(4))!)) \times (- (7! - 0!)))) \\
 85487 &:= - (((C(F(8), 5) + 4) - (F(8) \times 7!)) \\
 85527 &:= - (((F(8) - (5! \times F(C(5, 2)))) \times F(7)) \\
 85637 &:= (- (8!) + (C((5!/6), F(3!)) - F(7))) \\
 85644 &:= (- (8!) + (C((5!/6), F((F(4))!)) - (F(4))!)) \\
 85645 &:= (- (8!) + (C((5!/6), F((F(4))!)) - (5!)) \\
 85650 &:= (- (8!) + C((5!/6), F((5 + 0!))) \\
 85779 &:= - ((F(8) - (5! \times C(F(7), (F(7) - 9)))) \\
 85791 &:= (- (8) + ((5! \times C(F(7), 9) - 1)) \\
 85793 &:= ((- (8) + (5! \times C(F(7), 9))) + F(F(3))) \\
 85794 &:= ((- (8) + (5! \times C(F(7), 9))) + F(F(4))) \\
 85799 &:= (8 + ((5! \times C(F(7), 9) - 9)) \\
 85836 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((5! \times C(8, F(3)))) \times 6) \\
 85877 &:= ((C(F(8), 5) + 8) + (7! \times F(7))) \\
 86025 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 6) + C(F(F((0! + 2))), 5)) \\
 86048 &:= (- (8) \times (C((F(F(6)) - 0!), F(F(4))) - F(F(8)))) \\
 86238 &:= (- (C(F(8), (6/2))) + (F(3!) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86254 &:= (- (F(F(8))) - ((- (C(6, 2) - 5!) \times ((F(4))!)!)) \\
 86273 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - F(2))) - (C(F(7), F(3!)))) \\
 86336 &:= (8 \times ((6! \times C(3!, F(3))) - F(6))) \\
 86365 &:= ((F(8) - C(F(6), 3)) + (6! \times 5!)) \\
 86366 &:= ((8! - F(C(6, F(3)))) + (6^6)) \\
 86421 &:= (F(8) + (6! \times ((C(4, 2) - 1)!)) \\
 86484 &:= (((8! + (6)) + F(4)) - C(F(8), F(F(4)))) \\
 86546 &:= (F(F(8)) - (F(F(6)) \times (- (C(5, 4) \times 6!))) \\
 86548 &:= ((- ((C(8, 6) \times 5)) + F(4)) + 8!) \\
 86553 &:= ((8 \times (F(F(F(6))) - 5!)) - F(C(5, 3))) \\
 86587 &:= (- (F(8)) - (F(6) \times (5! - F(F(C(8, 7)))))) \\
 86636 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times (3! - F(6))) \\
 86679 &:= ((8! + F(((C(F(6), 6) / 7)!)) - 9) \\
 86744 &:= ((8! + C(F(6), (7 - 4))) + F(4!)) \\
 87232 &:= (8 \times (F(C(7, 2)) - (F(F(3!)) \times 2))) \\
 87332 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) - C(F(3!), 2)) \\
 87355 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / C(3!, 5)) - (5)) \\
 87361 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) + 3!) / C(6, 1)) \\
 87381 &:= (((8! \times F(7)) / 3!) + F(C(8, 1))) \\
 87396 &:= ((8! + C(F(7), 3!)) + (9! / F(6))) \\
 87403 &:= ((8! + C(F(7), 4) + F(((0! + 3)!)) \\
 87404 &:= ((8! + (C(F(7), 4) + 0!)) + F(4!)) \\
 87443 &:= (((8! + (C(7, 4))) + F(4!)) + 3!) \\
 87471 &:= (((F(F(8)) - F(7)) \times F((F(4))!)) + C(7, 1)) \\
 87504 &:= ((- (8) + F(C(7, 5))) \times F((04)!)) \\
 87520 &:= (8 \times (F(C(7, 5)) - ((2 + 0)!))!)) \\
 87532 &:= ((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - (3!^2)) \\
 87542 &:= (((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - 4!) - 2) \\
 87543 &:= (((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - 4!) - F(F(3))) \\
 87544 &:= ((8 \times F(C(7, C(5, 4)))) - 4!) \\
 87562 &:= ((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - ((6/2)!)) \\
 87574 &:= ((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + ((7 - 4)!)) \\
 87576 &:= (((8! \times F(C(7, 5))) / 7!) + F(6)) \\
 87583 &:= (((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + F(8)) - 3!) \\
 87584 &:= (((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) - 8) + 4!) \\
 87594 &:= (((8 \times F(C(7, 5))) + F(9)) - F((F(4))!)) \\
 87633 &:= (8! + (7 \times (F(C(6, 3)) - 3!)) \\
 87638 &:= ((8! + F(F(7))) + ((F(C(6, 3)) + 8!)) \\
 87641 &:= (((8! + F(F(7))) + (6!)) + F((C(4, 1)!)) \\
 87647 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (C(F(F(6)), 4) + (7!)) \\
 87733 &:= ((F(8) - F(F(7))) - (- (F(7)) \times F(C(3!, 3)))) \\
 87744 &:= (((8 + C(F(7), 7)) \times 4!) + F(4!)) \\
 87953 &:= (8 + (C(F(7), 9) \times (5! + 3))) \\
 87975 &:= ((8! + F(((F(7) - 9)!)) + (C(F(7), 5)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 88288** := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((2 + C(8,8))!))!
88288 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + ((2 + C(8,8))!))!
88332 := (((8! - F(F(8))) × 3) + C(F(F(3!)), 2))
88386 := (((F(8) - F(F(8))) × F(F(3!))) + (F(C(8,6))))
88466 := (((- (C(F(8), 8)) × F((F(4)!)) / (-F(F(6)))) + F(F(F(6))))
88474 := (F(F(8)) + (C((F(8) - F(F(F(4))))), 7) + F((F(4)!)))
88531 := ((8 × (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + C(3, 1))
88543 := ((8 × (F(F(8)) + 5!)) + C((F(4)!), F(3)))
88645 := ((F(F(8)) + (C(F(8), 6) / F((F(4)!))) × 5)
88648 := (8! + (C((8 + F(6)), (F(4)!)) + 8!))
88678 := ((8! + (C(F(8), 6) + 7!)) - F(F(8)))
88735 := ((F(F(8)) × 8) + (C(F(7), F(3!)) - 5!))
89054 := -((F(F(8)) - (9 + 0!)^{C(5,4)}))
89453 := ((F((8 + 9)) × C(F((F(4)!), 5)) + F(F(3!)))
89594 := (8 - (- (C(9, 5)) × (-9) + ((F(4)!))!))
90444 := ((9! / 04) - C(4!, F(F(4))))
91245 := ((C((9 + 1), 2)^{F(4)}) + 5!)
91436 := (((9! - 1) + F(4!)) - F(C(F(3!), 6)))
92079 := (9 × (F(F(F((2 + 0!)!))) - C(F(7), 9)))
92344 := (- (F(9)) + C((- (2) + F(F(3!))), (F(4) × F(4))))
92393 := (9 + (C((- (2) + F(F(3!))), 9) + 3!))
92664 := (9 × (C(F((F(2) + (6))), 6) × (F(4)!))
92673 := (9 × (F(2) + (6 × C(F(7), 3!))))
92741 := (- (9) - (2 × (- (7) - F((C(4, 1)!))))
92744 := (((9 × 2) × 7!) + C(4!, F(4)))
92954 := (- (F(9)) - (2 × (- (C(9, 5)) - F(4!))))
93456 := ((C(9, 3)^{F(F(4))}) + (5! × 6!))
93534 := (- ((C(9, F(3)) - (5^{3!}))) × (F(4)!))
93563 := (((F(9)³) - (5)) + C(F(F(6)), 3!))
93646 := (9! - (F(3) × (F(F(6)) + (C(4!, 6))))
93653 := (- (9!) + ((F(F(3!)) + C(F(6), 5))³))
93854 := ((C(9, 3) × F((F(8) - (5)))) + F(F(F((F(4)!))))
93864 := (- (((9 - 3)! - 8!)) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!))
93872 := ((9! / F(3)) + (- (8) × F(C(7, 2))))
93976 := (F(9) × (((F(3!))! / 9) - C(F(7), 6)))
94243 := ((- (F(9)) - (F((F(4)!))!)) + (F(2) + C(4!, 3!)))
94344 := (((C(9, F(4)) + 3!) + F(4!)) × F(F(4)))
94356 := (9 × (- (C((F(4) + F(3!)), 5)) + F(F(F(6))))
94374 := (((C(9, 4) + (F(3!))!) × 7) / F(4))
94593 := (9 + (C(F(F(F(4)!)), (F(- ((5 - 9))))!) + (F(3!))!))
94638 := ((9 × (F(4)!)) + (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + 8!))
94668 := (C(9, F(4)) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) + 8!))
94686 := (((F(9) × F(4)) + (F(6)!)) + (C(F(8), 6)))
94743 := ((- (9) - F(4!)) + (7! × C(F((F(4)!), F(3))))
94783 := ((- (F(9)) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + ((F(F(7)) + (C(F(8), 3!))))
94786 := ((F(9) - F(4!)) - (7! × (-C(8, 6))))
94995 := (- (9) - (((F(4)!))! + F(9)) × (-C(9, 5)))
95244 := (((C(9, 5)²) - F(F(4))) × (F(4)!))
95248 := (((C(9, 5)²) × (F(4)!)) - 8)
95256 := ((C(9, 5)²) × ((- (5) + F(6)))!))
95264 := (((C(9, 5)²) × 6) + F((F(4)!))
95664 := ((9 × 5!) + (F(6)!)) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!))
95747 := (((C(9, 5) + 7) × ((F(4)!))! - F(7))
95886 := (((C(9, 5) × F(8)) × F(8)) + (F(6)!))
96336 := (9 × ((C(F(F(6)), 3) + F(3!)) × F(6)))
96444 := (9 × ((6! / F((F(4)!)) + (C(4!, 4))))
96464 := (((9 × F(F(F(6)))) - ((F(4)!))! - C(F(F(6)), F(4)))
96490 := ((9 × F(F(F(6)))) - (C(4!, F((9 - 0!))))
96544 := (((F(9) × C(F(6), 5)) + F(4!)) × F(F(4)))
96774 := ((9 × F(F(F(6)))) - (C(F(7), 7) + 4!))
96804 := (9 × (F(F(F(6))) - C((F(8) - 0!), F(F(4))))
97554 := ((9 × F(C(7, 5))) - (5! × F((F(4)!))!))
97794 := ((9 × F(C(7, - ((7 - 9)))) - ((F(4)!))!))
98254 := (- ((F(9) - (C(C(8, 2), 5))) + F((F(4)!))!))
98331 := ((9 × (F(F(8)) - F(F(3!)))) + (C(3, 1)!))
98332 := ((9 × (F(F(8)) - C(3!, 3)) - 2)
98333 := ((9 × (F(F(8)) - C(3!, 3)) - F(F(3)))
98335 := ((F(9) + F(8)) + C(C(F(3!)), F(3)), 5))
98337 := ((9 × F(F(8))) + (C(F(3!), 3) - F(F(7))))
98434 := ((9 × F(F(8))) - (4 × C(3!, F(4))))
98453 := (((9 × F(F(8))) - (F(4)!)) - (F(C(5, 3))))
98462 := ((9 × F(F(8))) - (4! + C(F(6), 2)))
98543 := ((9 × F(F(8))) + (5 + (C(4, 3)!))
98634 := (F(9) × (C((F(8) + (6)), 3) - 4!))
98655 := (((9 × F(F(8))) + F(F(C(6, 5)))) + 5!))
98732 := (((9 × F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - C(3!, 2))
98936 := ((- (9) + C((8 + 9), 3!)) × F(6))
99333 := ((9! - F((F(9) - 3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), 3!))
99346 := ((F(9) × C((F(9) - F(3!)), F(4))) + F(F(F(6))))
99444 := ((F(9) × C((9 × F(4)), 4!)) - (F(4)!))

$$99445 := ((F(9) \times C((9 \times F(4)), 4!)) - (5))$$

$$99855 := (((9! / (-9)) + C(F(8), 5)) \times (-5))$$

$$99450 := (F(9) \times C((9 \times F(4)), F((5 - 0!))))$$

$$99954 := (9 \times ((F(9) + (C(9, 5))) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))))$$

$$99484 := (F(9) + (F(9) \times C(((F(4))! + (F(8))), F(4))))$$

$$99633 := ((9 + (9! / F(6))) + C(F(F(3!)), 3!))$$

2.3 Square-Root

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with square-root**. The results are in terms of digit's order. The work is up to 6 digits. This subsection is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

2.3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$54720 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 0$$

$$54721 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 1$$

$$54722 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 2$$

$$54723 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 3$$

$$54724 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 4$$

$$54725 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 5$$

$$54726 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 6$$

$$54727 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 7$$

$$54728 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 8$$

$$54729 := 5 \times \left(-\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, 2)) \right) + 9$$

2.3.2 Non Symmetric and Consecutive

$$969 := C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(6))\right), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$1329 := \left(-1 + C\left(F(F((3 \times 2)), \sqrt{9}\right)\right)$$

$$1899 := \left(\left(-1 - C\left(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) \times (-9)\right)$$

$$3649 := \left(F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))\right) / F\left(C\left(4, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)$$

$$3984 := \left(-3\right) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - C(F(8), F(4))\right)$$

$$3989 := -\left(F(F(3)) - \left(\sqrt{9} \times C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right)\right)\right)$$

$$4843 := \left(C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(8)\right), 4\right) - F(3)\right)$$

$$4844 := -\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - C\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{4}), 4\right)\right)$$

$$4845 := \left(C\left(-\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8)\right), F(4)\right) \times 5\right)$$

$$4984 := \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 9\right)\right) \times C(8, F(4))\right)$$

$$5964 := -\left(F\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - C(F(F(6)), 4)\right)$$

$$5984 := -\left(F\left(\left(5 - \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - C(F(8), 4)\right)$$

$$5985 := C\left(F\left(5 + \sqrt{9}\right), \sqrt{F(8) - 5}\right)$$

$$6479 := \left(F(C(6, F(4))) - C(F(7), \sqrt{9})\right)$$

$$6969 := \left(F\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - (-6) \times F(9)\right)$$

$$6997 := \left(\left(F\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F\left(F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right) + F(F(7))\right)$$

$$6998 := \left(F\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + F((F(9) - F(8)))\right)$$

$$8749 := \left(F(F(8)) - \left(F(7)^{F(C(4, \sqrt{9}))}\right)\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9384 &:= (F(9) \times C(3 \times 8, \sqrt{4})) \\
 9792 &:= (F(9) \times (C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) + 2)) \\
 9688 &:= -((F(\sqrt{9}) + (C(F(F(6)), 8) / (-F(8)))) \\
 10485 &:= (C(10, \sqrt{4}) \times F((8+5))) \\
 10584 &:= (C(10, 5) \times F(8)) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 10889 &:= (- (1) + F(F(08))) - C(8, \sqrt{9}) \\
 10897 &:= (- (F(10)) + F(F(8))) + \sqrt{C(9, 7)} \\
 10898 &:= ((- (C(10, 8)) - \sqrt{9}) + F(F(8))) \\
 10935 &:= (C(10, F(\sqrt{9})) \times (3^5)) \\
 10938 &:= (F(C((10 - \sqrt{9}), F(3))) - 8) \\
 10949 &:= (F((F(10) - F(9))) + F(C(4, \sqrt{9}))) \\
 10991 &:= (C(10, F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F((9 - 1)))) \\
 11964 &:= (1 + 1) \times (- (\sqrt{9}) + C(F(F(6)), 4)) \\
 11969 &:= (- (1) - (- ((1 \times 9) \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}))) \\
 12397 &:= (C(1 \times 23, \sqrt{9}) \times 7) \\
 12649 &:= (C(- ((1 - 26)), 4) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 12759 &:= (- (1) - (F(2) - F(F(7))) \times F(C(5, \sqrt{9}))) \\
 12869 &:= (1 + C((2 \times 8), F(6))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 14399 &:= (- (1) + (C((4^{F(3)}), F(\sqrt{9}))^{F(\sqrt{9})})) \\
 14949 &:= (C((- (1) + (F(4) \times 9)), 4) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))) \\
 15939 &:= (C((F(F((1 + 5))) + F(\sqrt{9})), 3) \times 9) \\
 15969 &:= (- (1) - (- (C(5, \sqrt{9})) \times F((F(6) + 9)))) \\
 16757 &:= ((\sqrt{\sqrt{16}} + C(F(7), 5)) \times F(7)) \\
 16796 &:= (C(F(F((1 \times 6))), (F(7) - \sqrt{9})) / F(F(6))) \\
 16956 &:= (1 + (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) + (5^6))) \\
 17289 &:= (- (1) + (F(7) \times C(F(2) \times F(8), \sqrt{9}))) \\
 17424 &:= ((C((- (1) + F(7)), \sqrt{4}) \times 2)^{\sqrt{4}}) \\
 17699 &:= (1 - F(7)) + F((C(F(6), \sqrt{9}) - F(9))) \\
 17744 &:= (- (1) + (F(7) \times C((F(7) + \sqrt{4}), 4))) \\
 17797 &:= -((F((1 + F(7))) - (C(F(7), F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 17976 &:= ((- (1) - F(7)) \times (\sqrt{9} - C(F(7), F(6)))) \\
 17996 &:= ((- (1) + C(F(7), \sqrt{9})) + F((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(F(6)))))) \\
 17998 &:= ((1 + C(F(7), \sqrt{9})) + F((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(8)))) \\
 18174 &:= (F(F(((1 \times 8) - 1))) \times C(F(7), \sqrt{4})) \\
 18480 &:= (C(1 + F(8), \sqrt{4}) \times 80) \\
 18755 &:= (\sqrt{1 + C(F(8), 7)} \times 55) \\
 18797 &:= (C(18, (7 - F(F(\sqrt{9})))) + F(F(7))) \\
 18876 &:= ((\sqrt{1 + 8} + 8) \times C(F(7), 6)) \\
 18990 &:= ((- (1) - C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9}))) \times (-90)) \\
 18998 &:= (F((1 + F(8))) + C(F((9 - F(\sqrt{9})), 8)) \\
 19448 &:= C((19 - \sqrt{4}), (\sqrt{4} + 8)) \\
 19449 &:= (1 + C((F(9) / \sqrt{4}), \sqrt{49})) \\
 20298 &:= (F(20) + F(2)) \times \sqrt{C(9, 8)} \\
 20995 &:= (C(20, 9) / (\sqrt{9} + 5)) \\
 21684 &:= (2 \times (1 + F(F(F(6)))) - C(F(8), \sqrt{4})) \\
 21898 &:= ((2 + 1) + F(F(8))) \times F(\sqrt{C(9, 8)}) \\
 21948 &:= (2 \times (C(- ((1 - 9)), \sqrt{4}) + F(F(8)))) \\
 22398 &:= (2 \times (C(23, F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(8)))) \\
 23398 &:= (- (2) - (C((3^3), \sqrt{9}) \times (-8))) \\
 23596 &:= (F(F((2^3))) + C((5^{F(\sqrt{9})}), F(F(6)))) \\
 23898 &:= ((- (2) + C(- ((F(F(3)) - F(8))), \sqrt{9})) \times F(8)) \\
 23944 &:= ((- (F(2)) - C(F((F(3)^{\sqrt{9}}), 4)) \times (-4)) \\
 24696 &:= ((F((2 \times 4)) \times C(F(6), \sqrt{9})) \times F(F(6))) \\
 24869 &:= (- (2) - (C((F(\sqrt{4}) + F(8)), 6) / (-\sqrt{9}))) \\
 25346 &:= ((C((2 \times 5), 3)^{\sqrt{4}}) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 26466 &:= ((F(2) + (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}) \times F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 26569 &:= (- (2) + C((6 + 5), F(6)))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 26946 &:= ((2 \times (C(6, \sqrt{9})^{F(4)})) + F(F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26992 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 \times F \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - F(9) \right) \times 2 \right) \\
 27456 &:= \left(C \left(2 \times 7, \left(\sqrt{4} + 5 \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 27689 &:= \left(-F(2) - \left(C \left(F(7), 6 \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 27696 &:= \left(-F(2) - F(F(7)) + \left(C \left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 27697 &:= \left(\left(F \left((F(2) + 7) \right) \right) \times C \left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 27698 &:= \left(F(2) - F(F(7)) - \left(C \left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9} \right) \times (-F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 27896 &:= \left(-F(2+7) - \left(-C \left(F(8), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \\
 27959 &:= \left(-F(2) + \left(F(F(7)) \times C \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 27962 &:= \left(2 + \left(F(F(7)) \times C \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(6) \right), 2 \right) \right) \right) \\
 28448 &:= \left(\left(F(2) - C \left(F(8), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right) \right) \right) \\
 28579 &:= \left(F(28-5) - C \left(F(7), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 28596 &:= \left(\left(F \left((2 + F(8)) \right) \right) - F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - 6 \\
 28599 &:= \left(\left(F \left((2 + F(8)) \right) \right) - F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \\
 28661 &:= \left(F \left((2 + F(8)) \right) + \sqrt{F(6) + F(C(6,1))} \right) \\
 28698 &:= \left(F \left((2 + F(8)) \right) + \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) + F(8) \right) \right) \\
 28699 &:= \left(2 \times F(8) + F \left(\left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 28848 &:= \left(F \left(\sqrt{2 \times 8} \right) \times \left(-C \left(F(8), F(4) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 28987 &:= \left(F \left((2 + F(8)) \right) + C \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + 8 \right), 7 \right) \right) \\
 29357 &:= \left(-F(2) - \left(-C \left(\left(\sqrt{9}^{F(3)} \right), 5 \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 29791 &:= \left((2 \times 9) + F(7) \right)^{\sqrt{C(9,1)}} \\
 29894 &:= \left(-2 \times \left(\sqrt{9} - C \left((-8) + F(9), 4 \right) \right) \right) \\
 29925 &:= \left(C \left(F \left(2^{\sqrt{9}} \right), (F(9)/2) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 31896 &:= \left(3 \times \left((-1) + C \left(F(8), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 32298 &:= - \left(\left(F(3) - C \left(22, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F(8) \right) \\
 32839 &:= \left(3 \times F \left((F(2) \times F(8)) \right) + C \left(3, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 33645 &:= \left(- \left(F(3) + F(3) \right) + C \left(\left(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4} \right), 5 \right) \right) \\
 33648 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(3)) - C \left(F(3) + F(F(6)), \sqrt{4 + F(8)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 33797 &:= \left(-3 + \left(C \left(F(3) \times F(7), \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(7) \right) \right) \\
 33995 &:= \left(\left(F \left(C \left(3+3, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(9) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 34884 &:= \left(3 \times C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8) \right) \right), (8 - F(4)) \right) \right) \\
 35649 &:= \left(F \left(F \left((F(3) + 5) \right) \right) \right) \times C \left((6 \times F(4)), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 35699 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(3)) - \left(-5 \times \left(C \left(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times (-F(9)) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36789 &:= \left(3 \times \left(F \left(F \left(F(6) \right) \right) - \left(F(7) - C \left(F(8), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 36965 &:= \left(\left(F(3) \times F \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) - C \left(F(F(6)), 5 \right) \right) \\
 37446 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(3)) + \left(C \left(F(7), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 37796 &:= \left(F(3) + C \left(F(7), 7 \right) \right) \times \left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \\
 38679 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{3^8} \right) - \left(C \left(F(F(6)), 7 \right) / (-\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 38696 &:= \left(C \left(- \left(F(F(3)) - F(8) \right), 6 \right) - \left(F(\sqrt{9})^6 \right) \right) \\
 38759 &:= \left(F(3) + \left(C \left(F(8), 7 \right) - 5 \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \\
 38764 &:= \left(F(3) \times \left(C \left(F(8), 7 \right) / 6 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 38962 &:= \left(C \left(F(3) + F(8), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \left(F(F(6)) + F(2) \right) \right) \\
 39359 &:= \left(F(F(3)) \times F(9)^3 + F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 39379 &:= \left((-3) + F(9)^3 + C \left(F(7), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 39648 &:= \left(\left(-F(3) - \left(-9 \times C \left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times F(8) \right) \\
 39689 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(3)) - \left(9 \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \times C \left(F(8), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 39843 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(- \left(F(3) - 9 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times C \left(\left(F(8) - \sqrt{4} \right), F(3) \right) \\
 39978 &:= \left(3 \times \left(C \left(\left(F(9) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right), F(7) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 40656 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(C \left(F(F(06)), 5 \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 40698 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times C \left(F(F(06)), - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 43758 &:= C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(3^{7-5} \right) \right), 8 \right) \\
 43766 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + 3 \right) + F(7) \right), F(6) \right) + F(6) \right) \\
 43874 &:= \left(4 \times \left(3 + F(F(8)) \right) \right) + C \left(F(7), \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44626 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + \left(4 \times \left(C \left(F(F(6)), 2 \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \right) \\
 44982 &:= \left(\left(C \left(F(4), \sqrt{4} \right) \times F(9) \right) \times \left(F(8)^2 \right) \right) \\
 45369 &:= \left(F(4) + C \left(C(5,3), 6 \right) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 46189 &:= \left(C \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(6)) \right), (1+8) \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 46248 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(6) \right), 2 \right) \right) + F \left((F(4) \times 8) \right) \right) \\
 46375 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left(-6 - F \left((3 + C(7,5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 46399 &:= \left(\left(F \left((4 + C(6,3)) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F(9) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 46424 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right), F(4) \right) + F(24) \right) \\
 46438 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (6) \right), 4 \right) + F((3 \times 8)) \right) \\
 46466 &:= - \left(\left(C \left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6)) \right) \right), \sqrt{4} \right) - (6^6) \right) \right) \\
 46475 &:= \left(C \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (6) \right) \right), 4 \right) \times (F(7) \times 5) \right) \\
 46494 &:= \left(F((4 \times 6)) + C \left(\left(F(4) \times \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) \right) \\
 46495 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((F((6 \times 4)) + (C(9, 5)))) \right) \\
 46671 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + ((6^6)) \right) + F(C(7, 1)) \right) \\
 46675 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (((6^6) + C(7, 5))) \right) \right) \\
 46686 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((6^6) + C(8, 6)) \right) \\
 46863 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 6 \right), 8 \right) + F((F(6) \times 3)) \right) \\
 46998 &:= \left(\left(F(4) \times C \left(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 47353 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - (-7) \times F((F(3) \times C(5, 3))) \right) \\
 47359 &:= \left(4 - (-7) \times F \left(\left(F(3) \times C(5, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 47363 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (-7) \times (F(F(3)) + (F(C(6, 3)))) \right) \\
 47364 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - (-7) \times (F(F(3)) + F(C(6, F(4)))) \right) \\
 47369 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times 7 \right) \times \left(F(3) + F(C(6, \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 47437 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) / 3 \right) \times F(7) \right) \\
 47646 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) - (C(F(F(6)), 4) \times F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 47647 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (7) \right) \times C(F(F(6)), 4) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 47648 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(7)) \right) + (C(F(F(6)), 4) \times 8) \right) \\
 47669 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(F(7)) - (6) \times C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \right) \\
 47693 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + C(F(7), F(6)) \right) \times (F(9) + 3) \right) \\
 47763 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), F(3)))) \right) \\
 47764 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), \sqrt{4}))) \right) \right) \\
 47766 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(F(6), 6))) \right) \\
 47965 &:= \left(F((4 + F(7))) + F \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(C(6, 5)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48279 &:= - \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (C(F(8), 2)) \right) \times \left(F(F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48297 &:= \left(- (F(4)) + \left(- (C(F(8), 2)) \times \left(\sqrt{9} - F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48387 &:= \left(C \left(- ((F(4) - F(8))), \sqrt{\sqrt{38}} \right) - F(F(7)) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48395 &:= \left(\left(C((4 + 8), 3)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - (5) \right) \\
 48399 &:= \left(\left(C((4 + 8), 3)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 48450 &:= \left(C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8) \right) \right), F(4) \right) \times 50 \right) \\
 48464 &:= \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times F \left(F \left(F(6) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 48477 &:= \left(\left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + (F(7)) \right) \\
 48619 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - C \left(F(8) - \sqrt{F(6) + 1}, 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 48624 &:= \left(C((-4) + F(8), F(6)) + 2 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \\
 48639 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8) \right) - (C((6 \times 3), 9)) \right) \right) \\
 48739 &:= \left(C \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8) \right), 7 \right) - F((3 \times 9)) \right) \\
 48896 &:= \left(\left(C((4 + F(8)), F(8)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 48926 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \right) \right) \\
 48928 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(- \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times F(F(-(F(2) - 8))) \right) \right) \\
 48929 &:= \left(- \left(F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - \left(- \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times F(F(-(2 - 9))) \right) \right) \\
 48934 &:= \left(4 + \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F((3 + 4))) \right) \right) \\
 48972 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times (F(F(7)) - 2) \right) \\
 48986 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + ((C(F(8), 9) - 8) / (-6)) \right) \right) \\
 48989 &:= \left((-4) - C(F(8), 9) \right) / \left(-8 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 48996 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - ((C(F(8), 9) + F(9)) / (-6)) \right) \\
 49627 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(\left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) - C(F(F(6)), 2) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 49629 &:= \left(F((4 + 9)) \times \left(C(F(F(6)), 2) + \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 49976 &:= \left(- (4) + \left(C \left(F(9) / F(\sqrt{9}), F(7) \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 49978 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - \left(C \left(F(9) / F(\sqrt{9}), F(7) \right) \times (-F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 52897 &:= \left(C \left((5^2), (8 - \sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 52984 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C \left((5^2), \sqrt{9} \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \right) \times (-4) \right) \\
 53696 &:= \left(\left(53 - F(C(6, \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times (-F(6)) \\
 54259 &:= \left(- (5) + C \left(F((4 \times 2)), (5 \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 54281 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left((5 + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right)^2 - C(8, 1) \right) \\
 54283 &:= \left(\left(F \left(C(5, \sqrt{4}) \right) \times F((2 \times 8)) \right) - F(3) \right) \\
 54284 &:= \left(\left(F \left(C(5, \sqrt{4}) \right) \times F((2 \times 8)) \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 54285 &:= \left(F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times F \left((F(2) \times F(8)) - (5) \right) \right) \\
 54344 &:= \left(F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + \left(F(F((3+4)))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 54479 &:= \left(C \left((5 \times 4), \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(F(F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 54664 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) - C(F(6), F(4)) \right) \\
 54669 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) - C(F(6), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 54676 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{5^4}) - C(F(F(6)), (F(7) - F(6))) \right) \\
 54691 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) - F(C(9, 1)) \right) \\
 54740 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4+0} \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 54741 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 54742 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 54744 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times \left(- \left(\sqrt{4} \right) - F \left(C \left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 54874 &:= \left(F((5 \times F(4))) + C(F(8), (F(7) + \sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 54885 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) + F(8) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 56879 &:= \left(- (5) - F(F(F(6))) + \left(C(F(8), F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 56889 &:= \left((5 - F(F(F(6)))) + \left(C(F(8), 8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 57696 &:= \left(\left(F(F((-5) + F(7))) - \left(C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 59374 &:= \left(F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left((3 \times F(7))^{F(4)} \right) \right) \\
 59845 &:= \left(\left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \times C(F(8), 4) \right) - (5) \right) \\
 59849 &:= \left(\left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \times C(F(8), 4) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 59876 &:= \left(\left(\left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \times F(8) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 63504 &:= \left(C((F(6) + F(3)), 5)^{\sqrt{0^4}} \right) \\
 63669 &:= \left(C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6) - F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 63696 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(3 - C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \times (-6) \right) \right) \\
 63846 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), 3) \times (-8) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (-6) \right) \\
 63987 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(6, 3)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times 8 \right) - F(7) \right) \\
 64467 &:= \left(C \left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right), \sqrt{4} \right) \times F((F(F(6)) - (7))) \right) \\
 64636 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) \times \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) + C((F(F(6)) - F(3)), F(6)) \right) \\
 64834 &:= \left(\left((F(F(6))^4) + (F(8)) \right) / C(3, \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 64897 &:= \left(C(F(6), 4) - \left(\left(F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times (-7) \right) \right) \\
 64926 &:= - \left(\left(F(C(6, 4)) - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(2) \right)^{F(6)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 64976 &:= \left(\left(- (C(F(6), 4)) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{F(7)} \right) \right) \times F(6) \right) \\
 65569 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times (5^5)) - C(F(6), \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 65669 &:= \left(C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6))) - \left(F(F(6)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 65691 &:= \left(((F(F(F(6))) + (5)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times \sqrt{C(9, 1)} \right) \\
 65736 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C(5, \sqrt{7-3}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 65754 &:= \left((F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) + F(7)) \times (5 + F(\sqrt{4})) \right) \\
 65779 &:= \left(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F((-7) + F(7)))) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 65796 &:= \left((F(F(6)) - (5)) + C((F(7) \times F(\sqrt{9})), F(F(6))) \right) \\
 65869 &:= \left(C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(8)) + F((F(6) + \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 66248 &:= \left(\left(C((F(6) + (6)), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 66396 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C(F(6) + F(3), \sqrt{9}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 66936 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times \sqrt{36} \right) \\
 66972 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(6^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(C(7, 2)) \right) \right) \\
 66975 &:= \left(\left(6 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) + C(F(7), 5) \right) \\
 66996 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)) - 9, \sqrt{9}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 67389 &:= \left(C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / 3 - \left(F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) \\
 67398 &:= \left(6 \times \left(\left(C(F(7), 3) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 67795 &:= \left(- (F(6)) + \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) + (5) \right) \right) \right) \\
 67817 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / \sqrt{8+1} \right) - (F(7)) \right) \\
 67829 &:= \left(C(F(F(6)), F(7)) - F((8/2)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 67844 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), F(7)) + \left(F(8) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) / F(4) \right) \\
 67879 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times 7) + C(F(8), F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 67974 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) + F((F(7) - F(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \\
 68793 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times C(F(8) + (7), \sqrt{9}) \right) - 3 \right) \\
 68794 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times C(F(8) + (7), \sqrt{9}) \right) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 68799 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times C(F(8) + (7), \sqrt{9}) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 69466 &:= \left(\left(C((F(F(6)) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))), 4) \times F(6) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \\
 69557 &:= - \left(\left(C((6 \times \sqrt{9}), 5) - (5^7) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 69825 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \times (-F(8)) \right) / (-2) \right) \times 5 \\
 69878 &:= - \left(\left(F(C(6, \sqrt{9})) - ((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (F(8))) \right) \right) \\
 69896 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(\sqrt{C(9, 8)^9} \right) \right) \right) \times (-F(6)) \right) \\
 71844 &:= (F(7) - 1) \times (C(F(8), 4) + \sqrt{4}) \\
 72774 &:= (F(F(7)) + F(2)) \times (F(F(7)) + (C(F(7), \sqrt{4}))) \\
 73216 &:= (C(F(7), 3) \times \sqrt{2^{16}}) \\
 74379 &:= (C(7, \sqrt{4}) + ((3^7) \times F(9))) \\
 74606 &:= (-7) + C((F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6))), 06) \\
 74638 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} + C(F(F(6)), -(3-8)) \right) \right) \\
 74699 &:= (C(F(7), 4) + (F(6) \times F(9))^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \\
 74764 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} + C((7 + F(F(6))), 4) \right) \right) \\
 74846 &:= (F(F(7)) + C(\sqrt{484}, 6)) \\
 74858 &:= (-7) \times (C((\sqrt{4} + 8), 5) - F(F(8))) \\
 74947 &:= (-C(F(7), \sqrt{4}) + F(((9 + F(4)) + F(7)))) \\
 74955 &:= \left(\left(-C(7, 4) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (F((5 \times 5))) \right) \\
 74959 &:= \left(\left(-C((F(7) - F(\sqrt{4})), F(\sqrt{9})) \right) + F(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \right) \\
 74969 &:= (F(((F(7) + F(4)) + 9)) - (C(F(6), \sqrt{9}))) \\
 74977 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 75454 &:= (C(F(7), 5) / F(4) + F(\sqrt{5^4})) \\
 76426 &:= (-7) \times (C(F(6), \sqrt{4}) - F(F((2+6)))) \\
 76494 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (\sqrt{4} + (C(9, 4))) \\
 76544 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - C(F((5 + \sqrt{4}), \sqrt{4})) \\
 76589 &:= (C(7, 6) \times (-5) + F(F(8))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 76592 &:= (7 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (5 \times \sqrt{C(9, 2)}) \\
 76624 &:= (7 \times F((6 + C(6, 2)))) + \sqrt{4} \\
 76741 &:= (C(F(7), 6) + F(((F(7) \times \sqrt{4}) - 1))) \\
 76754 &:= (C(F(7), 6) + F(7)) + F(\sqrt{5^4}) \\
 76998 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(7) \times F(C(6, \sqrt{9})) \right) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) - F(F(8)) \right) \\
 77284 &:= \left(\left(C(F(7), \sqrt{7+2}) - 8 \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77636 &:= (-F(7)) \times (F(7) - C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(3) \times F(6)})) \\
 77649 &:= (F(7) \times (-F(7) + C(F(F(6)), 4) + F(F(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 77897 &:= (F((7+7)) + C((F(8) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))), 7)) \\
 77987 &:= (F(7) \times (C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(8) - (7))) \\
 78897 &:= (F(7) \times F(8)) \times (C(8, \sqrt{9}) + F(F(7))) \\
 78937 &:= - \left(\left(F(F(7)) - (C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \times F((F(3) \times 7))) \right) \right) \\
 79092 &:= \left(\left(F(7)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \times C(09, 2) \right) \\
 79445 &:= \left(\left(F(7) + (C(9, 4)^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 79524 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) - (5) \right) + F(2) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 79856 &:= (7 \times (C((\sqrt{9} + 8), 5) + F(F(F(6)))))) \\
 81793 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{8+1} - (C(F(7), \sqrt{9})^{F(3)}) \right) \right) \\
 83647 &:= \left(\left(8 + C(\sqrt{3^6}, \sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 83895 &:= (F(8) \times ((3 \times C(F(8), \sqrt{9})) + (5))) \\
 83979 &:= \left(\left(C(F(8), 3) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times (7 \times 9) \right) \\
 83984 &:= (C((F(8) - F(F(3))), 9) + 8) / \sqrt{4} \\
 84645 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) - \sqrt{4} \right) + C(F(F(6)), 4) \right) \times 5 \right) \\
 84654 &:= ((-C(F(8), 4) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-5)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 84655 &:= ((-C(F(8), 4) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-\sqrt{5 \times 5})) \\
 84672 &:= \left(\left(C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times F(F(6)) \right) \times F((F(7) - F(2))) \right) \\
 84984 &:= (-8) \times (F(4) - C((\sqrt{9} \times 8), 4)) \\
 85885 &:= \sqrt{(F(8) - 5)^8 + C(F(8), 5)} \\
 85897 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (5 - C(F(8), \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \times 7 \\
 85965 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \right) - C(6, 5) \right) \\
 86448 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (C(F(6), 4) \times \sqrt{4}) \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 86634 &:= (F(F(8)) - (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(3)))) \times (-\sqrt{4}) \\
 86636 &:= - \left(\left((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times F(\sqrt{3+6}) \right) \right) \\
 86639 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)) \times (-F(3))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 86977 &:= \left(\left(\left(C(F(8), F(6)) \times \sqrt{9} \right) / 7 \right) - F(F(7)) \right) \\
 87294 &:= (8 \times (F(C(7, 2)) - F(9))) - \sqrt{4}
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 87299 &:= (8 \times (F(C(7,2)) - F(9))) + \sqrt{9} \\
 87477 &:= \left((8 \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) + (-7) \times F(7) \right) \\
 87479 &:= \left((8 \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) - F((F(7) - F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 87484 &:= \left((8 \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) - (84) \right) \\
 87493 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) - 9)) - 3 \right) \\
 87496 &:= \left((8 \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) + (-9) \times F(6) \right) \\
 87499 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) - 9)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 87546 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7,5)) - \sqrt{4})) - (6) \right) \\
 87549 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7,5)) - \sqrt{4})) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 87562 &:= (8 \times F(C(7,5))) - \sqrt{6^2} \\
 87574 &:= ((8 \times F(C(7,5))) + (7)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \\
 87579 &:= ((8 \times F(C(7,5))) + F(7)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 87591 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7,5)) + \sqrt{9})) - 1 \right) \\
 87592 &:= \left(8 \times \left((F(C(7,5)) + \sqrt{9}) \times F(2) \right) \right) \\
 87593 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7,5)) + \sqrt{9})) + F(F(3)) \right) \\
 87594 &:= \left((8 \times (F(C(7,5)) + \sqrt{9})) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 87599 &:= \left((8 \times F(C(7,5))) - \sqrt{9} \right) + F(9) \\
 87719 &:= (C(F(8),7) - (F(7)^{1+\sqrt{9}})) \\
 87928 &:= \left((F(F(8)) + C((F(7) - \sqrt{9}), 2)) \times 8 \right) \\
 87953 &:= \left(8 + (F(7) \times F((F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(5,3)))) \right) \\
 87963 &:= - \left((F(8) - (F(7) \times (\sqrt{9} + F(C(6,3)))) \right) \\
 88242 &:= \left((F(8) + (C(F(8), 2)^{\sqrt{4}})) \times 2 \right) \\
 88389 &:= (F(8) \times (F((F(8) - F(3))) + C(8, F(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 88464 &:= \left(8 \times (F(F(8)) + (\sqrt{4} \times C(F(6), F(4)))) \right) \\
 88466 &:= (F(F(8)) + C((F(8) - F(\sqrt{4})), (-F(6) + F(F(6)))) \\
 88793 &:= \left((8 \times F(F(8))) + \left((C(7, \sqrt{9})^{F(3)}) \right) \right) \\
 88894 &:= \left((8 \times F(F(8))) + \left((C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) - (4)) \right) \right) \\
 88898 &:= \left((8 \times F(F(8))) + (C(F(8), \sqrt{C(9,8)})) \right) \\
 88936 &:= \left((F(F(8)) + C((F(8) - F(\sqrt{9})), F(3))) \times F(6) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89296 &:= \left((F(F(8)) + (\sqrt{C(9,2)}^{\sqrt{9}})) \times F(6) \right) \\
 89432 &:= (C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times F(((4^{F(3)}) + F(2)))) \\
 89686 &:= - \left(((F(F(8)) - F(\sqrt{9} \times F(6))) - (C(F(8), 6))) \right) \\
 89974 &:= \left(((C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times F(9)) - F(F(7))) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 89992 &:= \left(-(8) + (C((F(9) - 9), F(\sqrt{9})^2)) \right) \\
 92379 &:= (F(F(\sqrt{9})) + C(-((2 - (3 \times 7)), 9)) \\
 93314 &:= \left(((C(9, F(3))^3 + 1) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 93885 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((F(F(3)) \times F(F(8))) + (C(F(8), 5)))) \\
 94647 &:= \left((-9) - (-\sqrt{4} \times F(C(6, F(4)))) \right) \times 7 \\
 94773 &:= \left((-C((9 \times \sqrt{4}), 7)) + F(F(7)) \right) \times (-3) \\
 94864 &:= \left(((9 + \sqrt{4}) \times C(8, 6))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 95487 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times (5 + C(-(F(4) - F(8)), 7))) \\
 96624 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), 2))) \times F(4))) \\
 96642 &:= \left(9 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}) - 2)) \right) \\
 96694 &:= (9 \times F(F(F(6)))) - C((F(6) \times F(\sqrt{9})), 4) \\
 96957 &:= (\sqrt{9^6} \times (C(9, 5) + 7)) \\
 97242 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} + (C(7, 2)^4)) / 2 \right) \\
 97342 &:= - \left((F(\sqrt{9}) - ((C(F(7), F(3)) \times 4^2))) \right) \\
 97343 &:= - \left((F(F(\sqrt{9})) - ((C(F(7), F(3)) \times 4^{F(3)}))) \right) \\
 97842 &:= \left((9 + (F(F(7)) \times (-C(F(8), \sqrt{4})))) \times (-2) \right) \\
 97847 &:= \left(((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})) - (F(7)) \right) \\
 97863 &:= (\sqrt{9} - (F(F(7)) \times (F(8) \times (-C(6, 3)))) \\
 97864 &:= (F(\sqrt{9}) \times ((-C(F(7), 8)) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-4)) \\
 97869 &:= \left(9 - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(8) \times C(6, \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 97888 &:= \left(((\sqrt{9} + C(F(7), 8)) + F(F(8))) \times 8 \right) \\
 97894 &:= (F(9) - (F(F(7)) \times (C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \times (-\sqrt{4})))) \\
 97899 &:= (\sqrt{9} \times ((F(F(7)) - (C(F(8), 9))) / (-9)) \\
 97979 &:= (C((F(9) - F(7)), 9) + (7)) / \sqrt{9} \\
 98109 &:= \left(9 \times (F(F(8)) - C(10, F(\sqrt{9}))) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$98212 := (\sqrt{9} - (F((C(8,2) - 1)) / (-2)))$$

$$98256 := (-((\sqrt{9} - (C(C(8,2), 5)))) - F(F(6)))$$

$$98264 := (9 \times (-C(8,2) + F(F(F(6)))) + \sqrt{4})$$

$$98282 := (F(\sqrt{9}) + C(C(8,2), (F(8) + 2)))$$

$$98283 := (\sqrt{9} + (C(C(8,2), (8 - 3))))$$

$$98285 := -((\sqrt{9} - (8 + C(28,5))))$$

$$98289 := (9 + C(C(8,2), (8 - \sqrt{9})))$$

$$98472 := (9 \times F(F(8))) - (\sqrt{4} \times C(7,2))$$

$$98493 := (9 \times F(F(8))) - C(\sqrt{49}, F(3))$$

$$98497 := (9 \times F(F(8))) - (C(4, \sqrt{9}) + F(7))$$

$$98504 := (9 \times F(F(8))) - C(5, \sqrt{04})$$

$$98534 := (9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(5,3) \times \sqrt{4})$$

$$98541 := ((-\sqrt{9}) - F(F(8))) \times (-C((5+4), 1))$$

$$98544 := (9 \times F(F(8))) + (C(5, \sqrt{4}) \times F(4))$$

$$98596 := ((9 \times (F(F(8)) + C(5, \sqrt{9}))) - F(6))$$

$$98669 := -(((\sqrt{9} - C((F(8) + (6)), 6)) / \sqrt{9}))$$

$$98697 := (9 \times (F(F(8)) + F(F(6)))) - \sqrt{C(9,7)}$$

$$98724 := (9 \times F(F(8))) + C(C(7,2), \sqrt{4})$$

$$98744 := ((9 \times F(F(8))) + F(F(7))) - C(F(4), \sqrt{4})$$

$$98749 := 9 \times F(F(8)) + F(F(7)) + \sqrt{C(4, \sqrt{9})}$$

$$98795 := (9 \times F(F(8))) + ((C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) - (5)))$$

$$98799 := (((9 \times F(F(8))) + C(F(7), \sqrt{9})) - F(F(\sqrt{9})))$$

$$98919 := (9 \times (F(F(8)) + C((9+1), F(\sqrt{9}))))$$

$$98969 := (9 \times F(F(8))) + C((9+6), \sqrt{9})$$

$$99449 := (F(9) \times C((9 \times F(4)), F(4))) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))$$

$$99957 := ((9 - (C(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (-5))) \times F(F(7)))$$

2.4 Factorial and Square-Root Together

In this case, only few results are given. Not all the 5-digits numbers possibilities are included. The rest numbers shall be given later on.

2.4.1 Symmetric Representations

$$3990 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 0$$

$$3991 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 1$$

$$3992 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 2$$

$$3993 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 3$$

$$3994 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 4$$

$$3995 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 5$$

$$3996 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 6$$

$$3997 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 7$$

$$3998 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 8$$

$$3999 := C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9} + 9$$

$$9690 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 0$$

$$9691 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 1$$

$$9692 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 2$$

$$9693 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 3$$

$$9694 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 4$$

$$9695 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 5$$

$$9696 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 6$$

$$9697 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 7$$

$$9698 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 8$$

$$9699 := C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9}!))) + 9$$

$$23940 := C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 0$$

$$23941 := C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 23942 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 2 \\
 23943 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 3 \\
 23944 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 4 \\
 23945 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 5 \\
 23946 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 6 \\
 23947 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 7 \\
 23948 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 8 \\
 23949 &:= C(-F(2) + F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(F(4!))) + 9 \\
 27930 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 0 \\
 27931 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 1
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27932 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 2 \\
 27933 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 3 \\
 27934 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 4 \\
 27935 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 5 \\
 27936 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 6 \\
 27937 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 7 \\
 27938 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 8 \\
 27939 &:= C(F(F(2) + 7), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F(3!)) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

2.4.2 Non Symmetric Representations

$$\begin{aligned}
 444 &:= (((F(4)!)! - C((4!), \sqrt{4})) \\
 692 &:= (6)! - C(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) \\
 924 &:= C(((\sqrt{9})! \times 2), (F(4)!)) \\
 1139 &:= (-1) + C((-1) + F(F((3)!)), \sqrt{9}) \\
 1279 &:= (-F(((1+2)!)) + C(F(7), F((\sqrt{9})!))) \\
 2444 &:= ((F(2) + F(C((F(4)!), \sqrt{4}))) \times 4) \\
 2599 &:= (-F(2)) + C((5 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), \sqrt{9}) \\
 2660 &:= 2 \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6)+0}) \\
 2938 &:= -(C(2 \times F((\sqrt{9})!), (3)!) - F(F(8))) \\
 3379 &:= (F(C((3)!, 3) - 7) / F(\sqrt{9})) \\
 3396 &:= ((C((3)!, F(3))^{\sqrt{9}}) + F(F(6))) \\
 3449 &:= ((F(F(F((3)!)) / \sqrt{4}) - C((4!), \sqrt{9})) \\
 3798 &:= (3 \times C(F(7), F((\sqrt{9})!)) - F(8)) \\
 3984 &:= -((3)! - (\sqrt{9} \times C(F(8), F(4)))) \\
 4046 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times (-((0)!) + C((4)!, F(F(6)))) \\
 4048 &:= (\sqrt{4} \times C((04)!, F(8))) \\
 4389 &:= (F(F(F(4)!)) \times (-F(F(3)) - C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})))) \\
 4416 &:= (C((4)!, \sqrt{4}) \times 16) \\
 4430 &:= -(F(C((F(4)!), \sqrt{4}) - ((3)! + (0)!))) \\
 4593 &:= (C((4)!, 5) / F((\sqrt{9})!) - ((3)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 4848 &:= (4)! \times (C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) - 8) \\
 4928 &:= ((F(4)! + F(C((\sqrt{9})!), 2)) \times 8) \\
 4976 &:= -(((4^{\sqrt{9}}) - C(7, 6)!) \\
 4999 &:= (C(((4)! - 9), 9) - (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 5865 &:= -5! + C(F(8), \sqrt{F(F(6)) - 5}) \\
 5984 &:= ((5 - (\sqrt{9})!) + C(F(8), 4)) \\
 5990 &:= (5 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (\sqrt{9} + (0)!))) \\
 6429 &:= (-6) + C(C((F(4)!), 2), F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 6434 &:= (C(C(6, 4), F((3)!)) - F(\sqrt{4})) \\
 6443 &:= (F(6) + C(C((F(4)!), \sqrt{4}), F((3)!))) \\
 6498 &:= (((6)! + \sqrt{4}) \times C(9, 8)) \\
 6624 &:= C((\sqrt{F(6)+F(6)!}, 2) \times 4! \\
 6639 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (-6)) + F(C((3)!, \sqrt{9})) \\
 6692 &:= (((F(6)! / 6) - C(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2)) \\
 6793 &:= (F(F(6)) + 7) + F(C((\sqrt{9})!), 3) \\
 6799 &:= (F(F(6)) + F(7)) + F(C((\sqrt{9})!), \sqrt{9}) \\
 6974 &:= ((F(C(6, \sqrt{9})) + F(F(7))) - ((4)!)) \\
 7596 &:= ((C(F(7), 5) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times 6) \\
 7968 &:= ((C(F(7), (\sqrt{9})!) - ((6)!)) \times 8) \\
 8896 &:= (F(F(8)) - (C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) + (6)!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 8943** := $\left(F(F(8)) + F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) - C((4)!, 3) \right)$
9233 := $- \left(C\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right), 2\right) - F(F((3)!)^3) \right)$
9289 := $\left(C\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right), 2\right) + F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right)$
9317 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), 3\right) + 1 \right) \times 7$
9395 := $\left(-F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) - F(F(F((3)!))) + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), 5\right) \right)$
9403 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), (4 + (0)!) - F(F(F((3)!))) \right)$
9476 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{4}\right) \times (-7) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$
9616 := $-C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{F(6)+1}\right) + F(F(F(6)))$
9659 := $\left(F\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)\right) - C\left((5 + F(6)), F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
9659 := $\left(F\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)\right) - C\left((F(6) + (5)), F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
9669 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F(F(6)) - F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
9669 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F(F(6)) - F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
9684 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F(8) - (F(4)!) \right)$
9685 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F(8) - (5) \right)$
9689 := $\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) - (F(8)) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
10296 := $\left(C\left(F\left((1 + ((0)! + 2)!\right)\right), F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \times F(6)$
10346 := $\left((10 - F\left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right)) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$
10479 := $\left(C\left(10, \sqrt{4}\right) \times F(F(7)) - \left(\sqrt{9}\right)! \right)$
10875 := $-\sqrt{1 + (-0! + 8)!} + F(C(7, 5))$
10931 := $\left(F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!))) - C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, ((0)! + 1)\right) \right)$
11399 := $\left(C(11, (3)!) - 9 + F\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)\right) \right)$
11409 := $\left(C(11, (F(4)!) + (0)!) + F\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)\right) \right)$
11794 := $\left(-(11) + (7)! + F\left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, F(4)\right)\right) \right)$
11936 := $\left(C\left(11, \sqrt{9}\right) \times (3)! + F(F(F(6))) \right)$
11949 := $\left((1 + 1) \times C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), 4\right) - F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
12739 := $\left(-1 + \left(2 \times \left((7)! + C\left(F(F((3)!), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \right)$
12849 := $- \left(F(F(((1 + 2)!)) - C\left(8 \times \sqrt{4}, F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) \right)$
12894 := $\left(C\left((1 \times 2) \times 8, F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) + ((4)!) \right)$
12936 := $\left(C\left(12, \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \times ((3)! + F(6)) \right)$
13049 := $\left(1 + \left(F(F(((3)! + (0)!)) \times C\left(F(F((4)!), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) \right)$
13293 := $\left((1 + C(F(F((3)!), 2)) \times \sqrt{9} \times F(F((3)!)) \right)$
13299 := $\left(-1 + \left((F((3)!) + 2) \times C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \right) \right)$
13391 := $F(1 + F(F(3!))) - 3!! \times \left(\sqrt{C(9, 1)}\right)!$
13649 := $\left(-1 + \left(F(F((3)!)) \times \left(-C(F(6), 4) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \right) \right) \right)$
13744 := $\left(F(((1 \times 3)!)) \times \left(C(F(7), (F(4)!) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$
13749 := $\left(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)) + C(F(7), (F(4)!) \times F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)) \right)$
13789 := $\left(-(1) + (3 \times (7)!) - C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \right)$
13793 := $\left(1 + \left(F((3)!) \times \left(C(F(7), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!) + F((3)!) \right) \right) \right)$
13799 := $\left(-1 + \left(F((3)!) \times \left(C(F(7), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!) + 9 \right) \right) \right)$
13869 := $\left(C(13, 8) + (F(6)!) / \sqrt{9} \right)$
13936 := $\left(C\left(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) - ((F((3)!) + (F(6)!)) \right)$
13938 := $\left(C\left(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) - (((3)! + (8)!) \right)$
13939 := $\left(1 + \left(C\left(F(F((3)!), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) - (F((3)!) - \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \right) \right)$
13942 := $\left(\left(-1 + C\left(F(F((3)!), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) - (F((F(4)!) - F(2)) \right) \right) \right)$
13946 := $\left(C\left(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)), \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) + \left(\sqrt{4} - (F(6)!) \right) \right)$
13948 := $\left(-1 + \left(C\left(\left(F((3)!) + \left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right), (F(4)!) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right)$
13964 := $\left(-1 + \left(C\left(F(F((3)!), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (-F(F(6))) / (-\sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$
13979 := $\left(-1 - \left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(7)) \times (-\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$
13985 := $\left(-(1) + (F((3)!)) - C\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) + (F(8)), 5\right) \right)$
13997 := $\left(1 + \left(F(3) \times \left(F\left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + F(F(7)) \right) \right) \right)$
13999 := $\left(-C\left(-1 + F(F((3)!)), F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) - F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right) / (-9) \right)$
14168 := $\left(C\left(-1 + (4)!, F\left(\sqrt{16}\right)\right) \times 8 \right)$
14169 := $\left(1 + \left(C((4)!, -(1 - 6)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$
14249 := $\left(-(1) + ((F(4)!) - (-2) \times F\left(C\left(F(4)!, \sqrt{9}\right)\right)) \right)$
14355 := $-\sqrt{1 + C(4!, 3)} + 5! \times 5!$
14396 := $\left(-(1 \times 4) + \left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9}\right) \times (6)! \right) \right)$
14398 := $(1 + 4)!^{F(3)} - F\left(\sqrt{C(9, 8)}\right)$
14639 := $\left(1 - \left(-(4)! \times F(C(6, F(3))) + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right) \right) \right)$
14669 := $\left(C(14, 6) + F(F(F(6))) + \left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \right)$
14779 := $-\sqrt{1 + C(F(F(F(4)!), 7) + 7! \times \sqrt{9}}$
14844 := $\left((-1) \times ((F(4)!)!) \times (-F(8)) - C\left((4)!, \sqrt{4}\right) \right)$
14889 := $\left(((1 - (F(4)!)!) \times (-F(8))) - C\left(F(8), F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right)$
14931 := $\left((-1) + ((F(4)!)!) - F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right) \times F(F(C(3, 1)!)) \right)$
14943 := $\left(1 + \left(C\left((4)! + F\left(\sqrt{9}\right)\right), 4\right) - F((3)!) \right)$

- 14944** := $\left(C \left(\left((-1) + (4)! + \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) - (F(4)!) \right)$
14945 := $\left(C \left(\left((-1) + (4)! + \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) - (5) \right)$
14946 := $\left(\left(C \left((-1) + (4)!, \sqrt{9} \right) + ((F(4)!)!) \right) \times 6 \right)$
14949 := $\left(1 + \left(C \left(((4)! + F(\sqrt{9})), 4 \right) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$
14950 := $C \left(\left((-1) + (4)! + \sqrt{9} \right), (5 - (0)!) \right)$
14951 := $\left(1 + C \left(((4)! + F(\sqrt{9})), (5 - 1) \right) \right)$
14954 := $\left((1 \times 4) + C \left((F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + (5)), 4 \right) \right)$
14959 := $\left(-1 + \left(F((F(4)!) \times (F(9) \times F(C(5, \sqrt{9})))) \right) \right)$
15329 := $\left(-1 + \left(((5)! + F(C((3)!, 2))) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \right) \right)$
15349 := $\left(((1 \times 5)^{3!}) - C(4)!, F(\sqrt{9}) \right)$
15396 := $\left(C((-1) - (1 - 5)!)!, F(3) + (((\sqrt{9})!)! \times F(F(6))) \right)$
15649 := $\left(((1 \times 5)^6) + \left(C(4, \sqrt{9})! \right) \right)$
15699 := $C(\sqrt{1+5!}, 6) \times F(9) - 9$
15971 := $\left((-15) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + (C(7, 1)!) \right)$
16193 := $\left(1 - \left(-F(6) \times C(((1 + \sqrt{9})!), 3) \right) \right)$
16399 := $\left(-1 + \left(C(F(F(6)), 3) + ((\sqrt{9})!)! \times F((\sqrt{9})!) \right) \right)$
16930 := $\left((-1) + F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (3 + (0)!) \right)$
16931 := $\left(F(F(F(1 \times 6))) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (3 + 1) \right)$
16932 := $\left((1 + F(F(F(6)))) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (F(3) + 2) \right)$
16934 := $\left((F(F(F(1 \times 6))) + \sqrt{9}) + C(F(F((3)!)!), 4) \right)$
16935 := $\left((F((1 + F(F(6)))) - ((\sqrt{9})!)!) - C(F((3)!)!, 5) \right)$
16954 := $-1 + C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) + 5^{F(4)!}$
16991 := $F(1 + F(F(6))) - (9 - \sqrt{C(9, 1)!})$
17369 := $\left(1 - \left(F(7) \times \left(-((3)!) - C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right)$
17393 := $\left(-1 + \left(F(7) \times \left(C(F(F((3)!)!), \sqrt{9}) + F((3)!) \right) \right) \right)$
17394 := $\left(F((1 \times 7)) \times \left(C(F(F((3)!)!), \sqrt{9}) + F((F(4)!)!) \right) \right)$
17491 := $\left(-C((-1) + F(7)), F(4) \right) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 1) \right)$
17935 := $-\sqrt{1+7!} \times F(9) + C(F(F(3)!), 5)$
17963 := $\sqrt{1+7!} \times C(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(6)), F(3))$
18329 := $\left((F((1 + F(8))) + F(C((3)!, 2))) + F((\sqrt{9})!) \right)$
18369 := $\left((1 + (8)!) - \left(C(F((3)!)!, 6)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$
18444 := $\left(C(18, (F(4)!)!) - \left((\sqrt{4} + F(4))! \right) \right)$
18445 := $\left(C(18, (F(4)!)!) + F(\sqrt{4}) - (5)! \right)$
18794 := $\left(C(18, F(7)) - \left((\sqrt{9})! \right)! + F(F(F((F(4)!)!)) \right)$
18996 := $\left(C(F(-((1 - 8))), (\sqrt{9})!) - ((9)!) / F(F(6)) \right)$
19236 := $\left(F(((1 + \sqrt{9})!)!) - C((-2) + F(F((3)!)!), 6) \right)$
19345 := $\left((-1) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + (C(F((3)!)!, 4) \times (5)!) \right)$
19373 := $\left((-1) - (\sqrt{9})! + (C(F(F((3)!)!), 7) / (3)!) \right)$
19374 := $\left((-1) \times (\sqrt{9})! - (C(F(F((3)!)!), 7) / (-F(4)!)!) \right)$
19376 := $\left((-1) - \sqrt{9} - (C(F(F((3)!)!), 7) / (-6)) \right)$
19379 := $\left(-1 + \left(C(F(F((9 - 3))), 7) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) \right)$
19382 := $\left(\left(1 + \left(C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F((3)!) / F(8)) \right) \right) \times 2 \right)$
19384 := $\left(C((-1) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (3)!) + 8 \right) / \sqrt{4}$
19569 := $\left(C(1 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), 5) - F(C(6, \sqrt{9})) \right)$
19596 := $\left(1 + \left(C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), 5) - (F(9) + (6)!) \right) \right)$
19629 := $\left((-1) \times ((\sqrt{9})!)! + C(F(F(6)), (2 + \sqrt{9})) \right)$
19630 := $\left(\left(1 - ((\sqrt{9})!)! \right) + (C(F(F(6)), ((3)! - (0)!)!) \right)$
19654 := $\left(\left(1 - ((\sqrt{9})!)! \right) + ((C(F(F(6)), 5) + ((4)!)!) \right)$
19924 := $\left(F((1 \times 9)) \times \left(F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2)) - ((4)!) \right) \right)$
19932 := $\left((1 - F(9)) \times \left((\sqrt{9})! - F(C((3)!, 2)) \right) \right)$
19935 := $\sqrt{1 \times 9} \times \left(F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 3)) - 5! \right)$
19949 := $\left(-1 + \left(C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), \sqrt{9}) \times ((4)! - 9) \right) \right)$
19953 := $\left(\left(1 - \left(C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), \sqrt{9}) \times (-5) \right) \right) \times 3 \right)$
19958 := $\left(-F((1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) - \left(C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), 5) - (8)! \right) \right)$
19964 := $\left(\left((-1) + ((\sqrt{9})!)! - (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times C(F(6), \sqrt{4}) \right)$
19992 := $\left(F(-((1 - 9))) \times F(9) \times C(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) \right)$
19995 := $\left(\left(((1 + \sqrt{9})!)! + (F((\sqrt{9})!)!) - C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), 5) \right) \right)$
20348 := $-F(2) + C(F(F(03!)), \sqrt{4 + F(8)})$
20369 := $\left(20 + C(F(F((3)!)!), (F(6) - \sqrt{9})) \right)$
20579 := $\left(C(F(F(((2 + (0)!)!)), 5) + (F(F(7)) - \sqrt{9}) \right)$
20989 := $\left(C(20, 9) / 8 - (\sqrt{9})! \right)$
20993 := $\left(C(20, 9) / F((\sqrt{9})!) - F(3) \right)$
20994 := $\left(C(20, 9) - F((\sqrt{9})!) \right) / F((F(4)!)!)$
20996 := $\left(C(20, 9) + F((\sqrt{9})!) \right) / F(6)$

- 21069** := $(C(21, -((0!) - (6)))) + ((\sqrt{9})!)!$
21922 := $((F(21) + C((\sqrt{9})!, 2)) \times 2)$
21932 := $((F(21) + C((\sqrt{9})!, 3)) \times 2)$
21972 := $((2 \times (1 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) + C(F(7), 2))$
22399 := $((- (F(22)) - C(F(F((3)!), F(\sqrt{9}))) + (F((\sqrt{9})!)!))$
22444 := $(2 \times (F(F((2 \times 4))) + (C(4!), \sqrt{4})))$
22446 := $(2 \times ((F(2) + C(4!, \sqrt{4})) + F(F(F(6))))$
22448 := $(2 \times ((2 + C(4!, \sqrt{4})) + F(F(8))))$
22492 := $(2 \times (F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + C(((4)! + F(2)), 2)))$
22749 := $F(22) + 7! - \sqrt{C(4, \sqrt{9})}$
22997 := $((- (2) + C((2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), \sqrt{9})) \times F(7))$
23179 := $(2 \times F(F(F((3)!))) + C(F((1 \times 7)), F((\sqrt{9})!)))$
23254 := $(2 \times (C((F(F((3)!)) - 2), 5) - F(\sqrt{4})))$
23259 := $(2 \times C((F(F((3)!)) - 2), 5) + \sqrt{9})$
23399 := $(- (F(2)) + (F((3)!) \times C(3 \times 9, \sqrt{9})))$
23598 := $(2 + F(F(F((3)!))) + (C(5^{F(\sqrt{9})}, F(8))))$
23749 := $C(2 \times F(3) + F(7), 4) - F(\sqrt{9})$
23792 := $(2 + ((\sqrt{9} \times F(7)) \times F(C(3!), 2)))$
23792 := $(2 + (3 \times F(7)) \times F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2)))$
23849 := $(F(((F(2) + 3)!)) + (C(F(8), F(4)))) / F(\sqrt{9})$
23894 := $(2 \times (F(F(F((3)!))) + C((8 + (\sqrt{9})!), 4)))$
23916 := $(2 \times F(F(F((3)!))) + C(((\sqrt{9} + 1)!)!, F(F(6))))$
23919 := $((C(- (F(2)) + F(F((3)!)), \sqrt{9}) - 1) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))$
23935 := $((C(- (F(2)) + F(F((3)!)), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F((3)!)) - (5))$
23938 := $(- (2) + (C(C(3!), \sqrt{9}), 3) \times F(8))$
23964 := $(F(2) + 3) \times ((\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(6)), 4))$
23994 := $((- (2) + (C(3!), \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}}) \times F(4))$
23999 := $(- (F(2) - (C(3!), \sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{9}} \times \sqrt{9}))$
24254 := $(- (F(2)) + ((F(F((F(4)!)))^2) \times F(C(5, \sqrt{4}))))$
24440 := $((F(2) + F(C(F(4)!, \sqrt{4}))) \times 40)$
24449 := $(- ((F(2) - C((4)!, 4)) - (4!)^{\sqrt{9}}))$
24475 := $(- (F(2)) + F((4)!) - (\sqrt{4} \times F(C(7, 5))))$
24529 := $(- (F(2)) + C(F(F((F(4)!)), 5) + F((- (2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))$
24889 := $(- (F(2)) - (F((F(4)!))!) + ((F(F(8)) + C(F(8), (\sqrt{9})!)))$
24987 := $(- (F(2)) + (C(4!), (\sqrt{9})!) + (8!) / 7)$
25289 := $(- ((F(2) + (5)!) \times (F(2) - C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9}))))$
25294 := $(2 \times (C(5^2), F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) - F(4))$
25299 := $(- (F(2)) + (C(5^2), F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times F(\sqrt{9}))$
25389 := $((2 + 5)! + C(F(F((3)!), (8 - \sqrt{9})))$
25410 := $C(\sqrt{F(2) + 5}, F(4)) \times F(10)$
25442 := $(2 + (5!) \times (C(F(F((F(4)!)), \sqrt{4}) + 2))$
25454 := $F(\sqrt{F(2) + 5}) \times C(F(\sqrt{4} + 5), F(4))$
25464 := $((- (2) \times (5!)^{\sqrt{4}}) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!))$
25644 := $((2 + (5)!) \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}) + (4)!)$
25698 := $(2 \times (C((- (5) + F(F(6))), F((\sqrt{9})!)) - (F(8))))$
25739 := $(- (F(2) + (- (5) \times (C(F(7), (3)!) \times \sqrt{9}))))$
25894 := $(F(2) + (5)!) \times (C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) + 4)$
26346 := $(F((- (2) + F(F(6))) + C(F(F((3)!), \sqrt{4})) \times 6)$
26397 := $((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) \times F(F((3)!)) - C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(7)))$
26455 := $(F(2) + (C((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4})), 5) + (5)!))$
26941 := $(- ((C(F((F(2) + (6))), (\sqrt{9})!) - F(((4)! - 1))))$
26948 := $(2 \times (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) + (((4)!) / (F(8)!)))$
27029 := $(2 - (- (C(F(7), F(((0)! + 2)!)) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))$
27069 := $(2 + C(F(7), F(06))) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))$
27134 := $(C((- (2) + F((7 + 1))), (3)!) + \sqrt{4})$
27344 := $(\sqrt{F(2) + 7} + F(C(3!, F(4)))) \times 4$
27345 := $((C((- (2) + F(7)), 3)^{\sqrt{4}} + (5)!)$
27679 := $(2 + (C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(7)) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))$
27693 := $((F(2) - C(F(7), 6) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) \times 3)$
27699 := $(- (2) + (C(F(7), F(6)) + F(9))) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))$
27898 := $(2 \times (C((- (7) + F(8)), (\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(8))))$
27909 := $((C(F((F(2) + (7))), \sqrt{9}) - (0)!) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))$
27944 := $((F(2) + (7))! - C((F(9) / \sqrt{4}), (F(4)!)))$

- 27992 := $(2 \times ((F(F(7)) + F(C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}))) \times 2))$
- 27993 := $((C(F((F(2) + (7))), \sqrt{9}) + \sqrt{9}) \times F(F((3)!)))$
- 27994 := $(2 + ((F(F(7)) + F(C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}))) \times 4))$
- 28397 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - (C((3)!, \sqrt{9}) \times F(7)))$
- 28404 := $(F((2 + F(8))) - C(((4)! - (0)!), \sqrt{4}))$
- 28494 := $((-2) + F(F(8))) + C(((4)! + \sqrt{9}), 4)$
- 28496 := $((F((F(2) + 8)) \times C((4)!, \sqrt{9})) - (F(6)!))$
- 28933 := $(F((2 + F(8))) + C((\sqrt{9} \times F((3)!), F(3)))$
- 28967 := $((-F(2)) + (C(F(8), F((\sqrt{9})!)) - ((6)!)) / 7)$
- 28974 := $((C(28, (\sqrt{9})!) / F(7)) - (F(4)!))$
- 28975 := $((C(28, (\sqrt{9})!) / F(7)) - (5))$
- 28979 := $(-F(2)) - ((C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) - ((7)!)) \times (\sqrt{9}!))$
- 28980 := $(C(28, (\sqrt{9})!) / F((8 - (0)!))$
- 29119 := $(F((2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) + C(11, (\sqrt{9})!))$
- 29214 := $(C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F((2 + 1)!)) - F((4)!))$
- 29240 := $((C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} - (0!))$
- 29241 := $(C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 2)^{F(4-1)}$
- 29242 := $((C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(2))$
- 29243 := $((C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(3))$
- 29244 := $((C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} + F(4))$
- 29249 := $((C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} + F((\sqrt{9})!))$
- 29269 := $((2 + F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2))) + F((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{9}))))$
- 29296 := $((2 + (F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2) \times (\sqrt{9})!)) \times F(6))$
- 29372 := $((2^{\sqrt{9}})! - (F(3) + F(C(7, 2))))$
- 29444 := $(2 \times ((F((\sqrt{9})!)^4) + (C((4)!, 4))))$
- 29447 := $(C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F((F(4)!)) - ((F((4)! - F(F(7))))))$
- 29489 := $(C((2 \times 9), (F(4)!)) + F(F(8))) - F(F((\sqrt{9})!))$
- 29649 := $((-F(2)) + (F((\sqrt{9})!))! - (F(F(F(6))) - C((4)!, F(\sqrt{9}))))$
- 29694 := $((2^{\sqrt{9}})! - C((F(6) \times \sqrt{9}), 4))$
- 29697 := $((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)))$
- 29739 := $((2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times (C(F(7), F((3)!)) + (\sqrt{9})!))$
- 29772 := $((2 \times \sqrt{9}) \times ((7)! - C(F(7), 2))$
- 29773 := $(F(2) + ((\sqrt{9})! \times ((7)! - C(F(7), F(3))))$
- 29833 := $(F((2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) + (F(8) \times C(F((3)!), 3))$
- 29845 := $(((-2) \times F((\sqrt{9})!)) + (C(F(8), 4)) \times 5)$
- 29869 := $((C((2 \times (\sqrt{9})!), 8) - F(F(F(6)))) + (F((\sqrt{9})!))!)$
- 29915 := $((-2) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), (\sqrt{9} + 1))) \times 5)$
- 29934 := $(C((-2) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F((\sqrt{9})!)) + (((3)! - F((4)!)))$
- 29935 := $((2 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), (\sqrt{9} + F(F(3)))))) \times 5)$
- 29944 := $(C(F(-(2 - 9)), F((\sqrt{9})!)) + F(((4)! - F(\sqrt{4}))))$
- 29945 := $((-F(2)) + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) - (C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), 4) \times (-5)))$
- 29993 := $(F((2 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) + (C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), \sqrt{9}) + (3)!))$
- 30849 := $(-F(F((3)!)) \times (0!) + (-C(8, 4) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))$
- 30894 := $(3!) + (C(F(-(0!) - 8)), F((\sqrt{9})!)) \times (4)!)$
- 30949 := $((((3)! + (0)!) \times C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), 4)) - F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))))$
- 31465 := $(F(3)! - C(-1 + 4!, \sqrt{F(F(6)) - 5}))$
- 31494 := $((C((F(F(3)!)) - 1), F((F(4)!)) + (\sqrt{9})!) / 4)$
- 31558 := $C(3 + 1!, \sqrt{5 \times 5}) - F(F(8))$
- 31559 := $-((F(F(F(3)!)) - (C((-((1 - 5)!), 5) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))))))$
- 31845 := $(F(F((3)!)) + (C(18, (\sqrt{4} + (5))))$
- 31894 := $-((F(3) + ((1 - C(F(8), \sqrt{9})) \times (4)!))$
- 32339 := $(C((F(F(3)!)) + F(2)), 3) \times F(F((3)!)) - F(F(\sqrt{9}))$
- 32369 := $(F(F(F(3)!)) \times (-2)) - (3 - C(F(F(6)), (\sqrt{9})!))$
- 32379 := $((C((3)!, 2) \times ((3)!)) - 7) \times \sqrt{9}$
- 32393 := $(F(F(F(3)!)) \times (-2)) + ((C(F(F(3)!), (\sqrt{9})!) + F(F((3)!)))$
- 32394 := $((C((3)!, 2) \times ((3)!)) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(4)$
- 32490 := $(3!! + 2) \times \sqrt{C(4!, \sqrt{9}) + 0!}$
- 32527 := $C(3!, 2)! / (\sqrt{5! + F(2)})! - F(F(7))$
- 32592 := $F(3)! - F((-F(2) + 5)! / \sqrt{C(9, 2)})$
- 32793 := $((-C((3)!, 2) + F((7 \times \sqrt{9}))) \times 3)$
- 32919 := $((C(F((3)!), 2) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) - 1) \times \sqrt{9}$
- 32922 := $((C(F((3)!), 2) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) \times F((2 + 2))$

- 32928** := $\left(C(F((3)!), 2)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \times (2 \times F(8)) \right)$
32929 := $\left(C\left((F(F((3)!)) + 2), (\sqrt{9} + 2) \right) - \left((\sqrt{9})! \right)! \right)$
32939 := $\left((F(C((3)!, 2)) \times (9 \times (3)!)) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$
32946 := $\left(\left((F(C((3)!, 2)) \times 9) + F\left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 6 \right)$
32949 := $\left(\left(\left(F(C((3)!, 2)) \times (\sqrt{9})! \right) + F\left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times 9 \right)$
32996 := $\left(\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), 2)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) / F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right)$
33044 := $F(3!)^{3!-0!} + \left(C\left(4!, \sqrt{4} \right) \right)$
33049 := $\left(((3 \times F(F(F((3)!)))) + (0)!) + C\left(F(F(F(4)!)), F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$
33154 := $-F(F(F(3!))) + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{-1+5} \right)^{\sqrt{4}}$
33339 := $\left((F((3)!))! - \left(F(C((3)!, 3)) + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right)$
33398 := $\left(C((F(3) \times F((3)!)), 3) + \left(\sqrt{9} \times F(F(8)) \right) \right)$
33435 := $-F(C(3!, 3)) + \left(\sqrt{4^3} \right)! + 5!$
33462 := $\left(3 \times \left(C\left(F(F((3)!)), \sqrt{4} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - 2 \right)$
33464 := $\left(\left(F(3)^{C(3!, \sqrt{4})} \right) + ((6)! - (4)!) \right)$
33529 := $\left(C((F(3) + F(F((3)!))), 5) - \left((2 + \sqrt{9})! \right) \right)$
33539 := $\left(((F((3)!))! - F(F((3)!))) + \left(5 - F\left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \right)$
33544 := $\left(\left(F(C((3)!, F(3))) \times F\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (F(4)!) \right)$
33545 := $\left(\left(F(C((3)!, F(3))) \times F\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - (5) \right)$
33598 := $\left(\left(C(F((3)!), 3) \times (-5) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + (8)!$
33693 := $\left((3^{F(3)}) + C\left(\left(F(F(6)) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), (3) \right) \right)$
33699 := $\left(((3)!)! - 3 \times \left(C\left(F(6), \sqrt{9} \right) - 9 \right) \right)$
33729 := $\left((F((3)!))! - \left(3 \times \left(C(F(7), F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \right) \right)$
33790 := $\left((F(C((3)!, 3)) - 7) \times \left((\sqrt{9})! - (0) \right) \right)$
33791 := $3 \times F(F(F(3!))) + F(F(7)) + \left(\sqrt{C(9, 1)} \right)!!$
33815 := $\left(-F(3) + F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{8+1} \right) \right) \right) \times 5$
33884 := $\left(-\left(C(C((3)!, F(3)), 8) - (8) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right)$
33893 := $\left((F((3)!))! + \left(\left(F((3)!) - C\left(\left(F(8) - (\sqrt{9})! \right), F((3)!) \right) \right) \right) \right)$
33895 := $\left(\left((F(C((3)!, 3)) + 8) + (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times 5 \right)$
33897 := $\left(F(C((3)!, 3)) + C\left(\left(F(8) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), F(7) \right) \right)$
33899 := $\left(-F((3)!) + \left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), 8) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) - F\left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right)$
33906 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) - ((0)! + F(6)) \right)$
33907 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) - ((0)! + (7)) \right)$
33908 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + ((0)! - 8) \right)$
33909 := $C(F(F(3!)), F(3!)) / (\sqrt{9})! - (\sqrt{09})!$
33913 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) - F((1 \times 3)) \right)$
33914 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) - (\sqrt{9})! \right) / (F((1 \times 4)!) \right)$
33916 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + (1^6) \right)$
33917 := $\left(F(3) - \left(C\left(F(F((3)!), F\left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) / (1 - 7) \right) \right)$
33919 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + (1 + \sqrt{9}) \right)$
33935 := $\left(\left(F(F((3)!)) + \left(\left(F\left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \right) \times 5 \right)$
33938 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + (F(3) + F(8)) \right)$
33940 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + ((4)! + (0)!) \right)$
33943 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + C(F(F(4)!), F(3)) \right)$
33945 := $\left(\left(F\left(C\left((3+3), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) + ((4)!) \times 5 \right)$
33947 := $\left((F((3)!))! - \left(C\left(F(F((3)!), \sqrt{9} \right) + ((F(4) + (7)!) \right) \right)$
33949 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + F\left((F(4) \times \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$
33955 := $\left(\left(\left(-F(3) - F\left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times (-5) \right) + (5) \right)$
33963 := $\left(\left(C(F(F((3)!), F((3)!)) / (\sqrt{9})! \right) + (F(6) \times (3)!) \right)$
33969 := $\left(\left(-3 \times F\left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + C\left(F(F(6)), (\sqrt{9})! \right) \right)$
33995 := $\left(F(C(3!, 3)) + \sqrt{F(9) \times F(9)} \right) \times 5$
33997 := $\left((F((3)!))! - \left(F\left(C\left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - ((F(9) \times F(7))) \right) \right)$
34092 := $\left(-\left(C(F(F((3)!), F(4)) - \left(F\left((0)! + F\left(F\left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times (-2) \right)$
34093 := $\left(-\left(\left(F(F(F((3)!)) - (F((4)!) + (0)!) + C\left(F\left(F\left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 3 \right) \right) \right) \right)$
34159 := $\left(C(F((3)!), F(4)) \times F(15) - F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right)$
34169 := $\left(C(F(F((3)!), F(4)) + 1) + \left(F(F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right)$
34279 := $\left(\left(C(F((3)!), 4^2) \times 7 \right) - F\left(F\left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right)$
34292 := $\left(-\left(\left(F((3)!))! - \left(C\left(((4)! - 2), (\sqrt{9})! \right) - F(2) \right) \right) \right)$
34334 := $\left((F((3)!))! - \left(F\left(\sqrt{4} \right) + C(F(F((3+3))), 4) \right) \right)$
34339 := $\left(((F((3)!))! + 4) - C\left(F(F((3)!), (F(F(3)) + \sqrt{9}) \right) \right)$
34365 := $3 - F(4) + C\left(\sqrt{3^6}, 5 \right)$
34482 := $\left(C\left(F(F((3)!), \sqrt{4} \right) - ((F((4)!) + ((8)! \times (-2))) \right)$

3 Binomial Coefficients Fibonacci Type Selfie Numbers: Reverse Order of Digits

This section brings **selfie numbers** with **Binomial Coefficients** and **Fibonacci sequence** values simultaneously. Results are in reverse order of digits in four different situations. First only with **basic operations**. Secondly, with use of **factorial**. Thirdly, by use of **square-root**. Forth way is when **factorial square-root** are together. The results are up to 5-digits numbers.

3.1 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers** just with basic operations and in reverse order of digits. Only basic operations are used. The work is up to six digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

3.1.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$3660 := 0 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$10987 := 7 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$
$3661 := 1 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$10988 := 8 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$
$3662 := 2 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$10989 := 9 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$
$3663 := 3 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25840 := 0 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$3664 := 4 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25841 := 1 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$3665 := 5 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25842 := 2 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$3666 := 6 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25843 := 3 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$3667 := 7 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25844 := 4 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$3668 := 8 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25845 := 5 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$3669 := 9 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$	$25846 := 6 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$03660 := 0 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$25847 := 7 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$03661 := 1 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$25848 := 8 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$03662 := 2 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$25849 := 9 + F(-F(4) + F(8)) \times C(5, 2)$
$03663 := 3 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44850 := 0 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$03664 := 4 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44851 := 1 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$03665 := 5 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44852 := 2 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$03666 := 6 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44853 := 3 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$03667 := 7 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44854 := 4 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$03668 := 8 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44855 := 5 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$03669 := 9 + 6 \times F(C(6, F(3))) + 0$	$44856 := 6 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$10980 := 0 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$44857 := 7 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$10981 := 1 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$44858 := 8 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$10982 := 2 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$44859 := 9 + C(5 + F(8), 4) \times F(4)$
$10983 := 3 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$47880 := 0 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$
$10984 := 4 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$47881 := 1 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$
$10985 := 5 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$47882 := 2 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$
$10986 := 6 + F(F(8)) + F(C(9, 01))$	$47883 := 3 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$
	$47884 := 4 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$

$$47885 := 5 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$$

$$47886 := 6 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$$

$$47887 := 7 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$$

$$47888 := 8 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$$

$$47889 := 9 + 8 \times C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)$$

$$48720 := 0 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48721 := 1 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48722 := 2 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48723 := 3 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48724 := 4 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48725 := 5 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48726 := 6 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48727 := 7 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48728 := 8 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48729 := 9 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48930 := 0 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48931 := 1 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48932 := 2 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48933 := 3 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48934 := 4 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48935 := 5 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48936 := 6 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48937 := 7 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48938 := 8 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$48939 := 9 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), F(F(4)))$$

$$53680 := 0 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53681 := 1 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53682 := 2 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53683 := 3 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53684 := 4 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53685 := 5 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53686 := 6 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53687 := 7 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53688 := 8 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$53689 := 9 + (F(F(8)) - C(F(F(6)), F(3))) \times 5$$

$$64350 := 0 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64351 := 1 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64352 := 2 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64353 := 3 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64354 := 4 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64355 := 5 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64356 := 6 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64357 := 7 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64358 := 8 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$64359 := 9 + 5 \times C(F(3)^4, F(6))$$

$$65780 := 0 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65781 := 1 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65782 := 2 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65783 := 3 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65784 := 4 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65785 := 5 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65786 := 6 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65787 := 7 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65788 := 8 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$65789 := 9 + C(F(C(8, 7)) + 5, F(F(6)))$$

$$67830 := 0 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67831 := 1 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67832 := 2 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67833 := 3 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67834 := 4 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67835 := 5 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67836 := 6 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67837 := 7 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67838 := 8 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$67839 := 9 + F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7)) / 6$$

$$77520 := 0 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77521 := 1 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77522 := 2 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77523 := 3 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77524 := 4 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77525 := 5 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77526 := 6 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77527 := 7 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77528 := 8 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

$$77529 := 9 + C(2 + 5 + F(7), F(7))$$

3.2 Symmetric and Non Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{00056} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 000 \\ \mathbf{00156} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 100 \\ \mathbf{00256} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 200 \\ \mathbf{00356} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 300 \\ \mathbf{00487} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 400 \\ \mathbf{00556} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 500 \\ \mathbf{00656} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 600 \\ \mathbf{00756} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 700 \\ \mathbf{00856} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 800 \\ \mathbf{00956} &:= C(F(6), 5) + 900 \end{aligned}$$

3.2.1 Non Symmetric Representations

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{56} &:= C(F(6), 5) & \mathbf{2582} &:= (-2) + F((8 + C(5, 2))) \\ \mathbf{168} &:= (F(8) \times F(C(6, 1))) & \mathbf{2594} &:= (F(F(F(4)) \times 9) + C(5, 2)) \\ \mathbf{189} &:= (9 \times F(C(8, 1))) & \mathbf{2648} &:= ((C(F(8), F(4)) - 6) \times 2) \\ \mathbf{378} &:= C((F(8) + 7), F(3)) & \mathbf{2728} &:= ((C(F(8), 2) \times F(7)) - 2) \\ \mathbf{0139} &:= (C(9, 3) + F(10)) & \mathbf{2796} &:= ((F(F(6)) - 9) \times F(C(F(7), F(2)))) \\ \mathbf{0168} &:= (F(8) \times F((C(6, 1) + 0))) & \mathbf{3025} &:= (F(C(5, 2))^{F(03)}) \\ \mathbf{0189} &:= (9 \times F((C(8, 1) + 0))) & \mathbf{3136} &:= (C(F(6), 3)^{F(1 \times 3)}) \\ \mathbf{0378} &:= C((F(8) + 7), F(3 + 0)) & \mathbf{3268} &:= (-8) + C(C(F(6), 2), 3) \\ \mathbf{1165} &:= (5 \times F(F((C(6, 1) + 1)))) & \mathbf{3276} &:= C((-6) + F((7 + 2)), 3) \\ \mathbf{1266} &:= (6 \times (C(F(F(6)), 2) + 1)) & \mathbf{3575} &:= ((5 \times F(7)) \times F(C(5, 3))) \\ \mathbf{1287} &:= C(F(7), ((8/2) + 1)) & \mathbf{3637} &:= ((-C(7, 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) / 3 \\ \mathbf{1292} &:= (F((2 \times 9)) / C(2, 1)) & \mathbf{3654} &:= C(((F(4) + 5) + F(F(6))), 3) \\ \mathbf{1329} &:= (C(F((9 - F(2))), 3) - 1) & \mathbf{3696} &:= (F(F(6)) \times (-F(9) + C(F(F(6)), F(3)))) \\ \mathbf{1597} &:= F((F(7) + C((9 - 5), 1))) & \mathbf{3718} &:= (F((8 - 1)) \times C(F(7), 3)) \\ \mathbf{1637} &:= ((C(F(7), F(3)) \times F(F(6))) - 1) & \mathbf{3861} &:= (C(F((1 + 6)), 8) \times 3) \\ \mathbf{1716} &:= C(F((6 + 1)), (7 - 1)) & \mathbf{3876} &:= C((6 + F(7)), (8 / F(3))) \\ \mathbf{1717} &:= (C(F(7), -((1 - 7))) + 1) & \mathbf{3887} &:= (F(F(7)) + (C((8 + F(8)), 3))) \\ \mathbf{1778} &:= ((-F(8) - F(F(7))) \times (-C(7, 1))) & \mathbf{4267} &:= ((7 \times F(C(6, 2))) - F(4)) \\ \mathbf{1872} &:= ((-F(2) - F(F(7))) \times (-C(8, 1))) & \mathbf{4368} &:= C((8 + F(6)), (F(3) + F(4))) \\ \mathbf{1877} &:= (F(7) - (F(F(7)) \times (-C(8, 1)))) & \mathbf{4829} &:= -(((F(9)^2) - C(F(8), 4))) \\ \mathbf{1925} &:= (F(C(5, 2)) \times (F(9) + 1)) & \mathbf{4843} &:= (-F(3) + C(-((F(F(F(4))) - F(8))), 4)) \\ \mathbf{1974} &:= (F(F(4)) \times F(C((7 + 9), 1))) & \mathbf{4844} &:= (-F(F(F(4)))) + C(-((F(F(F(4))) - F(8))), 4)) \\ \mathbf{2529} &:= (F((9 \times 2)) - F(C(5, 2))) & \mathbf{4977} &:= (7 \times (C(F(7), 9) - 4)) \\ \mathbf{2572} &:= (2 \times (C(F(7), 5) - F(2))) & \mathbf{5946} &:= (C(F(F(6)), 4) - (F(9) + 5)) \\ \mathbf{2573} &:= ((F(3) \times C(F(7), 5)) - F(2)) & \mathbf{5983} &:= -((F(3) - C(F(8), (9 - 5)))) \\ \mathbf{2574} &:= ((4 \times C(F(7), 5)) / 2) \end{aligned}$$

- 5984** := $-(F(F(F(4))) - (C(F(8), (9-5))))$
6435 := $(5 \times C(F((3+4)), F(6)))$
6456 := $(F(F(6)) + (C((5 \times F(4)), F(6))))$
6469 := $(F(9) + C(C(6,4), F(6)))$
6746 := $(F(C(6, F(4))) - (F(7) + (6)))$
6748 := $(C(8, F(F(4))) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6)))$
6864 := $(4 \times C(-(F(6) - F(8)), 6))$
7456 := $((F(C(6,5)) \times 4) \times F(F(7)))$
7826 := $((F(C(6,2)) - 8) \times F(7))$
9384 := $(C((F(4) \times 8), F(3)) \times F(9))$
00139 := $(C(9,3) + F((10+0)))$
00168 := $(F(8) \times F((C(6,1) + 00)))$
00189 := $(9 \times F((C(8,1) + 00)))$
00378 := $C((F(8) + (7)), F((3+00)))$
01165 := $(5 \times F(F(((C(6,1) + 1) + 0))))$
01277 := $(C(F(7), (7-2)) - 10)$
01287 := $C(F(7), ((8/2) + 1) + 0)$
01292 := $(F((2 \times 9)) / (C(2,1) + 0))$
01297 := $(C(F(7), (9 - F(2))) + 10)$
01329 := $(C(F((9 - F(2))), 3) - (1 + 0))$
01338 := $((C(F(8), 3) - F(3)) + 10)$
01383 := $-(F(3) - (C(F(8), 3) + F(10)))$
01384 := $-(F(F(F(4))) - ((C(F(8), 3) + F(10))))$
01386 := $(F(F(6)) \times (C(8,3) + 10))$
01428 := $(C(8,2) \times (-4) + F(10))$
01637 := $((C(F(7), F(3)) \times F(F(6))) - (1 + 0))$
01667 := $((C(F(7), 6) + (6)) - F(10))$
01726 := $(C(F((F(6) - F(2))), 7) + 10)$
01736 := $(C(F(6), F(3)) \times (7 + F(10)))$
01772 := $(F(2) + (C(F(7), 7) + F(10)))$
01773 := $(F(3) + (C(F(7), 7) + F(10)))$
01774 := $(F(4) + (C(F(7), 7) + F(10)))$
01778 := $((-F(8)) - F(F(7))) \times (-C(7,1) + 0))$
01947 := $(C((7 \times F(F(4))), 9) - (F(10)))$
01974 := $(F(F(4)) \times F((C((7+9), 1) + 0)))$
02564 := $(F((F(4) \times C(6,5))) - (20))$
02572 := $(2 \times (C(F(7), 5) - F((2+0))))$
02573 := $((F(3) \times C(F(7), 5)) - F((2+0)))$
02574 := $((4 \times C(F(7), 5)) / (2+0))$
02582 := $(-2) + F((8 + (C(5,2) + 0)))$
02594 := $(F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) + (C(5,2) + 0))$
02648 := $((C(F(8), F(4)) - (6)) \times (2+0))$
03025 := $(F(C(5,2))^{F(03+0)})$
03268 := $(-8) + C(C(F(6), 2), (3+0))$
03276 := $C((-6) + F((7+2)), (3+0))$
03575 := $((5 \times F(7)) \times F((C(5,3) + 0))$
03654 := $C(((F(4) + 5)) + F(F(6))), (3+0))$
03696 := $(F(F(6)) \times (-F(9) + C(F(F(6)), F((3+0))))$
03718 := $(F((8-1)) \times C(F(7), (3+0)))$
03861 := $(C(F((1+6)), 8) \times (3+0))$
03876 := $C((6 + F(7)), (8/F((3+0))))$
03887 := $(F(F(7)) + (C((8 + F(8)), (3+0))))$
04267 := $((7 \times F(C(6,2))) - F((4+0)))$
04368 := $C((8 + F(6)), (F(3) + F((4+0))))$
04829 := $-(((F(9)^2) - C(F(8), (4+0))))$
04977 := $(7 \times (C(F(7), 9) - (4+0)))$
05946 := $(C(F(F(6)), 4) - (F(9) + ((5+0))))$
05983 := $-(F(3) - C(F(8), ((9-5) + 0)))$
05984 := $-(F(F(F(4))) - (C(F(8), ((9-5) + 0))))$
06435 := $(5 \times C(F((3+4)), F((6+0))))$
06456 := $(F(F(6)) + (C((5 \times F(4)), F((6+0))))$
06746 := $(F(C(6, F(4))) - (F(7) + (6+0)))$
06748 := $(C(8, F(F(4))) \times (F(F(7)) + F((6+0))))$
06783 := $((F(3) \times C(F(8), F(7))) / 60)$
06846 := $(F(C(6, F(4))) + ((F(8) + (60))))$
07456 := $((F(C(6,5)) \times 4) \times F(F((7+0))))$
07826 := $((F(C(6,2)) - 8) \times F((7+0)))$
09384 := $(C((F(4) \times 8), F(3)) \times F((9+0)))$
09576 := $(F(6) \times (C(F(7), 5) - (90)))$
09956 := $(F(F(F(C(6,5)))) - (990))$
10679 := $((-F(9)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(C(6,01))))$
10736 := $-(C(F(F(6)), F(3)) - F(F((7+01))))$
10883 := $((-3) \times F(8)) + F(F(C(8,01)))$
10891 := $(-F((1+9))) + F(F(C(8,01)))$
10912 := $(F(21) - F(C(9,01)))$
10928 := $(F(F(8)) - C((2 \times 9), 01))$
10937 := $(F((7 \times 3)) - C(9,01))$
10956 := $(F(F(F(C(6,5)))) + (9+01))$
11156 := $(F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F((5+1))), (1+1)))$
11366 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(F(6)), F(3)) \times (1+1)))$

- 11386** := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}) - C(1, 1)))$
11388 := $(F(F(8)) + ((F(8)^{F(3)}) + C(1, 1)))$
11628 := $C((F(8) - 2), C((6 - 1), 1))$
11898 := $(F(F(8)) + (F(9) \times C(8, (1 + 1))))$
12276 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C(C(7, 2), (2 + 1))))$
12486 := $(F(F(F(6))) + C((F(8) + F(F(F(4))))), (2 + 1)))$
12576 := $(- (6) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(C(5, 2)) - 1)))$
12582 := $(F(F(- (F(2) - 8))) \times (F(C(5, 2)) - 1))$
12626 := $((C(F(F(6)), 2) \times F(6)) + F(21))$
12645 := $(- (5) + C((4 + F(F(6))), 21))$
12648 := $(C((F(8) + 4), F(F(6))) - C(2, 1))$
12652 := $(C(25, F(F(6))) + C(2, 1))$
12662 := $(C(F((F(2) + 6))), 6) + F(21))$
12769 := $(9 + (F(6) \times F(7)))^{C(2, 1)}$
12831 := $(13 \times F(C((8 \times 2), 1)))$
12868 := $(C((8 + F(6)), 8) - C(2, 1))$
12873 := $(C((3 + F(7)), 8) + (2 + 1))$
12875 := $(- (5) \times ((C(F(7), 8) \times (-2)) - 1))$
12915 := $(- (5) \times (1 - F(C((9 \times 2), 1))))$
12935 := $(- (5) \times (- (3) - F(C((9 \times 2), 1))))$
13564 := $(F(F(4)) \times ((C(F(F(6)), 5) / 3) - 1))$
13566 := $(C(F(F(6)), F(6)) / C((5 \times 3), 1))$
13676 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (- (F(7)) \times (C(F(F(6)), F(3)) \times (-1))))$
14401 := $((C(10, F(4))^{F(F(4))}) + 1)$
14568 := $(8 \times (C((F(F(6)) - 5), 4) + 1))$
14629 := $((9 + 2) \times C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - 1)$
14632 := $(2 \times (C((F(F(3)) + F(F(6))), 4) + 1))$
14643 := $(F(3) + ((F(4) + F(6))^{C(4, 1)}))$
14644 := $(F(4) + ((F(4) + F(6))^{C(4, 1)}))$
14646 := $(- (6) \times ((- (4) \times F(C(6, 4))) - 1))$
14664 := $((4 \times 6) \times (F(C(6, 4)) + 1))$
14759 := $((9^5) - F(7)) / C(4, 1)$
14848 := $((8^{F(4)}) \times (C(8, F(F(4))) + 1))$
14883 := $(3 \times (F(F(8)) + (C(F(8), 4) \times (-1))))$
14884 := $((F(4) \times (F(F(8)) - (C(F(8), 4)))) + 1)$
14949 := $(C(((F(9) / F(F(4))) + 9), 4) - 1)$
14951 := $(C(- ((F((1 + 5)) - F(9))), 4) + 1)$
15388 := $((F(F(8)) - C((F(8) + F(F(3))), 5)) \times (-1))$
15456 := $(F((C(6, 5) \times 4)) / F((5 - 1)))$
15469 := $(- ((F(9) - (C(C(6, F(4))), 5) - 1)))$
15502 := $(C(20, 5) - F(F((5 - 1))))$
15547 := $(- ((C(F(7), F(F(4))) - ((5^{5+1}))))$
15624 := $((F(4) + 2)^{C(6, 5)} - 1)$
15626 := $((6 - F(2))^{C(6, 5)} + 1)$
15659 := $F(9) + 5^{C(C(6, 5), 1)}$
15665 := $((5^6) + (F(6) \times C(5, 1)))$
15826 := $((F(C(6, 2)) \times 8) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))$
15951 := $(C(15, 9) + F(F(F((5 + 1))))$
16367 := $(- (F(7)) \times ((C(F(F(6)), F(3)) \times (-6)) + 1))$
16381 := $((- (1) \times C(F(8), 3)) + F((F(F(6)) + 1)))$
16717 := $((F(7) \times (- (1) + C(F(7), F(6)))) - 1)$
16718 := $(F((8 - 1)) \times (C(F(7), F(6)) - 1))$
16731 := $(13 \times C(F(7), (6 - 1)))$
16744 := $(F((F(4) + 4)) \times (C(F(7), F(6)) + 1))$
16792 := $((2 + (9 \times F(F(7)))) \times F(C(6, 1)))$
16868 := $(F(F(8)) - (- (6) \times F((8 + F(C(6, 1))))))$
16996 := $(- ((C(- ((F(F(6)) - F(9))), 9) - F((F(F(6)) + 1))))$
16997 := $(F((F(7) + 9)) + (- (F(9)) \times F(F(C(6, 1))))$
17456 := $(F(6) \times (- (5) + (F(4)^{C(7, 1)}))$
17479 := $(C((F(9) - 7), 4) - 71)$
17481 := $((F((1 + F(8))) + F(4)) - F(F(C(7, 1))))$
17482 := $((F((F(2) + F(8))) + 4) - F(F(C(7, 1))))$
17496 := $(F(6) \times ((9 / F(4))^{C(7, 1)}))$
17699 := $(F((C(9, 9) + F(F(6)))) - (F(7) - 1))$
17712 := $(F((21 + C(7, 7))) + 1)$
17718 := $(F((F(8) + 1)) + C(7, (7 - 1)))$
17724 := $(F(((F(4)^2) + F(7))) + F(C(7, 1)))$
17782 := $(F((F(2) + F(C(8, 7)))) + 71)$
17855 := $(F((C(5, 5) + F(8))) + F((F(7) - 1)))$
17944 := $(F(((- (4) \times F(4)) + F(9))) + F(F(C(7, 1))))$
17947 := $((F(F(7)) + F(4)) + F((9 + F(C(7, 1))))$
17954 := $((F(4)^5) + F((9 + F(C(7, 1))))$
17997 := $((F(7) - F((9 + 9))) \times (-C(7, 1)))$
18177 := $((F(F(7)) + F(F(7))) + F((1 + F(C(8, 1))))$
18399 := $((C((F(9) - 9), 3) \times 8) - 1)$
18426 := $(C(F((F(6) - F(2))), 4) + F((F(8) + 1)))$
18564 := $C((F(4) \times 6), ((5 + 8) - 1))$
18667 := $((C(F(7), F(6)) \times 6) + F(F(8))) - 1$
18777 := $((C(F(7), 7) \times 7) + F((F(8) - 1)))$
18842 := $((F((2^4)) \times 8) + F(F(C(8, 1))))$

- 19383** := $((3 + C(F(8), F(3))) \times 91)$
19448 := $C((8 + (F(4) \times F(4))), (9 + 1))$
19649 := $(- (F(9)) + (F((-4) + F(6)))^{C(9,1)})$
19658 := $(C(F(8), 5) - 691)$
19693 := $((3^{C(9,F(6))}) + (9 + 1))$
19838 := $((C(F(8), F(3)) + 8) \times 91)$
20348 := $(C(F(8), (F(4) + F(3))) - F(02))$
20349 := $C(F(F((9 - F(4)))) , (3 + 02))$
20358 := $(C(F(8), 5) + (3^{02}))$
20474 := $(C((4 \times 7), 4) - F(02))$
20476 := $(C((F(F(6)) + (7)), 4) + F(02))$
20735 := $(F(C(5,3)) \times F((7 \times 02)))$
21437 := $((((C(7,3)^{F(4)}) - 1) / 2)$
21682 := $((2 \times F(F(8))) - C(F(F(6)), (1 \times 2)))$
21828 := $((F(F(8)) \times 2) - (C(8,1)^2))$
21835 := $(- (F(C(5,3))) - ((F(F(8)) - 1) \times (-2)))$
21836 := $((- (C(F(6), F(3))) + F(F(8))) \times (1 \times 2))$
21878 := $((F(F(8)) - (7)) \times F(F((C(8,1) / 2))))$
21879 := $((F(9) \times C(F(7), 8)) / (1 \times 2))$
21882 := $((2 \times F(F(8))) - (C(8,1) + 2))$
21884 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) - C(8, (1^2)))$
21886 := $((- (6) + F(F(8))) + F(C((8 - 1), 2)))$
21888 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F(8))) - (C(8,1) / 2))$
21892 := $(2 \times F((C(9,8) + 12)))$
21893 := $((F(3) \times F(F((C(9,8) - 1)))) + F(2))$
21928 := $((F(F(8)) \times 2) + C(C(9,1), 2))$
23182 := $(- (2) + (F((C(8,1) \times 3)) / 2))$
23188 := $((- (8) - F((C(8,1) \times 3))) / (-2))$
23329 := $((- ((C(9,2)^3) - F(3)) / (-2))$
23388 := $(- ((F(8) - (C((F(8) - 3), F(3))^2)))$
23576 := $((F(F(F(6))) / (-F(7))) \times (-C((5 + 3), 2)))$
23675 := $((5 + (-7) \times F(C(6,3))) / (-2))$
23688 := $((F((8 + 8)) \times F(6)) \times C(3, 2))$
23716 := $((F(F(6)) + 1) \times 7)^{F(C(3,2))}$
23738 := $(83 \times C(F(7), C(3, 2)))$
23866 := $((F((F(6) + F(6))) + F(F(8))) \times F(C(3, 2)))$
23938 := $((C(F(8), 3) \times 9) \times F(3)) - 2$
23946 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) \times 9) + 3) \times 2$
24395 := $(((-5) + F(9))^3) + C(4, 2)$
24446 := $((F(C(F(6), F(F(4)))) / F((F(4) + (4)))) - F(2))$
24448 := $((F(C(8, F(F(4)))) / F((F(4) + (4)))) + F(2))$
24467 := $((F(F(7)) \times C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) + (4)) / 2$
24468 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F(C(6, F(4))) - (4)) \times (-2)))$
24488 := $(8 \times (C((F(8) - F(4)), 4) + F(2)))$
24496 := $(F(6) \times (C((9 \times F(F(4))), 4) + 2))$
24546 := $((F(6)^4) - (5)) \times C(4, 2)$
24569 := $((C((F(9) - (6)), 5) / 4) - F(2))$
24768 := $(86 \times (C(F(7), F(4)) + 2))$
24872 := $(2 \times ((F(F(7)) + (C(F(8), 4))) \times 2))$
24874 := $((4 \times (F(F(7)) + (C(F(8), 4)))) + 2)$
24964 := $((4 \times F(6)) + (C(9, 4)))^2$
25397 := $(F(F(7)) \times (C(9, 3) + (5^2)))$
25662 := $(26 \times F((6 + C(5, 2))))$
25738 := $((F(8) - F(F(3))) \times C(F(7), 5)) - 2$
25745 := $(- (5) \times ((- (4) \times C(F(7), 5)) - F(2)))$
25835 := $(- (5) + (F((-3) + F(8))) \times C(5, 2))$
25872 := $((2 - F(F(7))) \times (- (C(8, 5) \times 2)))$
25896 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C((F(9) - 8), (5 - F(2))))))$
26334 := $C((F((4 \times F(3))) + F(F(3))), (6 - F(2)))$
26336 := $(C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), (- (3) + F(6))) + 2)$
26367 := $(- ((F(F(7)) - (C(F(F(6)), 3) \times (F(F(6)) - F(2))))))$
26466 := $(6 \times ((C(F(F(6)), F(F(4))) \times F(F(6))) + F(2)))$
26484 := $((- (F(4)) + F(C(8, F(F(4)))))) / (6 \times 2)$
26486 := $((- (F(F(6))) - F(C(8, F(F(4)))))) / (- (6 \times 2))$
26691 := $(C(19, 6) - (F(F(6))^2))$
26796 := $(F(F(6)) \times (- (9) + (C(F(7), F(6)) - 2)))$
26827 := $((F((F(7) + 2)) - (C(F(8), 6))) / (-2))$
26857 := $((C(F(7), 5) - 8) \times F(F(6))) - 2$
26878 := $((- (F(8)) - F(F(7))) + (C(F(8), 6) / 2))$
26936 := $(C(F(6), F(3)) \times 962)$
27132 := $(C(F((2^3)), - (1 - 7)) / 2)$
27225 := $((F(C(5, 2))^2) \times (7 + 2))$
27358 := $((F(F(8)) \times (-5)) / (-F(3))) - C(7, F(2))$
27366 := $((C(F(F(6)), 6) / F(3)) + F(F(7))) + F(2)$
27367 := $(F(F(7)) + (C((F(F(6)) - F(3)), F(7)) + 2))$
27378 := $((8 + (7^3)) \times C(F(7), 2))$
27456 := $(F(6) \times (C(F((5 + F(F(4)))) , 7) \times 2))$
27496 := $((- ((F(6) - (C(9, 4)))) \times F(F(7))) + 2)$
27636 := $(C(F(6), F(3)) \times F((C(F(6), 7) \times 2)))$
27676 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(7)) - F(2))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 27677 &:= ((F(7) \times C(F(7), F(6))) + F(C(7, 2))) \\
 27678 &:= (F(F(8)) + ((C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(7)) + F(2))) \\
 27768 &:= ((-F(8)) + F((F(F(6)) - (7)))) \times C(F(7), 2) \\
 27783 &:= (3 \times (F(8)^{C(7,7)+2})) \\
 27846 &:= (F(F(6)) \times ((-4) + F(8)) \times C(F(7), 2)) \\
 27888 &:= (F(8) \times (C(F(8), (F(8)/7)) - 2)) \\
 28336 &:= (C((F(F(6)) + F(3)), 3) \times (8 \times 2)) \\
 28371 &:= ((-1) \times C(F(7), 3) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28372 &:= ((F(2) - C(F(7), 3)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28373 &:= ((F(3) - C(F(7), 3)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28374 &:= ((F(4) - C(F(7), 3)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28426 &:= -((C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), F(F(4))) - F((F(8) + 2)))) \\
 28447 &:= (F((7 + (4 \times 4)) - C(F(8), 2)) \\
 28448 &:= ((-C(F(8), F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28492 &:= (-C((2 + 9), F(4)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28494 &:= ((C((F(4) \times 9), 4) + F(F(8))) - 2) \\
 28496 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + (C((9 \times F(4)), (8/2)))) \\
 28497 &:= ((C((-7) + F(9)), 4) + F(F(8))) + F(2) \\
 28561 &:= (F((1 + C(6, 5))^{8/2})) \\
 28629 &:= (F(((F(9)/2) + (6))) - C(8, 2)) \\
 28656 &:= (-C(C(6, 5), 6) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28665 &:= (F((5 + C(6, 6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28666 &:= ((F(6) + C(6, 6)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28672 &:= (((2^7) \times F(6)) \times C(8, 2)) \\
 28685 &:= (F(-((5 - C(8, 6)))) + C(8, 2)) \\
 28725 &:= ((F(C(5, 2)) + F(7)) + F((F(8) + 2))) \\
 28848 &:= ((-C(F(8), F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times F((8/2)) \\
 28867 &:= (F(((7 + F(6)) + 8)) + (C(F(8), 2))) \\
 28944 &:= (F((F(4) \times 4)) \times (-9) + C(F(8), 2)) \\
 28982 &:= (F((2 + F(8))) + C((F(9) - 8), 2)) \\
 29359 &:= ((C(9, 5) \times F(F(-((F(3) - 9)))) + F(2)) \\
 29465 &:= (5 \times (C(F(F(6)), 4) - 92)) \\
 29482 &:= ((C(28, F(4)) \times 9) - 2) \\
 29484 &:= ((4 \times F(8)) \times C((F(4) \times 9), 2)) \\
 29529 &:= (((C(9, F(2))^5) + 9) / 2) \\
 29591 &:= ((1 + C(9, 5)) \times F(F((9 - 2))) \\
 29885 &:= (-5) \times (8 - C(F(8), (F(9)/2))) \\
 29925 &:= (5 \times C(F(-((F(2) - 9))), (F(9)/2))) \\
 31668 &:= (F((8 + 6)) \times C((F(6) + 1), 3)) \\
 32268 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C((F(F(6)) - F(2)), 2)) \times 3)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32368 &:= (C(8, 6) \times (F((3^2)^{F(3)})) \\
 32478 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C((F(7) + F(4)), 2)) \times 3) \\
 32538 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 3) - (C((5^2), F(3)))) \\
 32539 &:= ((F(9)^3) - F(C((5 + F(2)), 3))) \\
 32558 &:= ((8^5) - C(F(F((5 + F(2))))), F(3)) \\
 32628 &:= (-C(F(8), 2) + (F(F((6 + 2))) \times 3)) \\
 32648 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) - C((F(F(6)) - F(2)), F(3))) \\
 32736 &:= ((F((6 + 3)) - F(C(7, 2))) \times (-3)) \\
 32775 &:= ((F((-5) + F(7))) - (F(C(7, 2)))) \times (-3) \\
 32778 &:= -((F(8) - ((F(7) - F(C(7, 2))) \times (-3))) \\
 32783 &:= ((3 \times F(F(8))) - F(C((7 - 2), 3))) \\
 32784 &:= (((F(4) - F(8)) + F(C(7, 2))) \times 3) \\
 32796 &:= -(((F(6) + F(9)) - (F(C(7, 2)) \times 3)) \\
 32797 &:= ((-7) - F(9)) + (F(C(7, 2)) \times 3) \\
 32833 &:= ((C(3, F(3)) \times F(F(8))) - (2 + 3)) \\
 32834 &:= ((F(C(4, 3)) \times F(F(8))) - (F(2) + 3)) \\
 32844 &:= ((F(C(4, F(4))) \times F(F(8))) + (2 \times 3)) \\
 32866 &:= (C(F(6), 6) + (F(F(8)) \times (F(2) + F(3)))) \\
 32883 &:= ((3 \times F(F(8))) + C((8 + 2), F(3))) \\
 32889 &:= ((C((F(9) - 8), F(8)) - 2) / F(3)) \\
 32967 &:= (((7 + F(F(F(6)))) + C(9, 2)) \times 3) \\
 33198 &:= ((F(F(8)) + C((9 + 1), 3)) \times 3) \\
 33466 &:= (((F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) \times 3) - F(3)) \\
 33468 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (C(F(6), 4) \times 3)) \times 3) \\
 33489 &:= ((9 - C(8, 4)) \times 3)^{F(3)} \\
 33498 &:= ((F(F(8)) + C((9 + F(4)), 3)) \times 3) \\
 33551 &:= ((F(15) \times F(C(5, 3))) + F(F(3))) \\
 33553 &:= ((F((3 \times 5)) \times F(C(5, 3))) + 3) \\
 33567 &:= (((F(F(7)) + F(F(F(6)))) + C(5, 3)) \times 3) \\
 33592 &:= (F((2 \times 9)) \times (C(5, 3) + 3)) \\
 33628 &:= (-F(8) + C((2 + F(F(6))), (F(3) + 3))) \\
 33646 &:= (C((F(F(6)) + F(F(4))), (F(6) - 3)) - 3) \\
 33648 &:= (C((F(8) + F(F(4))), (F(6) - 3)) - F(F(3))) \\
 33649 &:= C(((F(9) - F(4)) - F(6)), (F(3) + 3)) \\
 33792 &:= ((2^9) \times C((F(7) - F(F(3))), F(3))) \\
 33798 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (F(9) + C(F(7), 3))) \times 3) \\
 33815 &:= (5 \times (F((-1) + F(8)) - F(C(3, F(3)))) \\
 33825 &:= (5 \times F((2 \times C((8 - 3), 3))) \\
 33835 &:= (-5) \times (-F(3) - F((F(8) - C(3, 3)))) \\
 33845 &:= (-5) \times (-4) - F((F(8) - C(3, 3)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 33859** := $(F(9) + (5 \times F((F(8) - C(3,3))))$
33862 := $(2 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(8), (F(3) + F(3))))))$
33865 := $(- (5) \times (- (F(6)) - F((F(8) - C(3,3))))$
33878 := $(F(F(8)) - (- (7) \times C(C(8, F(3)), 3))$
33995 := $(5 \times (F(9) + F(C((9 - 3), 3)))$
34584 := $(4 \times (F(F(8)) - C((5^{F(4)}), 3)))$
34658 := $((F(8) + (5)) \times (C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + 3)$
34662 := $(((- (2) + F(F(F(6)))) + F(C(6, 4))) \times 3)$
34664 := $(- (4) + ((F(F(F(6))) + F(C(6, 4))) \times 3)$
34668 := $((F(F(8)) + F(C(6, (6 - 4)))) \times 3)$
34686 := $((((6 + F(F(8))) + (F(C(6, 4)))) \times 3)$
34697 := $(- (F(7)) \times (- (9) + (C(F(F(6)), F(4)) \times (-F(3))))$
34749 := $((9 \times F(4)) \times C(F(7), (F(4) + F(3))))$
34848 := $8 \times (4 - C(8, 4))^{F(3)}$
34867 := $- ((F(F(7)) - (C((6 + F(8)), 4) \times F(3)))$
34884 := $(C(- ((F(F(4)) - (F(8))))), (8 - F(4))) \times 3)$
36078 := $(F(8) \times (C(F(7), 06) + F(3)))$
36366 := $((F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(6), 3) \times F(F(6)))) \times 3)$
36385 := $(- (5) \times (- ((8^3)) - F(C(6, 3)))$
36432 := $(C(23, F(F(4))) \times F((6 \times F(3))))$
36464 := $(4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + (- (F(4)) \times F(C(6, F(3))))))$
36492 := $(C(29, F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 3)$
36642 := $(2 \times (F((F(F(F(4))) + (F(F(6)))) + F(C(6, F(3))))))$
36665 := $(C((- (5) + F(F(6))), 6) + F((F(F(6)) + F(3))))$
36678 := $((- (C(F(8), F(7))) / F(F(6))) + F((F(6) \times 3)))$
36686 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((C((8 + F(6)), F(6)) \times F(3))))$
36828 := $(F((8/2)) \times (F(F(8)) + C(F(F(6)), 3)))$
36834 := $(F(4) \times ((F(3) + F(F(8))) + C(F(F(6)), 3)))$
36836 := $(F(6) + (3 \times (F(F(8)) + C(F(F(6)), 3))))$
36846 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + F(F(8))) + (6)) \times 3)$
36875 := $(5 \times (F((7 + 8)) + F(C(6, 3)))$
37249 := $((- ((F(9) + C(4, 2))) + F(F(7)))^{F(3)})$
37268 := $(C(8, 6) \times ((- (2) + F(7))^3))$
37646 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7))) / (-F(3)))$
37791 := $(C(19, F((- (7) + F(7)))) / F(3))$
37845 := $(C(5, 4) \times (87^{F(3)}))$
37986 := $((F(F(F(6))) + C(- ((F(8) - F(9))), 7)) \times 3)$
38377 := $- ((F(F(7)) + (C((F(7) + 3), 8) \times (-3)))$
38445 := $((F(C(5, F(4))) \times F(4)) \times F(F((F(8) / 3))))$
38464 := $(- (4) \times ((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times F(F(3))))$
38479 := $(F(9) + (F(F(7)) \times C((F(4) + 8), 3)))$
38586 := $((F(6) - C((F(8) - (5)), 8)) \times (-3))$
38625 := $((- (5) - C((2 \times F(6)), 8)) \times (-3))$
38634 := $((C((4^{F(3)}), F(6)) + 8) \times 3)$
38673 := $((C((3 + F(7)), F(6)) + F(8)) \times 3)$
38677 := $(C((F(7) + (7)), 6) - (83))$
38753 := $((C(F((3 + 5)), 7) - F(8)) / 3)$
38761 := $(C((- (1) + F(F(6))), (- (7) + F(8))) + F(F(3)))$
38762 := $(C((- (F(2)) + F(F(6))), (- (7) + F(8))) + F(3))$
38764 := $(- (4) \times ((C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / (-F(8))) - F(F(3))))$
38767 := $((C((F(7) + F(6)), 7) + F(8)) / 3)$
38788 := $(F(8) - ((C(F(8), 7) + F(8)) / (-3)))$
38868 := $(F(F(8)) - ((F(6) - (F(8) \times C(F(8), 3))))$
38876 := $(F((F(6) + F(7))) + ((F(8) \times C(F(8), 3))))$
38927 := $- ((F((7 \times 2)) - (F(C(9, 8))^3))$
39226 := $- ((C(F((F(6) - F(2))), 2) - (F(9)^3))$
39227 := $- ((C(F(7), 2) - F(2)) - (F(9)^3))$
39246 := $- ((C(F(6), F(4)) + 2) - (F(9)^3))$
39248 := $- ((C(8, F(4)) - (F(2) \times F(9)^3))$
39249 := $((F(9)^{F(4)}) - C((2 + 9), F(3)))$
39268 := $((- (8) - C(F(6), 2)) + (F(9)^3))$
39312 := $((C(2, 1)^3) + (F(9)^3))$
39313 := $((C(3, 1) \times 3) + (F(9)^3))$
39314 := $(C((4 + 1), 3) + (F(9)^3))$
39327 := $((C(7, 2) + F(3)) + (F(9)^3))$
39338 := $(F((8 + C(3, 3))) + (F(9)^3))$
39424 := $(C((4^2), F(F(4))) + (F(9)^3))$
39447 := $((C(F(7), F(4)) / F(F(4))) + (F(9)^3))$
39457 := $(C((F(7) + (5)), F(F(4))) + (F(9)^3))$
39467 := $(F(F(7)) - (C(F(6), 4) - (F(9)^3)))$
39537 := $(F(F((C(7, 3) / 5))) + (F(9)^3))$
39577 := $((F(7) \times C(7, 5)) + (F(9)^3))$
39588 := $((C((8 + F(8)), 5) + 9) / 3)$
39648 := $(- (C(8, F(4))) \times (F(F(6)) - ((9^3))))$
39726 := $((F((F(F(6)) - 2)) + F(F(7))) \times C(9, F(F(3))))$
39728 := $((F(C(8, 2)) + F(7)) / F((9 - 3)))$
39876 := $- ((F(F(6)) - ((C(F(7), 8) \times (F(9) - 3))))$
40656 := $((C(F(F(6)), 5) - F(F(6))) \times F(F(04)))$
40775 := $((5 \times F(F(7))) \times C(7, 04))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 40858 &:= ((C(F(8), 5) + (80)) \times F(F(4))) \\
 42436 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), F(3)) - (4))^{-2+4}) \\
 42438 &:= (((C(F(8), F(3)) - (4))^2) + F(F(4))) \\
 42584 &:= (4 \times (F(F(8)) - C(5^2, F(F(4)))) \\
 42636 &:= (C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), (F(6) - F(2))) / 4) \\
 42797 &:= -((F((7+9)) + (F(C(7, 2)) \times (-4))) \\
 42873 &:= -((F(3) - (C(7, (8/2))^{F(4)})) \\
 42874 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) - (C(7, (8/2))^{F(4)})) \\
 42888 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (8 \times C(8, 2))) \times 4) \\
 42896 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(C(9, 8)) + F(2))^{F(4)})) \\
 43262 &:= (-2) + ((C(F(F(6)), 2) - F(3))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 43263 &:= -((F(F(3)) - ((C(F(F(6)), 2) - F(3))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 43264 &:= ((-4) + (C(F(F(6)), 2) + F(3))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 43448 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C((F(4) \times F(4)), 3)) \times 4) \\
 43548 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (-4) - F(C(5, 3))) \times 4) \\
 43562 &:= (-2) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F(C(5, 3))) \times 4) \\
 43563 &:= (-F(F(3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - F(C(5, 3))) \times 4) \\
 43568 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (C(F(6), 5) - F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43664 &:= ((4 \times F(F(F(6)))) - C((F(6) + F(3)), F(4))) \\
 43666 &:= (-6) + ((F(F(F(6))) - C(F(6), F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43672 &:= ((F(F((F(2) + 7))) - C(F(6), F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43676 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (7 + C(6, 3))) \times 4) \\
 43746 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 4) - (C(7, 3) + F(4))) \\
 43754 &:= (-4) + C(5 + F(7), (F(3))^{F(4)}) \\
 43776 &:= -((C(F(6), 7) + (F((7 \times 3)) \times (-4))) \\
 43785 &:= (5 + ((F(F(C(8, 7))) - F(F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43788 &:= ((C(8, 8) + F((7 \times 3))) \times 4) \\
 43789 &:= (9 + ((F(F(C(8, 7))) - F(F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43835 &:= (F(C(5, 3)) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(3))) \times 4) \\
 43839 &:= (C((9 \times F(3)), 8) + (3^4)) \\
 43846 &:= (C(F(6), 4) + ((F(F(8)) - F(3)) \times 4) \\
 43891 &:= (((-1) + F(9)) \times C(F(8), 3) + F(F(F(4)))) \\
 43893 &:= (((F(F(3)) - F(9)) \times (-C(F(8), 3))) + F(4)) \\
 43928 &:= ((F(F(8)) + C((F(2) \times 9), F(3))) \times 4) \\
 44087 &:= (-F(7)) + (C(F(8), F(F(04)))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 44148 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 4) + (C(14, F(4)))) \\
 44264 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + C(2^4, F(F(4)))) \\
 44265 &:= (5 \times (C((F(F(6)) + 2), 4) - F(F(4)))) \\
 44267 &:= ((F(F(7)) \times C((F(F(6)) - F(2)), F(F(4)))) - F(4))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44285 &:= (-5) \times (-C((F(8) + 2), 4) - F(F(4))) \\
 44466 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), 4)) \times F(4)) \\
 44468 &:= ((F(F(8)) + C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), F(F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 44521 &:= ((1 + C((2 \times 5), 4))^{F(F(4))}) \\
 44624 &:= ((F(F((4 \times 2))) + C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 44626 &:= (((-C(F(F(6)), 2) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-4) + F(F(4))) \\
 44628 &:= (((F(F(8)) + F(2)) + C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) \times 4) \\
 44684 &:= (4 \times (F(F(8)) + (C(6, 4))^{F(F(4))})) \\
 44736 &:= (((F(6))^{F(3)} \times F(F(7))) \times F(C(4, F(4)))) \\
 44828 &:= (C(8, 2) \times (F((F(8) - 4)) + 4)) \\
 44876 &:= (((F(F(6)) \times F(7)) + F(F(8))) \times C(4, F(4))) \\
 44928 &:= ((F(F(8)) + C(F(-((2-9))), F(4))) \times 4) \\
 45389 &:= ((F(9) \times (C(F(8), 3) + 5)) - F(F(F(4)))) \\
 45639 &:= (-((9^3)) + F((C(6, 5) \times 4))) \\
 45696 &:= ((F(6) \times F(9)) \times (C(F(6), 5) \times F(4))) \\
 45746 &:= ((F(C(6, 4)) \times 75) - 4) \\
 45764 &:= (4 \times (F(F(F(6))) + C((7+5), 4))) \\
 46158 &:= (F((8 \times F((5-1)))) - C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) \\
 46224 &:= -((F((C(4, 2) \times 2)) - F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46242 &:= (F(24) - C((F(2) + F(6)), 4)) \\
 46248 &:= (F((8 \times F(4))) - C((2 + F(6)), F(4))) \\
 46255 &:= (-5) \times (C(5, 2) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})) \\
 46256 &:= ((C(F(6), 5) \times (-2)) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46277 &:= (-C((7+7), 2) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46284 &:= ((F(4) \times (-C(8, 2))) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46312 &:= (F((21+3)) - C(F(6), F(4))) \\
 46329 &:= (-((C(9, 2) + 3) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46337 &:= (((-C(7, 3)) + F((3 \times F(6)))) + 4) \\
 46347 &:= (((-7) \times F(C(4, 3))) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46353 &:= (F(((3+5) \times 3)) - C(6, 4)) \\
 46354 &:= (-((4 + C(5, 3))) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46357 &:= ((F((C(7, 5) + 3)) - F(6)) - F(4)) \\
 46359 &:= (-9) + F((C((5+3), 6) - 4)) \\
 46364 &:= (-4) + F(((6+3) + C(6, 4))) \\
 46368 &:= F((C(((8-6)^3), 6) - 4)) \\
 46369 &:= (C((9-6), 3) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46378 &:= (C((-8) + F(7)), F(3)) + F((6 \times 4)) \\
 46396 &:= (C(F(6), F((9/3))) + F((6 \times 4))) \\
 46422 &:= ((-2) + F(24)) + C(F(6), F(4)) \\
 46424 &:= (C((4 \times 2), F(4)) + F((6 \times 4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 46425** := ((F(C(5,2)) + F(F(4))) + F((6 × 4)))
46429 := ((- (9) + F(24)) + C(F(6), 4))
46434 := (C((4 × 3), F(F(4))) + F((6 × 4)))
46438 := ((C(F(8), F(3)) / F(4)) + F((6 × 4)))
46442 := ((F(24) + (4)) + C(F(6), 4))
46466 := ((6⁶) - C(-((F(F(F(4))) - (F(F(6))))), F(F(4))))
46473 := ((3 × C(7, 4)) + F((6 × 4)))
46492 := (-((2 - C(9, 4)) + F((6 × 4)))
46493 := -((F(F(3)) + (-C(9, 4) - F((6 × 4))))
46494 := (F(F(F(4))) × (C(9, 4) + F((6 × 4))))
46578 := (C(F(8), (7 - 5)) + F((6 × 4)))
46583 := ((F((3 × 8)) + (5)) + C(F(F(6)), F(F(4))))
46585 := (- (5) × (- (C(8, 5)) - (F(F(6))^{F(4)})))
46626 := (- ((C(F(6), 2) - ((6⁶)))) - F(F(4)))
46628 := (- (C(8, 2)) + ((6 × 6)^{F(4)}))
46655 := (- (C(5, 5)) + ((6 × 6)^{F(4)}))
46669 := (C(9, F(6)) + (((6⁶) + 4)))
46676 := (((6⁷) / 6) + C(6, F(4)))
46678 := ((F(C(8, 7)) + ((6⁶))) + F(F(F(4))))
46726 := ((6^{-F(2)+7}) + (C(F(6), 4)))
46728 := (- (8) × (F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) - (C(F(F(6)), 4))))
46745 := ((F((5 × 4)) × 7) - F(C(6, 4)))
46776 := (F(6) × ((F(F(7)) + C(F(7), 6)) × F(4)))
46863 := (C((F(3) × 6), 8) + F((6 × 4)))
46866 := ((6⁶) + C(F(8), (6 - 4)))
46868 := (C(F(8), 6) - (86^{F(4)}))
46977 := ((F(F(7)) × (F(F(7)) - F(9))) + (F(C(6, 4))))
47083 := (F((3 × 8)) + C(F(07), 4))
47268 := ((- (8) + C(F(F(6)), 2)) × (F(F(7)) + F(F(F(4))))
47336 := (((F(C(6, 3)) - 3) × 7) + F(F(4)))
47346 := (((F(C(6, F(4))) - F(F(3))) × 7) - F(F(4)))
47348 := (F(F(8) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(3))) × C(7, F(F(F(4))))
47351 := ((F(C((1 + 5), 3)) × 7) - (4))
47352 := ((F((2 × C(5, 3)) × 7) - F(4))
47353 := ((F((F(3) × C(5, 3)) × 7) - F(F(4)))
47356 := ((F(C(C(6, 5), 3)) × 7) + F(F(F(4))))
47361 := (((1 + F(C(6, 3))) × 7) - F(F(F(4))))
47362 := (((F(2) + F(C(6, 3))) × 7) × F(F(F(4))))
47363 := (((F(F(3)) + (F(C(6, 3)))) × 7) + F(F(F(4))))
47364 := (((F(F(F(4))) + F(C(6, 3))) × 7) + F(F(4)))
- 47366** := (F(6) - ((F(C(6, 3)) × (-7)) - F(4)))
47367 := (((7 × F(C(6, 3))) + F(7)) - F(F(F(4))))
47467 := (7 × (F(C(6, F(4))) + (F(7) + F(4))))
47488 := ((C((8 + F(8)), 4) - (7)) × F(F(4)))
47496 := (- (6) + (C(9, 4) × F((7 × F(F(4))))))
47524 := (((C(F(4), F(2)) × (-5)) + F(F(7)))^{F(F(4))})
47636 := ((F(C(6, F(3))) - (F(F(F(6))) × (-F(7)))) / F(4))
47646 := (((C(F(F(6)), 4) × F(6)) - F(F(7))) - F(F(F(4))))
47648 := (((C(F(8), 4) × F(6)) - F(F(7))) + F(F(F(4))))
47766 := (((- (C(F(6), 6)) + F(F(7))) × F(F(7))) + F(F(F(4))))
47768 := (((- (C(8, 6)) + F(F(7))) × F(F(7))) + F(4))
47776 := (F(6) × (- (F(7)) + C(F(F((- (7) + F(7))))), 4))
47846 := ((C(F(F(6)), 4) × 8) - F((F(7) - (4))))
47848 := (8 × (- (4) + C(F(C(8, 7)), 4)))
47854 := (- (C((F(4) × 5), 8)) + (F(F(7))^{F(F(4))}))
47867 := -((F(7) - (F(6) × C(F(C(8, 7)), 4))))
47936 := ((F(6)^{F(3)}) × (F(9) + C(F(7), 4)))
48277 := -((F(F(7)) - ((F(F(7)) - 2) × C(F(8), F(F(4))))))
48387 := (- (F(F(7))) + C((F(8) - 3), (8 + F(F(F(4))))))
48464 := (- ((F(F(4)) - C(F(F(6)), F(F(4)))) × F(F((F(8) / F(4))))))
48468 := (F(8) × (F(6) + C((4 + F(8)), F(4))))
48477 := (F(7) - (F(F(7)) × (F(F(4)) - C(F(8), F(F(4))))))
48488 := ((F(F(8)) + ((C(8, F(4)) × F(8))) × 4)
48636 := ((6^{F(3)}) × (F(F(6)) + C(F(8), F(4))))
48715 := (- (5) - ((1 - F(F(7))) × C(F(8), F(F(4))))))
48745 := ((5 × F((F(4) × 7))) - (C(F(8), 4)))
48748 := (C((F(8) - (4)), F(7)) + F((8 × F(4))))
48758 := ((F(F(8)) × 5) + (F(7) - C(F(8), 4)))
48776 := ((67 × F(7)) × C(8, F(4)))
48791 := (C(19, 7) - F((F(8) - (4))))
48794 := ((- (4) × F(9)) + (F(F(7)) × C(F(8), F(F(4))))))
48796 := ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(9) - C(F(7), 8))) × 4)
48925 := (- (5) + (F(F(-((2 - 9)))) × C(F(8), F(F(4))))))
48926 := ((C(F(F(6)), 2) × F((F(9) - F(8)))) - (4))
48928 := ((C(F(8), 2) × F((F(9) - F(8)))) - F(F(4)))
49152 := ((2^{C(5,1)+9}) × F(4))
49257 := ((F(C(7, 5)) × (2 × 9)) / 4)
49278 := (F(8) - ((F(C(7, 2)) × (-9)) / F(F(4))))
49476 := ((- (F(F(6))) + F((F(7) + F(F(4)))) × C(9, F(4)))
52616 := -((F(F(F(6))) + ((1 - F(C(F(6), 2))) / 5)))

- 52668** := $((8 - 6) \times C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), 5))$
52684 := $(F(F(4)) \times (8 + C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), 5)))$
52897 := $-((F(F(7)) - C((9 + (8 \times 2)), 5)))$
53133 := $(3 \times F(((C(3, 1)^3) - 5)))$
53361 := $(C((1 + F(F(6))), F(3))^{-3+5})$
53654 := $(C(F((F(4) + (5))), 6) - (F((3 \times 5))))$
53667 := $(F(7) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) - (F((3 \times 5))))$
53827 := $((F(F(7))^2) - (C((8 + 3), 5)))$
53887 := $-((F((-7) + F(8))) - (C(F(8), (3 \times 5))))$
53899 := $(F(9) - (-9 \times C(F(8), -(F(F(3)) - (5))))))$
54256 := $(C(F(F(6)), (5 + F(2))) - (F(4) + (5)))$
54258 := $((C(F(8), (5 + F(2))) - F(F(F(4)))) - (5))$
54262 := $(-2 + C(F((6 + 2)), (F(4) \times 5)))$
54263 := $-((F(F(3)) - (C(F((6 + 2)), (F(4) \times 5))))$
54264 := $C(F(((4 + 6) - 2)), (F(4) \times 5))$
54266 := $(C(F(F(6)), 6) + F(((2 \times 4) - 5)))$
54268 := $((C(F(8), 6) + 2) - F(4) + (5))$
54277 := $(F(7) + C(C(7, 2), (F(4) \times 5)))$
54288 := $(8 \times (C(F(8), F(2)) + F((4 \times 5))))$
54366 := $(C(F(F(6)), 6) + (3 \times F((4 + 5))))$
54497 := $-((F(F(7)) - (F(F((9 - C(4, 4)))) \times 5)))$
54568 := $(8 \times (C(F(6), 5) + F((4 \times 5))))$
54637 := $(-C(F(7), F(3)) - ((F(F(F(6))) - F(4)) \times (-5)))$
54641 := $(F(14) + C(F(F(6)), (F(4) \times 5)))$
54647 := $(-C(F(7), \sqrt{4})) + (F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{4})) \times 5$
54665 := $((5 \times F(F(F(6)))) - (C(F(6), 4) - (5)))$
54866 := $((C(F(F(6)), 6) - 8) + F((F(4) \times 5)))$
54874 := $(F((F(F(4)) + (F(7)))) + (C(F(8), (F(4) \times 5))))$
55566 := $(6 \times (F(F(6))^{F(5-C(5,5))}))$
55754 := $((4^5) - (F(C(7, 5)) \times (-5)))$
56287 := $((7 \times (F(F(8)) + 2)) - C(F(F(6)), 5))$
56448 := $((F(8) + F((4 \times 4))) \times C(F(6), 5))$
56793 := $((F(F(3)) - F(9)) \times (-C(F(7), 6) + (5)))$
56873 := $((3^7) \times F(8)) + F(F(F(C(6, 5))))$
57312 := $(2 \times (-1) + F((F(3) + (C(7, 5))))))$
57492 := $((2 + F(9)) \times F(-((4 - C(7, 5))))$
57684 := $(C((F(F(4)) + (F(8))), F(F(6))) \times (F(F(7)) - (5)))$
57855 := $((5^5) - (F(F(C(8, 7))) \times (-5)))$
57876 := $(-6) \times ((F(7) - F(F(8))) + C(F(7), 5))$
57915 := $((C(5, 1) \times 9) \times C(F(7), 5))$
57925 := $(-5) \times (-2) + (-9 \times C(F(7), 5))$
58463 := $-((F((3 \times 6)) - (F(4) \times C(F(8), 5))))$
58786 := $(C(F(F(6)), ((8 - 7) + 8)) / 5$
58959 := $((9^5) - F(9)) - (C(8, 5))$
58994 := $-((F((F(F(F(4))) + 9)) - ((C(9, 8)^5))))$
59127 := $(C(F(7), 2) + ((1 \times 9)^5))$
59267 := $(F(F(7)) - ((C(6, 2) - (9^5))))$
59335 := $(C(F((5 + F(3))), 3) + (9^5))$
59337 := $((C(F(7), 3) + F(3)) + (9^5))$
59374 := $(C((F(F(4)) \times F(7)), F(3)) + (9^5))$
59472 := $(2 \times ((F(F(7)) + F(4)) \times C(9, 5)))$
59659 := $((9^5) + F(C(6, (9 - 5))))$
59759 := $((9^5) + (C(F(7), 9) - (5)))$
59974 := $-((F(F(4)) - (7 \times C((9 + 9), 5))))$
59976 := $((-6) + F(7)) \times C((9 + 9), 5)$
61385 := $(-5) \times (-((C(F(8), 3) + 1) - F(F(F(6))))))$
61389 := $(9 \times (C(8, 3) + F((-1) + F(F(6))))))$
61776 := $(F(6) \times (C(F(7), (7 + 1)) \times 6))$
62584 := $(4 \times (F(8) + (C(5, F(2))^6)))$
62968 := $(C(F(8), 6) + (F(9) \times (2^{F(6)})))$
63469 := $((9 \times F(C(6, F(4)))) + F((3 \times 6)))$
63525 := $((F(C(5, 2))^{5-3}) \times F(F(6)))$
63648 := $(8 \times ((4 - C(F(F(6)), 3)) \times (-6)))$
63664 := $((-F(4)) - F(F(F(6)))) + C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6))$
63667 := $-((F((F(7) + F(6))) - C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6)))$
63688 := $((F(8) - F(F(8))) + C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6))$
63726 := $((F(F(F(6))) - C((2 \times F(7)), F(3))) \times 6)$
63846 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) \times (-8)) - F(F(3))) \times (-6)$
63848 := $(8 \times (F(F(F(4))) - (C(F(8), 3) \times (-6))))$
63864 := $((4 + (F(6) \times C(F(8), 3))) \times 6)$
63888 := $((F(8) + C(8, 8))^3) \times 6$
64335 := $(-5) \times (3 - C((F(3)^4), F(6)))$
64345 := $(-5) \times (F(F(F(4))) - C((F(3)^4), F(6)))$
64346 := $(-C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + ((F(3) + 4) \times F(F(F(6))))))$
64365 := $((5 + C((6 \times 3), 4)) \times F(F(6)))$
64386 := $(F(F(6)) \times (C((F(8) - 3), 4) + (6)))$
64395 := $(-5) \times (-9 - C((F(3)^4), F(6)))$
64467 := $(F(7) \times (-((C(F(F(6)), 4) + F(F(4)))) + F(F(F(6))))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 64636 &:= -F(F(F(6))) \times F(F(3)) + C(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}, F(6)) \\
 64744 &:= -((C((F(4) \times 4), 7) - (4^{F(6)}))) \\
 64758 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C((5 + F(7)), F(F(4)))) \times 6) \\
 64772 &:= (- (2) - (F(F(7)) \times (- (C(F(7), F(4)) - F(6)))) \\
 64773 &:= -((F(F(3)) + (F(F(7)) \times (- (C(F(7), F(4)) - F(6)))))) \\
 64774 &:= (F(F(F(4))) \times (F(F(7)) \times (C(F(7), F(4)) - F(6)))) \\
 64829 &:= ((9 \times (2 + C(F(8), 4))) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 64938 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((3 - C(9, 4)))) \times 6) \\
 64968 &:= ((F(F(8)) + ((F(6) - (C(9, 4)))) \times 6) \\
 65326 &:= -((C(F(F(6)), 2) - (F(3)^{-5+F(F(6))})) \\
 65547 &:= (C((F(7) \times F(F(4))), 5) - F((5 + F(6)))) \\
 65634 &:= ((- ((4 + 3)) + F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) \times 6) \\
 65636 &:= -((F((6 \times F(3))) - C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65639 &:= (- ((F(9) + 3)) + (C(6, 5) \times F(F(F(6)))) \\
 65646 &:= ((F((C(6, 4) + 6) - (5)) \times 6) \\
 65652 &:= (((F(2) - (5)) + F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) \times 6) \\
 65661 &:= (((- (1) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-C(6, 5))) - (F(F(6)))) \\
 65676 &:= (6 \times F(C(7, ((6 + 5) - 6))) \\
 65678 &:= ((F(F(C(8, 7))) \times 6) + F((- (5) + F(6)))) \\
 65685 &:= (((- (5) - F(F(8))) \times (-C(6, 5))) - F(F(6))) \\
 65688 &:= ((F(F(8)) + (8 - C(6, 5))) \times 6) \\
 65689 &:= (F(9) + ((F(F(8)) \times C(6, 5)) - F(F(6)))) \\
 65697 &:= ((F(- ((F(7) - F(9)))) \times C(6, 5)) + (F(F(6)))) \\
 65699 &:= (- ((9 \times 9)) + C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65718 &:= (((8 - 1) + F(C(7, 5))) \times 6) \\
 65724 &:= (((4 \times 2) + F(C(7, 5))) \times 6) \\
 65736 &:= (((F(6) + F(3)) + F(C(7, 5))) \times 6) \\
 65738 &:= (- ((F(8) - C((F(3) \times F(7)), 5))) - F(F(6))) \\
 65746 &:= (C(F(6), 4) + (F(C(7, 5)) \times 6) \\
 65748 &:= (((8 + 4) + F(C(7, 5))) \times 6) \\
 65754 &:= ((F((F(F(4)) + (5))) + (F(C(7, 5)))) \times 6) \\
 65759 &:= (C(- ((9 - (5 \times 7))), 5) - F(F(6))) \\
 65765 &:= (F((5 + 6)) + (F(C(7, 5)) \times 6) \\
 65766 &:= ((F(F(6)) + (- (6) + F(C(7, 5)))) \times 6) \\
 65767 &:= (- (F(7)) + C(((F(6) + F(7)) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65771 &:= (- (1) + (C((F(7) + F(7)), 5) - F(6))) \\
 65772 &:= (C((2 \times F(7)), C(7, 5)) - F(6)) \\
 65773 &:= (F(F(3)) + (C((F(7) + F(7)), 5) - F(6))) \\
 65774 &:= (C(((F(4) \times F(7)) - F(7)), 5) - (6)) \\
 65775 &:= (- (5) + C((F(7) \times (7 - 5)), F(F(6))))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 65778 &:= (- (8) + (C((F(7) + F(7)), 5) + (6))) \\
 65779 &:= (- (9) + (C((F(7) + F(7)), 5) + F(6))) \\
 65835 &:= (F(C(5, 3)) + C((F(8) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65836 &:= (C(F(6), 3) + C((F(8) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65856 &:= ((C(F(6), 5) \times F(8)) \times 56) \\
 65864 &:= ((4 \times F(F(6))) + C((F(8) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65869 &:= (C((F(9) - F(6)), F(8)) + F((5 + 6))) \\
 65885 &:= ((5 \times F(8)) + C((F(8) + (5)), F(F(6)))) \\
 65886 &:= (((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) - C(8, 5)) \times (-6)) \\
 65892 &:= (((2 \times F(9)) \times C(F(8), 5)) / F(F(6))) \\
 66292 &:= ((2^9) + C(26, F(F(6)))) \\
 66348 &:= (((C(8, F(4)) \times F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66377 &:= (F(F(7)) + ((C(F(7), F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66397 &:= (C(F(7), 9) + ((F(F(3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66738 &:= (((- (C(8, 3)) + F(F(7))) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 66996 &:= ((C((F(F(6)) - 9), 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6) \\
 67158 &:= -(((F(F(8)) - ((C(5, 1)^7)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 67337 &:= ((C(F(7), 3) + 3) \times F((7 + 6))) \\
 67386 &:= ((6 \times (F(F(8)) - F(F(3)))) + C(F(7), 6)) \\
 67627 &:= (7 \times ((2 + F(F(F(6)))) - C(F(7), F(6)))) \\
 67656 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) + C((5 + 6), 7)) \times 6) \\
 67825 &:= (- (5) + (2 \times (C(F(8), F(7)) / 6))) \\
 67848 &:= (8 \times (F(- ((F(F(F(4))) - (F(8)))) + C(F(7), 6))) \\
 68336 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), 3) \times F(3)) + (F(F(8)) \times 6)) \\
 68536 &:= ((C((6 \times 3), 5) \times 8) - F(6)) \\
 68538 &:= ((C((F(8) - 3), 5) \times 8) - (6)) \\
 68646 &:= ((C((F(6) + (4)), F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68766 &:= ((C((F(6) + F(6)), 7) + F(8)) \times 6) \\
 69564 &:= ((C(- ((F(F(4)) - F(F(6))), 5) - F(9)) \times 6) \\
 69768 &:= ((C(F(8), 6) / 7) \times C(9, F(6))) \\
 69966 &:= (6 \times (C(- ((F(F(6)) - F(9))), 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 70844 &:= (4 \times F((F(F(F(4))) + F(C(8, 07)))) \\
 71564 &:= -(((F(4)^{F(6)}) - (C(5, 1)^7)) \\
 72366 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(C(6, F(3))) - 2)) \times 7) \\
 72774 &:= ((F(F(F(4))) + F(F(7))) \times (C(F(7), 2) + F(F(7)))) \\
 73461 &:= ((F((1 + C(F(6), F(F(4)))) - F(3)) / 7) \\
 73626 &:= (C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), 6) - F((3 + F(7)))) \\
 73866 &:= -((F(F(F(6))) + (- (C((6 + 8), 3)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 73878 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (7 \times C(8, 3))) \times 7) \\
 73938 &:= (C(F(8), F(3)) - (- (9) \times (F(3)^{F(7)}))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 74368 := $(8 \times ((C(F(F(6)), 3) - F(F(4))) \times 7))$
 74382 := $(F(2) \times (C((8 \times 3), 4) \times 7))$
 74383 := $(F(F(3)) + (C((8 \times 3), 4) \times 7))$
 74384 := $(F(F(4)) + (C((8 \times 3), 4) \times 7))$
 74415 := $(F((C(5, 1) \times 4) \times (4 + 7)))$
 74466 := $((F(6) \times C(F(F(6)), F(4))) - F(F(4))) \times 7$
 74612 := $(- (F(2)) + C((1 + F(F(6))), (F(4) + F(7))))$
 74613 := $C((F(F(3)) + F(F((1 \times 6))), (F(4) + F(7)))$
 74614 := $(F(F(F(4))) + C((1 + F(F(6))), (F(4) + F(7))))$
 74616 := $(C((F(F(6)) + 1), 6) - ((4 - 7)))$
 74618 := $((C((F(8) + 1), 6) - F(F(4))) + (7))$
 74622 := $((C(22, 6) - 4) + F(7))$
 74626 := $(C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), (F(6) - F(F(4)))) + (F(7)))$
 74628 := $((C((F(8) + F(2)), 6) + F(F(4))) + (F(7)))$
 74646 := $((F(C(6, F(4))) + F(F(6))) \times (4 + 7))$
 74736 := $(F((6 \times F(3))) \times (C(F(7), F(4)) + F(F(7))))$
 74746 := $(F((F(F(6)) + (4))) - (C(F(7), F(4)) - (7)))$
 74752 := $(F(25) - (C(F(7), F(4)) - F(7)))$
 74786 := $((- (6) + F((F(C(8, 7)) + (4)))) - F(F(7)))$
 74793 := $((F(F(3)) + (F(9) + C(F(7), F(4)))) \times F(F(7)))$
 74828 := $((- (C(F(8), 2)) + F((F(8) + (4)))) + (F(7)))$
 74835 := $(F((5^{F(3)})) - (C(F(8), F(4)) / 7))$
 74846 := $(C((F(F(6)) + F(F(F(4))))), (8 - F(F(4)))) + F(F(7)))$
 74848 := $((C(8, F(4)) + F((F(8) + (4)))) - F(F(7)))$
 74883 := $(C(- ((F(3) - F(8))), 8) - (F(4) \times F(F(7))))$
 74947 := $- ((C(F(7), F(F(4))) - F((9 + F(4)) + F(7))))$
 74948 := $(F((F(8) + (4))) - (C(9, F(4)) - (7)))$
 75228 := $((C(F(8), 2) + F(25)) - (7))$
 75248 := $(C(F(8), F(F(4))) + ((F(25) + F(7))))$
 75254 := $((- (4) + F((C(5, F(2)) \times 5))) + F(F(7)))$
 75582 := $C((- (2) + F(8)), (C(5, 5) + 7))$
 75635 := $(F((5^{F(3)})) + F(C(6, - ((5 - 7))))$
 75837 := $((C(F(7), 3) \times (-8)) + (5^7))$
 75838 := $((F(F(8)) - (F(3) \times C(8, 5))) \times 7)$
 75957 := $((F(C(7, 5)) - (95)) \times 7)$
 76336 := $- ((C(F((F(6) - F(F(3))))), 3) + (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)))$
 76337 := $((- (C(F(7), 3)) + F(F(3))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)))$
 76346 := $(- (C((6 \times 4), F(3))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)))$
 76374 := $(- (F(4)) + ((- (C(7, 3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7))$
 76377 := $(- (7) \times (C(7, 3) - F((F(6) + F(7))))$
 76389 := $((C(9, 8) - F(3)) \times F(F(F(6)))) - F(F(7))$
 76397 := $((F(F(7)) + (C(9, 3))) \times (F(6) + F(F(7))))$
 76412 := $(- (C(21, F(F(4)))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)))$
 76426 := $((F(F(F(6))) - C((2 \times 4), 6)) \times 7)$
 76433 := $((C(3, F(3))^{F(4)} - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-7))$
 76446 := $((6^{F(4)+4}) - C(F(F(6)), F(7)))$
 76478 := $((F(F(8)) \times 7) - F((4 + C(F(6), 7))))$
 76481 := $((- (1) + F(F(8))) + ((4^{C(F(6), 7)}))$
 76482 := $(F((F(2) \times F(8))) + ((4^{C(F(6), 7)}))$
 76483 := $((F(F(3)) + F(F(8))) + ((4^{C(F(6), 7)}))$
 76484 := $((F(F(4)) + F(F(8))) + ((4^{C(F(6), 7)}))$
 76549 := $(C((9 \times F(4)), 5) - F((6 + F(7))))$
 76563 := $(- (3) + ((F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) - F(6)) \times 7))$
 76564 := $(- (F(F(4))) + ((F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) - F(6)) \times 7))$
 76573 := $((F(F(3)) + (F(C(7, 5)) - F(6))) \times 7)$
 76575 := $(- (5) + ((F(C(7, 5)) - (6)) \times 7))$
 76588 := $(C(8, 8) + ((- (5) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7))$
 76594 := $((- (4) + F((C(9, 5) / 6))) \times 7)$
 76619 := $(- ((C(9, 1) - 6) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)))$
 76622 := $(F((22 - C(6, 6)) \times 7)$
 76656 := $(- (F(C(6, 5))) + ((F(F(F(6))) + 6) \times 7))$
 76727 := $((F(C(7, 2)) + (7)) + F(6)) \times 7$
 76748 := $(F((F(8) + (4))) + (C(F(7), 6) + (7)))$
 76818 := $((F(F(8)) + C((1 \times 8), 6)) \times 7)$
 76855 := $((- ((C(5, 5) - 8)) \times F(F(F(6)))) + F(F(7)))$
 76976 := $(C(F(F(6)), 7) - (F(9)^{F(F(6)) / 7}))$
 77266 := $- ((F(F(6)) - (C((F(F(6)) - F(2)), F(7)) - F(F(7))))$
 77284 := $(- ((F(4) - C((F(8) - F(2)), F(7))) - F(F(7)))$
 77285 := $((- (5) + C(F(8), 2)) \times F((7 + 7)))$
 77287 := $(C(((F(7) + 8) - F(2)), F(7)) - F(F(7)))$
 77356 := $((C((F(F(6)) + (5)), F(3)) + (7)) \times F(F(7)))$
 77467 := $(F(7) \times (C(F(F(6)), 4) - (F(7) + F(7))))$
 77468 := $((8 - C(F(F(6)), 4)) \times (-F(7)) - F(F(7)))$
 77486 := $(- (F(F(6))) + (C((F(8) - F(F(F(4))))), 7) - F(7))$
 77515 := $(- (5) + C((- (1) + F((- (5) + F(7))))), F(7))$
 77533 := $(C(((F(3) + F(3)) \times 5), F(7)) + F(7))$
 77548 := $(F(8) + (C((4 \times 5), 7) + 7))$
 77636 := $((C(F(F(6)), - ((F(3) - (6)))) - (F(7))) \times F(7))$
 77736 := $((6^3) + C((F(7) + (7)), F(7)))$
 77746 := $((C(C(6, F(4)), F(7)) - (7)) + F(F(7)))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 77753 &:= (C(((F(3) + (5)) + F(7)), F(7)) + F(F(7))) \\
 77798 &:= ((C(F(8), (-9) + F(7))) \times F(7)) - (7)) \\
 77844 &:= (4 \times (C((-4) + F(8)), 7) + F(7)) \\
 77896 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), (9+8)) + (7)) \times F(7)) \\
 78145 &:= ((5^4) + C((-1) + F(8)), F(7)) \\
 78249 &:= ((9^{F(4)}) + C(-(F(2) - F(8))), F(7)) \\
 78414 &:= (((C(4, 1)^4) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78442 &:= (C((2^4), 4) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 78646 &:= (C((6 \times 4), F(F(6))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-7))) \\
 79462 &:= ((C((2 + F(F(6))), 4) \times 9) - F(F(7))) \\
 79847 &:= ((7 \times C((F(F(4)) \times 8), 9)) - F(F(7))) \\
 82664 &:= (((-F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) - (F(C(6, 2)))) \times 8) \\
 82684 &:= (-4) - ((F(F(8)) - (F(C(6, 2)))) \times (-8)) \\
 82688 &:= ((8 \times F(F(8))) - (F(C(6, 2)) \times 8)) \\
 83387 &:= ((7 \times F(F(8))) + F((-C(3, 3) + F(8)))) \\
 83628 &:= ((F((F(8) - 2)) \times C(6, 3)) + 8) \\
 83676 &:= (F(F(6)) + ((F(7) \times C(C(6, F(3)), 8))) \\
 83832 &:= ((2 - (-3) \times C(F(8), 3)) \times F(8)) \\
 84368 &:= (-8) \times ((C(6, 3)^{F(F(4))}) - F(F(8))) \\
 84645 &:= (-5) \times (F(F(4)) - (C(F(F(6)), 4) + F(F(8)))) \\
 84653 &:= (-F(3)) - (-5) \times (C(F(F(6)), 4) + F(F(8))) \\
 84654 &:= -((F(F(F(4))) + (-5) \times (C(F(F(6)), 4) + F(F(8)))) \\
 84672 &:= (F(-((F(2) - F(7)))) \times (C(F(6), F(F(4))) \times F(8))) \\
 84887 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (8 \times (C(F(8), F(4)) \times 8))) \\
 84928 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (C((2+9), 4))) \times 8) \\
 84968 &:= (-8) \times (C(-((F(6) - F(9))), F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) \\
 85848 &:= (((C(F(8), F(F(4))) - F(F(8))) + (5)) \times (-8)) \\
 85864 &:= ((4^{F(6)}) + (C(F(8), 5) - F(8))) \\
 85888 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C(F(8), F((8-5)))) \times 8) \\
 86236 &:= -(((C(F(F(6)), 3) + 2) + (-F(6)) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86238 &:= (-C(F(8), 3) - (F(F((2+6))) \times (-8))) \\
 86246 &:= (-C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - ((-F(2) - F(F(F(6)))) \times 8)) \\
 86294 &:= ((4 \times C((F(9)/2), F(6))) - F(F(8))) \\
 86428 &:= (-C((F(8) - F(2)), F(4)) - (-F(6)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 86436 &:= ((C(6, 3) + (4^6)) \times F(8)) \\
 86457 &:= ((C(7, 5) + (4^6)) \times F(8)) \\
 86496 &:= (F(6) \times ((-C(9, 4) - F(6)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 86528 &:= (F(F(8)) + C((25 - 6), 8)) \\
 86544 &:= (-((C(4, F(4))^5)) - (-F(6)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 86628 &:= (-8) - (-2) \times (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86632 &:= (2 \times (-F(3)) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(8)))) \\
 86633 &:= (-3) - (-F(3)) \times (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(8))) \\
 86634 &:= -((F(F(4)) + (-F(3)) \times (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(8)))) \\
 86636 &:= ((6/3) \times (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(8))) \\
 86642 &:= (2 \times (F(4) + (C(F(F(6)), 6) - F(F(8)))) \\
 86644 &:= (-C((F(4) \times 4), 6) - (-F(6)) \times F(F(8))) \\
 86797 &:= (-C(F(7), 9) - ((-7) + F(F(F(6)))) \times (-8)) \\
 86846 &:= ((C((F(F(6)) + (4)), F(8)) \times 6) + F(F(8))) \\
 86896 &:= (F(6) \times (-C(C(9, 8), 6) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87176 &:= (F(6) \times (-((C(7, 1) \times 7) + F(F(8)))) \\
 87258 &:= (F(F(8)) + (F((5^2)) + C(F(7), 8))) \\
 87514 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (-1) + C((5 + F(7)), 8)) \\
 87552 &:= ((-2) + F(F((C(5, 5) + 7))) \times 8) \\
 87559 &:= (-9) - (F(F((C(5, 5) + 7))) \times (-8)) \\
 87564 &:= (-4) - (-F(C(6, 5)) \times F((F(7) + 8))) \\
 87567 &:= ((C((7 + F(F(6))), 5) + F(F(7))) - F(F(8))) \\
 87568 &:= (8 \times F(((C(6, 5) + 7) + 8))) \\
 87576 &:= (((-6) + F(C(7, 5))) + (7)) \times 8) \\
 87966 &:= ((F(C(6, -((6-9)))) \times F(7)) + (F(8))) \\
 88384 &:= (C(-((F(4) - F(8))), 3) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 88464 &:= (((F(F(4)) \times C(F(6), F(4))) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 88466 &:= (F(F(F(6))) + C(C(6, F(4)), (-8) + F(8))) \\
 88555 &:= (5 \times F(((C(5, 5)^8) + F(8))) \\
 88576 &:= (((6 \times C(7, 5)) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 88592 &:= (((2 + C(9, 5)) + F(F(8))) \times 8) \\
 88687 &:= (C(F(7), 8) + ((F(F(6)) - F(F(8))) \times (-8))) \\
 88876 &:= ((F(F(6)) + C(F(7), 8)) - (-8) \times F(F(8))) \\
 89248 &:= ((C(F(8), F(F(4))) + F(F(-((F(2) - 9)))) \times 8) \\
 89432 &:= (C((2^3), F(4)) \times F((9+8))) \\
 89936 &:= (C(F(6), 3) \times (9 + F((9+8)))) \\
 92369 &:= (-9) + C(((6 \times 3) + F(2)), 9) \\
 92378 &:= C((F(8) - ((7-3) - 2)), 9) \\
 92386 &:= (F(6) + C((F(8) - F(C(3, 2))), 9)) \\
 93294 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((C(9, 2)^3) - 9)) \\
 93678 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(7)) - (C((6 \times 3), 9))) \\
 94647 &:= (7 \times ((F(F(4)) \times F(C(6, F(4)))) - 9)) \\
 94676 &:= (((F(F(6)) - (7)) \times F(C(6, F(4)))) - F(9)) \\
 94826 &:= (((C(F(F(6)), 2) + F(F(8))) / (-4)) \times (-F(9))) \\
 94962 &:= (C((-2) + F(F(6))), 9) + F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) \\
 96789 &:= ((9 \times F(F(8))) - (C(F(7), 6) + 9))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 96798 &:= (- (C(-((F(8) - F(9))), 7)) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-9))) \\
 97494 &:= ((F((F(4) \times 9)) / F(F(4))) - (C(F(7), 9))) \\
 97635 &:= (F(5^{F(3)})) + (C(F(F(6)), F(7)) / 9) \\
 97799 &:= ((9 \times F((F(9) - F(7)))) - (C(F(7), 9))) \\
 97988 &:= (((- (F(8)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9)) - (C(F(7), 9))) \\
 98237 &:= (- (C(F(7), 3)) + ((- (F(2)) - F(F(8))) \times (-9))) \\
 98238 &:= (- (C((8 \times 3), 2)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98246 &:= (C(C(F(6), F(F(4))), (2 + F(8))) - F(9)) \\
 98261 &:= (- (1) + ((- (C(F(6), 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98263 &:= (F(F(3)) + ((- (C(F(6), 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98264 &:= (F(F(4)) + ((- (C(F(6), 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98283 &:= -((C((F(F(3)) + (F(8))), 2) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98349 &:= -((C((9 + F(F(4))), 3) + (F(F(8)) \times (-9)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 98458 &:= (- (C(8, C(5, 4))) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98477 &:= (- (C(7, 7)) + ((- (4) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98515 &:= (C(C(5, 1), 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98535 &:= (C((5 + F(3)), 5) - (F(F(8)) \times (-9))) \\
 98547 &:= (C(F(7), F(F(4))) + ((- (5) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98548 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times C((4 + 5), 8)) + F(9)) \\
 98564 &:= (- (4) + ((C(6, 5) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98578 &:= (- (8) + ((F(C(7, 5)) + 8) \times 9)) \\
 98669 &:= ((C(9, F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + F(F(8)))) - F(9)) \\
 98737 &:= (C(F(7), 3) + ((- (7) + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98766 &:= ((C(F(6), 6) + F((F(7) + 8))) \times 9) \\
 98838 &:= (((C(8, F(3)) + 8) + F(F(8))) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

3.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers with factorial** in reverse order of digits. The work is up to six digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

3.3.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 2440 &:= 0 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2441 &:= 1 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2442 &:= 2 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2443 &:= 3 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2444 &:= 4 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2445 &:= 5 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2446 &:= 6 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2447 &:= 7 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2448 &:= 8 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2)) \\
 2449 &:= 9 + 4 \times F(C(F(4)!, 2))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 14640 &:= 0 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14641 &:= 1 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14642 &:= 2 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14643 &:= 3 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14644 &:= 4 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14645 &:= 5 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14646 &:= 6 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14647 &:= 7 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1)) \\
 14648 &:= 8 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$14649 := 9 + 4! \times F(C(6, 4 \times 1))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24530 &:= 0 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24531 &:= 1 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24532 &:= 2 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24533 &:= 3 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24534 &:= 4 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24535 &:= 5 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24536 &:= 6 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24537 &:= 7 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24538 &:= 8 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2) \\
 24539 &:= 9 + C(F(F(3!)), 5) + F(F(F(F(4)!)) - 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 24840 &:= 0 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24841 &:= 1 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24842 &:= 2 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24843 &:= 3 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24844 &:= 4 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24845 &:= 5 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24846 &:= 6 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2) \\
 24847 &:= 7 + F(4)! / 8 \times C(4!, 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$24848 := 8 + F(4)!!/8 \times C(4!, 2)$$

$$24849 := 9 + F(4)!!/8 \times C(4!, 2)$$

$$26460 := 0 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26461 := 1 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26462 := 2 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26463 := 3 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26464 := 4 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26465 := 5 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26466 := 6 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26467 := 7 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26468 := 8 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$26469 := 9 + F(F(6)) \times F(4)! \times C(F(F(6)), 2)$$

$$32340 := 0 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32341 := 1 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32342 := 2 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32343 := 3 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32344 := 4 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32345 := 5 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32346 := 6 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32347 := 7 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32348 := 8 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$32349 := 9 + F(F(F(4)!)) \times C(F(F(3!)) + F(2), 3)$$

$$33250 := 0 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33251 := 1 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33252 := 2 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33253 := 3 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33254 := 4 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33255 := 5 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33256 := 6 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33257 := 7 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33258 := 8 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33259 := 9 + 5^2 \times C(F(F(3!)), 3)$$

$$33560 := 0 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33561 := 1 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33562 := 2 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33563 := 3 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33564 := 4 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33565 := 5 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33566 := 6 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33567 := 7 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33568 := 8 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33569 := 9 + F(6)! + 5 - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$36330 := 0 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36331 := 1 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36332 := 2 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36333 := 3 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36334 := 4 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36335 := 5 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36336 := 6 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36337 := 7 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36338 := 8 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36339 := 9 + F(3)! - 3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3)$$

$$36660 := 0 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36661 := 1 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36662 := 2 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36663 := 3 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36664 := 4 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36665 := 5 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36666 := 6 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36667 := 7 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36668 := 8 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$36669 := 9 + F(6)! - 6 \times F(C(6, F(3)))$$

$$37940 := 0 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37941 := 1 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37942 := 2 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37943 := 3 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37944 := 4 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37945 := 5 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37946 := 6 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37947 := 7 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37948 := 8 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$37949 := 9 - C(F(F(4)! + 9, F(7)) + F(3)!)$$

$$38040 := 0 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!)$$

$$38041 := 1 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38042 &:= 2 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38043 &:= 3 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38044 &:= 4 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38045 &:= 5 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38046 &:= 6 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38047 &:= 7 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38048 &:= 8 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \\ 38049 &:= 9 - F(4)!! + C(-0! + F(8), 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38760 &:= 0 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38761 &:= 1 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38762 &:= 2 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38763 &:= 3 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38764 &:= 4 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38765 &:= 5 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38766 &:= 6 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38767 &:= 7 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38768 &:= 8 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \\ 38769 &:= 9 + C(6 - 7 + F(8), 3!) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38880 &:= 0 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38881 &:= 1 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38882 &:= 2 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38883 &:= 3 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38884 &:= 4 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38885 &:= 5 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38886 &:= 6 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38887 &:= 7 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38888 &:= 8 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \\ 38889 &:= 9 + 8! - 8! / C(8, F(3)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 38990 &:= 0 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38991 &:= 1 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38992 &:= 2 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38993 &:= 3 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38994 &:= 4 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38995 &:= 5 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38996 &:= 6 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38997 &:= 7 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38998 &:= 8 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \\ 38999 &:= 9 + 9! / 9 - C(F(8), 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 39760 &:= 0 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39761 &:= 1 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39762 &:= 2 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39763 &:= 3 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39764 &:= 4 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39765 &:= 5 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39766 &:= 6 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39767 &:= 7 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39768 &:= 8 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \\ 39769 &:= 9 + F(6)! - C(7 + 9, 3) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 40530 &:= 0 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40531 &:= 1 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40532 &:= 2 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40533 &:= 3 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40534 &:= 4 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40535 &:= 5 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40536 &:= 6 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40537 &:= 7 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40538 &:= 8 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \\ 40539 &:= 9 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), F(F(4))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41460 &:= 0 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41461 &:= 1 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41462 &:= 2 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41463 &:= 3 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41464 &:= 4 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41465 &:= 5 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41466 &:= 6 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41467 &:= 7 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41468 &:= 8 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \\ 41469 &:= 9 + F(6)! + C(F(F(F(4)!)) - 1, F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 41860 &:= 0 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41861 &:= 1 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41862 &:= 2 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41863 &:= 3 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41864 &:= 4 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41865 &:= 5 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41866 &:= 6 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \\ 41867 &:= 7 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4)) \end{aligned}$$

$$41868 := 8 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4))$$

$$41869 := 9 + F(6)! + C(F(8) + 1, F(4))$$

$$43740 := 0 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43741 := 1 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43742 := 2 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43743 := 3 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43744 := 4 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43745 := 5 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43746 := 6 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43747 := 7 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43748 := 8 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$43749 := 9 + F(4)^7 \times C(3!, F(4))$$

$$46830 := 0 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46831 := 1 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46831 := 2 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46832 := 3 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46833 := 4 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46834 := 5 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46835 := 6 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46837 := 7 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46838 := 8 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$46839 := 9 + C(3 + 8, 6) + F(4!)$$

$$49340 := 0 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49341 := 1 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49342 := 2 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49343 := 3 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49344 := 4 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49345 := 5 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49346 := 6 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49347 := 7 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49348 := 8 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$49349 := 9 + C(4! - 3!, 9) + F(4)!!$$

$$53130 := 0 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53131 := 1 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53132 := 2 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53133 := 3 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53134 := 4 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53135 := 5 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53136 := 6 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53137 := 7 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53138 := 8 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$53139 := 9 + C((3! - 1)^{F(3)}, 5)$$

$$54360 := 0 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54361 := 1 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54362 := 2 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54363 := 3 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54364 := 4 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54365 := 5 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54366 := 6 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54367 := 7 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54368 := 8 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54369 := 9 + C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 4! + 5!$$

$$54380 := 0 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54381 := 1 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54382 := 2 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54383 := 3 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54384 := 4 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54385 := 5 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54386 := 6 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54387 := 7 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54388 := 8 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$54389 := 9 + C(F(8), 3!) - 4 + 5!$$

$$55440 := 0 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55441 := 1 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55442 := 2 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55443 := 3 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55444 := 4 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55445 := 5 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55446 := 6 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55447 := 7 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55448 := 8 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$55449 := 9 + C(F(4) + F(F(4)!), 5) \times 5!$$

$$63840 := 0 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6)$$

$$\begin{aligned} 63841 &:= 1 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63842 &:= 2 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63843 &:= 3 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63844 &:= 4 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63845 &:= 5 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63846 &:= 6 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63847 &:= 7 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63848 &:= 8 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \\ 63849 &:= 9 + F(4)! \times C(F(8), 3) \times F(6) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64630 &:= 0 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64631 &:= 1 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64632 &:= 2 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64633 &:= 3 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64634 &:= 4 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64635 &:= 5 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64636 &:= 6 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64637 &:= 7 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64638 &:= 8 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \\ 64639 &:= 9 + F(3)! + C(F(F(6)) - 4, F(6)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 64850 &:= 0 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64851 &:= 1 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64852 &:= 2 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64853 &:= 3 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64854 &:= 4 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64855 &:= 5 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64856 &:= 6 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64857 &:= 7 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64858 &:= 8 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \\ 64859 &:= 9 + 5 \times (F(F(8)) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65330 &:= 0 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65331 &:= 1 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65332 &:= 2 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65333 &:= 3 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65334 &:= 4 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65335 &:= 5 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65336 &:= 6 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65337 &:= 7 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \\ 65338 &:= 8 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6))) \end{aligned}$$

$$65339 := 9 + C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + 5! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$\begin{aligned} 65340 &:= 0 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65341 &:= 1 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65342 &:= 2 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65343 &:= 3 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65344 &:= 4 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65345 &:= 5 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65346 &:= 6 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65347 &:= 7 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65348 &:= 8 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \\ 65349 &:= 9 + F(4)! \times (-C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74380 &:= 0 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74381 &:= 1 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74382 &:= 2 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74383 &:= 3 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74384 &:= 4 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74385 &:= 5 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74386 &:= 6 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74387 &:= 7 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74388 &:= 8 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \\ 74389 &:= 9 + C(F(8) + F(F(3)), F(4)!) - F(F(7)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74480 &:= 0 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74481 &:= 1 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74482 &:= 2 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74483 &:= 3 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74484 &:= 4 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74485 &:= 5 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74486 &:= 6 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74487 &:= 7 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74488 &:= 8 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \\ 74489 &:= 9 + C(F(8), F(4)) \times F(F(4)!) \times 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 74600 &:= 0 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \\ 74601 &:= 1 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \\ 74602 &:= 2 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \\ 74603 &:= 3 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \\ 74604 &:= 4 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \\ 74605 &:= 5 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \\ 74606 &:= 6 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7) \end{aligned}$$

$$74607 := 7 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7)$$

$$74608 := 8 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7)$$

$$74609 := 9 + C(0! + F(F(6)), F(4)!) - F(7)$$

$$74620 := 0 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74621 := 1 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74622 := 2 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74623 := 3 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74624 := 4 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74625 := 5 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74626 := 6 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74627 := 7 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74628 := 8 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$74629 := 9 + C(F(2) + F(F(6)), F(4)!) + 7$$

$$75960 := 0 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75961 := 1 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75962 := 2 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75963 := 3 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75964 := 4 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75965 := 5 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75966 := 6 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75967 := 7 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75968 := 8 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$75969 := 9 - F(6)! + C(F(F(F(9-5)!)), 7)$$

$$76680 := 0 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76681 := 1 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76682 := 2 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76683 := 3 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76684 := 4 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76685 := 5 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76686 := 6 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76687 := 7 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76688 := 8 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$76689 := 9 - 8! + 6! + C(F(F(6)), 7)$$

$$83980 := 0 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83981 := 1 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83982 := 2 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83983 := 3 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83984 := 4 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83985 := 5 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83986 := 6 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83987 := 7 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83988 := 8 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

$$83989 := 9 + C(F(8), 9) \times 3! / F(8)$$

3.3.2 Non Symmetric Representations

$$24 := C(4!, F(2))$$

$$273 := (F(F(3!)) \times C(F(7), F(2)))$$

$$336 := (C(F(6), 3) \times 3!)$$

$$444 := (((F(4)!)! - C(4!, F(F(4))))$$

$$448 := (C(8, F(4)) \times F((F(4)!))$$

$$594 := (((F(4)!)! - (C(9, 5)))$$

$$0133 := (C(F(F(3!)), 3) / 10)$$

$$0209 := (C(F((9-0!)), 2) - 0!)$$

$$0278 := (- (8) + C(F(7), (2+0!)))$$

$$0286 := C(- ((F(6) - F(8))), (2+0!))$$

$$0287 := (C(F(7), F((8/2))) + 0!)$$

$$0296 := (F(6) \times (C(9, 2) + 0!))$$

$$0299 := (C((F(9) - 9), 2) - 0!)$$

$$0324 := (C((4! + 2), F(3)) - 0!)$$

$$0463 := (C((3 + F(6)), (F(4)!) + 0!)$$

$$0496 := (C((F(F(6)) - 9), 4) + 0!)$$

$$0567 := (C(F(7), F(6)) - ((5+0!)!))$$

$$0572 := (2 \times C(F(7), F((5-0!))))$$

$$0588 := (F(8) \times C(8, (5+0!)))$$

$$0594 := (((F(4)!)! - (C(9, 5) + 0))$$

$$0623 := (F(C(3!, 2)) + F((F(6) - 0!)))$$

$$0644 := (F(C((F(4)!)!, F(F(4)))) + F((F(6) + 0!)))$$

$$0748 := (C(8, F(F(4))) + ((7-0!)!))$$

$$0843 := (F(C(3!, 4)) + F(F((8-0!))))$$

$$0924 := (C(F((F(4)!)!), 2) \times (F(9) - 0!))$$

- 1331** := $(C(F(F((1 \times 3)!)), 3) + 1)$
1332 := $(F(2) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 1))$
1333 := $(C(F(F(3!)), 3) + C(3, 1))$
1334 := $(F(4) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 1))$
1335 := $(5 - (C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times (-1)))$
1336 := $(C(F(F(6)), 3) + (C(3, 1)!))$
1337 := $(7 - (C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times (-1)))$
1338 := $(C(F(8), 3) + F((C(3, 1)!)))$
1339 := $(9 - (C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times (-1)))$
1343 := $(C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) + F((3! + 1)))$
1365 := $C((5!/F(6)), (3 + 1))$
1374 := $((-4) + F(F(7))) \times (C(3, 1)!)$
1398 := $(F(-((F(8) - F(9)))) \times (C(3, 1)!))$
1436 := $((6! \times F(3)) - C(4, 1))$
1597 := $F((-7) + (C((9 - 5), 1)!))$
1737 := $(C(F(7), 3!) + F((7 + 1)))$
1944 := $((F(4))^{F(4)} \times C(9, 1))$
2024 := $C(4!, F((2 + 02)))$
2344 := $(4 \times (-4!) + F(C(3!, 2)))$
2377 := $((7! - C(F(7), 3)) / 2)$
2437 := $((C(F(7), 3!) + ((F(4)!))!) + F(2))$
2474 := $((F((F(4)!)) \times F(F(7))) + F(C((F(4)!), 2)))$
2484 := $((F(4!) / F(8)) + C(4!, 2))$
2492 := $(F((2 + 9)) \times C(F((F(4)!), 2))$
2497 := $(F(7) + (9 \times C(4!, 2)))$
2634 := $(C(4!, 3) + F(C(6, 2)))$
2744 := $(C(4!, F(4)) + ((7 - F(2)))!)$
3003 := $C((F((3! + 0!)) + 0!), 3!)$
3248 := $(C((F(8) + F((F(4)!)), 2) \times F(3!))$
3284 := $(F((F(4)!)) + C(C(8, 2), 3))$
3355 := $(-5) + (5! \times C(F(3!), F(3)))$
3416 := $(61 \times C(F((F(4)!), 3))$
3432 := $(2 \times C(F((3 + 4)), 3!))$
3438 := $(-8!) + C((3! \times F(4)), F(3!))$
3447 := $(C(F(7), F((F(4)!)) + (F(4) \times 3!))$
3464 := $((F(F(4)) \times 6!) + (C(4!, 3)))$
3477 := $((7! - F(F(7))) - C(F(F((F(4)!)), 3))$
3633 := $(-((F(F(3!)) - C((F(3!) + F(F(6))), 3)))$
3647 := $(-F(7) + ((F(4)! \times F(C(6, F(3))))))$
3656 := $((6! \times 5) + C(F(6), 3))$
3747 := $((7! - (F(4)!)) - C(F(7), F(3!)))$
3753 := $((F(3) + (5!))! - C(F(7), F(3!)))$
3837 := $((C(F(7), F(3!)) - 8) \times 3)$
3844 := $((C(F((F(4)!), 4) - 8)^{F(3)})$
4391 := $(F(19) + C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4))))$
4431 := $((1 + C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4)))) \times F(F((F(4)!)))$
4536 := $(F(F(6)) \times (C(3!, 5)^{F(4)}))$
4544 := $(C(4!, F(4)) - (-5!) \times F(F((F(4)!))))$
4648 := $((C(F(8), (F(4)!)) - (F(6)!)) / F(4))$
4728 := $((C(F(8), 2) - F(7)) \times 4!)$
4754 := $((F(F(4)) + (5!))! - (C(F(7), F(4))))$
4795 := $((5! \times F(9)) + C(F(7), 4))$
4824 := $(-((F(F((F(4)!)) - (C(-((F(2) - F(8))), 4))))$
4837 := $((F(F(7)) \times F(F(3!))) - C(8, F(4)))$
4877 := $((7! - F(F(7))) + C(8, 4))$
4914 := $((F(4)! + 1)! - C(9, 4))$
5844 := $(C(F(F((F(4)!)), 4) - (F(8) + 5!))$
5964 := $(-((F(F((F(4)!)) - (C(F(F(6)), (9 - 5))))$
5985 := $C(F(F((-((5 - 8)!)), (9 - 5))$
6046 := $(F(C(6, F(4))) + (0! - 6!))$
6327 := $(7! + C(F((F(2) + 3!)), F(6)))$
6344 := $(C(4!, F(4)) + (3! \times 6!))$
6427 := $(C((F(7) + 2), F((F(4)!)) - F(6))$
6433 := $(-((F(3) - C(C(3!, 4), F(6))))$
6434 := $(-((F(F(F(4))) - (C(C(3!, 4), F(6))))$
6443 := $(F(3!) + C(C((F(4)!), F(F(4))), F(6)))$
6524 := $(C(F((F(4)!), 2) \times F((5 + F(6))))$
6669 := $(C(9, F(6)) \times (6! + F(F(6))))$
6777 := $((C(F(7), 7) + 7!) + F(F(6)))$
6885 := $(5! + F(-((8 - C(8, 6))))$
7064 := $(C(4!, F(F(6))) + (07)!)$
7237 := $((F(7)^{C(3, 2)} + 7!)$
7244 := $((F(4)! - (C(F((F(4)!), 2) \times (-F(F(7))))$
7488 := $((8! / C(8, 4)) \times F(7))$
7624 := $(F((C(F(4), F(2)) \times 6) + (7!))$
7764 := $((F(4!) - (F(6)!)) + C(F(7), 7))$
8372 := $((-2) \times C(F(7), F(3!)) + F(F(8)))$
8475 := $(5 \times (C(F(7), (F(4)!)) - (F(8))))$
8546 := $(-((C(6, F(4)) \times 5!)) + F(F(8)))$
8944 := $(-((C(((F(4)! + F((F(4)!)), 9) - F(F(8))))$

- 00124** := $(C(4!, F(2)) + 100)$
00197 := $-((F(7) - C(F((9-1))), (0! + 0!)))$
00218 := $(8 + C(F(F(((1+2)!))), (0! + 0!)))$
00219 := $(9 + C(F(F(((1+2)!))), (0! + 0!)))$
00275 := $(5 \times C((F(7) - 2), (0! + 0!)))$
00278 := $(- (8) + C(F(7), (2 + (00)!)))$
00286 := $C(-((F(6) - F(8))), (2 + (00)!))$
00287 := $(C(F(7), F((8/2))) + (00!))$
00296 := $(F(6) \times (C(9, 2) + (00)!))$
00315 := $(F(F((5+1))) \times C(3!, (0! + 0!)))$
00324 := $(C(4!, F(2)) + 300)$
00327 := $((C((F(7) \times 2), F(3)) + 0!) + 0!)$
00345 := $((5! \times F(4)) - C(3!, (0! + 0!)))$
00351 := $C((F(-((1-5))^3), (0! + 0!))$
00394 := $((4! \times (-9)) + F(C(3!, (0! + 0!))))$
00426 := $((C(F(F(6)), 2) + F(4)) \times (0! + 0!))$
00453 := $((C((3 \times 5), F(4)) - 0!) - 0!)$
00463 := $(C((3 + F(6)), (4 + 0!)) + 0!)$
00524 := $(C(4!, F(2)) + (500))$
00561 := $(C(16, F((5-0!))) + 0!)$
00567 := $(C(F(7), F(6)) - ((5 + (00)!)))$
00568 := $(8 \times (C(F(6), (5-0!)) + 0!))$
00572 := $(2 \times C(F(7), ((5-0!) - 0!))$
00573 := $((F(3) \times C(F(7), F((5-0!)))) + 0!)$
00597 := $((C(F(7), 9) - 5!) + 0!) + 0!)$
00623 := $(F((3! + F(2))) + F(C(6, (0! + 0!))))$
00643 := $((F(C(3!, 4)) + F((F(6) + 0!))) - 0!)$
00675 := $((5 \times F(7)) + F(C(6, (0! + 0!))))$
00724 := $(C(4!, F(2)) + (700))$
00748 := $(C(8, F(F(4))) + ((7 - (00)!)))$
00794 := $((C((F(4) + 9), 7) + 0!) + 0!)$
00798 := $(F(8) \times ((C(9, 7) + 0!) + 0!))$
00824 := $(C(4!, F(2)) + 800)$
00842 := $(2 + (4 \times C(F(8), (0! + 0!))))$
00843 := $(3 + (4 \times C(F(8), (0! + 0!))))$
00923 := $((C(F(3!), 2) \times (F(9) - 0!)) - 0!)$
00924 := $(C(4!, F(2)) + 900)$
00935 := $((F(C(5, 3)) \times F(9)) / (0! + 0!))$
01157 := $(F(7) \times F((C(5, (1+1)) + 0!)))$
01236 := $((F(6) + F(C(3!, 2))) \times (1 + 0!))$
01244 := $(4! + (F(C((F(4)!), 2)) \times (1 + 0!)))$
01255 := $((5! \times C(5, 2)) + F(10))$
01275 := $(5! - (- (C(7, 2)) \times F(10)))$
01279 := $(- (9) + (C(F(7), F(((2+1)!)) + 0!))$
01288 := $(C((- (8) + F(8)), F(((2+1)!)) + 0!)$
01328 := $((C(C(F(8), F(2)), 3) - 1) - 0!)$
01332 := $((C(F((2^3)), 3) + 1) + 0!)$
01333 := $((3 + 3!) + F(C(3!, (1 + 0!))))$
01335 := $(F((5 + 3!)) \times C(3!, (1 + 0!)))$
01337 := $((7 + 3!) + F(C(3!, (1 + 0!))))$
01339 := $((9^3) + F(C(3!, (1 + 0!))))$
01341 := $(1 + (C(F(F((F(4)!)), 3) + 10))$
01346 := $(C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + (3! + 10))$
01348 := $((C(F(8), F(4)) + F(3!)) + 10)$
01349 := $(9 + (C(F(F((F(4)!)), 3) + 10))$
01364 := $(F((4! + (6))) / F(C(3!, (1 + 0!))))$
01365 := $C((5! / F(6)), ((3 + 1) + 0))$
01436 := $((6! \times F(3)) - (C(4, 1) + 0))$
01456 := $(C(F(6), 5) \times ((4! + 1) + 0!))$
01464 := $((4! \times F(C(6, 4))) / 10)$
01468 := $((F(8) \times C(F(6), 4)) - (1 + 0!))$
01541 := $(C((1 + F(F((F(4)!))), F((5-1))) + 0!)$
01664 := $(C(4!, F(F(6))) + (6! / (- (1) - 0!)))$
01706 := $(C(F((F(6) - 0!)), 7) - 10)$
01726 := $((6! \times 2) + C(F(7), 10))$
01734 := $((F(4)!) \times (3 + C(F(7), 10)))$
01737 := $(C(F(7), 3!) + F(((7+1) + 0)))$
01849 := $((C(9, F(4)) \times (F(8) + 1)) + 0!)$
01894 := $(4! + (F(C(9, 8)) \times F(10)))$
01979 := $((C(9, 7) \times F((9+1))) - 0!)$
02037 := $(F(7) + C(((3+0)!), (2+0!)))$
02044 := $(C(4!, F(4)) - (0 - 20))$
02046 := $(F(F(6)) + ((C(4!, (0! + 2)) + 0!)))$
02144 := $(C(4!, F(4)) + (120))$
02244 := $(C(4!, F(4)) + (220))$
02257 := $(F(F(7)) + C(((5 - F(2))!), (2 + 0!)))$
02275 := $(5 \times C((F(7) + 2), (2 + 0!)))$
02288 := $(8 \times C(F((8 - F(2))), (2 + 0!)))$
02299 := $(C((F(9) - 9), F((2 + 2))) - 0!)$

- 02311** := ((11 × C(F(F(3!)), 2)) + 0!)
02344 := (C(4!, F(4)) + 320)
02349 := ((9^{F(F(4))}) × (C(F(3!), 2) + 0!))
02377 := ((7! - C(F(7), 3)) / (2 + 0))
02379 := ((F(9) × (C(7, 3) × 2)) - 0!)
02384 := (C(4!, F(8)) + (3! / (2 + 0)))
02434 := ((4 × F(C(3!, 4))) - ((2 + 0)!))
02437 := ((C(F(7), 3!) + (C(4, 2))!) + 0!)
02443 := ((F(C(3!, 4)) × 4) + (2 + 0!))
02444 := (C(4!, F(4)) + 420)
02446 := ((F(C(6, 4)) × 4) + ((2 + 0)!))
02483 := (((F(F(3)) + 8) × C(4!, 2)) - 0!)
02484 := ((F(4!) / F(8)) + (C(4!, (2 + 0))))
02492 := -((F(2) - (9 × (C(4!, 2) + 0!)))
02493 := (F(F(3)) × (9 × (C(4!, 2) + 0!)))
02496 := (F(F(6)) + (9 × (C(4!, 2) - 0!)))
02497 := (F(7) + (9 × C(4!, (2 + 0))))
02499 := (F(9) - C(9, F(4)))² - 0!
02544 := (C(4!, F(4)) + 520)
02554 := ((F(F(F(4)!)) × 5!) + F((C(5, 2) - 0!)))
02571 := (((-1) + C(F(7), 5)) × 2) - 0!
02572 := (2 × (C(F(7), 5) - ((2 × 0)!))
02634 := (C(4!, 3) + F((C(6, 2) + 0)))
02644 := (C(4!, F(4)) + (620))
02649 := ((C(9, 4) × F(F(6))) + (2 + 0!))
02659 := ((95 × C(F(6), 2)) - 0!)
02664 := (4! × ((6! - F(C(6, 2))) + 0!))
02668 := (-F(8) + (((F(6))! / C(6, 2)) + 0!))
02674 := (F(F(4)) × (7 + C(F(F(6)), (2 + 0!))))
02717 := (F(7) × (C(F((1 + 7)), 2) - 0!))
02744 := (C(4!, F(4)) + (720))
02797 := ((F(F(7)) × (-9 - C(7, 2))) + 0!)
02835 := ((5 × F(F(3!))) × (C(8, 2) - 0!))
02844 := (C(4!, F(4)) + 820)
02933 := (F(3!) + C((3 × 9), (2 + 0!)))
02939 := ((C(9, 3) × (F(9) + F(2))) - 0!)
02944 := (C(4!, F(4)) + 920)
03004 := (C((F((F(4)! + 0!) + 0!), 3!) + 0!)
03082 := (2 × (C((F(8) + 0!), 3) + 0!))
03248 := (((C(8, F(4)) + F(2))^{F(3)}) - 0!)
03256 := ((C(F(6), 5)²) + ((3! - 0)!))
03257 := (F(F(7)) + ((F(C(5, 2))^{F(3)}) - 0!))
03275 := (C(C((-5) + F(7)), 2, 3) - 0!)
03284 := (F((F(4))!) + (C(C(8, 2), 3) + 0))
03325 := ((-F(C(5, 2))) + 3!) × (3! - 0!)
03353 := (-3!) + ((5! × C(F(3!), F(3))) - 0!)
03366 := (6 × (C((F(6) × F(3)), 3) + 0!))
03367 := (-7) + ((C(6, F(3))³) - 0!))
03377 := (((7! + C(F(7), 3!)) / F(3)) - 0!)
03392 := (-F(2)) + (9 × F((C(3!, F(3)) - 0!)))
03393 := ((F(F(3)) × 9) × F((C(3!, F(3)) - 0!)))
03395 := (5! + (C((F(9) - 3!), 3) - 0!))
03423 := (3 × (C((-F(2)) + F(F((F(4)!))), 3) + 0!))
03463 := ((F(3) × 6!) + (C(4!, 3) - 0!))
03466 := ((F(F(6)) × C((F(6) + F(4)), 3)) + 0!)
03472 := (2 × ((C(F(7), (F(4))!) + F(F(3!))) - 0!))
03583 := (((F(3!) × C(8, 5)) × F(3!)) - 0!)
03623 := (((F(C(3!, 2)) - 6) × 3!) - 0!)
03646 := (6! + (C(((F(4))! + F(F(6))), 3) + 0!))
03656 := ((6! × 5) + C(F(6), (3 + 0)))
03661 := (((1 × 6) × F(C(6, F(3)))) + 0!)
03662 := (F(2) + ((6 × F(C(6, F(3)))) + 0!))
03689 := (F(9) + (C((F(8) + F(6)), 3) + 0!))
03717 := ((F(7) × C(F((1 × 7)), 3)) - 0!)
03752 := (((2 + 5)! - (C(F(7), F(3!)) + 0!))
03753 := (((F(3) + (5))!) - (C(F(7), (3! - 0!))))
03787 := (-((C(F(7), 8) - 7!)) + F((F(3!) + 0!)))
03795 := ((5! × F(9)) - (C(F(7), 3) - 0!))
03843 := (((C(F(3!), 4) - 8)^{F(3)}) - 0!)
03857 := ((F(7) + 5!) × (C(8, F(3)) + 0!))
03862 := ((C(F((F(2) + (6))), 8) × 3) + 0!)
03873 := (3 × ((C(F(7), 8) + 3) + 0!))
03874 := (((-4) - C(F(7), 8)) × (-3)) + 0!)
03875 := (((-5) - C(F(7), 8)) × (-3)) - 0!)
03995 := (((5! × F(9)) - (C(9, 3))) - 0!)
04235 := ((-5) + F(C(3!, 2))) × ((F(4))! + 0!)
04238 := ((C(8, 3) + F((-2) + F(F((F(4)!)))) + 0!)
04263 := -(((F(F(3)) - (F(C(6, 2)))) × ((F(4))! + 0!))
04264 := -(((F(4))! + (-F(C(6, 2))) × ((F(4))! + 0!))
04265 := (-5) - (-F(C(6, 2))) × ((F(4))! + 0!))

- 04277** := $(F(7) \times (C((F(7) - 2), 4) - 0!))$
04296 := $(6 \times (C(F((9 - 2)), 4) + 0!))$
04297 := $((((C(F(7), 9) + F(2)) \times (F(4))!) + 0!))$
04319 := $((((C(9, 1) - 3))! \times (F(4))!) - 0!)$
04376 := $(F(6) + C((F(7) + 3), (4 + 0!)))$
04389 := $(- (F((9 + 8))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + 0!))$
04391 := $(F(19) - (C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4))) \times (-0!)))$
04397 := $((((7! - F(9)) - F(C(3!, 4))) + 0!)$
04415 := $(- ((C(5, 1)^4)) + (((F(4))! + 0!))!)$
04423 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 2) \times F(F((F(4))!))) + F(((F(4))! + 0!)))$
04425 := $(- (F(C(5, 2))) + ((F((F(4))!))! / (F((F(4))! + 0!)))$
04426 := $(- ((F(C(6, 2)) + (4))) + (((F(4))! + 0!))!)$
04431 := $((1 - F(C(3!, 4))) + (((F(4))! + 0!))!)$
04432 := $((2 \times F(3!)) \times (C(4!, F(F(4))) + 0!))$
04661 := $((F(F((1 + 6))) \times C(6, F(4))) + 0!)$
04677 := $(7! - (C((-7) + F(F(6))), F(4)) - 0!)$
04692 := $((2 \times F(9)) \times (C(F(6), 4) - 0!))$
04728 := $((C(F(8), 2) - F(7)) \times ((4 + 0!)))$
04754 := $((((F(F(4)) + (5)))! - C(F(7), F((4 + 0))))$
04795 := $((5! \times F(9)) + C(F(7), (4 + 0)))$
04823 := $(- ((F(F(3!)) - (C(-((F(2) - F(8))), 4) - 0!)))$
04831 := $((((1 + 3!))! - (C(F(8), F(F(4))) - 0!))$
04877 := $((7! - F(F(7))) + (C(8, 4) + 0))$
04965 := $(C((5! / F(6)), 9) - 40)$
04996 := $((C((6 + 9), 9) - F((F(4))!)) - 0!)$
05144 := $(4 \times (C(F(((F(4))! + 1)), 5) - 0!))$
05147 := $((C(F(7), (F(4))!) \times F(-((1 - 5)))) - 0!)$
05244 := $(C(4!, F(F(4))) \times (-2) + F(F((5 + 0!))))$
05266 := $(- (6!) + (C(F(F(6)), -((F(2) - (5)))) + 0!))$
05293 := $((F(F(3!)) \times C((9 + F(2)), 5)) + 0!)$
05401 := $((C(10, F(F(4))) \times 5!) + 0!)$
05434 := $(- ((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 3) - (F((4 \times 5)) - 0!)))$
05435 := $(F((5! / 3!)) - C(F(F((F(4))!)), F((5 - 0!))))$
05469 := $((9 \times F(C(6, 4))) - F(F((5 + 0!))))$
05674 := $((4! + 7!) + F(C(6, (5 - 0!))))$
05748 := $((C(F(8), 4) - F(F(7))) - (5 - 0!))$
05776 := $(F(6) \times (7 + C(F(7), (5 - 0!))))$
05794 := $((F(4!) / (-9)) + F((C(7, 5) + 0)))$
05837 := $(F(7) \times ((F(3!) \times C(8, 5)) + 0!))$
05838 := $(- ((C(F(8), F(3)) + 8!)) + F(((5 - 0!))!))$
05849 := $((F(9) \times (-4)) + C(F(8), (5 - 0!)))$
05865 := $(- (5!) + C(F(F(6)), ((8 - 5) + 0!)))$
05878 := $(F(F(8)) - ((7! + C(8, (5 + 0!))))$
05948 := $((C(F(8), 4) - F(9)) - F((5 - 0!)))$
05963 := $(- ((F(F(3!)) - (C(F(F(6)), (9 - 5)) - 0!)))$
05982 := $(- (2) + (C(F(8), (9 - 5)) - 0!))$
05983 := $(- (3) + (C(F(8), (9 - 5)) + 0!))$
05985 := $(C((-((5 + 8)) + F(9)), (5 - 0!))$
05986 := $(C(F(F(6)), (8 + 9)) + ((5 \times 0!))$
05988 := $(C(F(8), (8 + 9)) + F((5 - 0!)))$
06043 := $(F(C(3!, F(4))) - (((0! + 6!) + 0!)))$
06046 := $(C(F(F(6)), 4) + (0! + (60)))$
06297 := $((F(7) \times (-C(9, 2))) + F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
06299 := $((C((F(9) - 9), 2) \times F(F(6))) - 0!)$
06325 := $((- (F(C(5, 2))) \times F(3!)) + F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
06344 := $(C(4!, F(4)) + (3! \times ((6 + 0!))!))$
06359 := $(- (C((F(9) - 5), F(3))) + F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
06375 := $((5 \times C(F(7), F(3!))) - 60)$
06376 := $(F(6) \times ((C(F(7), F(3)) + 6!) - 0!))$
06432 := $(- (2) + (C(C(3!, 4), F(6)) - 0!))$
06433 := $(- (3) + (C(C(3!, 4), F(6)) + 0!))$
06434 := $(C((F(4) + (3 \times 4)), F(6)) - 0!)$
06436 := $(C((F(6) + (3 + 4)), F(6)) + 0!)$
06447 := $(F(7) + (C(C((F(4))!, F(F(4))), F(6)) - 0!))$
06523 := $((C(F(3!), 2) \times F((5 + F(6)))) - 0!)$
06533 := $((F(C(3!, 3)) - F((5 + F(6)))) + 0!)$
06545 := $(F(C(5, F(4))) \times (5! - ((6 \times 0!))!))$
06627 := $(F(C(7, 2)) - ((6! \times 6) - 0!))$
06646 := $(F(C(6, F(4))) - ((6! / 6) - 0!))$
06681 := $(- (C((1 + 8), 6)) + F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
06729 := $(- (C(9, 2)) + F(((F(7) + (6)) + 0!)))$
06743 := $(F(C(3!, F(4))) - ((F(7) + F(6)) + 0!))$
06747 := $(C(F(7), (F(4))!) + (((7! - F(6)) - 0!)))$
06756 := $(C((F(6) + (5)), 7) + ((F(6) - 0!))!)$
06778 := $((F(8) + 7!) + (C(F(7), 6) + 0!))$
06784 := $((4! \times C(F(8), F(7))) / 6! + 0!)$
06833 := $(F(C(3!, 3)) + (8 + 60))$
06849 := $(C(9, F(4)) + F((F(8) - ((6 \times 0!))!)))$
06997 := $((F(F(7)) - C(9, 9)) + F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))$
06998 := $(F(F((8 - C(9, 9)))) + F((F(F(6)) - 0!)))$

- 07064** := $(C(4!, F(F(6))) + ((07 + 0)!))$
07143 := $((F(C(3!, F(4))) + 1) + F((F(7) + 0)!))$
07233 := $(F(C(3!, 3)) - (-2) \times (F(F(7)) + 0!))$
07237 := $((F(7)^{C(3,2)} + ((7 + 0)!))$
07243 := $(3!! + ((C(F((F(4))!), 2) \times F(F(7))) - 0!))$
07244 := $((F(4))!) + (C(F((F(4))!), 2) \times F(F((7 + 0))))$
07267 := $(F(7) \times (C((F(6) \times 2), F(7)) - 0!))$
07314 := $(C((F(F(F(4))!)) + 1), -((3 - 7))) - 0!$
07316 := $(C((F(F(6)) + 1), -((3 - 7))) + 0!$
07332 := $((F(2) + F(C(3!, F(3)))) \times (F(7) - 0!))$
07437 := $((C(F(7), 3!) / F(4)) \times F(7)) + 0!$
07488 := $((8! / C(8, 4)) \times F((7 + 0)))$
07546 := $(C(F(F(6)), 4) + ((5! \times F(7)) + 0!))$
07623 := $((F((C(3, 2) \times 6)) + 7!) - 0!)$
07624 := $(F((C(F(4), F(2)) \times 6)) + ((7 + 0)!))$
07643 := $((C(F(3!), F(F(4))) \times F(F(6))) \times F(7)) - 0!$
07716 := $(-6) \times (1 - C(F(7), (7 + 0)!))$
07722 := $((F((2 + 2)))! \times C(F(7), (7 + 0)!))$
07734 := $((F(4))! \times (F(3) + C(F(7), (7 + 0)!)))$
07738 := $((C(F(8), 3!) / 7) - F(7)) - 0!$
07743 := $(F(F(3!)) + ((F(4))! \times C(F(7), (7 + 0)!)))$
07746 := $(-6) \times (-4 - C(F(7), (7 + 0)!))$
07764 := $((F(4!) - (F(6))!) + C(F(7), (7 + 0)))$
07766 := $((C(F(F(6)), 6) / 7) + (F(7) + 0!))$
07784 := $((C(4!, F(8)) + 7!) + ((7 - 0)!))$
07889 := $((F(9) \times (-C(8, 8)) + F(F(7))) + 0!)$
07894 := $((F(4))! + (F(C(9, 8)) \times (F(F(7)) - 0!)))$
07944 := $(4! \times (C((F(F(4)) + 9), 7) + 0!))$
07955 := $(-C(5, 5)) - (-F(9) \times (F(F(7)) + 0!))$
07986 := $(6 \times (C(F(8), F((-9) + F(7))) + 0!))$
08248 := $(C(8, F(4)) + (2^{F(8-0!)}))$
08345 := $(-((C((5 + F(F((F(4))!))), 3) - ((F(F(8)) - 0!))))$
08372 := $((-2) \times C(F(7), F(3!)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-0!)))$
08394 := $((F(4))! + (C(9, F(3)) \times F(F((8 - 0!))))$
08398 := $(C(F(8), 9) / (F(F(3)) + F((8 + 0!))))$
08472 := $((2 \times C(F(7), (F(4))!)) + ((8 - 0)!))$
08473 := $(-((F(3!) - (C(F(7), (F(4))!) + F((F(8) - 0!))))$
08477 := $((C(F(7), 7) - 4) + F((F(8) - 0!)))$
08496 := $((F(6))! - C((9 \times F(F(4))), (8 - 0!)))$
08546 := $((C((-6) + 4!), 5) - F(8)) - 0!$
08548 := $((C((F(8) - F(4)), 5) - F(8)) + 0!)$
08574 := $((F(4))! + C((F(7) + 5), F((8 - 0!))))$
08575 := $((C((5 + F(7)), 5) + 8) - 0!)$
08679 := $((9 \times C(F(7), 6)) - F((F(8) - 0!)))$
08777 := $(-((F(F(7)) - ((7 \times C(F(7), 8)) + 0!)))$
08943 := $(-((C((F(3!) + (F(4))!), 9) - F(F(8))) + 0!))$
09266 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(F(6)), 2) \times (9 - 0!)))$
09324 := $((-C(4!, 2) + 3!) \times F((9 - 0!)))$
09349 := $((F(9) \times C(4!, F(3))) - (F(9) + 0!))$
09355 := $(5 \times ((F(C(5, 3)) \times F(9)) + 0!))$
09372 := $((-2) + C(F(7), 3)) \times (F(9) - 0!)$
09383 := $((C((3 \times 8), F(3)) \times F(9)) - 0!)$
09403 := $(C(F(F(3!)), (0! + 4)) - F(F((9 - 0!))))$
09404 := $((C((F(F((F(4))!) + 0!), F((F(4))!)) / F(9)) - 0!)$
09406 := $(-C((F(F(6)) + 0!), F(4)) + F(F((9 - 0!))))$
09437 := $((C(F(7), 3) \times (4! + 9)) - 0!)$
09438 := $(C(F((F(8) / 3)), F(4)) \times (F(9) - 0!))$
09445 := $(-5) \times ((C(F(F((F(4))!)), F(F(4))) \times (-9)) + 0!)$
09471 := $((1 + C(F(7), F(4))) \times (F(9) - 0!))$
09684 := $(-((F(4))! + (-C(F(8), F(6)) / F((9 - 0!))))$
09685 := $(-5) - (-C(F(8), F(6)) / F((9 - 0!)))$
09845 := $(-5) \times (-C(4!, F(8)) + F((9 + 0!)))$
10227 := $((F(C(7, 2)) - ((2 + 0)!))! + 1)$
10246 := $((F(F(F(6))) - ((F(4))!) + C(20, 1))$
10333 := $(F(F(F(3!))) - (3 + F(C(3!, (0! + 1))))$
10338 := $((F(F(8)) + F(3)) - F(C(3!, (0! + 1))))$
10374 := $(F(F(F((F(4))!)) - (C(F(7), 3) \times (0! + 1)))$
10437 := $((-F(F(7))) + F(F(F(3!))) - (C(4!, (0! + 1))))$
10456 := $((F(F(F(6))) + 5!) - F(C((F(4))!, (0! + 1))))$
10625 := $(C(((5 - F(2))!), (F(F(6)) - 0!)) - 1)$
10638 := $((C(F(8), 3) \times F(6)) - 0!) - 1)$
10646 := $(F(F(6)) + (C(4!, (F(F(6)) - 0!)) - 1))$
10648 := $(F(8) + (C(4!, (F(F(6)) - 0!)) + 1))$
10673 := $((F(F(3!)) \times (-F(7))) + F(F(F(C(6, 01))))$
10734 := $((F(F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(3!))) - F(F(C(7, 01))))$
10825 := $(-((5! + F(2))) + F(F(C(8, 01))))$
10854 := $(F(F(F((F(4))!)) - (5! - C(8, (0! + 1))))$
10918 := $(F(F(8)) - C(-((1 - 9)), (0! + 1)))$
10956 := $(F(F(F(6))) + C(5, ((9 \times 0)! + 1)))$

- 10957** := (((F(C(7,5)) + 9) + 0!) + 1)
11136 := (F(F(F(6))) + C((F(F(3!)) - 1), (1 + 1)))
11246 := (F(F(F(6))) + C((4! + F(2)), (1 + 1)))
11497 := (((F(7)!)/(-9!)) + F((4! - C(1,1))))
11638 := ((F(F(8)) + 3!) - C(F(6), (1 + 1)))
11643 := (((3! - 4!) + F(F(F(6)))) + C(1,1))
11665 := (((5! × 6) + F(F(F(6)))) - C(1,1))
11666 := (6! + F((6 + C(6, (1 + 1)))))
11667 := (F((F(7) + F(6))) + (6! + C(1,1)))
11674 := (((((F(4)! + 7) + F(F(F(6)))) + C(1,1)))
11678 := (F(F(8)) + ((F(7) + 6!) - C(1,1)))
11686 := ((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) + (6! - C(1,1)))
11694 := (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (F(9) × (F(F(6)) + C(1,1))))
11744 := (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (((F(4)! + C(F(7), (1 + 1))))))
11933 := (F((F(3) × F(3!)) + F(F(C((9 - 1), 1))))
12086 := (F(F(F(6))) + C((F(8) - 0!), (2 + 1)))
12144 := (C(4!, F(4)) × (((1 × 2) + 1)!))
12233 := (F(F(F(3!))) + C(F((3! + F(2))), F(((2 + 1)!)))
12368 := ((- (F(8)) × (F(F(6)) - F(C(3!, 2)))) - 1)
12376 := C(((F(6) + (7)) + F(3)), ((2 + 1)!))
12417 := -((F(F(7)) - C((1 + 4!), 21))
12437 := (((F(F(7)) + C(F(F(3!)), 4)) × 2) + 1)
12536 := -F(6) + (F(3!) - 5!)^{C(2,1)}
12546 := (F(F(F(6))) + (F((F(4)! × 5)^{C(2,1)}))
12558 := (F(8) × ((5! × 5) - C(2,1)))
12574 := -F(F(4)!) + (F(F(7)) × (F(C(5,2)) - 1))
12634 := (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (F(3!) × (C(F(F(6)), 2) + 1)))
12637 := -((F(F(7)) - C((F(3) × F(6)), F(((2 + 1)!))))
12642 := (C((F(2) + 4!), F(F(6))) - F(((2 + 1)!))
12643 := -(((F(F(3!)) × (F((F(4)! - F(C(6,2)))) - 1))
12644 := -(((F(4)! - C((4 + F(F(6))), 21))
12663 := (F(F(3!)) × ((- (6) + F(C(6,2))) - 1))
12862 := (C((2 × F(6)), 8) - F(((2 + 1)!))
12864 := (C((4! - F(6)), 8) - ((2 + 1)!))
12865 := (- (5) + C((F(6) + 8), F(((2 + 1)!)))
12866 := (((F(6)!)/F(F(6))) + F(F(C(8, (2 - 1))))
12924 := (((F(4)! - 2) × C((9 × 2), 1))
12942 := ((- (F(2)) + ((F(4)!)) × C((9 × 2), 1))
12948 := (C((8 + (F(4)!), 9) + F(21))
12996 := (((6!/9) + F(9))^{C(2,1)})
13048 := (C(8, F(4)) × F(F((0! + (C(3,1)!))))
13122 := 2 × (2 + 1)^F(C(3,1)!)
13133 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (3^{1+C(3,1)!}})
13143 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (F(((F(4)! + 1))^{C(3,1)}}))
13154 := ((F(4)!/F(F((5 + 1)))) + F(F(F((C(3,1)!))))
13207 := (- (F(F(7))) + ((F(((0! + 2)!)))/C(3,1)))
13233 := (3 × ((C(F(F(3!)), 2) × F(F(3!))) + 1))
13243 := ((F(F(3!)) + F(C(F((F(4)!), 2))) / ((3 + 1)!))
13246 := (F(F(F(6))) + C((4! + F(2)), C(3,1)))
13297 := (- ((F(F(7)) - F((9 × 2))) + F(F(F((C(3,1)!))))
13301 := ((10 × C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 1)
13326 := (F((F(F(6)) - F(2))) + (3^{F(C(3,1)!}}))
13338 := ((F(8) + 3!) × (3 × (C(3,1)!))
13342 := (((2 × 4!) / (F(F(3!))) - F(F(F((C(3,1)!))))
13346 := (F(F(F(6))) + (C((F(4)!), 3) × ((3! - 1)!))
13348 := ((8! - C(4!, F(3))) / C(3,1))
13364 := (C((- (4) + F(F(6))), F(3!)) - F(F(F((C(3,1)!))))
13375 := ((- (5) × F(7)) + ((F(3)!)/C(3,1)))
13376 := (- ((F(6) + (7!/(-3))) × F((C(3,1)!))
13384 := (((F((F(4)! × (-F(8))) + (F(3)!)/C(3,1))
13386 := ((6! - C(F(8), 3!)) / (- (3 + 1)))
13394 := (((4! × F(9)) × 3) + F(F(F((C(3,1)!))))
13395 := (- ((5 × 9) + ((F(3)!)/C(3,1)))
13419 := (((9 - 1)!/F(4)) - F(F((C(3,1)!)))
13424 := (((4! × 2) - (F((F(4)!)))/(-C(3,1)))
13426 := (((F(F(6)) × 2) - (F((F(4)!)))/(-C(3,1)))
13429 := (((F(9) - F(2)) - (F((F(4)!)))/(-C(3,1)))
13434 := (((4!/3)!/F(4)) - (C(3,1)!))
13436 := (((F(6)!)/3) - C(C(4,3), 1))
13437 := (((- (7!) × F(3!)) / (-F(4))) - C(3,1))
13461 := (((F((1 × 6)!)/F(4)) + F(F((C(3,1)!)))
13475 := ((5 × 7) + ((F((F(4)!)))/C(3,1)))
13479 := (((9 × F(7)) + (F((F(4)!)))/C(3,1))
13488 := ((8! + F((8 + 4))) / C(3,1))
13496 := (F(F(F(6))) + (- (F(9)) + F((4! - (C(3,1)!))))
13542 := (2 × (F((4 × 5)) + (C(3,1)!))
13552 := (- ((F(2) + 5!) × (- (5!) + F((C(3,1)!)))
13582 := ((- (2) + C(F(8), 5)) - F((F(F(3!)) - 1)))
13593 := (F(F(F(3!))) + ((C(9,5) × F(F(3!))) + 1))
13623 := ((F(F(3!)) - 2) × (6! - C(3,1)))

- 13633** := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (((F(3!))/C(6, F(3))) - 1))$
13636 := $(C(F(6), F(3)) \times (6! - F(F((3! + 1))))$
13637 := $((F(F(7)) - 3!) \times (-C(F(6), F(3)))) + 1$
13656 := $((6! + F((-5) + F(F(6)))) \times F((C(3, 1)!))$
13674 := $((F(4)! + F(7)) \times 6!) - (C(3, 1)!)$
13675 := $(-5) + ((F(7) + 6)) \times ((C(3, 1)!))$
13692 := $((-2) \times F(9) + 6!) \times F(F((C(3, 1)!))$
13724 := $(-4) \times ((-2) \times C(F(7), 3!)) + 1$
13726 := $((62 \times F(F(7))) - ((C(3, 1)!))$
13727 := $((7 + F(2)) \times C(F(7), 3!)) - 1$
13728 := $(8 \times C((F(2) \times F(7)), (C(3, 1)!))$
13729 := $((9 - F(2)) \times C(F(7), 3!)) + 1$
13733 := $(3! - ((F(3!) \times (-C(F(7), 3!))) + 1))$
13736 := $(F(6) \times (C((3! + 7), 3!) + 1))$
13742 := $((2 \times (F(4)!)) \times F(F(7))) + F(F(F((C(3, 1)!)))$
13743 := $((F(3!) \times (F(F(4)) + C(F(7), 3!))) - 1$
13744 := $(F((F(4)!)) \times (F(4) + (C(F(7), 3!) - 1)))$
13768 := $(8 \times (6 + (C(F(7), 3!) - 1)))$
13776 := $(F(6) \times (C(F(7), 7) + (C(3, 1)!))$
13817 := $(F((F(7) + 1)) + (8!/C(3, 1)))$
13832 := $((-2) + F(F(3!))) \times (8 + ((C(3, 1)!))$
13842 := $((2 \times (F(4)^8)) + ((C(3, 1)!))$
13845 := $((5^4) \times F(8)) + ((C(3, 1)!))$
13869 := $((-9) \times 6!) + C(F(8), (3! - 1))$
13934 := $(C(F(F((F(4)!)), 3!) - ((9 + (F(3!))! + 1))$
13936 := $((C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 9) - (F(3!))! + 1)$
13972 := $((F((-2) + F(7))) \times F(9)) + F(F(F((C(3, 1)!)))$
14349 := $((9 \times F((-4) + F(F(3!)))) - (C(4, 1)!)$
14366 := $((6! \times C(6, 3)) - F((F((F(4)!)) + 1)))$
14367 := $(-F(7)) + (C(6, 3) \times ((F(4)! - 1)))$
14378 := $(F(F(8)) + (C(F(7), 3!) \times F((4 - 1))))$
14399 := $(((-C(9, 9) + 3!)!^{F(F(4))}) - 1)$
14404 := $((((4 + 0!)!^{F(F(4))}) + C(4, 1))$
14433 := $(F(C(3!, F(3))) + (((4!^{F(4)} - 1)))$
14448 := $((-8!) - F(4!)) / (4! / (-C(4, 1)))$
14456 := $(C(F(6), 5) - (-((F(4)!))! \times (F(F((F(4)!)) - 1)))$
14478 := $((F(8) + F(F(7))) \times (C(F((F(4)!), F(4)) + 1))$
14487 := $((C(F(7), 8) \times (F(4)!)) + F((F(F((F(4)!)) - 1)))$
14496 := $((-6) + F((-9) + 4!)) \times (C(4, 1)!)$
14534 := $((C(F(F((F(4)!)), (F(3) + 5))) / F((F(4)!)) - 1)$
14535 := $(-5) \times (C(F(F(3!)), 5) / (-((F(4)! + 1)))$
14544 := $((4!^{F(4)}) + ((C(5, 4) + 1)!)$
14616 := $(F(F(6)) \times ((1 \times 6)! - (C(4, 1)!))$
14663 := $((3! - (F(6)!)) + (C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!)) - 1)$
14664 := $(4! \times (F(C(6, (6 - 4)) + 1))$
14756 := $(C(F(F(6)), 5) + ((F(F(7)) \times (-4!)) - 1)$
14758 := $(C(F(8), 5) + ((F(F(7)) \times (-4!)) + 1))$
14763 := $(F(F(3!)) \times ((6! - F(7)) - C(4, 1)))$
14767 := $(F(F(7)) + ((C(F(F(6)), 7) / F((F(4)!)) - 1))$
14807 := $(F(7) \times (C(-((0! - F(8))), F(4)) - 1))$
14823 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + (C((-2) + F(8)), 4) + 1)$
14833 := $((F(C(3!, F(3))) + 8) \times 4! + 1)$
14844 := $(-((C(4!, F(F(4))) - (F(8) \times (((4 - 1)!)))))$
14868 := $(F(8) \times (6! - C((8 + 4), 1)))$
14943 := $(-F(3!)) + (C(-((F((F(4)!)) - F(9))), 4) + 1)$
14945 := $(-5) + C(-((F((F(4)!)) - F(9))), C(4, 1))$
14972 := $(((-2) + C(F(7), 9)) \times F(F((F(4)!)) - 1)$
14984 := $((F(4)!))! \times F(8) - (F(9) \times C(4, 1))$
15005 := $(F(5^{0!+0!}) / C(5, 1))$
15146 := $((F(F(6)) \times ((F(4)!))! + 1) + C(5, 1))$
15238 := $((F(8) \times 3!) + (-2) + (C(5, 1)!))$
15307 := $(-((7! + 0!)) + (C(F(F(3!)), 5) - 1))$
15308 := $(-(((8 - 0)!)) + (C(F(F(3!)), 5) - 1))$
15334 := $((F(4!) / 3) - (F(3) + (C(5, 1)!))$
15359 := $((C(9, 5) + F(3)) \times 5!) - 1$
15385 := $(-5!) + (C((F(8) - F(F(3))), 5) + 1)$
15428 := $(-C(8, 2) - (F(4!) / (-F((5 - 1))))$
15454 := $((C((F(4)!), 5) - F(4!)) / (-F((5 - 1))))$
15475 := $((5! + 7!) \times F(4) - C(5, 1))$
15499 := $((F((9 + 9)) \times (F(4)!)) - C(5, 1))$
15506 := $(C((F(F(6)) - 0!), 5) + F(F((5 - 1))))$
15508 := $(C((F(8) - 0!), 5) + (5 - 1))$
15528 := $(C((F(8) - F(2)), 5) + ((5 - 1)!))$
15542 := $(2 \times (((F(4)!^5) - C(5, 1)))$
15567 := $(C(F(7), F(6)) + (5! \times (5 - 1)))$
15624 := $(C(4!, F(2)) \times 651)$
15645 := $((5^{(F(4)!))} + C(6, F((5 - 1))))$
15666 := $(F(F(6)) \times (F(F(6)) + (6! + C(5, 1))))$
15734 := $(F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (F(F(3!)) \times (F(F(7)) - C(5, 1))))$
15737 := $(F(F(7)) + (3! \times F((F(7) + C(5, 1))))$

- 15839** := $((F(9) + 3!) \times F(8)) + C(5, 1)$
15867 := $((C(7, 6))! + F(F(8))) - ((5! - 1))$
15947 := $((7! + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) - (F(9) + C(5, 1)))$
15984 := $(F((4 + 8)) \times (-9) + (C(5, 1))!)$
16184 := $((C(4!, F(8)) - 1) \times F(C(6, 1)))$
16254 := $(F(F((F(4)!)) \times ((F(C(5, 2)) + 6!) - 1))$
16348 := $((-8) + C(4!, F(3))) \times 61$
16363 := $((F(3)^{F(6)+3!}) - F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16398 := $((F(F(8)) \times 9) / 3! - F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16424 := $-((C(F((F(4)! + F(2))), F((F(4)!)) - F((F(F(6)) + 1))))$
16425 := $((5!^2) + (C(4!, F(F(6))) + 1))$
16436 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(C(3!, 4)) \times (F(6) + 1)))$
16706 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((07)! + (C(6, 1))!))$
16732 := $((F((F(2) + 3!)) \times C(F(7), F(6))) + 1)$
16737 := $((C(F(7), F(3!)) \times F(7)) + C(6, 1))$
16758 := $(F(8) \times ((5! + F(7)) \times C(6, 1)))$
16797 := $((F(F(7)) \times (9!/7!)) + F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16824 := $(4! \times ((2 - F(8)) + (C(6, 1))!))$
16837 := $(C(F(7), 3!) + ((F(8) \times 6!) + 1))$
16839 := $((9!/F(F(3!))) - (F(8) \times F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16857 := $((-((7! - 5)) + F(F(8))) + F(F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16873 := $((F(F(3!)) - (7! - F(F(8)))) + F(F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16937 := $(-((7^3)) + (9!/F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16982 := $(F((F(2) + F(8))) - (9 + (C(6, 1))!))$
16994 := $((F(4!) + (9!/(-9))) + F(F(F(C(6, 1))))$
16996 := $((F(6))! + (F(9) \times (F(9) - (C(6, 1))!))$
17046 := $((6! \times 4!) - 0!) - F(F(C(7, 1)))$
17147 := $((F(7))! / ((F((F(4)! + 1))! - F(C(7, 1))))$
17167 := $((F(7))! / ((F(6) + 1))! + C(7, 1))$
17184 := $((4!)! / (F(8))! - (-1) \times (C(7, 1))!)$
17246 := $((6! \times 4!) - F(C((2 + 7), 1)))$
17269 := $((9!/F(F(6))) - (-2) + F(C(7, 1)))$
17279 := $((9! - (C(7, 2))) / F(7 + 1))$
17289 := $((9!/F(8)) + C((2 + 7), 1))$
17334 := $(F((4! - F(3))) - F((F(3) \times C(7, 1))))$
17336 := $(F(6) \times ((3 \times 3!) + C(7, 1)))$
17368 := $((C(F(8), 6) / 3) - ((7 - 1))!)$
17376 := $(-6!) - (-C(F(7), F(3))) \times (F(F(7)) - 1))$
17438 := $(F((F(8) + F(F(3)))) - (F(F((F(4)!)) \times F(C(7, 1))))$
17444 := $((F(4))! + (4 \times F((F(4)! + F(C(7, 1))))$
17489 := $((9!/F(8)) - 4!) + F(F(C(7, 1)))$
17494 := $(F(F(F((F(4)!))) + ((9^4) - F(C(7, 1))))$
17513 := $((3! \times (-((1 - 5)))! + F(F(C(7, 1))))$
17527 := $((C(7, F(2))^5) + ((7 - 1))!)$
17584 := $((F((F(4)!)) - (F(8) \times 5!)) \times (-C(7, 1)))$
17633 := $(F((F(F(3)) + F(F(3!)))) - (6 \times F(C(7, 1))))$
17653 := $((3! + 5!) \times F(F(6))) + F(C(7, 1))$
17654 := $((F(F(4)) + (5! \times F(F(6)))) \times C(7, 1))$
17666 := $((F(6))! / 6 + F((F(6) + F(C(7, 1))))$
17746 := $((6! \times 4!) + F(F(7))) + F(F(C(7, 1)))$
17784 := $(4! \times (F(C(8, 7)) + ((7 - 1))!))$
17831 := $(((-1) + 3!)! + F((F(C(8, 7)) + 1)))$
17844 := $(F(F(4)) \times (-C(4!, F(8))) + F(F((7 + 1))))$
17984 := $((C(4!, F(8)) \times 9) - F(F(7))) + 1$
17993 := $((3! \times (F(9) - 9)) - C(7, 1))$
18323 := $((F(C(3!, 2)) + F(3)) + F((F(8) + 1)))$
18324 := $(F(C((F(4)!), 2)) - (-3) - F((F(8) + 1)))$
18386 := $((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) \times (-F(3))) + (C(8, 1))!$
18449 := $((9 \times C(4!, F(4))) + F(F((8 - 1)))$
18574 := $((F(4))! \times (7! - 5!)) - F(F(C(8, 1)))$
18648 := $((F(8) \times F((F(4)!)) + (6!)) \times F(C(8, 1)))$
18654 := $((F(4!) - 5!) / 6 + F(F(C(8, 1))))$
18762 := $(2 \times ((6! \times F(7)) + F(C(8, 1))))$
19264 := $((F(4!) + (F(6))!) \times (-2)) / (-C(9, 1))$
19413 := $((3! - 1) \times (F(4) \times C(9, 1)))$
19431 := $((-1) + (3! \times F(4))) \times C(9, 1)$
19435 := $(-5) - (3! \times (F(4) \times (-C(9, 1))))$
19443 := $((3! / (-F(4))) + (F(4)^{C(9, 1)}))$
19445 := $(5 + (((F(4))! \times (F(4) \times C(9, 1))))$
19446 := $(6 + (((F(4))! \times (F(4) \times C(9, 1))))$
19448 := $C((F(8) - 4), ((4! - F(9)) \times (-1)))$
19464 := $(4! + ((6! \times F(4)) \times C(9, 1)))$
19584 := $((4!^{F(8-5)}) \times F(C(9, 1)))$
19586 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((8 \times 5!) \times C(9, 1)))$
19845 := $((5 \times F(F((F(4)!))) \times (F(8) \times C(9, 1)))$
20244 := $((F(4) + ((F(4))!)) \times C(F(((2 + 0))!), 2))$
20337 := $(-F(7)) + (C(F(F(3!)), (3! - 0!)) + F(2))$
20339 := $(-9) + (C(F(F(3!)), (3! - 0!)) - F(2))$
20343 := $(C(F(F(3!)), (F(4) + F(3))) - ((0! + 2))!)$
20344 := $(-((F(4))! + (C(F(F((F(4)!)), (3! - 0!)) + F(2))))$

- 20345** := $(- (5) + (C(F(F((F(4)!)), (3! - 0!)) + F(2)))$
20346 := $(C(F(F(6)), (F(4) + F(3))) - (0! + 2))$
20347 := $(C((7 \times F(4)), (3! - 0!)) - 2)$
20348 := $(C(F(8), (F(4) + F(3))) - ((0 \times 2)!))$
20351 := $(C(F(F((1 + 5))), (3! - 0!)) + 2)$
20353 := $(C(F(F(3!)), 5) + (F(3) + 02))$
20354 := $(C(F(F((F(4)!)), 5) + (3 + 02))$
20356 := $(C(F(F(6)), 5) + (3! + ((0 \times 2)!))$
20368 := $(F(8) + (C(F(F(6)), (3! - 0!)) - 2))$
20433 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (3!! + C((4! - 0!), 2)))$
20436 := $(((F(6))! / F(3)) + (C(4!, 02)))$
20467 := $(C((7 + F(F(6))), 4) - F(((0! + 2)!))$
20469 := $(C((F(9) - 6), 4!) - ((0! + 2)!))$
20473 := $(C((F(F(3!)) + 7), 4) - 02)$
20476 := $(C((F(F(6)) + 7), 4) + ((0 \times 2)!))$
20478 := $((C((F(8) + 7), 4!) + 0!) + 2)$
20496 := $(C((-6) + F(9), 4!) + F(F(((0! + 2)!)))$
20576 := $(F(6) \times ((C(F(7), 5) - 0!) \times 2))$
20727 := $(C(7, 2) \times F(((7 + 0!) \times 2))$
20757 := $(C(7, 5) + (F((F(7) - 0!)^2))$
21244 := $((C(4!, 4) \times 2) - F(((1 + 2)!))$
21282 := $((2 \times F(F(8))) - F(C(((2 + 1)!), 2)))$
21652 := $(- (2) \times (5! - F(C((6 + 1), 2))))$
21756 := $((F(6))! - C((5 + F(7)), ((1 + 2)!))$
21924 := $((F(4))! \times C(29, (1 + 2)))$
22048 := $((F(F(8)) + C(F(((F(4))! + 0!)), 2)) \times 2)$
22074 := $((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + C((F(7) + 0!), 2)) \times 2)$
22234 := $((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 2)) \times 2)$
22312 := $((- (F(21)) - C(F(F(3!)), 2)) \times (-2))$
22314 := $((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (1 + C(F(F(3!)), 2))) \times 2)$
22342 := $(2 \times (F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (C(3!, 2^2))))$
22437 := $(- (7) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + (C(4!, 2))) \times 2)$
22438 := $((F(F(8)) + (- (3) + C(4!, 2))) \times 2)$
22442 := $(((- (F(2)) + F(F(F((F(4)!)))) + (C(4!, 2))) \times 2)$
22444 := $((F(F((4 + 4))) + C(4!, 2)) \times 2)$
22448 := $((F(F(8)) + F(F(4))) + C(4!, 2)) \times 2)$
22454 := $((F(F(F((F(4)!))) + (5 + C(4!, 2))) \times 2)$
22486 := $((F(F(6)) + F(F(8))) + C(4!, 2)) \times 2)$
22624 := $((C((F(4))!, 2) + (F(6))!) - F(22))$
22693 := $((F(3!))! + (C(9, 6) - F(22)))$
22723 := $(- ((C(F(3!)), 2) - (7! + F(22))))$
22736 := $(- (((C(6, F(3)) - 7!) - F(22)))$
22849 := $((F(9) \times 4!) \times C(8, 2) + F(2))$
23074 := $((F(4!) - (C((F(7) - 0!), 3))) / 2)$
23124 := $((F(4!) - ((C(2, 1) + 3)!)) / 2)$
23156 := $((- (C(F(6), 5)) + F(((1 + 3)!)) / 2)$
23356 := $((C(F(6), 5) + (3!^{3!})) / 2)$
23375 := $((5! \times C(F(7), 3) - F(F(F(3!)))) + F(2))$
23399 := $((9 \times C((F(9) - F(3!)), 3)) - F(2))$
23433 := $((C(F(F(3!)), F(3)) + ((F(4))^{3!})) / 2)$
23434 := $((F(4!) - 3!) / F(F(4))) + F(C(3!, 2))$
23458 := $((85 \times C(4!, F(3))) - 2)$
23466 := $((6^6 + C(4!, F(3))) / 2)$
23476 := $((6 \times 7!) - F(C((F(4))!, 3))) + F(2))$
23493 := $((3!! \times F(9)) - F((C(4, 3^2)))$
23527 := $(7 \times (F(2) - (- (5!) \times C(F(3!), 2)))$
23544 := $((F(4!) / F(F(4))) + (5! \times C(3, 2)))$
23575 := $(- (5) \times (- (7!) + C((5 + F(F(3!))), 2)))$
23608 := $(C(F((8 - 0!)), 6) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2)))$
23633 := $((3!^{3!} + F(C(6, F(3)))) / 2)$
23646 := $((C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) + (F(6))!) / (F(3) + 2))$
23649 := $(- ((F(9) \times (4! - 6!)) + C(3!, 2)))$
23666 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (- (6!) + ((F(6))! / C(3, 2)))$
23694 := $((4! + 9) \times (6! - F(C(3, 2))))$
23696 := $((6! \times F(9)) - (C(F(6), F(3))^2))$
23726 := $((F(C(F(6), 2)) / F(7)) - 3!) - F(2))$
23728 := $((F(C(8, 2)) / F(7)) - 3!) + F(2))$
23747 := $(- (F(7)) + (((F(4))!) \times (C(7, 3) - 2)))$
23756 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F((- (5) + F(7))) \times F(C(3!, 2))))$
23775 := $(5 \times (7! - (C(F(7), 3) - F(2))))$
23794 := $((F(4!) / (9 - 7)) + F(C(3!, 2)))$
23827 := $((- (7!) + F((2 + F(8)))) + C(F(F(3!)), 2))$
2384 := $(C(4!, F(8)) - (3! / (-2)))$
23843 := $(- (3!) + ((F(4!) + (C(F(8), 3))) / 2))$
23844 := $(- (4) \times (4! - C(F(8), (F(3) + 2))))$
23846 := $((- (6) + F(4!)) + (C(F(8), 3))) / 2)$
23849 := $((F(9) \times ((F(4))!)) - (F(8) + F(C(3!, 2))))$
23944 := $((C(F(F((F(4)!)), F(4)) \times (-9)) - F(3)) \times (-2))$
23989 := $(F(9) + (F((8 + 9)) \times C(3!, 2)))$
24024 := $((C((F(4))!, 2) - 0!) / ((F((F(4))!) + 2)!))$

$$24054 := (-((F(4))! - 5!)) \times (0! + C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$$

$$24186 := (-6) + (((8+1)! / C((F(4))!, 2)))$$

$$24235 := (5 \times (C((F(F(3!)) - F(2)), 4) + 2))$$

$$24247 := -((F(F(7)) + (F((F(4)^2)) \times (-C(4, 2)!)))$$

$$24249 := ((F(9) \times ((F(4))!)) - C((-2) + 4!), 2)$$

$$24253 := (((F(F(3!)) \times F(C(5, 2))) \times F(F((F(4))!)) - 2)$$

$$24254 := (((F(F((F(4))!)) \times F(C(5, 2))) \times F(F((F(4))!)) - F(2))$$

$$24256 := (((F(F(6)) \times F(C(5, 2))) \times F(F((F(4))!)) + F(2))$$

$$24269 := (((F(9) \times 6!) - F(2)) - C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$$

$$24299 := (-9) + (C((F(9)/2), F((F(4))!)) - 2)$$

$$24308 := (C(((F(8) - 0!) - 3), F((F(4))!)) - 2)$$

$$24309 := ((F(9) \times C(F((0! + 3!)), 4)) - F(2))$$

$$24311 := (C((11 + 3!), F((F(4))!)) + F(2))$$

$$24324 := (C((F(F((F(4))!)) - F(2)), 3) + (F(4!) / 2))$$

$$24329 := ((C((F(9)/2), F(3!)) + F(F((F(4))!))) - 2)$$

$$24356 := (F(F(F(6))) + (-5!) - (F(C(3!, F(4))) \times (-2)))$$

$$24373 := (F(F(F(3!))) + (-F(7)) + (((F(3!))! / C(F(4), F(2))))$$

$$24374 := (C((4! - 7), F(3!)) + (F((F(4))!^2)))$$

$$24378 := ((F(8) + F(7)) \times (-3) + (C(4, 2)!))$$

$$24394 := (-((F(4))! - (-((F(9) + 3!)) \times F(C((F(4))!, 2))))$$

$$24405 := (-5) \times (-0!) - (F((F(4))!) \times F(C((F(4))!, 2)))$$

$$24425 := (-F(C(5, 2))) - (((F(4))! \times (-F((F(4)^2))))$$

$$24446 := ((6! - C(4, 4)) \times F((F(4)^2)))$$

$$24468 := ((-8) + F(C(6, F(4)))) + F((4! - 2))$$

$$24471 := (C(F((1 \times 7)), F((F(4))!)) + (F(4!) / 2))$$

$$24476 := (F(C(6, (7 - 4))) + F((4! - 2)))$$

$$24479 := ((F(9) \times ((7 - C(4, 4))!)) - F(2))$$

$$24482 := (((-2) \times F(F(8))) + (F(4))! + F(C(4!, F(2))))$$

$$24484 := (((4 - F(F(8))) \times F(F(4))) + F(C(4!, F(2))))$$

$$24495 := (((5! \times F(9)) \times (F(4))! + C((F(4))!, 2))$$

$$24499 := (F(9) + ((F(9) \times ((F(4))!)) - C((F(4))!, 2)))$$

$$24528 := (C((8 \times 2), 5) - ((F((F(4))!))! / (-2)))$$

$$24543 := -((F(F(3!)) - (F(((F(4))! + 5))) \times C(4!, 2)))$$

$$24547 := (-F(F(7))) + (-((F(F(4)) - 5!)) \times C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$$

$$24562 := (-2) + (F((6 + 5)) \times C(4!, 2))$$

$$24563 := -((F(F(3)) - ((F((6 + 5)) \times C(4!, 2))))$$

$$24577 := (-((F(7) + (7! \times (-5)))) - F(C((F(4))!, 2)))$$

$$24691 := ((1 + (F(9) \times 6!)) + C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$$

$$24697 := (F(7) - (F(9) \times (-6) - (C(4, 2)!)))$$

$$24698 := ((8 + (F(9) \times 6!)) + C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$$

$$24699 := ((9 + (F(9) \times 6!)) + C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2))$$

$$24718 := (F((8 + 1)) \times (7 + (C(4, 2)!)))$$

$$24746 := (-6) + (C((4! - 7), (F(4))!) \times 2)$$

$$24747 := (((-F(7)) + ((F(4))!)) \times C(7, 4) + 2)$$

$$24749 := ((F(9) \times ((F(4))!)) + (-7) + C(4!, 2))$$

$$24834 := -(((F(4))! - ((3! / 8) \times C(4!, 2)))$$

$$24876 := ((F(6))! - ((C(F(7), 8) \times 4!) / 2))$$

$$24888 := ((-8!) + F(F(8))) + (C(F(8), (F(4))!) - 2)$$

$$24895 := (C((5 + 9), 8) - (F(F(F((F(4))!))) \times (-2)))$$

$$24912 := (((2 + 1)!)! - (-9!) / C((F(4))!, 2))$$

$$24913 := ((3! + 1) - (-9!) / C((F(4))!, 2))$$

$$24924 := (((F(4))! \times (F(2) + F(9))) - (C(4!, 2)))$$

$$24937 := (((F(7) + 3!) \times F(9)) + C((F(4))!, 2))$$

$$24984 := ((4! \times F(8)) + (F(9) \times (C(4, 2)!)))$$

$$24992 := ((2^9) + (F(9) \times (C(4, 2)!)))$$

$$25145 := ((5 \times ((F(4))! + 1))! - F(C(5, 2)))$$

$$25228 := ((C(F(8), 2) + 2) \times (5! - F(2)))$$

$$25257 := (((7! \times 5) + 2) + F(C(5, 2)))$$

$$25366 := (F(F(F(6))) + (C(6, 3) + (5!^2)))$$

$$25387 := (7! + (C(C(F(8), F(F(3))), 5) - 2))$$

$$25613 := -((3! - (C((1 + F(F(6))), 5) - F(2)))$$

$$25614 := (((F(4))! - (C((1 + F(F(6))), 5))) \times (-F(2)))$$

$$25616 := (-6!) + (C((1 + F(F(6))), 5) + 2)$$

$$25638 := ((F(F(8)) \times 3) + (6! \times (-C(5, 2))))$$

$$25644 := -(((C(4!, F(F(4))) - (F(6))! + (5!^2)))$$

$$25724 := ((C((F(4))!, 2) - F(F(7))) \times (-5! - 2))$$

$$25741 := (((1 - F(F((F(4))!))) \times (-C(F(7), 5))) + F(2))$$

$$25769 := ((F(9) \times 6!) + (C(F(7), 5) + 2))$$

$$25823 := ((F(F(F(3!))) / 2) + (C(F(8), 5) + F(2)))$$

$$25824 := ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) / 2) + (C(F(8), 5) + 2))$$

$$25984 := (F((F(4))!) \times (8 \times C((F(9) - 5), 2)))$$

$$26144 := (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 4) - (1 - ((F(6))! / 2)))$$

$$26146 := ((C(F(F(6)), 4) + 1) + ((F(6))! / 2))$$

$$26264 := (F(4!) - ((C(F(6), 2) \times (6! - 2)))$$

$$26313 := -((F(F(3!)) - C((1 + F(F(3!))), (6 - F(2))))$$

$$26326 := (-F(6)) + C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), (6 - F(2)))$$

$$26332 := (C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), (-3) + F(6)) - 2)$$

$$26333 := (C((F(F(3)) + F(F(3!))), (-3) + F(6)) - F(2))$$

$$26334 := C((4! - F(3)), -((3 - 6) - 2))$$

$$26346 := (6 \times (F((-F(F(4)) + F(F(3!)))) + C(F(F(6)), 2))$$

- 26347** := $(F(7) + C((4! - F(3)), (6 - F(2))))$
26348 := $((C((F(8) - 4), 3!) + (F(6)!)) / 2)$
26368 := $((- (C(F(8), 6) - F(3!)) - ((F(6)!) \times (-2)))$
26374 := $-C(F(F(F(4)!)), F(7)) + F(F(3!)) \times F(F(F(6))) - 2$
26378 := $(- (C(F(8), F(7))) + ((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(F(6)))) + 2))$
26384 := $(F((F(4)!)) + (- (C(F(8), 3!)) - ((F(6)!) \times (-2))))$
26412 := $(- (((2 + 1)!)!) - (C(F(F((F(4)!)), 6) / (-2)))$
26413 := $(- ((3! - 1)) - (C(F(F((F(4)!)), 6) / (-2)))$
26544 := $((F(4!) / F(F(4))) + ((5! \times C(F(6), 2))))$
26547 := $(- (((F(F(7)) \times ((F(4)!) - 5!)) + C(6, 2)))$
26633 := $(- (C(((F(3) + F(3))!), F(F(6)))) + F((F(F(6)) + 2)))$
26634 := $((4!^3) - (F(F(6)) \times (-F(C(6, 2))))$
26656 := $((F(6) \times 5!) - F(6)) \times C(F(6), 2)$
26667 := $((C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(F(6))) + (6! / (-2)))$
26677 := $(- (7) + ((F(F(7)) + 6!) \times C(F(6), 2)))$
26686 := $((F(6)!) - F(F(8))) + ((F(6)!) / (-C(6, 2)))$
26784 := $(C(- (F(4) - F(8)), 7) - ((F(6) - F(2))!))$
26844 := $((4! \times 4!) - C(F(8), 6)) / (-2)$
26852 := $(- ((F(2) - (5! \times 8)) \times C(F(6), 2)))$
26968 := $((C(F(8), F(6)) + 9!) / F(F(6))) - 2$
26978 := $(- (8!) - (C(((F(7) - 9)!), 6) / (-2)))$
27044 := $(4 \times (- (4) + F(- ((0! - C(7, 2))))))$
27131 := $(C((- (1) + F(F(3!))) - 1), F(7)) - F(2)$
27133 := $(C(((3 \times 3!) + 1), F(7)) + F(2))$
27134 := $(C(((4! - 3!) + 1), F(7)) + 2)$
27136 := $((C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (1 + 7)) / 2)$
27138 := $((C(F(8), 3!) - 1) + F(7)) / 2$
27248 := $((C(F(8), (F(4)!) - F(2)) + F(F(7))) / 2)$
27324 := $(- (C(4!, 2)) \times (F(F(3!)) - ((7 - 2)!))$
27384 := $((- (C(4!, F(8))) + 3!) \times (-C(7, 2)))$
27464 := $(F((F(4)!) \times (C((F(6) + (F(4)!) , 7) + F(2))))$
27484 := $((F(F(4)) \times F(F(8))) - (- (4!) \times F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
27494 := $((4! + 94) \times F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
27536 := $((6! + (C(F(3!), 5) \times F(F(7)))) \times 2)$
27635 := $(- (5) \times ((F(3!) \times (-6!)) + F(C(F(7), F(2))))$
27637 := $((F(F(7)) + 3!) \times (F(6) + (C(7, 2))))$
27742 := $(C((- (2) + F(F((F(4)!)!)), F(7)) + F((F(7) + 2)))$
27837 := $(- (7!) + (3 \times (F(F(8)) + C(F(7), F(2))))$
27888 := $((8! - C(F(8), (8 + 7))) \times (-2))$
27928 := $((C(F(8), 2) + 9!) / F(7)) - 2$
27944 := $(C(4!, F(4)) - (9! / (- (7 \times 2))))$
27951 := $((1 + 5!) \times C((9 + F(7)), 2)$
27954 := $(- (((F(4)!) + (- (5!) \times F((F(9) - (C(7, 2))))))$
27955 := $(- (5) - (- (5!) \times F((F(9) - (C(7, 2))))))$
28046 := $(- ((F(C(6, 4) + 0!)) + F((F(8) + 2)))$
28226 := $((6! \times ((2 + 2)!) + F(C(F(8), F(2))))$
28327 := $(C((F(7) + 2), F(3!)) - (F(F(8)) \times (-2)))$
28348 := $(- (((C(F(8), 4) \times F(3)) - 8!) + 2))$
28358 := $((8^5) - (F(F(3!)) \times C(F(8), 2)))$
28404 := $(F((4! - 0!)) - C((F(F(4)) + (F(8))), 2))$
28433 := $((C(F(3!), 3) \times (-4)) + F((F(8) + 2)))$
28436 := $((C(F(F(6)), 3) + (4!)) \times F(8)) + 2$
28444 := $((C((4! + 4), F(4)) + F(F(8))) \times 2)$
28496 := $((F(6)!) - ((F(9) \times C(4!, F(8)))) \times (-F(2)))$
28498 := $(- (8! - ((F(9) \times C(4!, F(8))) + 2)))$
28558 := $((F(8) - 5!) + F(- ((5 - C(8, 2))))$
28567 := $(- ((7! / C(F(6), 5)) + F((F(8) + 2)))$
28633 := $(F((C(3!, F(3)) + F(6))) - ((8/2)!))$
28634 := $(F((4! - C(3!, 6)) - (F(8) + 2))$
28663 := $(3! + F((F(6) + C(6, (8/2))))$
28664 := $((F(4)!) + C(6, 6) + F((F(8) + 2)))$
28747 := $(- ((F(F(7)) - ((F(4)!) \times (7! - C(F(8), 2))))$
28775 := $(5 \times (7! + C(F(7), (8/2))))$
28797 := $((7! / C(9, 7)) + F((F(8) + 2)))$
28834 := $(F(C((F(4)!), F(3))) + ((8 \times F(8))^2))$
28837 := $(- (F(F(7))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 8) / (8 - F(2))))$
28864 := $(- (((F(4)!)! - ((F(6)!) - F(F(8))) + (C(F(8), 2))))$
29164 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) - (F(F(F(6))) + C(F(- ((1 - 9))), 2)))$
29254 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) - (5! + F(C(- ((2 - 9))), 2)))$
29336 := $(- (((F(F(F(6))) - (F(3)!) + (F(3) + C(9, 2))))$
29341 := $((F((- (1) + 4!)) + 3!) - C(9, 2))$
29346 := $((- (C(F(6), F(F(4)))) + (F(3)!) - F(F((9 - F(2))))$
29363 := $((F(3)!) - F(F(F(6)))) - C((F(3) + 9), F(2))$
29393 := $(C(F(F(3!)), 9) / ((3 + 9) - 2))$
29413 := $((3! + F((- (1) + 4!)) + C(9, 2))$
29434 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) - F(F(F(3!))) + (4! + C(9, 2)))$
29444 := $((F((F(4)!)!)) + ((C(F((F(4)!) , 4) - F(F((9 - F(2))))))$
29485 := $((5! - F(F(8))) + (F((F(4)!)!)) - C(9, F(2)))$
29487 := $(7! + (F(C(8, F(F(4)))) / F((9 - 2)))$
29547 := $((C(F(7), F((F(4)!) + 5!) \times F((9 - F(2))))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 29754 &:= (C((F(4)!, 5) \times (7! - (9^2)))) \\
 30384 &:= (4! \times ((C(F(8), F(3)) + 0!) \times 3!)) \\
 30428 &:= (F((F(8) + 2) + C((4! - 0!), 3)) \\
 30678 &:= ((F(F(C(8, 7))) - (6!)) \times 03) \\
 31248 &:= (-((F(8) \times (C(4, 2)!)) + F(((1 + 3)!))) \\
 31344 &:= (- (4!) \times (4! - C(F(F(3!)), (1 \times 3)))) \\
 31437 &:= ((F(7) \times C(F(F(3!)), 4)) - F(((1 + 3)!))) \\
 31438 &:= (- (C(F(8), 3) + (F((F(4)!)^{-1+3!}))) \\
 31549 &:= ((- (9) + C(4!, 5)) - F(F(F(((1 \times 3)!)))) \\
 31554 &:= ((C(4!, 5) - (5 - 1)) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 31558 &:= -((F(F(8)) - C((5!/5), (- (1) + 3!))) \\
 31559 &:= ((C(((9 - 5)!, 5) + 1) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 31816 &:= -((F(6) - C(18, (1 + 3!))) \\
 31837 &:= (F(7) + C((- (3) + F(8)), (1 + 3!))) \\
 32064 &:= (4! \times (C(F(F(6)), (0! + 2)) + 3!)) \\
 32118 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times (C(1, 1) + 2)) - 3!)) \\
 32175 &:= (5 \times C(C((7 - 1), 2), F(3!))) \\
 32208 &:= ((- (F(F(8))) + C(F(F(((0! + 2)!)), 2)) \times (-3)) \\
 32312 &:= ((F(((2 + 1)!))! - C((F(3!) \times 2), 3!)) \\
 32335 &:= ((- (5) \times F((C(3!, F(3)) + 2))) + (F(3)!))! \\
 32337 &:= ((F(F(7))^{F(3)}) - (C(F(3!), 2^3))) \\
 32338 &:= (- (((C(F(8), 3) \times 3!) + 2)) + (F(3)!))! \\
 32361 &:= ((C((1 + F(F(6))), 3) + F(2)) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 32364 &:= (4! + (F(F(6)) \times C((F(F(3!)) + F(2)), 3))) \\
 32366 &:= (C(F(F(6)), 6) + ((F(F(F(3!))) \times (-2)) - 3!)) \\
 32367 &:= (7! - (C(F(F(6)), 3) - (F(23)))) \\
 32377 &:= ((- (F(7)) + (- (F(7)) \times F(C(3!, 2)))) + (F(3)!))! \\
 32382 &:= ((C((F(2) + F(8)), 3) + 2) \times F(F(3!))) \\
 32383 &:= ((3 \times F(F(8))) - C(C(3!, 2), 3)) \\
 32384 &:= ((C(4!, F(8)) \times F(3)) \times (2^3)) \\
 32436 &:= (C(F(F(6)), 3) - (((F((F(4)!))! / (-2)) - F(F(F(3!)))))) \\
 32453 &:= ((F(3!)^5) - (C((F(4)!, 2) \times F(F(3!)))) \\
 32463 &:= (3 \times (F(F(6)) + (C((F(4)!), 2) \times 3!))) \\
 32466 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (6 + C((4! - 2), 3))) \\
 32474 &:= (((F(4)! \times (F(7) \times C(4!, 2))) + F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 32493 &:= ((3^9) + (F(C((F(4)!), 2)) \times F(F(3!)))) \\
 32554 &:= (- (((F(4)!)^5) - C(5, 2))) + (F(3)!))! \\
 32565 &:= (((- (5!) - F(F(6))) \times F(C(5, 2))) + (F(3)!))! \\
 32604 &:= (C(F(((F(4)! + 0!)), 6) \times (- (2) + F(F(3!)))) \\
 32636 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) \times 3) - (C(F(F(6)), 2) - F(3!)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 32658 &:= (((8^5) + F(C(6, 2))) - 3!)) \\
 32715 &:= -((5! - ((- (1) + F(C(7, 2))) \times 3))) \\
 32736 &:= ((F((C(6, 3) + 7)) - 2) / 3!) \\
 32783 &:= (F(3!) + ((F(8) - F(C(7, 2))) \times (-3))) \\
 32793 &:= (((3! + 9) - F(C(7, 2))) \times (-3)) \\
 32946 &:= (((F(C(6, 4)) \times 9) + F(2)) \times 3!) \\
 33048 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) + C(F(F((03)!)), F(3))) \\
 33054 &:= ((F((F(4)!)^5) + C(F((0! + 3!)), 3)) \\
 33154 &:= ((C(F(F((F(4)!)), F(F((5 - 1))))^{F(3)}) - F(F(F(3!)))) \\
 33164 &:= (- (C(4!, 6)) - (- (F(13)) \times 3!)) \\
 33178 &:= ((8! - F((F(7) + 1))) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33224 &:= ((- (C(F((F(4)!), 2)) + F((- (2) + F(F(3!)))) \times F(3!)) \\
 33225 &:= ((5^2) \times (- (F(2)) + C(F(F(3!)), 3)) \\
 33234 &:= ((F(4!) \times (-F(3))) + C((- (F(2)) + F(F(3!))), F(3!)) \\
 33245 &:= (- (5) + ((4! + F(2)) \times C(F(F(3!)), 3))) \\
 33264 &:= ((F(4)!) \times (C((6 \times 2), 3!) \times 3!)) \\
 33324 &:= (- (C(4!, 2)) - (((F(3)!)/3!) - (F(3)!))!)) \\
 33325 &:= ((5^2) \times (C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 3)) \\
 33344 &:= ((4! \times 4!) + (F(3)^{C(3!, F(3))})) \\
 33356 &:= ((F(6)^5) + (F(F(3!)) \times C(F(3!), F(3)))) \\
 33378 &:= (F((8 + 7)) + (F(3)^{C(3!, F(3))})) \\
 33387 &:= (((7! - F(8)) \times F(3!)) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33397 &:= (F(7) \times (F((9 \times F(3))) - C(3!, F(3)))) \\
 33428 &:= ((F((F(8) - 2)) \times F((F(4)!)) - C(3!, 3)) \\
 33435 &:= ((- (5!) - F(C(3!, F(4)))) + (F((3 + 3)!))! \\
 33462 &:= (26 \times C(F((4 + 3)), F(3!))) \\
 33464 &:= ((F((4 + C(6, 4))) + F(3)) \times F(3!)) \\
 33466 &:= (((F(6)!) - F((F(6) + F(4)))) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33485 &:= (- (5) \times ((- (C(F(8), 4)) - 3!) + F(3!))) \\
 33487 &:= (((F(7) + F(F(8))) \times F(4)) + F(C(3!, F(3)))) \\
 33528 &:= ((F((F(8) - 2)) + C(5, 3)) \times F(3!)) \\
 33545 &:= (- (5) \times (- (F((4 \times 5))) + C(F(3!), 3))) \\
 33548 &:= (((8! - F(F(4))) - (5)) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33556 &:= (((F(6)!) + C(5, 5)) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33574 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((7^5) - C(3!, 3))) \\
 33577 &:= ((F(7) \times F((F(7) + (5)))) - C(3!, F(3))) \\
 33584 &:= (((4! + 8!) + (5)) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33638 &:= ((83 + (F(6)!)) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33639 &:= ((C(9, 3) + (F(6)!)) - F(C(3!, 3))) \\
 33641 &:= (C((- (1) + 4!), (6 \times 3)) - F(3!))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 33643** := $-(3! - ((C(4!, 6) / F(3)) / F(3)))$
33645 := $(-5) \times (((F(4)!) \times 6) - F(C(3!, 3)))$
33646 := $((-6) + (C(4!, 6) / F(3))) / F(3)$
33648 := $((C(F(8), 4) - F((F(6) + 3!))) \times 3!$
33649 := $(C(((9) + 4!) + F(6)), 3!) / 3$
33662 := $(F((2 + F(F(6)))) + (C(C(6, F(3)), 3!)))$
33663 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (6 + F((C(6, 3) - 3)))$
33682 := $-(F(F(-((F(2) - 8))) - (C(F(F(6)), F(3!)) / 3!)))$
33685 := $(-5) \times (C(8, 6) - F(C(3!, 3)))$
33695 := $(-5) \times ((F(9) - F(6)) - F(C(3!, 3)))$

33745 := $((5! - F(F(4))) \times C(F(7), 3) - 3)$
33754 := $((F(F(4)) - 5!) \times (-C(F(7), 3))) + 3!$
33765 := $((-5!) + (F(6)!) - C((F(7) + F(3)), F(3!)))$
33775 := $(-5) \times (-((7! + C(F(7), 3!))) + F(F(3)))$
33779 := $((9 \times (7! - C(F(7), F(3!)))) + F(3))$
33784 := $((-4) + 8!) + F(F(7)) - F(C(3!, 3))$
33788 := $((-8) + 8!) - (F(F(7)) \times C(F(3!), F(3)))$
33795 := $(-5!) + (C((F(9) - F(7)), F(3!)) / 3!)$
33805 := $((5 \times F(-((0! - F(8)))) - C(3!, 3))$
33824 := $(F(4!) - (2 \times C(8, 3))^{F(3)})$
33856 := $((F(6) + 5!) + (C(8, 3))^{F(3)})$
33866 := $-(((F(6)^6) - C((F(8) + 3!), 3!)))$
33875 := $((-5) \times (C(F(7), 8) + F(3))) + (F(3!))!$
33879 := $(-C(9, 7) + (C(F(8), F(3!)) / 3!))$
33881 := $(-F((1 + 8))) + (C(F(8), F(3!)) / 3!)$
33883 := $(-((F(3) - 8!)) - C((F(8) - 3!), F(3!)))$
33884 := $(-((F(F(F(4))) - (8! - C((F(8) - 3!), F(3!))))))$
33885 := $(-C((5!/8), 8) + (F((3 + 3)))!$
33886 := $(-((F(6) + F(8))) + (C(F(8), F(3!)) / 3!))$
33887 := $((-7) - F(8)) + (C(F(8), F(3!)) / 3!)$
33888 := $(-((F(8) - ((C(F(8), 8) / 3!) - 3!)))$
33889 := $(-((F(9) - (C(F(8), 8) / 3!))) + F(3!))$
33893 := $((-C((3! + 9), 8) + (F(3!))!) + F(3!))$
33898 := $(-((8 + 9)) + (C(F(8), F(3!)) / 3!))$
33914 := $((F(4)!) - C(F(-((1 - 9))), F(3!))) / (-3!))$
33915 := $(C(F(F((5 + 1))), F((9 - 3))) / 3!$
33916 := $((C(F(F(6)), -(1 - 9))) / 3! + F(F(3)))$
33918 := $((C(F(8), -(1 - 9))) / 3! + 3)$
33935 := $((-5!) - C(F(F(3!)), F((9 - 3))) / (-3!))$
33945 := $(5 \times (4! + F(C((9 - 3), 3)))$

33949 := $(F(9) - (C(F(F((F(4)!)!), F((9 - 3))) / (-3!)))$
33965 := $(-5) \times ((6 - F(9)) - F(C(3!, 3)))$
34035 := $(5! + (C(F(F(3!)), F((F(04)!)!) / 3!))$
34104 := $((F(F(F(4)!)!) / (-0! + 1)) + C(F(F((F(4)!)!), 3!))$
34215 := $(-5!) - (C(F(F(((1 + 2)!)!), 4) - (F(3!))!))$
34224 := $(F(4!) - (C(((2 + 2)!)!, F(4)) \times 3!))$
34244 := $((-F(4!)) - C(F((F(4)!)!, 2)) + (F(F(4)) \times (F(3!))!))$
34248 := $(8! + (F(4) \times (-C(24, 3)))$
34264 := $((4 - (F(6)!) \times (-2)) - F((C(4, 3)!)!))$
34284 := $((F(4)!) + 8!) \times 2 - F((C(4, 3)!)!))$
34288 := $((8 + 8!) \times 2 - F((C(4, 3)!)!))$
34313 := $((F(3!))! - 1) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + F(F(3!)))$
34314 := $((F(((4 - 1)!)!) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + F(F(3!))))$
34328 := $((8! - F(2)) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + 3!))$
34329 := $((9 - F(2))! - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + 3!))$
34331 := $((-1) + (F(3!))! - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + 3))$
34332 := $((-2) + (F(3!))! - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) + F(F(3))))$
34334 := $((-4) + (F(3!))! - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - 3))$
34335 := $(-C(F(((5 - 3)^3), 4)) + (F(3!))!)$
34338 := $(8! - (C(F(F((3 + 3))), 4) - 3))$
34342 := $((F(2) + (F(4)!) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))!))$
34346 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C((4! + 3), 4!) \times F(3!)))$
34348 := $(-((F(8) - (C(4!, 3!) / 4))) + 3!))$
34354 := $((4! - 5) - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))!))$
34359 := $((9 - 5)! - (C(F(F(3!)), 4) - (F(3!))!))$
34365 := $(-5) \times ((-C(F(F(6)), 3!) - ((F(4)!)!) / F(3!)))$
34372 := $((2 \times F(7)) \times (C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) - F(3!)))$
34374 := $((-4) - F(7)) \times (F(3) - C(4!, 3))$
34384 := $(-((F(4)!) - ((8! + C(F(3!), F(4))) \times F(3))))$
34399 := $(-9) + ((F(9) / F(3)) \times C(4!, 3))$
34408 := $((F(8) - 04) \times C(4!, 3))$
34425 := $(-5) \times (-((F(2) + (4)!)!) - F(C((F(4)!)!, 3)))$
34429 := $((F(9) / 2) \times C(4!, F(4))) + F(F(3!))$
34442 := $((2 + C(4!, F(4))) \times (-4) + F(F(3!)))$
34447 := $(7 \times ((C(F((F(4)!)!), 4)^{F(F(4))}) + F(F(3!))))$
34457 := $(F(F(7)) + ((5! + (4)) \times C(4!, F(3))))$
34468 := $((8! - C(F(6), F(4))) - (F(4!) / F(3!)))$
34562 := $((2 \times (C(6, 5)!) \times 4!) + F(3))$
34585 := $(-((5! + 8!)) + F((C(5, 4)^{F(3)})))$
34588 := $(8 - (-((F(8) + (5))) \times C(F(F((F(4)!)!), 3)))$

- 34595** := $(- (5) \times (- ((F(9) + 5!)) - F(C((F(4)!, 3))))$
34627 := $((- (C(F(7), 2)) - (F(6)!) + F((4! + F(F(3))))$
34635 := $((C(F((5 + 3)), F(6)) / (F(4)!) + 3!))$
34636 := $((C(F(F(6)), F(3!)) + 6) / (F(4)!) + 3!))$
34642 := $(F(- ((F(2) - 4!))) + (C(F(F(6)), C(4, 3))))$
34646 := $((- (C(F(6), F(4))) - F(F(F(6)))) + ((F(4!) - 3!)))$
34664 := $(- ((4^6)) + C(C(6, F(4)), 3!))$
34667 := $((- (7!) + (F(6)!) - (F(C(6, 4)) + 3))$
34669 := $(F(9) + ((C(F(F(6)), F(6)) / (F(4)!) + 3!))$
34671 := $((1 - 7!) + (F(6)!) - F(C((F(4)!, F(3))))$
34673 := $((F(3!))! - ((7! + F(C(6, 4))) - 3))$
34675 := $((5 - 7!) + (F(6)!) - F(C((F(4)!, F(3))))$
34676 := $((F(6)!) - ((7! + F(C(6, 4))) - 3!))$
34678 := $((8! - 7!) - F(C(6, 4)) + F(3!))$
34741 := $(F((- (1) + 4!)) + (C(F(7), F(F(4)))^{F(3)}))$
34748 := $((8! + (- (4!) \times F(F(7)))) + C((F(4)!, 3))$
34749 := $((9^{F(4)}) \times C(F(7), F(4))) / 3!$
34759 := $((F(9) + (5! \times F(F(7)))) + F(C((F(4)!, 3)))$
34762 := $((2 \times F(F(F(6)))) + C((F(7) + F(4)), F(3!))$
34775 := $((5! - F(7)) \times C((F(7) \times F(F(4))), F(3))$
34778 := $(- (F(F(8))) + (7 \times (- (F(F(7))) + F(C((F(4)!, 3))))$
34812 := $((2 \times F((1 + F(8)))) - F(C((F(4)!, F(3))))$
34829 := $((- (C(9, 2)) - F(F(8))) / F(F(4))) + (F(3!))!$
34836 := $((6! \times 3!) \times 8) + C(4!, F(3))$
34862 := $((F(- ((2 - 6))) \times F(F(8))) + (C(4!, 3)))$
34864 := $(C(4!, F(F(6))) + ((F(F(8)) \times F(4)) + F(3)))$
34875 := $(5! + ((7! + C(F(8), F((F(4)!)!)) / 3!))$
34883 := $((3 \times F(F(8))) + ((F(8) + C(4!, 3)))$
34887 := $((C(F(7), 8) - (8! / (F(4)!)!)) + (F(3!))!$
34896 := $((6! - F(9)) + F(F(8))) \times F(C(4, 3))$
34926 := $((- (C((F(6) \times 2), 9)) + F(4!)) - F(3))$
34928 := $(- (C((8 \times 2), 9)) + F((C(4, 3))!))$
34934 := $((- (C((4^{F(3)}), 9)) + F(4!)) + 3!)$
34936 := $((- (C((F(6) \times F(3)), 9)) + F(4!)) + F(3!))$
34947 := $((F(F(7)) \times (4! + (C(9, 4)))) - 3)$
34956 := $((C(F(F(6)), (5 + 9)) - F(4!)) / F(3))$
34973 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 7) - (- (F(9)) + F(4!))) / F(3))$
35146 := $(- ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(4!) - C((- ((1 - 5)))!, F(3))))$
35214 := $(F(4) \times (C(12, 5) + F(F(F(3!))))$
35262 := $(C((- (2) + F(F(6))), F((F(2) + (5)))) - (F(3!))!$
35312 := $(2 \times (F((1 + F(F(3!)))) - F(C(5, 3)))$
35314 := $((F((F(4)!)!) - (1 + C((3 \times 5), 3!))$
35315 := $((F((5 + 1)))! - C((3 \times 5), 3!))$
35316 := $((F(6)!) + (1 - C((3 \times 5), 3!))$
35328 := $(C(((8/2)!)!, F(3)) \times (5! + F(3!))$
35334 := $((C(4!, F(3)) \times (F(3!) + 5!)) + 3!)$
35335 := $((- (((5 + F(3)))! + (F(3!))! + F(C(5, 3)))$
35379 := $((9 + C(F(7), 3)) \times 5! - F(F(3!))$
35399 := $((C((F(9) - 9), 3!) / 5) - F(F(3!))$
35412 := $((- (F(21)) + F(4!)) - C(5, 3))$
35425 := $(5 \times (F(2) + (C(4!, 5) / 3!))$
35441 := $((C((1 + 4!), (F(4)!) / 5) + F(F(3!))$
35475 := $((5! + 7!) / F((F(4)!) \times F(C(5, 3)))$
35634 := $((C(4!, F(3)) + F(F(6))) \times 5! - 3!)$
35658 := $((F(8) \times 5!) - C(F(F(6)), 5)) \times (-F(3))$
35676 := $((F(F(6)) \times C(F(7), 6)) + (5! \times (-3))$
35797 := $(F(7) + ((9! - 7!) / C(5, 3))$
35946 := $((C(F(F(6)), 4) + (F((9 - 5)))! \times 3!)$
35952 := $(- (C((25 - 9), 5) + (F(3!))!)$
35974 := $(C(F(F((F(4)!)!), (7 + 9)) + ((5^3)))$
36032 := $((2 \times F((F(F(3!)) + 0!)) + F(C(6, F(3))))$
36033 := $((F(F(3!)) \times C(F((3! + 0!)), 6)) - 3)$
36037 := $((C(F(7), 3!) \times F(F(06))) + F(F(3))$
36038 := $((F(8) \times C(F((3! + 0!)), 6)) + F(3))$
36044 := $(F((F(4)!) + (C(F(((F(4)!) + 0!)), 6) \times F(F(3!))))$
36056 := $((6! \times 50) + C(F(6), 3))$
36259 := $((9! / C(5, 2)) - F(F(6))) - F(3!)$
36264 := $((F(4)!) \times (- ((6! + F(2)) - F(C(6, 3))))$
36296 := $(F(6) + ((9! \times 2) / C(6, 3))$
36328 := $((8! - 2) - (3 \times C(F(F(6)), 3))$
36344 := $((((F(4)!)^4) + F(3)) \times C(F(6), F(3))$
36346 := $(- ((F(F(F(6))) - (F(4!) + C((F(3) \times 6), 3))))$
36349 := $((9! + F(C((F(4)!, F(3)))) / (F(6) + F(3)))$
36367 := $((7 \times (F(C(6, 3)) - (6))) - F(F(F(3!))))$
36382 := $((2 - C(F(8), F(3!))) / (-F(6))) + F(F(F(3!)))$
36382 := $((2 - C(F(8), F(3!))) / (-F(6))) + F(F(F(3!)))$
36383 := $(F(F(F(3!))) + ((C(F(8), F(3!)) + 6) / F(3!))$
36384 := $((C(4!, F(8)) \times 3) - F(6)) \times 3!$
36414 := $(F(4) \times ((1 - C(4!, F(F(6)))) \times (-3!))$
36429 := $((9 \times 2) \times C(4!, F(F(6))) - 3)$

- 36431** := $(- (1) + (3 \times (C(4!, F(F(6))) \times 3!)))$
36434 := $(((C(4!, 3) \times F(4)) \times 6) + F(3))$
36435 := $(([5!^{F(3)}] \times F(4)) - F(C(6, 3)))$
36436 := $(- ((C((F(F(6)) - F(3)), 4) - (F(6)!) + F(3!)))$
36444 := $((4 - (C(4!, F(4)) \times (-6))) \times 3)$
36445 := $((- (C((- (5) + 4!), 4) + (F(6)!) + F(F(3))))$
36446 := $(- ((C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), 4) - (F(6)!) - F(3)))$
36447 := $(- ((C((F(7) + (F(4)!)!), 4) - (F(6)!) - 3))$
36454 := $((C(4!, 5) - F(4!)) + (F(6)!) - F(3))$
36457 := $((- ((C(F(7), 5) \times F(4))) + (F(6)!) - F(3))$
36465 := $(5 \times (C((- (6) + 4!), F(6)) / 3!))$
36467 := $((- ((C(F(7), F(6)) \times F(4))) + (F(6)!) + F(3!))$
36478 := $((F(8) \times (C(F(7), (F(4)!) + F(F(6)))) + F(F(3)))$
36499 := $(F((9+9)) + (C(F(F((F(4)!)!), F(6)) / 3!))$
36548 := $((C(F(8), (F(4)!) - 5) - F((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))))$
36673 := $((F(3)!) - (- (F(7)) + (6 \times F(C(6, F(3))))))$
36694 := $((F((F(4)!)!) - (- (F(9)) + (6 \times F(C(6, F(3))))))$
36724 := $((- ((C(4!, 2) \times F(7))) + (F(6)!) - F(3!))$
36729 := $((F(9) - F(2)) + C(F(7), 6) \times F(F(3!)))$
36734 := $((- ((C(4!, F(3)) \times F(7))) + (F(6)!) + F(3))$
36736 := $((F(6)!) - ((F(3)^7) \times C(F(6), F(3))))$
36756 := $((F(F(C(6, 5))) \times C(F(7), 6) + 3!)$
36764 := $(- ((C(4!, 6) - (7! \times F((6+3))))$
36766 := $((6 \times (F(F(F(6))) - (7!))) + C(F(F(6)), 3))$
36834 := $(- (((4^3!) - 8!)) + F(C(6, F(3))))$
36858 := $((C(F(8), 5) - (8! / F(F(6)))) \times F(3))$
36873 := $((F(3)!) - (C(F(7), 8) - (6! \times (-3))))$
36888 := $(8! - (C((- (8) + F(8)), 6) \times F(3)))$
36984 := $(4! \times (F((8+9)) - C(F(6), 3)))$
37134 := $(F(4) \times (F(3) + C(17, 3!)))$
37136 := $(F(6) - (- (3) \times C(17, 3!)))$
37184 := $((F((F(4)!)!) - ((C(8, 1) \times 7)^{F(3)}))$
37187 := $(- ((F(7) - C((F(8) - 1), F(7)))) - (F(3)!)!$
37235 := $((- (5) \times (F(C(3!, 2)) + 7)) + (F(3)!)!$
37278 := $(8! - ((C(F(7), 2) \times F(7)) \times 3))$
37296 := $(- ((C((- (6) + F(9)), 2) - 7!) \times F(3!))$
37308 := $((C(F(8), (0! + 3)) + F(F(7))) \times 3)$
37313 := $((C((F(F(3!)) + 1), 3!) + F(7)) / F(3))$
37316 := $((F(6)!) - (1 + C((F(3) \times 7), 3!)))$
37317 := $((7+1)! - C((F(3) \times 7), 3!))$
37318 := $((8! + 1) - C((F(3) \times 7), 3!))$
37323 := $((32 - 3) \times C(F(7), F(3!)))$
37335 := $((- (5) \times (F(C(3!, F(3))) - F(7))) + (F(3)!)!$
37343 := $((F(3)!) - ((C(4!, 3) + F(F(7))) + 3!))$
37444 := $((C(4!, F(4)) \times (4! + F(7))) / F(3))$
37457 := $(- ((7^5)) + C((F(4) \times 7), 3!))$
37468 := $(C(8, 6) - ((- (4) \times F(7)) \times 3!))$
37475 := $((5! \times F(7)) \times 4! + C(7, 3))$
37487 := $(- ((F(F(7)) - 8!) + C((F(F(4)) \times F(7)), 3)))$
37548 := $(8! - (F(4) \times C((5+7), 3!)))$
37708 := $((F(8) + 0!) \times (C(F(7), 7) - F(3)))$
37731 := $((1 + F(F(3!))) \times C(F(7), 7) - F(F(3!)))$
37746 := $((F(6)!) - (F(4) \times (C(F(7), 7) / F(3))))$
37814 := $((F((F(4)!)!) - (F(18) - C(F(7), F(3))))$
37837 := $(- (((F(7)^3) - 8!) + C(F(7), 3)))$
37846 := $(- ((F(C(6, 4)) - 8!) - (F(F(7)) \times F(3!)))$
37856 := $((C(F(6), 5) + 8!) - (7! / F(3)))$
37857 := $(- (C(F(7), 5) - ((- (F(8)) \times F(F(7))) \times F(3!)))$
37893 := $(- ((3! - ((9+8!) - C(F(7), 3!)))$
37937 := $((- (C(F(7), 3) - (9 \times F(F(7)))) + (F(3)!)!$
37956 := $((F(6)!) - ((5! \times F(9)) - C(F(7), 3!)))$
37964 := $((4! - C((F(6) + 9), F(7))) + (F(3)!)!$
37974 := $(F(4!) - ((F(F(7)) \times C(9, 7)) + 3!))$
38034 := $(- (((F(4)!) + 3!) - C(- ((0! - F(8))), 3!)))$
38035 := $((- (5) - 3!) + C(- ((0! - F(8))), 3!))$
38054 := $(C(F(F((F(4)!)!), 5) + ((F((0! + F(8))) - 3!)))$
38058 := $((C(F(8), 5) + F((0! + F(8)))) - F(3))$
38064 := $((4! - 6!) + C(- ((0! - F(8))), 3!))$
38082 := $(2 \times (F((F(8) + 0!)) + (C(F(8), 3))))$
38268 := $((8! - 6!) - 2) - C(F(8), 3))$
38294 := $(- ((C(4!, F((9 - F(2)))) - ((8! - F(3))))$
38296 := $((F(6)!) - C((F(9) - (2+8)), 3))$
38304 := $(- ((C(4!, 03) - 8!)) + F(3!))$
38326 := $(C(6, 2) + ((F(F(3!)) \times F(F(8))) / 3!))$
38335 := $(F(C(5, 3)) \times (3! - (F(8) + F(3))))$
38337 := $(- (F(F(7))) + ((F(3!) + F(F(3!))) \times C(F(8), 3)))$
38346 := $(C((F(6) + F(4)), 3!) \times 83)$
38347 := $((- (F(7)) + F(4!)) - (C((F(3) \times 8), 3!)))$
38373 := $((C((F(3) \times F(7)), 3!) + 8) / 3!)$
38377 := $(- ((F(F(7)) - (C((F(7) + F(3)), 8) \times 3!)))$

- 38394** := $(F(4!) + ((F(9) - C((F(3) \times 8), 3!)))$
38402 := $(C(20, F((F(4)!)) - (F(F(8)) \times F(3!)))$
38415 := $((5! - 1) - C(4!, F(8))) + (F(3!))!$
38431 := $(1 + (F(C(3!, 4)) \times (F(8) \times 3)))$
38432 := $(2 + (F(C(3!, 4)) \times (F(8) \times 3)))$
38433 := $((F(C(3!, F(3))) \times (F(4) \times F(8))) + 3)$
38442 := $(((-2) - (F((F(4)!))!) \times (-F(4)!)) - C(F(8), F(3!)))$
38454 := $((4! - 5) \times C(4!, F(8))) - F(3)$
38456 := $(((-6) + 5!) \times C(4!, F(8))) / 3!$
38462 := $(((-2) + F(F(6))) \times C(4!, F(8))) + 3!$
38466 := $((F(6)! - ((F(C(6, 4)) + 8) \times 3))$
38478 := $(8! - ((C(F(7), F(4)) + F(8)) \times 3!))$
38486 := $((F(6)! - ((F(8) \times 4!) + C(F(8), 3)))$
38527 := $-((F(F(7)) - C(-((F(2)^5!) - F(8))), 3!))$
38556 := $(F(F(6)) \times (5! + C((5 + 8), 3!)))$
38564 := $(F(4!) - ((6^5) + C(8, F(3))))$
38594 := $(4! + ((F(9) - 5) \times C(F(8), 3)))$
38603 := $-(((C(F((3! + 0!)), 6) - 8!) + F(F(3))))$
38604 := $((F(4)! \times (-0!) + C((-6) + F(8), F(3!)))$
38607 := $-(((C(F(7), 06) - 8!) - 3))$
38658 := $((8 + C((5!/F(6)), 8)) \times 3!)$
38667 := $((-C(F(7), 6) + (F(6)!)) + (F(8) \times 3))$
38725 := $-(((F((C(5, 2) + 7)) - 8!) - F(3)))$
38736 := $((C(C(6, F(3)), 7) + F(8)) \times 3!)$
38747 := $-((F(7) - C(((4 \times 7) - 8), 3!))$
38784 := $(4! + C((F(8) + ((7 - 8))), 3!))$
38824 := $((((F(4)!))! \times (-2)) + ((8! - C(8, 3))))$
38837 := $((F(F(7)) + (F(3!))!) - C((-8) + F(8), 3!))$
38846 := $(((-6) \times 4!) + 8!) - C(F(8), 3)$
38848 := $(((-C(8, 4)) \times F(8)) + 8!) - F(3)$
38857 := $-(((F(7) + 5!) - 8!) + C(F(8), 3))$
38867 := $((-F(7) + (F(6)!)) - ((8!/C(8, F(3))))$
38875 := $(-5) \times (F(F(7)) - (C((8 + 8), 3!)))$
38933 := $((F(3!))! - F((F(3!) + 9))) + C(F(8), F(3))$
38944 := $((((F(4)!))! / (-F(F(4)))) + ((F(C(9, 8))^3)))$
38948 := $(8! - (49 \times C(8, F(3))))$
38956 := $((F(C(6, 5)))! - ((F(9) + C(F(8), 3))))$
38977 := $((-F(7) + (F((F(F(7) - 9)))!)) - (C(F(8), 3)))$
38981 := $((((1 \times 8)! - 9) - C(F(8), 3))$
38982 := $((F(2) + 8!) - 9) - C(F(8), 3)$
38984 := $((F(4) + 8!) - 9) - C(F(8), 3)$
39033 := $((F(3!))! - C(F((3! + 0!)), F((9 - 3))))$
39067 := $(-((C(F(7), F(6)) - F(09))) + (F(3!))!)$
39105 := $(F(C(5, (0! + 1))) \times (-9 + 3!))$
39328 := $((C((8/2), 3))! + (F(9)^3))$
39435 := $-((F(C(5, 3)) \times (F(4) - ((9 - 3)!)))$
39516 := $((F(6)! - ((1 + 5)! + C(9, 3)))$
39604 := $(F(4!) + (0! - F(C(6, (9/3))))$
39633 := $(((-3) - 3!) + (F(6)!)) + C(9, F(3))$
39648 := $(C(8, F(4)) \times (6! - (9 + 3)))$
39653 := $((F(3!))! - (-5 - (F(6) \times (-C(9, 3))))$
39675 := $-(((5! - C(F(7), F(6))) \times F(9)) + 3)$
39759 := $((F(9) + 5!) - C(F(7), 9)) + (F(3!))!$
39825 := $((F(((5 - 2)!))! - C((F(8) - 9), F(3!)))$
39858 := $(8! - C(((5! - F(8)) / 9), 3!))$
39859 := $-(((F((9 + 5)) - 8!) + C(9, 3)))$
39897 := $((F(7) + F(C(9, 8))) \times (-9)) + (F(3!))!$
39915 := $(-(((C(5, 1) \times 9) \times 9)) + (F(3!))!)$
39923 := $(F(C(3!, 2)) + (9 + (F(9)^3)))$
39956 := $((F(6)! - C((5 + 9), (9/3)))$
40034 := $((F((F(4)!))! - C(F((3! + 0!)), F(04)))$
40042 := $((-2) - C(4!, (0! + 0!))) + (F((F(4)!))!)$
40043 := $((F(3!))! - (C(4!, (0! + 0!))) - F(F(F(4))))$
40044 := $-((C(4!, F(F(4))) - ((0! + 0!)^{F(4)}))!)$
40046 := $((F(6)! - C(4!, (0! + 0!))) + F(F(4)))$
40086 := $((F(6)! - (C(F(8), (0! + 0!)) + 4!))$
40134 := $((4! + (F(3!))!) - C(10, 4))$
40236 := $((F(6)! - C((3^2), F(04)))$
40237 := $((-F(7) + (F(3!))!) - C(F(((2 + 0!))!), 4))$
40252 := $((-2) \times F((C(5, 2) - 0!)) + (F((F(4)!))!))$
40254 := $((C(F((F(4)!)), 5) - F(20)) \times (-F(4)!))$
40305 := $((F((5 + 0!))! - C(3!, 04))$
40369 := $((F(9) + (F(6)!)) + C(3!, 04))$
40389 := $((F(9) + 8!) + C((3! + 0!), F(4)))$
40403 := $((F(3!))! - 0!) + C((F((F(4)!)) + 0!), F(4))$
40446 := $((F(6)! + C((F(4) \times F(4)), 04))$
40459 := $((C(9, 5) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + F((0! + (F(4)!))!))$
40469 := $((-C(9, 6) + (F((F(4)!))!)) + F(F((0! + (F(4)!))!)))$
40475 := $((5! + (C(7, 4))) + (F((F(04)!))!))$
40491 := $(C(19, F(F(4))) + (F((F(04)!))!))$

- 40526** := ((C(F(F(6)), 2) + (F((5+0)!))!) - 4)
40544 := (C(F((F(4)!), F(4)) × ((5+0)! + 4))
40588 := ((- (8) + 8!) + C(((5-0)!), F(F(4))))
40606 := ((F(6)! + C(F((0! + (6))), F(04)))
40637 := ((F(F(7)) + (F(3)!))! + C((F(6) + 0!), F(4)))
40645 := (F(C(5, F(4))) - (F((F(F(6)) - 0!) × (- (F(4)!)))
40647 := (- (((C(F(7), 4) × F(6)) + 0!) + F(4!))
40689 := (- (9) + (C(F(8), F(6)) / (0! + (4))))
40794 := ((F(4)! × (F(9) + F(C((7-0!), F(4))))
40924 := (F(C((F(4)!), 2)) + (((9-0)! - (F(4)!))
40933 := ((F(C(3!, F(3))) + ((9-0)!))! + F(4))
40934 := (F(C((F(4)!), F(3))) + (((9-0)! + 4))
40984 := (((F(4)!))! + (8! - C((9-0!), F(4))))
41068 := ((8! + C(F(6), (0! + 1))) + ((F(4)!))!
41148 := (8! + (C(4!, (1+1)) × F(4))
41184 := (4! × C(F((8-1)), (F((1×4)!))
41244 := ((F((F(4)!))! + C((4!/2), (F((1×4)!))
41273 := ((3!! + F(F(7))) + (((C(2, 1) × 4)!))
41328 := (F(((8/2)!)) - (((C(3, 1) + 4)!))
41334 := (F(4!) + 3! - ((C(3, 1) + 4)!))
41343 := ((C(3!, 4) - ((3! + 1)!)) + F(4!))
41363 := ((C((- (3!) + F(F(6))), 3!) × (-1)) + F(4!))
41365 := ((5 × (C(F(F(6)), F(3)) - 1)) + (F((F(4)!))!))
41373 := ((F(3)!))! + (F(7) × (C(3, 1)⁴))
41376 := ((F(6) + C(F(7), 3!)) × ((1×4)!))
41484 := ((4 × F(F(8))) - C((4! + 1), F(4)))
41494 := (((F((F(4)!))! + F(9)) + C((F(F((F(4)!)) - 1), F(4)))
41523 := - ((C((F(F(3!)) - F(2)), (5-1)) - F(4!))
41573 := (((F(3)!))! + (C(F(7), 5))) - F((1 + F((F(4)!))!))
41577 := ((F(7) × F((C(7, 5) - 1))) - F(4!))
41606 := (((F(6)! - 0!) + C(F((6+1)), F((F(4)!))
41607 := (((7+0)!))! + C(F((6+1)), F((F(4)!))
41608 := ((8! + 0!) + C(F((6+1)), F((F(4)!))
41616 := ((F(6)! + (C((1×6), 1)⁴))
41636 := ((C(F(F(6)), 3) + (F(6)!)) - 14)
41645 := ((- (5) + (F((F(4)!))!))! + C(F(F(6)), F((1×4)))
41646 := ((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + (F(6)!)) - (1×4))
41648 := ((C(F(8), F(4)) + (F(6)!)) - (- (1) + F(4)))
41664 := ((4! + 6!) × C(F(6), F((1×4)))
41775 := - ((5! - (7 × C(F((7+1)), 4)))
41847 := ((- (F(7)) + (F((F(4)!))!))! + C((F(8) + 1), F(4)))
41873 := ((F(3)!))! + (F(7) + C((F(8) + 1), F(4)))
41884 := ((4! + 8!) + C((F(8) + 1), F(4)))
41937 := (7 × (3! + C(F((9-1)), 4)))
41984 := - (((F(4)! - (C(F(8), 9) / (1 + (F(4)!))!))
41985 := (- (5) + (C(F(8), 9) / (1 + (F(4)!))!))
42025 := ((- (5) + C(F(F(((2+0)!))!)) , 2))^{F(F(4))}
42037 := ((C(F(7), 3!) + 0!) + ((2×4)!))
42168 := (8! + (C((F(F(6)) + 1), 2) × F((F(4)!))!))
42187 := - ((F((F(7) + (C(8, 1) - 2))) - F(4!))
42264 := (F(4!) + (C((F(F(6)) - 2), 2) × (-4!))
42337 := ((- (7) + (F(3)!))! + C(((F(3) + 2)!), F(4)))
42341 := ((- (1) + (C(4!, 3) - 2)) + (F((F(4)!))!))
42343 := - ((F(F(3)) - (C(4!, 3) + ((2×4)!))!))
42344 := (C(4!, F(4)) + ((32/4)!))
42345 := (((C(C(5, F(4)), F(3))²) + (F((F(4)!))!))
42346 := ((F(6)! + (C(4!, 3) - ((2-4)))
42354 := (C(4!, 5) - (3! × (F(2) + 4!))
42364 := ((C((4! - F(6)), 3!) / (-2)) + F(4!))
42368 := (8! + ((F(6)^{C(3,2)}) × 4))
42373 := ((F(3)!))! + (F(F(7)) + C((F(3!) × 2), 4))
42428 := (((C(F(8), 2) - (4)²) - F((F(4)!))
42433 := (((C(F(F(3!)), F(3)) - 4)²) - F(4))
42434 := ((((- (4) + C(F(F(3!)), F(F(4))))²) - F(F(4)))
42435 := (((5! + F(F(3!))) × C((F(4)!), 2)) + (F((F(4)!))!))
42447 := (- (F(F(7))) + ((F(F(F((F(4)!))!)) - (C(4!, 2))) × 4))
42448 := - ((C(8, F(4)) - C(4!, (F(2) + (4))))
42449 := - ((F((F(9) - 4!)) - (C(4!, (F(2) + (4))))
42459 := (- ((9 × 5)) + C(4!, (F(2) + (4))))
42463 := - ((F((- (F(3)) + F(F(6)))) + (- (C(4!, 2)) - F(4!)))
42464 := (F(F(4)) × (- (6!) + (C(F((F(4)!), 2))^{F(4)}))
42476 := - ((F(F(6)) + (7 - C(4!, (F(2) + (4))))
42491 := ((- (C(19, 4)) - F(2)) + F(4!))
42493 := - (((F(3) + 9) - C(4!, (F(2) + (4))))
42494 := ((4! - F(9)) + C(4!, (F(2) + (4))))
42502 := (- (2) + C((- ((0! - 5)))! , (F(2) + (4)))
42503 := (C(((3+0)!), 5) - (F(2)^{4!}))
42505 := (C(((5-0)!), 5) + (F(2)^{4!}))
42513 := ((C(((3+1)!), 5) + F(2)) + F((F(4)!))
42514 := ((C(4!, (1×5)) + 2) + F((F(4)!))

- 42525** := $(C(((5 - F(2)))!, 5) + F((2 \times 4)))$
42548 := $(F(8) + ((C(4!, 5) - F(2)) + 4!))$
42552 := $(C((-((F(2) - (5))))!, 5) + (2 \times 4!))$
42554 := $((C(4!, 5) + (52)) - F(F(4)))$
42559 := $(C(((9 - 5))!, 5) + F((2 + F((F(4))!))))$
42625 := $(F(C(5, 2)) \times (F((F(6) + 2)) + ((F(4))!)))$
42644 := $((4 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - C((F(F(6)) - F(2)), F(4)))$
42654 := $(C(4!, 5) + (6 \times (F(2) + 4)))$
42693 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (9 + C(((6 - 2))!, F(4))))$
42694 := $((F((F(F(4)) \times 9)) - C(F(F(6)), 2)) + (F((F(4))!)))$
42721 := $((F(((1 + 2))!))! + (C(7, F(2))^4))$
42723 := $((F(3!))! + (2 + (C(7, F(2))^4)))$
42733 := $(-((F(C(3!, F(3))) - (F(F(7))^2))) - F(F(F((F(4))!))))$
42737 := $(F(F(7)) + C((-((3 - 7))!), (F(2) + (4))))$
42775 := $((- (5) + C(F(7), 7)) \times (F(2) + 4))$
42843 := $-3! + (F(4) - C(F(8), 2))^{F(F(4))}$
42866 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(F(6)), F((8/2))) \times 4!))$
42898 := $((8! + F((C(9, 8) \times 2))) - (F(4))!)$
42967 := $-((F(F(7)) - (6! \times (C(9, 2) + 4))))$
42984 := $((C(4!, F(8)) - F(F((9 - 2)))) \times 4!)$
43024 := $((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - C(20, F(3))) \times 4)$
43038 := $(C((F(8) - 3), F((03)!)) - ((F(4))!))$
43089 := $((9! - F(8)) - C((0! + F(F(3))), F((F(4))!)))$
43092 := $(- (C((29 - 0!), 3)) + F(4!))$
43097 := $(- ((F(7) - 9!) - C((0! + F(F(3))), F((F(4))!)))$
43109 := $((9! - 0!) - C((1 + F(F(3))), F((F(4))!)))$
43144 := $((C(4!, 4) + F(F(F(((1 \times 3))!)))) \times F(F(4)))$
43174 := $((4 \times F(F((7 + 1)))) - F(C(3!, 4)))$
43232 := $-(((2 \times C(F(3!), 2))^{F(3)} - F(4!)))$
43233 := $-((((C(F(3!), 3)^2) - F(F(3))) - F(4!)))$
43238 := $((- ((C(8, 3)^2)) + 3!) + F(4!))$
43253 := $((- ((C(F(3!), 5)^2)) + F(F(3!))) + F(4!))$
43256 := $((6! \times 5!) / 2) + C(F(3!), F(4))$
43258 := $(- ((F(F(8)) + (5!/2))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43265 := $((- (5) \times (- (F(C(6, 2))) + F(F(3!)))) + (F((F(4))!)))$
43278 := $((8! + C(F(7), 2)) - (3! \times (-4)))$
43286 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (F(8) \times C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), F(4))))$
43294 := $((- (4!) - F(F((9 - F(2)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43299 := $(9 \times (- (F(9)) + C((- (F(2)) + F(F(3!))), 4))$
43309 := $((- (9) - F(F(F((03)!)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43312 := $(- (F(21)) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - (F(4))!))$
43313 := $((- ((3! - 1)) - F(F(F(3!)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43314 := $((- (4) - F(F(F(((1 \times 3))!)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43315 := $-((F(F(F((5 + 1)))) - (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - F(4)))$
43317 := $((C((F(7) + 1), 3!) + (F(3!))! - (F(4))!)$
43318 := $(C(F(8), ((1 \times 3))!) - F((- (3) + 4!))$
43319 := $(- (F(F((9 - 1)))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + F(F(F(4))))$
43321 := $((1 + 2) - F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43322 := $((2 + 2) - F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43323 := $((F((3 \times 2))! + C((3! + F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43324 := $(- (F(F((4 \times 2)))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + (F(4))!))$
43325 := $((5 + 2) - F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43327 := $((C((7 \times 2), 3!) + (F(3!))! + 4)$
43329 := $((9 + 2) - F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43331 := $((13 - F(F(F(3!)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43335 := $((- ((F(C(5, 3))^{F(3)})) - F(3!)) + F(4!))$
43344 := $(F(4!) - (4! \times C((3 \times 3), 4)))$
43345 := $((F(C(5, F(4)))^{F(3)} + ((F(3))^{F(4)}))!)$
43353 := $((F(3!))! + (F(C(5, 3))^{F(3)})) + F((F(4))!))$
43359 := $(- ((C((9 + 5), 3!) + 3!) + F(4!))$
43363 := $(- ((C((3! + F(6)), 3!) + F(3))) + F(4!))$
43364 := $((F(4!) + (F(6))!) / F(3)) + C(3!, F(4))$
43365 := $((5! + (F(6))!) + C((3^3), 4!))$
43366 := $((- (C((F(6) + (6)), 3!) + F(F(3))) + F(4!))$
43367 := $((- (F(7)) + (F(6))!) + C((3 \times 3!), 4))$
43371 := $(- ((C((1 + F(7)), 3!) - 3!) + F(4!))$
43373 := $((F(3!) - C((7 \times F(3)), 3!)) + F(4!))$
43397 := $((79 - F(F(F(3!)))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43398 := $((C((F(8) - 9), F(3!)) \times (-3!)) + F(4!))$
43399 := $((9 \times 9) - F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$
43425 := $((52 \times ((F(4))!)) + C(F(F(3!)), 4)$
43438 := $(- (F(F(8))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!) + ((F(3) + F(4))!))$
43442 := $((- (F(2)) + F(4!)) - C((4! + 3), 4!))$
43443 := $(F((3! \times 4)) - C((4! + 3), 4!))$
43456 := $((C(F(6), 5)^{F(F(4))}) + ((F(3))^{F(4)}))!$
43458 := $((C(8, 5)^{F(F(4))}) + (F(3!))! + F(F(4)))$
43475 := $(- ((5! - ((C(7, 4)^3)))) + ((F(4))!))$
43478 := $((8! + F(F(7))) + C((4! + 3), 4!))$
43543 := $((3! \times (-4)) + (F(C(5, 3)))) + F(4!))$
43558 := $(- ((F(F(8)) - (5! + 5!))) + C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!))$

- 43596** := $((F(6))! + C((9+5) \times F(3), F(4)))$
43629 := $((9! - (2 \times 6!)) - F(C(F(3), F(F(4))))$
43638 := $(C(F(8), 3!) - C((F(6) \times 3), 4))$
43644 := $(- (C(4!, 4) + (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (F(4))!))$
43658 := $(((8^5) + F(F(F(6)))) - C(F(3!), F(4)))$
43684 := $(F(4!) - ((8!/C(6, F(3))) - (4)))$
43685 := $((5 - (8!/C(6, F(3)))) + F(4!))$
43694 := $(((4^9) + C(6, 3)) / (F(4))!)$
43704 := $(4! \times (0! + C((F(7) + 3), 4)))$
43714 := $((4 \times F(F((1+7)))) - C(F(3!), 4))$
43716 := $((F((F(6) + 1)) \times (-C(F(7), F(3)))) + F(4!))$
43735 := $(- (5) + ((3^7) \times C(3!, F(4))))$
43753 := $(F(F(3)) + (C((5 + F(7)), F(3!)) - (F(4))!))$
43759 := $(C((C(9, 5) / 7), F(3!)) + F(F(F(4))))$
43778 := $((F(F(8)) \times (C(7, 7) + 3)) - (F(4))!)$
43804 := $((4 \times F(F(08))) + C(3!, F(4)))$
43874 := $((F(4!) - F(F(7))) - (C(F(8), 3!) / 4!))$
43891 := $((F(19) + 8!) - F(C(3!, 4)))$
43894 := $((4! + 9) \times C(F(8), 3)) + (4)$
43993 := $((3^9) + C((F(9) / F(3)), F((F(4))!)))$
43997 := $(F(F(7)) + (C((9+9), F(3!)) + (F(4))!))$
44034 := $((F(4))! \times (C((F(F(3!)) + 0!), 4) + (4!)))$
44038 := $(- (F(F(8))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(04))!) + ((F(4))!)))$
44073 := $((F(3!))! + (7!)) - C(F((0! + (F(4))!)), F((F(4))!))$
44095 := $(- (5) + (C((9+0!), 4)^{F(F(4))}))$
44104 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!)), (0! + 1))^{F(F(4))}) + 4)$
44106 := $((C(F(F(6)), (0! + 1))^{F(F(4))}) + (F(4))!)$
44108 := $((C(F(8), (0! + 1))^{F(F(4))}) + F((F(4))!))$
44124 := $(4! + (C(21, F(F(4)))^{F(F(4))}))$
44149 := $((F(9)^{F(4)}) + C((- (1) + F(F((F(4))!))), 4))$
44187 := $((- (C(F(7), 8)) \times (- (1) - ((F(4))!))) / F(F((F(4))!)))$
44196 := $((F(6))! + C((F((9-1)) - F(F(4))), 4))$
44224 := $((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 2) + 2)^{F(F(4))}) - (((F(4))!)))$
44235 := $(- (5) \times (F(3!) - C(- ((F(2) - 4!)), 4)))$
44245 := $(- (5) \times (- (C((4! - F(2)), 4) + (F(4))!))$
44249 := $9 \times F(F(F(F(4)))) - F(2) - C(F(F(F(4))), F(4))$
44254 := $(- ((F(F((F(4))!)) - (C((5^2), (F(4))!) / 4)))$
44313 := $((F(3!))! + ((1 + C(F(F(3!)), F(4))) \times F(4)))$
44318 := $((- (C(F(8), (1 \times 3))) + F(4!)) - ((F(4))!))$
44333 := $((C(F(F(3!)), F(3))^{F(3)}) + F(F((F(4) + (4))))$
44334 := $((F(4!) - F(3!)) - ((F(3) + C(4!, F(4))))$
44335 := $((5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) + (C(F(F(3!)), 4))) - (F((F(4))!)))$
44336 := $((F((F(6) \times 3)) - F(3!)) - (C(4!, F(4))))$
44337 := $(- (7) - (C(((F(3) + F(3)))!, F(4)) - F(4!)))$
44338 := $((F((8 \times 3)) - 3!) - C(4!, F(4)))$
44341 := $((- (1) + F(4!)) - ((F(3) + C(4!, F(4))))$
44342 := $((F(24) - F(3)) - C(4!, F(4)))$
44343 := $((- (3) + F(4!)) + (F(3) - C(4!, F(4))))$
44345 := $((- (5) + F(4!)) + (3! - C(4!, F(4))))$
44346 := $((F((6 \times 4)) + F(3)) - C(4!, F(4)))$
44354 := $(F(4!) - (- (C(5, 3)) + C(4!, F(4))))$
44357 := $((- (C(F(7), 5)) - 3!) + F(4!)) - 4$
44359 := $((9! - C((- (5) + F(F(3!))), (F(4))!)) / F((F(4))!))$
44361 := $(- ((C(F((1+6)), F(3!)) - F(4!))) - ((F(4))!))$
44364 := $(F(4!) - (- (C(6, 3)) + C(4!, F(4))))$
44366 := $((C((F(6) + F(6)), 3!) / (-4)) + F(4!))$
44368 := $(8! - (- ((6/3) \times C(4!, F(4))))$
44404 := $(F((F((F(4))! + 0!)) \times (C(F(F((F(4))!)), F(4)) - 4!))$
44436 := $((F(F(6)) + F(3)) \times F(4!)) / (C(4, F(4))!)$
44448 := $((8! + (C(4!, F(4)) \times 4!)) / F(F(4)))$
44456 := $((- ((F(6) - 5!)) + F(4!)) - (C(4!, F(4))))$
44457 := $((- (7) + 5!) + F(4!)) - (C(4!, F(4)))$
44458 := $((- ((F(8) \times 5!)) + F(4!)) + F(C((F(4))!, F(F(4))))$
44462 := $((F(2) + F(F(6))) \times (C(4!, F(4)) - F(4)))$
44472 := $((2^7) + F(4!)) - (C(4!, F(4)))$
44475 := $((C((5 + F(7)), F((F(4))!)) - F(4)) + ((F(4))!))$
44485 := $((5! + F(8)) + F(4!)) - (C(4!, F(4)))$
44523 := $(- ((C(3!, 2) \times (5! + F(4)))) + F(4!))$
44528 := $((F(8) + (F(2)^5!)) \times C(4!, F(4)))$
44543 := $((F(C(3!, 4)) \times 5!) - F((4! - F(F(F(4)))))$
44548 := $(- (C(((8 + F(4)) + (5)), 4)) + F(4!))$
44574 := $(C(4!, F(7)) / C((5 + F(4)), F(4)))$
44583 := $(F(F(3!)) \times (- ((F(8) - 5!) - C(4!, F(4))))$
44584 := $(- (C(4!, F(8))) - ((- (5!) \times F(F(4))) - F(4!)))$
44585 := $(5 \times (F(F(8)) + (- (5) - C(4!, F(4))))$
44597 := $((C(((F(7) - 9))!, 5) / (-4!)) + F(4!))$
44605 := $(- (5) \times ((0! - F(F(F(6)))) + (C(4!, F(4))))$
44615 := $(- (5) \times ((- (1) - F(F(F(6)))) + (C(4!, F(4))))$
44631 := $((- (1) + (3!^6)) - C(4!, F(4)))$

- 44632** := $((2 \times 3)^6) - C(4!, F(4))$
44633 := $(F(F(3)) + ((3!)^6) - C(4!, F(4)))$
44636 := $((6! \times 3! + C(F(6), F(4))) - (4))$
44639 := $((9!/F(3!)) - (6! + C(4, 4)))$
44651 := $(- (1) - (C((5 + F(6)), (F(4))!) - F(4!)))$
44654 := $(F(4!) - (C((5 + F(6)), (F(4))!) - F(F(4))))$
44656 := $((- (C((F(6) + 5), 6)) + F(4!)) + 4)$
44658 := $((- (C((8 + 5), 6)) + F(4!)) + (F(4)!))$
44661 := $(- ((F(16) + 6!)) + F((C(4, F(4))!))$
44673 := $(((- (3) - C(F(7), 6)) + F(4!)) + (4!))$
44675 := $(- (5) \times ((- (F(7)) - F(F(F(6)))) + (C(4!, F(4))))$
44676 := $((F(F(6)) - C(F(7), 6)) + F(4!)) + F(4)$
44677 := $(((- (C(F(7), 7)) + F(F(6))) + F(4!)) + 4)$
44684 := $((- (4) - 8!) + (F(6) \times C(4!, 4)))$
44697 := $((F(F(7)) - ((F(9) \times C(F(6), F(4)))) + F(4!))$
44757 := $(C(7, 5) + ((- (F(F(7))) \times F((F(4))!) \times (-4!)))$

44804 := $(F(4!) - (C((0! + F(8)), F(4)) + 4!))$
44808 := $(- (8!) + (C(- ((0! - F(8))), (F(4))!) + F(4!))$
44819 := $((- (9) - C((1 + F(8)), F(4))) + F(4!))$
44828 := $((F(8) + F(2)) \times (-C(8, 4)) + F(4!))$
44829 := $((- (9) \times C((- (2) + F(8)), F(F(4)))) + F(4!))$
44846 := $(- (((F(6) \times 4!) + C(F(8), F(4)))) + F(4!))$
44864 := $((C(4!, 6) - (8 - 4)) / F(4))$
44877 := $((F(F(7)) \times (7 \times F(8))) + C(4!, 4))$
44889 := $((- (9) + (F(8) \times (-C(8, 4)))) + F(4!))$
44914 := $(F((F((F(4))!) + 1)) \times (- (9) + C(F(F((F(4))!)), F(4))))$
44969 := $(- ((F(9) + (C((6 + 9), 4)))) + F(4!))$
44987 := $(- ((C(F(7), 8) + (94))) + F(4!))$
44994 := $(F(4!) - (9 + C((- (9) + 4!), 4)))$
45024 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(((2 + 0!))!), 5) \times 4!))$
45033 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) \times (-0!)) - (5 - F(4!)))$
45034 := $(F(4!) - (C(F(F(3!)), F(- ((0! - 5)))) + 4)$
45036 := $((- (C(F(F(6)), 3)) + F(- ((0! - 5)))) - F(F(4)))$
45038 := $(- (C(F(8), 3)) + F(((0 \times 5) + 4)!))$
45043 := $((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) \times (-0!)) - (- (5) - F(4!)))$
45044 := $((F(4!) + (F(4))!) - C(F(F((0! + 5))), F(4)))$
45046 := $(- (((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - F((0! + 5)))) - F(4!)))$
45057 := $((- (C(F(7), 5)) - (- ((0! - 5)))) + F(4!))$
45068 := $(- (((F(C(8, 6)) + 0!) - ((5 + 4)!)))$
45073 := $(- (((F(3!) + (C(F(7), 05))) - F(4!)))$

45081 := $(- (1) \times (C(F((8 - 0!)), 5) - F(4!)))$
45082 := $(F(2) - (C(F((8 - 0!)), 5) - F(4!)))$
45084 := $(F(4!) - (C(F((8 - 0!)), 5) - F(4!)))$
45087 := $(- (((C(F(7), 8) - 0!) - (5))) + F(4!))$
45158 := $(- ((C(F(8), F((5 - 1))) - 5!) + F(4!))$
45165 := $(C((5!/6), - ((1 - 5))) + (F((F(4))!))$
45239 := $((9!/F(3!)) - (F(2) + (C(5, 4)!))$
45261 := $(- ((F((1 + C(6, 2))) + 5!) + F(4!))$
45318 := $((C(F(8), F((1 \times 3))) \times (-5)) + F(4!))$
45323 := $((F(3!))! - (2 - C((3 \times 5), (F(4))!))$
45325 := $((F(((5 - 2)!))! + (C((3 \times 5), (F(4))!))$
45328 := $((C(F(8), 2) - F(3)) \times (-5)) + F(4!))$
45339 := $((9!/F(3!)) - F((3 + C(5, 4)))$
45343 := $(- (((F(F(3)) - F(4!)) + (F(3)^{C(5, F(4))}))$
45344 := $(F(4!) - (C(4, 3)^{C(5, 4)}))$
45417 := $((7! + 1) + C(F((F(4))!), 5) + (F((F(4))!))$
45418 := $((C((F(8) - 1), F(F(4))) \times (-5)) + F(4!))$
45438 := $((C(F(8), F(3)) - 4!) \times (-5)) + F(4!))$
45439 := $((9!/F(3!)) + (4!)) + F(C(5, F(4)))$
45446 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C(4!, F(F(4))) \times (5^{F(4)}))$
45449 := $(- (((C((9 + F(4)), (F(4))!) - (5)) - F(4!))$
45475 := $(((- (5) + 7!) + (F((F(4))!))! + (C(5, 4)!))$
45476 := $((F(6))! + ((7! - 4) + (C(5, 4)!))$
45477 := $((7! + F(7)) \times (4 + C(5, 4)))$
45494 := $((F(4!) - F(9)) - ((F(4))!)) - (C(5, 4)!))$
45543 := $((C(3!, 4) \times (-55)) + F(4!))$
45567 := $((7! - (C(F(F(6)), 5) - 5!)) \times (-F(4)))$
45571 := $(- ((C((- (1) + F(7)), 5) + (5))) + F(4!))$
45573 := $(- ((3 + C((7 + 5), 5))) + F(4!))$
45574 := $((F(4!) - C((7 + 5), 5)) - F(F(4)))$
45627 := $((- (C(7, 2)) - (C(6, 5)!)) + F(4!))$
45634 := $(F(4!) - ((3^6) + C(5, 4)))$
45636 := $(((- (6) \times F(3)) - (C(6, 5)!)) + F(4!))$
45638 := $((F((8 \times 3)) - 6!) - C(5, F(4)))$
45642 := $((- (2) + F(4!)) - ((C(6, 5)! + 4)))$
45644 := $(F(4!) - (4 + (C(6, (5 - 4))!))$
45649 := $((- (9) + F(4!)) - (6! - C(5, F(4))))$
45652 := $(- (((F(2) - 5)) + (C(6, 5)!)) + F(4!))$
45661 := $((F((1 + 6)) - (C(6, 5)!)) + F(4!))$
45667 := $((F(7) + (6)) - (C(6, 5)!)) + F(4!))$

$$45676 := ((F(F(6)) - (-7) + (C(6,5)!)) + F(4!))$$

$$45693 := (-3) + (F(9) \times (C(F(6), 5) \times 4!))$$

$$45694 := ((F(4!) - (9 + 6!)) + F(C(5, F(4))))$$

$$45726 := ((F(C(6,2)) \times 75) - 4!)$$

$$45759 := (((F(9) - 5)) \times (-C(7,5))) + F(4!))$$

$$45766 := ((F(6) - F(C(6, (7-5)))) + F(4!))$$

$$45789 := ((9!/8) + (C(F(7), 5) / F(4)))$$

$$45794 := ((F(4!) + C(9,7)) - F((5 \times F(4))))$$

$$45797 := (-((C(F(7), 9) - F((7+5)))) + F(4!))$$

$$45798 := ((F(F(8)) + (C(9,7) \times 5!)) \times F(4))$$

$$45838 := ((F(F(8)) + C((3! + F(8)), 5)) / F(F(4)))$$

$$45856 := (-((F(C(6,5))^{8-5})) + F(4!))$$

$$45884 := (F(4!) - ((C(8,8) + 5!) \times 4))$$

$$45894 := ((F(4!) - F(9)) - (8 \times F(C(5, F(4))))$$

$$45906 := -((C((F(F(6)) - (0! + 9)), 5) - F(4!))$$

$$45933 := (-((C(3!, F(3)) \times (F(9) - 5))) + F(4!))$$

$$45962 := (F(-((2-6)))! - C((F(9) - 5), F(F(4))))$$

$$46004 := (F(4!) - C((0! + F((0! + 6))), F(4)))$$

$$46038 := (((C(8,3) - 0!) \times (-6)) + F(4!))$$

$$46115 := -((C(((5-1)! - 1), F(F(6))) - F(4!))$$

$$46163 := ((C(F(3!), 6) - F(F((1+6)))) + F(4!))$$

$$46185 := (-((5! - 8!)) + C(F(F((1 \times 6))), 4))$$

$$46236 := (-(((C(6,3) + 2) \times 6)) + F(4!))$$

$$46241 := ((-1) + F(4!)) - C((F(2) + F(6)), 4))$$

$$46243 := ((F(F(3)) + F(4!)) - C((F(2) + F(6)), 4))$$

$$46248 := -((C((-8) + 4!), 2) - F((6 \times 4)))$$

$$46269 := (-((C((9+6), 2) - 6)) + F(4!))$$

$$46289 := ((-9) + F(((8/2)!)) - C(F(6), 4))$$

$$46311 := ((-1) + F(((1+3)!)) - C(F(6), F(4)))$$

$$46313 := (F(((3+1)!)) - F(C((-3) + F(6)), F(4)))$$

$$46318 := (-((C(C(8,1), 3) - 6)) + F(4!))$$

$$46323 := ((C(3!, 2) \times (-3)) + F((6 \times 4)))$$

$$46403 := (C((3! + 0!), F(4)) + F((6 \times 4)))$$

$$46412 := (-((C(2,1) - 46)) + F(4!))$$

$$46413 := (F(((3+1)!)) + (F(4) \times C(6,4)))$$

$$46418 := ((-((F(8) - 1)) + F(4!)) + C(F(6), 4))$$

$$46421 := ((-((1+2)) + F(4!)) + C(F(6), F(4)))$$

$$46427 := ((-((F(7) - 2)) + F(4!)) + C(F(6), 4))$$

$$46475 := ((5! - F(7)) + F(C(4!, F((6-4))))$$

$$46488 := (((C(8,8) + 4)! + F((6 \times 4)))$$

$$46504 := (F(4!) + ((0! + 5!) + C(6,4)))$$

$$46524 := ((C(4!, 2) - 5!) + F((6 \times 4)))$$

$$46532 := (-((F(2) - C((3! + 5)), F(6))) + F(4!))$$

$$46542 := ((-2) + F(4!)) + (5! + C(F(6), F(4)))$$

$$46549 := ((-9) + F(4!)) + (5! + C(F(6), 4))$$

$$46554 := (F(4!) + (C((5+5), 6) - 4!))$$

$$46586 := ((6^{(8-5)!}) - C(F(6), 4))$$

$$46621 := (C((-1) + (-((2-6)))!), F(F(6))) + F(4!))$$

$$46641 := (((F((1 \times 4)))!^6) - C(6,4))$$

$$46708 := ((8! - F((0! + F(7)))) + F(C(6, F(4))))$$

$$46725 := (((C(5,2) + 7) \times F(F(6))) + F(4!))$$

$$46746 := ((6^{(F(4)!)} + (7!/C(F(6), F(4))))$$

$$46747 := ((-F(7)) + F(4!)) + (7 \times C(F(6), F(4)))$$

$$46758 := (8! + ((5 \times C(F(7), F(6))) + F(4)))$$

$$46766 := ((F(F(6)) + F((C(F(6), 7) + 6))) + F(4!))$$

$$46823 := (F(((F(3) + 2)!)) + C((F(8) - 6), F(4)))$$

$$46842 := ((C((2 \times (F(4)!)), 8) - F(F(6))) + F(4!))$$

$$46852 := -(((F(F((2+5))) - 8!) - F(C(6, F(4))))$$

$$46857 := ((C((7+5), 8) - 6) + F(4!))$$

$$46869 := ((C((-9) + F(F(6))), 8) + 6) + F(4!))$$

$$46874 := (F(4!) + ((F(7) \times (-8)) + F(C(6,4))))$$

$$46894 := (F(4!) - ((F(9) - C((8 + F(6)), F(4))))$$

$$46923 := ((3!! - C((2+9), F(6))) + F(4!))$$

$$46948 := ((-F(8)) + F(4!)) + (-9) + F(C(6,4)))$$

$$46965 := ((-5!) + (F(6)!)) + F(C(((9-6)!), F(4)))$$

$$46977 := ((-C(7,7)) + F((9+6))) + F(4!))$$

$$47048 := (C((F(8) - 4), (0! + F(7))) + F(4!))$$

$$47049 := ((-F(9)) + F(4!)) + C(F(07), 4))$$

$$47068 := (C(8,6) \times (0! + (7!/F(4))))$$

$$47084 := (F(4!) + (((8 \times 0)! + C(F(7), 4)))$$

$$47097 := (((C(F(7), 9) + 0!) + F(7)) + F(4!))$$

$$47122 := ((2 \times F((C(2,1) \times 7))) + F(4!))$$

$$47144 := (((F(4)!))! + (F(4!) + C((1+7), F(4))))$$

$$47194 := -((F(F(F(F(F(4)!))) - (C(F((9-1), 7) / F(F(4))))$$

$$47223 := ((C(F(F(3!)), (2+2)) / 7) + F(4!))$$

$$47226 := ((C((6 \times 2), 2) \times F(7)) + F(4!))$$

$$47227 := (-((F((C(7,2) - 2)) - 7!)) + F(4!))$$

$$47237 := (-F(7)) + (C(F(F(3!)), 2) \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(4)!))))$$

$$47245 := (-5) + (C(F(F(F(F(4)!)), 2) \times (F(F(7)) - F((F(4)!))))$$

$$47264 := (F(4!) + (F(C(6,2)) + C(F(7), F(4))))$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 47337 &:= (F(((7-3)!)) + C((3! + F(7)), F(4))) \\
 47343 &:= ((3! + F(4!)) + C((3! + F(7)), F(4))) \\
 47348 &:= ((-F(8) + F(4!)) + C((F(3) \times 7), 4)) \\
 47367 &:= (((C(F(7), F(6)) + (F(3!))!) + (7!)) + ((F(4!))!)) \\
 47371 &:= (1-7)^{3!} + C(F(7), 4) \\
 47376 &:= (6! + (C((7 + F(3)), 7)^{F(4)})) \\
 47384 &:= (C(4!, F(8)) + ((3 \times 7!) \times F(4))) \\
 47395 &:= ((-((5 - C(9, 3))) \times F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47426 &:= ((F(6))! + (C((-2) + 4!), 7) / 4!) \\
 47439 &:= ((C(9, 3) + F(4!)) + F((F(7) + F(4)))) \\
 47443 &:= (((3! / F(F(4))) + F(4!)) + C(F(7), 4)) \\
 47482 &:= (F(2) + ((C(F(8), (F(4!)) \times 7) / F((F(4!)))))) \\
 47487 &:= ((C(F(7), 8) + F(4!)) - (7 \times 4!)) \\
 47497 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times F(9)) \times (F(4!)) - C(7, 4)) \\
 47541 &:= ((C(((1 \times 4)!), 5) + 7!) - F(4)) \\
 47542 &:= (F(2) + ((C(4!, 5) + 7!) - F(4))) \\
 47543 &:= (F(3) + ((C(4!, 5) + 7!) - F(4))) \\
 47552 &:= ((C((-((F(2) - (5))))!), 5) + (7!)) + F((F(4!))!) \\
 47592 &:= ((C((2 \times 9), 5) / 7) + F(4!)) \\
 47648 &:= ((C(F((F(8) / F(4))), F(6)) - 7) + F(4!)) \\
 47655 &:= (F((5! / 5)) + C((6 + 7), F((F(4!)))))) \\
 47657 &:= ((C(F(7), 5) + F((F(F(6)) / 7))) + F(4!)) \\
 47662 &:= ((C(F((F(2) + (6))), F(6)) + 7) + F(4!)) \\
 47668 &:= ((C((F(8) - F(6)), F(6)) + F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47676 &:= ((F(6) + (C(F(7), F(6)) + F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 47689 &:= (-9) + (C(F(8), (F(F(6)) / 7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47698 &:= (C(F(8), F(-((9 - 6) - 7))) + F(4!)) \\
 47707 &:= -(((F((F(7) + 0!)) - C(F(7), 7)) - F(4!)) \\
 47733 &:= ((C(C(3!, F(3)), F(7)) \times F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47749 &:= ((C((F(9) - (F(4!))!), F(7)) / 7!) + (F((F(4!))!))! \\
 47759 &:= (((-C(9, 5)) + F(F(7))) \times F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47766 &:= ((6 \times F(F((6 + C(7, 7)))) + F(4!)) \\
 47767 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times 6) + C(7, 7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47775 &:= (5! + (C(F(7), F((-7) + F(7)))) + F(4!)) \\
 47879 &:= (((-9) + C(F(7), 8)) + F(F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 47908 &:= (C((F(8) + 0!), F((-9) + F(7))) + F(4!)) \\
 47929 &:= ((F((F(9) / 2)) - C(9, 7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47967 &:= ((C(F(7), 6) + (-9) \times F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 47978 &:= ((F((C(8, 7) + 9)) + F(7)) + F(4!)) \\
 48027 &:= (((C(F(7), 2) + 0!) \times F(8)) + F(4!))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 48077 &:= (((C(F(7), 7) + 0!) - 8) + F(4!)) \\
 48136 &:= (((C(F(F(6)), F(3!)) \times (-1)) + F(F(8))) / (-4)) \\
 48144 &:= ((C(4!, F(4)) - (18)) \times 4!) \\
 48216 &:= ((C((F(F(6)) + 1), 2) \times 8) + F(4!)) \\
 48258 &:= (((F(8) \times (C(5, 2))!) / 8!) + F(4!)) \\
 48259 &:= (((F(9) \times F(C(5, 2))) + F(8)) + F(4!)) \\
 48304 &:= ((C((4! + 0!), 3) \times F(8)) + (4)) \\
 48324 &:= ((C((4! + F(2)), 3) \times F(8)) + 4!) \\
 48328 &:= (8! + C((2 \times F(3!)), (F((8 - 4))))!) \\
 48332 &:= (C((2 \times F(3!)), 3!) + ((8! + (4)))) \\
 48366 &:= (((6! - F(C(6, 3))) \times (-8)) + (F(4!))! \\
 48367 &:= (((C(F(7), F(6)) + 3!) - 8) + F(4!)) \\
 48386 &:= ((-6) + C((8 \times 3), F(8))) + F(4!)) \\
 48413 &:= ((C(((3 + 1)!), F(4)) + F(8)) + F(4!)) \\
 48414 &:= (F(F((F(4!))!)) + ((1 + C(4!, F(8))) + F(4!))) \\
 48416 &:= ((F(6))! - (C(((1 \times 4)!), F(8)) \times (-4))) \\
 48426 &:= ((F((F(6) + F(2))) + (C(4!, F(8)))) + F(4!)) \\
 48431 &:= (-1) - ((3! - C(4!, F(8))) \times 4!) \\
 48432 &:= ((-((2 \times 3)) + C(4!, F(8))) \times 4!) \\
 48433 &:= (F(F(3)) - ((3! - C(4!, F(8))) \times 4!)) \\
 48434 &:= (F(F(4)) - ((3! - C(4!, F(8))) \times 4!)) \\
 48435 &:= ((-5!) - F(F(3!))) + ((C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!)) \\
 48442 &:= ((-2) \times (C(4!, 4) - 8!)) - F(F(F((F(4!)))))) \\
 48447 &:= ((F((F(7) - F(4))) + (C(4!, F(8)))) + F(4!)) \\
 48448 &:= (8! - ((C(4!, F(4)) + 8) \times (-4))) \\
 48451 &:= (1 + (5 \times (C(F(F((F(4!))!), 8) / F(F((F(4!))!)))))) \\
 48452 &:= (2 + (5 \times (C(F(F((F(4!))!), 8) / F(F((F(4!))!)))))) \\
 48453 &:= ((-3) - 5!) + (C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!) \\
 48454 &:= ((4! \times (-5) + C(4!, F(8))) - F(F(4))) \\
 48456 &:= (F(6) \times ((-5) + C(4!, F(8))) \times F(4)) \\
 48457 &:= (((F(7) \times 5) + C(4!, F(8))) + F(4!)) \\
 48466 &:= (C(F(F(6)), 6) + ((F(4!) / (-8)) - F(F(4))) \\
 48477 &:= (((F(F(7)) \times C(7, 4)) + 8!) + F(F(4))) \\
 48479 &:= (-97) + (C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!) \\
 48486 &:= ((6! / (-8)) + (C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!)) \\
 48488 &:= (-88) + (C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!) \\
 48494 &:= (((F(4) \times F(9)) + C(4!, F(8))) + F(4!)) \\
 48496 &:= ((6! / (-9)) + (C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!)) \\
 48497 &:= (-79) + (C(4!, F(8)) \times 4!) \\
 48514 &:= (((-C(4!, (1 + 5))) - F(F(8))) / (-F(4)))
 \end{aligned}$$

- 48546** := $((- (6) + (C (4!, 5) - 8!)) + F (4!))$
48552 := $- (((F (2) - C ((5!/5), F (8))) \times 4!))$
48576 := $(C (((6 - 7) + 5)!, F (8)) \times 4!)$
48624 := $((C (4!, 2) + (6)) \times 8) + F (4!)$
48644 := $(4! + (C ((- (4) + F (F (6))), 8) \times F (F (4))))$
48648 := $((C (F (8), 4) \times F (6)) / F (8)) + F (4!)$
48707 := $(- (F (7)) + ((- (0!) + F (F (7))) \times C (F (8), F (F (4))))$
48714 := $- (((F (4))! - ((- (1) + F (F (7))) \times C (F (8), F (F (4))))$
48738 := $((C (F (8), F (3)) \times F (F (7))) - (8 \times 4!))$
48744 := $((C (4!, F (4)) + (7)) \times ((8 - 4)!))$
48746 := $((- (C ((- (6) + 4!), F (7))) + F (F (8))) + F (4!))$
48769 := $((C ((9 + F (6)), F (7)) + F (8)) + F (4!))$
48783 := $((F (F (3!)) \times (-F (8))) - (7! - C (F (8), (F (4))!)))$
48892 := $((- (2) \times F (9)) \times (C (8, 8) - ((F (4))!)))$
48897 := $- ((7! + (9 \times (- (8) - C (F (8), 4))))$
48904 := $- ((F (F (F ((F (4))!))) - ((0! + 9) \times C (F (8), 4)))$
48924 := $((F (4!) + F ((2 \times 9))) - C (8, F (F (4))))$
48938 := $((C (F (8), F (3)) \times F ((F (9) - F (8)))) + F ((F (4))!))$
48944 := $(F (4!) - ((4! - C ((F (9) - 8), F (4))))$
48986 := $((- (6) + (C (F (8), 9) - 8)) / (F (4))!)$
48987 := $((C ((F (7) + 8), 9) - 8) / (F (4))!)$
49324 := $- (((C (F (F ((F (4))!)), 2) + F (F (F (3!)))) - (9! / (F (4))!))$
49371 := $(C ((1 + F (7)), - ((3 - 9))) + F (4!))$
49383 := $((F (F (F (3!))) + C (8, F (3))) \times 9) / F (F (4))$
49428 := $(F (((8/2)!) + C ((F (F (4)) \times 9), 4))$
49496 := $((F (6) + C (9, F (4))) \times F (9)) + F (4!)$
49504 := $(4 \times C ((F ((0! + 5))) + 9), (F (4))!)$
49562 := $((2 \times F ((F (C (6, 5)) + 9))) + F (4!))$
49618 := $- ((F (F (8)) - ((1 + 6!) \times C (9, F (4))))$
49625 := $(- (F (C (5, 2))) - (- (69) \times ((F (4))!)))$
49642 := $((- (2) + F (4!)) + (C ((- (6) + F (9)), F (4)))$
49643 := $- (((F (F (3)) - F (4!)) - (C ((- (6) + F (9)), F (4))))$
49644 := $(C ((4! + 4), - ((6 - 9))) + F (4!))$
49658 := $((C (F (8), 5) - ((F (6))! / (-9))) \times F (F (4)))$
49706 := $(F (F (F (6))) + C (- ((0! + F (7)) - F (9))), (F (4))!)$
49728 := $((C (F (8), 2) \times (7 + 9)) + F (4!))$
49742 := $(C ((- (2) + 4!), F (7)) / (F (9) - 4!))$
49743 := $((C (3!, 4)^{F (F (7) - 9)}) + F (4!))$
49746 := $((C (F (F (6)), F (F (4))) \times F (F (7))) + ((F (9) \times 4!))$
49766 := $((C ((F (6) + (6)), 7) - F (9)) + F (4!))$
49784 := $(F (4!) + ((C (F (8), 7) / F (9)) - (4)))$
49788 := $((C (F (8), (F (8) - (7))) / F (9)) + F (4!))$
49789 := $((F (9) + C (F (8), 7)) / F (9)) + F (4!))$
49944 := $((F (4))! + (F (4!) + ((F (9) \times C (9, F (4))))$
49967 := $((C (7, 6))! \times F (9)) - F ((F (9) - F ((F (4))!)))$
50244 := $(F (4!) + C ((F (F ((F (4))!)) - 2), - ((0! - (5))))$
50383 := $(C (- ((F (3) - F (8))), (3! + 0!)) - (5))$
50946 := $((F (6))! + (C (4!, (9 - 05))))$
51238 := $(F (F (8)) - (C (F (3!), 2) - (F ((1 + 5))!))$
51248 := $((8 \times F (C ((F (4))!, 2))) + F ((- ((1 - 5))!))$
51268 := $((F (F (8)) + (F (6))! + C (2, (1^5)))$
51274 := $(F ((F (4))! - (- (F (C (7, 2))) - (F ((1 + 5))!))$
51644 := $(F (F (F ((F (4))!))) + (F (F (4)) \times C (F (F (6)), (1 \times 5)))$
51948 := $(8! + C (((F (F (4)) \times 9) + 1), 5))$
52274 := $(F (4!) + ((F (C (7, 2)) - ((2 + 5))!))$
52348 := $((C (F (8), 4) + F (((F (3) + 2))!)) - (5))$
52353 := $(C (F (F (3!)), (5 - F (F (3)))) + F ((- ((F (2) - (5))!))$
52374 := $(F (4!) + (C (F (7), 3) \times F (F ((F (2) + (5)))))$
52434 := $((4! - 3!) + (C ((4! + F (2)), 5))$
52548 := $((C ((F (8) + F (F (F (4))))), 5) \times 2) - 5!$
52644 := $(- (4!) + (F (F (4)) \times C ((F (F (6)) + F (2)), 5))$
52696 := $((F (6))! + C ((9 + F (6)), (F (2) + (5))))$
52738 := $((C (F (8), 3) + 7!) + F ((- ((F (2) - (5))!))$
52744 := $((C (4!, F (4)) \times F (7)) \times 2) + 5!$
52749 := $(- (9) \times (F (F (F ((F (4))!)) - (C (7, F (2))^{5})))$
52936 := $(F (F (F (6))) - (C (F (F (3!)), 9) / (- (2 + 5)))$
53117 := $- ((F (7) - C ((1 + ((1 + 3))!), 5))$
53124 := $- (((F (4))! - C ((F (2) + ((1 + 3))!), 5))$
53125 := $(- (5) + C ((F (2) + ((1 + 3))!), 5))$
53135 := $(5 + C (((3! - 1)^{F (3)}), 5))$
53154 := $(4! + C ((5^{F (1 \times 3)}), 5))$
53304 := $(C (F (F ((F (4))!)), (03)!) + (F (3!) \times (-5!))$
53345 := $(- (5) + ((- (C (4!, F (3))) + F (F (F (3!)))) \times 5))$
53368 := $((F ((F (8) - F (6))) + 3!) \times C (F (3!), 5))$
53373 := $((3! + F (F (7))) \times C (F (3!), 3)) + (5))$
53374 := $((F (4))! + ((F (F (7)) + 3!) \times C (F (3!), 5))$
53376 := $(F (6) + ((F (F (7)) + 3!) \times C (F (3!), 5))$
53384 := $(4 \times (F (F (8)) + (C (3!, 3) \times 5!))$
53443 := $(- (C (F ((3 + 4)), F ((F (4))!))) - (F (F (F (3!))) \times (-5))$
53446 := $(F (F (F (6))) + (- (4) + C ((C (4, 3))!, 5))$

- 53454 := ((C(4!, 5) + (4)) + F(F((3 + 5))))
53467 := (-((C(F(7), F(6)) - 4!)) - (F(F(F(3!))) × (-5)))
53472 := ((-((2^{F(7)})) - ((F(4)!)!) × (-C(3!, 5)))
53476 := ((F(6)!) + (C((F(7) × F(F(4))), F(F(3!))) / 5))
53481 := ((C((1 + F(8)), F(F(4)))^{F(3)}) + 5!)
53507 := (F((F(7) + 0!)) + (C((5^{F(3)}), 5)))
53633 := (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - (6! - F((3! + (5))))))
53646 := (C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!) - (F(6) + F((3 × 5))))
53648 := (C(F(8), (F(4)!) - (6 + F((3 × 5))))
53662 := (- (2) + ((C(F(F(6)), 6) - 3!) + 5!))
53663 := -((F(F(3)) - ((C(F(F(6)), 6) - 3!) + 5!))
53666 := (C(F(F(6)), 6) - ((6! - F(3)) - 5!))
53676 := (F(F(6)) × ((C(F(7), 6) + 3!) + 5!))
53688 := (8 × ((8! - F(C(6, 3))) / 5))
53828 := -(((F(8)²) - (C(F(8), 3!) + (5))))
53843 := (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + (- (F(F(8))) / (F(F(3!)) + (5))))
53938 := ((C(F(8), 3!) + F(9)) + (- (3) × 5!))
54036 := ((C(F(F(6)), 3!) - F(F((0! + (F(4)!)))) + (5))
54138 := ((C(F(8), 3!) - (F((1 × 4)!)) - 5!))
54146 := (C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!) - ((1 - F(4)) + 5!))
54148 := ((C(F(8), ((4 - 1)!) + (4)) - 5!))
54157 := (F(7) + (C(F(F((5 + 1))), (F(4)!) - 5!))
54166 := (((C(F(F(6)), 6) + 1) + F(F((F(4)!))) - 5!))
54168 := ((C(F(8), 6) + ((1 × 4)!) - 5!))
54208 := (C(F(8), ((0! + 2)!) - C(F((F(4)!), 5))
54224 := (C(F(F((F(4)!)), (F((2 + 2)!) - (F((F(4)!)) × 5))
54233 := (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - ((2 + 4!) + (5)))
54236 := (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (((F(2) - 4!) - (5))))
54238 := ((C(F(8), 3!) - F((2 × 4))) - (5))
54246 := (C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!) - (2 × (4 + 5)))
54253 := (C(F(F(3!)), ((5 - 2)!) - ((F(4)!) + (5)))
54254 := (C(F(F((F(4)!)), ((5 - 2)!) - (F(F(4)) × 5))
54256 := (C(F(F(6)), ((5 - 2)!) - ((F(4) + (5))))
54258 := (C(F(8), ((5 - 2)!) - C((F(4)!), 5))
54259 := (C(F(((9 - 5) × 2)), (F(4)!) - (5))
54263 := (- (3!) + (C(F(F(6)), (2 + 4)) + (5)))
54269 := (C((9 + (6 × 2)), (F(4)!) + (5))
54283 := (C(F(F(3!)), (8 - 2)) + (4! - (5)))
54303 := (F((F(3!) + 0!)) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + (5)))
54304 := (40 + C(F(F(3!)), C((F(4)!), 5)))
54309 := (C(F((9 - 0!)), 3!) + 45)
54315 := (51 + C(F(F(3!)), C((F(4)!), 5)))
54324 := (F((F((F(4)!) + 2)) + ((C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + (5))))
54326 := (62 + C(F(F(3!)), C((F(4)!), 5)))
54328 := ((8²) + C(F(F(3!)), C((F(4)!), 5)))
54329 := (- (F((9 + F(2)))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54333 := (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + ((F(3)^{(F(4)!)}) + (5)))
54342 := ((- (2) × F(F((F(4)!))) + ((C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!)))
54343 := ((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) × 3!) + ((F(4!) - (5))))
54344 := (F(4!) + ((C(4!, 3) × 4) - 5!))
54349 := ((- (F(9)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54359 := (95 + C(F(F(3!)), C((F(4)!), 5)))
54371 := ((- (1) × F(7)) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54372 := ((F(2) - F(7)) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54376 := (- (F(6)) + (C((7 × 3), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54378 := ((C(F(C(8, 7)), 3!) - (F(4)!) + 5!))
54393 := ((F(F(3)) × 9) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54394 := (- ((4! - F(9))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54397 := (F(7) + (C(F(F((9 - 3))), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54405 := ((C(F(F((5 + 0!))), (F(4)!) + F(F((F(4)!))) + 5!))
54408 := (C(F(8), (F(04)!) + (4! + 5!))
54419 := ((F(9) + 1) + (C(F(F((F(4)!))), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54438 := (C(F(8), 3!) + ((F(4)!) × (4! + (5))))
54444 := (F(4!) + (4 × (C(4!, F(4)) - (5))))
54448 := (C(F(8), (F(4)!) + ((4^{F(4)}) + 5!))
54451 := (1 + (5 × (F(F(F((F(4)!))) - C(F((F(4)!), 5))))
54452 := (2 + (5 × (F(F(F((F(4)!))) - C(F((F(4)!), 5))))
54454 := ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 5) - C(4!, - ((F(4) - (5))))
54459 := (9 + (5 × (F(F(F((F(4)!))) - C(F((F(4)!), 5))))
54483 := -((F(F(3!)) - (C(F(8), (F(4)!) + (F(F(4)) × 5!)))
54487 := ((F(F(7)) + C(F(8), (F(4)!) - (F(F(4)) × 5))
54492 := (F(F(-((2 - 9)))) + (C(F(F((F(4)!))), (F(4)!) - (5)))
54495 := ((5! - 9) + (C(F(F((F(4)!))), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54504 := (C(F(F((F(4)!)), (0! + (5))) + (F(F(4)) × 5!))
54534 := (C(F(F((F(4)!)), 3!) + (54 × 5))
54544 := (C(F(F((F(4)!))), (F(4)!) + (5 × C(F((F(4)!), 5)))
54554 := ((F(F(F((F(4)!))) × 5) + (- (5!) - C(F((F(4)!), 5)))
54617 := (F(F(7)) + (C(F(F((1 × 6))), (F(4)!) + 5!))
54624 := (C(F((4 × 2)), 6) + (F(4) × 5!))
54646 := (F((F(6) + (F(4)!))) + ((C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!) + (5))))

- 54663** := $(C(F(F(3!)), 6) + (F(F(6)) \times (4! - (5))))$
54746 := $((F(6))! + ((C(4!, 7) / 4!) + (5)))$
54792 := $(((-2) + F(9)) \times C(F(7), (F(4))!)) - 5!$
54855 := $((C(5, 5) + F(F(8))) + (4!)) \times 5$
54869 := $(F((9 + 6)) + (C(F(8), (F(4))!) - (5)))$
54924 := $(- (C(4!, 2)) \times ((- (F(9)) \times (F(4))!) + (5)))$
54928 := $(C(8, 2) - ((F(9) + F(F(F(F(F(4))!)))) \times (-5)))$
54934 := $((F(4!) - F(3)) + C((9 \times F(F(4))), 5))$
54944 := $(F((F(4))!) + (F(4!) + C((9 \times F(F(4))), 5)))$
54956 := $(C(F(6), 5) - ((F(9) + F(F(F(F(F(4))!)))) \times (-5)))$
55344 := $(C(F(F(F(F(4))!)), (F(4))!) - ((F(3!) \times (-5!)) - 5!))$
55374 := $((F(4))! - (7!)) \times (- (C(3!, 5) + (5)))$
55377 := $((7 \times C(F(7), F(3!))) + F((5!/5)))$
55434 := $- (((F(4))! + (C((F(3!) + F(4)), 5) \times (-5!)))$
55435 := $((C((5 + 3!), (F(4))!) \times 5!) - (5))$
55464 := $(4! + (C((F(6) + F(4)), 5) \times 5!))$
55473 := $((3 + 7!) \times (C((F(4))!, 5) + (5)))$
55642 := $((2 - (F(4!) \times (-C(6, 5)))) / 5)$
55775 := $(- (5!) + ((F(F(7)) + (F(C(7, 5)))) \times 5))$
55824 := $((F((F(4))!))! + (C((- (F(2)) + F(F(((8 - 5)!))))), 5)))$
55945 := $((5^{(F(4))!}) + ((9 - C(5, 5))!))$
56238 := $(C(F(8), 3!) - (- (2) \times F((F(F(6)) - (5))))))$
56275 := $(5! + ((C(F(7), 2) \times 6!) - (5)))$
56306 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (((0! + 3!)! + (F(C(6, 5))!)))$
56307 := $((7! + 0!) + (F(3!))! + F(F(F(C(6, 5))))))$
56336 := $((F(6))! + (F(3!) \times C((3! + F(6)), 5)))$
56364 := $((F(4))! \times (C(F(F(6)), 3) - ((F(6))! / (-5))))$
56376 := $(6 \times ((- (7) - F(F(F(3!)))) + (C(F(F(6)), 5))))$
56396 := $(F(F(F(6))) + ((- (9!) - 3!) / (-F(C(6, 5))))))$
56426 := $((F(C(6, 2)) + 4!) \times F((6 + 5)))$
56427 := $((7! \times 2) + F(4!)) - F(F(C(6, 5)))$
56448 := $((8! / 4) + F((4 \times C(6, 5))))$
56488 := $((8! - F((F(8) - F(F(4)))))) + (C(F(F(6)), 5)))$
56529 := $((C(9, F(2))^5) - (F(F(6)) \times 5!))$
56594 := $((F(4!) - ((F((9 - 5))!))! + F(F(F(C(6, 5))))))$
56664 := $(F(4!) - (- (F(6)) \times C((F(F(6)) - F(6)), 5)))$
56704 := $((4^{07}) + (F(C(6, 5))!))$
56724 := $(C(4!, 2) - ((- (7) \times (F(6))!) / 5))$
56784 := $(F(4!) + ((8 \times C(F(7), F(6))) + 5!))$
56826 := $((F(6))! \times 2) + C(F(8), F(6)) / 5$
56843 := $(F((3! \times F(4))) + (C(F(8), 6) - (5)))$
56938 := $(- (83) \times (F(9) - (C(6, 5))!))$
57194 := $((F(4!) + F(F(C((9 - 1), 7)))) - 5!$
57254 := $(F(4!) + ((5! / (-2)) + F(C(7, 5))))$
57306 := $((- (F(6)) + F(((0! + 3))!)) + F(C(7, 5)))$
57307 := $((- (7) + F(((0! + 3))!)) + F(C(7, 5)))$
57312 := $((- (2) + F(((1 + 3))!)) + (F(C(7, 5))))$
57313 := $((F(((3 + 1))!) - F(F(3))) + (F(C(7, 5))))$
57314 := $(F(4!) + F(C(((1^3) \times 7), 5)))$
57315 := $((F(((5 - 1))!) + F(F(3))) + (F(C(7, 5))))$
57334 := $(F(4!) + (C(3!, 3) + F(C(7, 5))))$
57335 := $(F(((5 - F(F(3))))!) + (F(F(3!)) + F(C(7, 5))))$
57344 := $(F(4!) + ((4! + 3!) + F(C(7, 5))))$
57349 := $((F(9) + F(4!)) + F(F(3))) + (F(C(7, 5))))$
57354 := $(F(4!) + ((5! / 3) + F(C(7, 5))))$
57384 := $(F(F(4)) \times (8! - C((3! + F(7)), 5)))$
57427 := $((F(C(7, 2)) + F(4!)) - (7 - 5!))$
57434 := $((F(4!) + ((F(3) + F(4))!)) + (F(C(7, 5))))$
57435 := $((5! + F(F(3))) + F(4!)) + (F(C(7, 5)))$
57554 := $(F(4!) + ((5! + 5!) + F(C(7, 5))))$
57684 := $((C(4!, F(8)) / F(6)) \times (F(F(7)) - (5)))$
57794 := $- (((F(4))! - (F(9) \times (C(F(7), 7) + (5))))))$
57864 := $(C(F(F(F(4))!), 6) + (((F(8) / 7))! \times 5))$
5794 := $((F(4!) / (-9)) + (F(C(7, 5))))$
57943 := $- (((F(3!) - F(4!)) + (- (9) \times C(F(7), 5))))$
57945 := $(5 \times ((F(4))! - (- (9) \times C(F(7), 5))))$
57951 := $(F((- ((1 - 5))!)) - (- (9) \times C(F(7), 5)))$
57984 := $(F(4) \times (C((8 + 9), 7) - 5!))$
58066 := $(- (6!) - (C(F(F(6)), (0! + 8)) / (-5)))$
58194 := $- (((F((F(4))!))! - (9 \times F(C(- ((1 - 8)), 5))))))$
58245 := $(5 \times (F(F(F(4))!)) + (C((- (2) + F(8)), 5)))$
58274 := $(F(4!) + (F(C(7, 2)) + (8 \times 5!)))$
58469 := $((9! / C(6, F(4))) + (8! + 5!))$
58476 := $((C(F(F(6)), 7) / F(F(4))) + ((8! / 5!)))$
58594 := $((C(F(F(F(4))!), 9) + (5! \times (-8))) / 5)$
58674 := $((F(4))! \times ((- (C(F(7), F(6))) + F(F(8))) + 5!))$
58698 := $(- (8!) - (- (9) \times (F(F(F(6))) + C(8, 5))))$
58744 := $(F(4!) + C((4! - (7)), ((8 - 5)!)))$
58863 := $(- (3) \times ((6! + 8) - C(F(8), 5)))$
58994 := $- ((F(- ((4! - F(9)))) - (C(9, 8)^5)))$

- 58996** := -(((6! - F(9)) × (F(C(9,8)) - 5!)))
59033 := -(((C(3!, F(3)) + 0!) - (9⁵)))
59164 := -(((F((F(4))!))! - (C((F(F(6)) + 1), 9) / 5)))
59259 := (C(F(F((F((9 - 5))!)), 2) + (9⁵))
59304 := (((F(4))! + 0!)! + C(F(F(3!)), (F((9 - 5))!))
59324 := ((C(4!, 2) - F(F(3))) + (9⁵))
59325 := (C(((5 - F(2))!), F(3)) + (9⁵))
59345 := -((F(C(5, F(4))) × (F(F(3)) - (9 × 5!)))
59346 := (F(F(6)) + ((C(4!, F(3)) + (9⁵))))
59396 := (F((6 + 9)) + (C(F(F(3!)), 9) / 5))
59445 := (5! + (C(4!, F(F(4))) + (9⁵)))
59446 := (F(F(F(6))) + (C((F(4) × (F(4))!), 9) - 5!))
59472 := (((2 × F(F(7))) + (F(4))!) × C(9, 5))
59506 := (6! + (C(F(F((0! + 5))), 9) / 5))
59724 := ((F(4))! × ((2 × 7!) - (C(9, 5))))
59756 := (((C(6, 5))! - F(7)) + (9⁵))
59774 := ((- (4!) + F(F(7))) × C(F(7), F((9 - 5))))
60394 := -((F(F(4)) - (- (C(9, 3)) × (0! - 6!)))
60425 := (- (F(C(5, 2))) + (((F((F(4))! + 0!)! / 6))
60434 := ((C(4!, F(3)) - ((F((F(4))! + 0!)! / (-6))
60493 := ((3!! × C(9, F(4))) + F((0! + (6))))
60626 := ((C((F(F(6)) + 2), 6) - 0!) - (F(6))!)
60628 := ((C((F(8) + 2), 6) + 0!) - (F(6))!)
60656 := ((C(F(F(6)), 5) + (F(6))!) - F((0! + (6))))
60663 := (- (3!) + (C(F(F(6)), (6 - 0!)) + (F(6))!)
60668 := ((C(F(8), (F(6) + F(6))) - 0!) + (F(6))!)
60676 := (((F(6))! + 7) + C(F(F(6)), - ((0! - (6))))
60969 := (C(9, 6) - (- (9) × F((- (0!) + F(F(6))))))
61334 := (C((- (F(F(4))) + F(F(3!))), (3! + 1)) + F(F(F(6))))
61656 := ((C(F(F(6)), 5) + (F(6))!) + (F(16)))
62268 := (((F(F(8)) + C(F(6), 2)) × 2) + (F(6))!)
62444 := (F(F((F(4) + (4)))) × (C(4!, 2) - F(6)))
62488 := (((F(F(8)) + F(F(8))) + C(4!, 2)) + (F(6))!)
62504 := (4 × (0! + (C(5, F(2))⁶)))
62632 := ((2 × (F(F(F(3!))) + C(F(F(6)), 2))) + (F(6))!)
63063 := (C((3! + F(6)), (03)!) × F(F(6)))
63145 := (5 × (C((4! + 1), F(F(3!))) - (F(F(6))))))
63308 := ((8 - 0!) × (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) / 6))
63344 := ((C((4 × 4), 3!) × F(3!)) - (6!))
63388 := ((88 × 3!) + C(F(3!), 6))
63448 := (- (C(8, F(4))) - ((F(4)! / (-F(3))) - (F(6))!))
63573 := ((C(F(F(3!)), 7) / 5) - (3 - (F(6))!))
63574 := ((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 7) / 5) - (F(3) - (F(6))!))
63576 := ((C(F(F(6)), 7) / 5) + ((F(3) + (6))!))
63578 := (((C(F(8), 7) / 5) + F(3)) + (F(6))!)
63634 := (- (C(4!, 3)) + ((F(F(F(6))) - 3) × 6))
63637 := ((F(7) × (F(F(3)) + (6!))) + C(F(F(3!)), 6))
63661 := ((C((1 + F(F(6))), 6) - 3!) - F(F(F(6))))
63744 := ((4^{F(4)}) × (C(F(7), 3!) - 6!))
63774 := ((C(4!, (F(7) + (7))) + 3) × 6)
63783 := (3!! + ((F(8) × C((7 × F(3)), F(6))))
63804 := ((C(4!, - ((0! - F(8)))) + F(3!)) × 6)
63813 := (F((C(3, 1) + 8)) × (- (3) + 6!))
63824 := (F((F(4))!) × (- (2) - (C(F(8), 3) × (-6))))
63832 := -(((F(2) - (3! × C(F(8), 3))) × F(6)))
63834 := (((4! × F(3)) × C(F(8), 3)) - (6))
63835 := (- (5) + (3! × (C(F(8), 3) × F(6))))
63864 := (4! - (F(6) × (C(F(8), 3) × (-6))))
63894 := ((F(4))! × (9 + (C(F(8), 3) × F(6))))
63896 := (C(F(F(6)), 9) - ((F(F(8)) + F(3!)) × F(F(6))))
63916 := ((- (6!) + C(19, F(3!))) - F(F(F(6))))
63945 := ((5! + C((F(4) × 9), 3)) × F(F(6)))
64064 := (C((4! - F(6)), (F(04))!) × F(6))
64133 := (C(F(F(3!)), (3! - 1)) + (4 × F(F(F(6))))
64206 := -(((C(F(F(6)), (0! + 2)) - (4^{F(6)})))
64245 := (5 × (C((4²), F((F(4))!)) - (F(F(6))))))
64287 := ((F(F(7)) × C(((8/2)!, F(F(4)))) - F(F(6)))
64334 := -((C(F(F((F(4))!)), 3) + (3! × (F(F(4)) - F(F(F(6))))))
64338 := ((F(F(8)) × 3!) - (C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) + F(6)))
64343 := -(((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) + 3) - ((F(4))! × F(F(F(6))))))
64348 := (- ((C(F(8), F(4)) - F(3))) + ((F(4))! × F(F(F(6))))
64378 := (C(F(8), F(7)) + ((- (3) × F(4!)) - F(6)))
64394 := (- ((4! × F(9))) + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(4))!) + F(F(F(6))))
64397 := (- (F(F(7))) + (C((F(9) / F(3)), F((F(4))!)) + (F(6))!))
64404 := ((- (C(4!, (0! + (F(4))!))) - (F((F(4))!))! / (-6))
64424 := (- (C(F(F(F(4))!), 2) + F(F(F(F(4))!))) × F(4)! + F(6)
64437 := (- (C(F(7), F(3!))) + ((F(4))! × (F((F(4))! + F(F(F(6))))))
64448 := (((8! / 4) - C(4!, F(4))) × F(6))
64466 := (F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(F(6)), (F(4))!) - ((4! + 6!)))
64467 := (C((F(7) + (6)), F(F(4))) × F(((F(4))! + F(6))))

- 64476** := $(6 \times ((F(F(7)) - C(4!, F(4)))) \times (-6))$
64478 := $((F(F(8)) \times 7) + (C(4!, F(4)) \times (-6)))$
64484 := $((F(4)!)! + (8 + (C(4!, 4) \times 6)))$
64485 := $(((-5) + C(F(8), (F(4)!) - ((F(4)!)!)) + F(F(F(6))))$
64486 := $(F(F(F(6))) + (C(F(8), (F(4)!) + (-4 - 6)!))$
64493 := $(F(F(3!)) - F(9)) \times (C(F(F(F(4)!)), 4) - F(F(F(6))))$
64545 := $((5 \times C((4 \times 5), 4)) + (F(6)!))$
64576 := $-((C(F(6), 7) \times 5!) - (4^{F(6)}))$
64624 := $-((F(F(4)) \times (C((2 \times F(6)), (F(4)!) - (F(6)!)))$
64628 := $((8! - 2) + C((F(F(6)) - 4), F(6)))$
64629 := $((C((F(9)/2), F(6)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(6)!))$
64642 := $C(-2 + F(F(F(4)!)), F(6)) + F(4)! - F(F(F(6)))$
64684 := $4 \times (-F(8) + F(6) \times C(4!, F(F(6))))$
64756 := $-((F(F(F(6))) + (-5!) - C((F(7) + (F(4)!), F(6))))$
64763 := $((F(C(F(3!), 6)) / F(7)) - (4 - (F(6)!)))$
64766 := $((F(C(F(6), 6)) / F(7)) - F(F(F(4)))) + (F(6)!))$
64768 := $((F(C(8, 6)) / F(7)) + F(F(F(4)))) + (F(6)!))$
64774 := $(((-4) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(7), F(4))) - (6!))$
64784 := $((F(4)!)! + (8 \times C((F(7) + F(4)), 6)))$
64814 := $((C(4, 1)^8) - F(F(4))) - (6!))$
64884 := $((F(4)!) / (F(8)!) - (C(F(8), F(4)))) \times 6$
64886 := $((6 \times F(F(8))) - (C(8, 4) + 6!))$
64895 := $(-5) \times ((-9) - F(F(8))) - C(4!, F(F(6)))$
64914 := $(F(4)!) \times (-((1 + C(9, 4)) + F(F(F(6))))$
64924 := $(F(4) + (C((2 \times 9), (F(4)!) - F(6)))$
64932 := $(F(((F(2) + 3)!) + C((9 \times F(F(4))), 6))$
64956 := $(-6) \times (5! - F((C(9, 4) / 6)))$
64961 := $(-C(F((1 + 6)), 9)) + ((F(4)!) \times F(F(F(6))))$
64977 := $-F(F(7)) + C(-F(7) + F(9), F(4)!) + F(F(F(6)))$
65234 := $(4! + (C(F(F(3!)), (F(2) + 5))) + F(F(F(6))))$
65236 := $(F(F(F(6))) - (F(C(3!, 2)) \times (-F((5 + 6))))$
65268 := $((F(8) \times (C(F(6), 2) + 5!)) \times F(F(6)))$
65328 := $((F(F(8)) - 2) - C(F(3!), 5)) \times 6$
65367 := $(C(F(7), F(6)) - (3! \times (-F((5 + 6))))$
65507 := $((7! - 0!) \times F((C(5, 5) + 6)))$
65548 := $((F(F(8)) \times C((F(4)!, 5)) - (5! + F(6)))$
65564 := $((F(4)!) \times F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) - (5! - F(6)))$
65639 := $((C((F(9) - F(3!)), F(F(6))) - 5!) - F(F(6)))$
65654 := $-(((F(4)!) + 5!) - C((F(F(6)) + 5), F(F(6))))$
65697 := $((F((F(7) - 9)!) \times F(F(F(C(6, 5)))) + (F(F(6))))$
65703 := $((3! \times (0! + F(C(7, 5)))) + F(F(6)))$
65706 := $((6 - 0!) + F(C(7, 5))) \times 6$
65709 := $((F(9) - 0!) + (F(C(7, 5)) \times 6))$
65712 := $((((2 + 1)!) + F(C(7, 5))) \times 6$
65733 := $((3! \times (3! + F(C(7, 5)))) + F(F(6)))$
65737 := $(F(7) + (3! \times (F(C(7, 5)) + F(6))))$
65754 := $((F(4)!) \times ((5 + F(C(7, 5))) + F(6)))$
65766 := $((6! / F(6)) + (F(C(7, 5)) \times 6))$
65843 := $((F(F(3!)) \times F(4)) + C((F(8) + 5), F(F(6))))$
65894 := $(C(-((F((F(4)!) - F(9))), F(8)) + (5! - 6)))$
66256 := $((C(6, 5) - 2)^{F(6)} + 6!)$
66267 := $-(((F(F(7)) - (6!)) - C(26, F(F(6))))$
66284 := $((4! \times F(8)) + C(26, F(F(6))))$
66368 := $((F(F(8)) \times 6) + 3!) - C(F(6), 6)$
66495 := $(-5) + (C((F(9) - F((F(4)!)!)), F(F(6))) + (6!))$
66633 := $((3 \times ((F(3)!) - (F(F(6)))) - (C(F(F(6)), 6)))$
66696 := $((F(6)!) \times (9 - 6)) - C(F(F(6)), 6)$
66732 := $(C((-2) + F(F(3!))), F(7)) + ((F(6)!) - (6!))$
66796 := $((F(6)!) / C(9, 7)) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 6)$
66837 := $(C(F(7), F(3!)) + ((F(F(8)) - F(F(6))) \times 6))$
66849 := $(9! - (C(((F(4)!) + (F(8))), 6) + F(F(6))))$
66894 := $((4! + 9!) - C((F(8) + 6), 6))$
66924 := $(-C(4!, 2)) + ((-9!) - (F(6)!) / (-6))$
66939 := $((C(9, 3) + 9) \times 6!) - F(F(6))$
67264 := $((C(4!, 6) / 2) - F(7)) - F(F(6))$
67333 := $((C(F(F(3!)), 3) - F(F(F(3!)))) \times (-7)) + (F(F(6)))$
67343 := $((C(F(F(3!)), F((F(4)!) / 3)) + (F(F(7)) - (6!)))$
67344 := $(F(4!) - (C(4!, F(3)) \times (-76)))$
67358 := $((C((8 + 5), 3) \times F(F(7))) + (6!))$
67384 := $((F(4)!) \times F(F(8))) - F(3!) + C(F(7), 6)$
67386 := $((6 \times F(F(8))) - ((3! - C(F(7), 6))))$
67444 := $((F((F(4)!)!) - ((F((F(4)!) - (C(((F(4)!) + F(7)), 6))))$
67445 := $((C((-5) + 4!), (F(4)!) - 7) + (F(6)!))$
67446 := $((F(6)!) - (F(4)!) + C(((F(4)!) + F(7)), 6))$
67448 := $((8! - 4) + C(((F(4)!) + F(7)), 6))$
67451 := $((-1) + C((-5) + 4!), F(7)) + (F(6)!))$
67452 := $(C(((F(2) \times (-5)) + 4!), F(7)) + (F(6)!))$
67453 := $((F(F(3)) + C((-5) + 4!), F(7)) + (F(6)!))$
67454 := $((F(F(4)) + C((-5) + 4!), F(7)) + (F(6)!))$
67458 := $(8! + (C((-5) + 4!), F(7)) + (6!))$

$$\begin{aligned}
 67473 &:= ((F(3!))! + (C((F(7) + (F(4))!), F(7)) + F(F(6)))) \\
 67475 &:= (-5) \times (F(F(7)) + (F((F(4))!) \times (-C(F(7), 6)))) \\
 67496 &:= (C(-(F(6) - F(9)), F(F((F(4))!)) + C(F(7), 6)) \\
 67613 &:= ((3! + 1) \times (F(F(F(6))) - (C(F(7), F(6)))) \\
 67644 &:= (C((F(F(4)) + (4!)), F(F(6))) - (F(F(7)) \times (-F(6)))) \\
 67683 &:= ((3! \times F(F(8))) + ((6! + C(F(7), F(6)))) \\
 67832 &:= (2 \times ((3! + C(F(8), F(7))) / 6)) \\
 67842 &:= (2 \times ((F(4))! - (C(F(8), F(7)) / (-6)))) \\
 67884 &:= ((F(4!) / F(8)) + (F(F(C(8, 7))) \times 6)) \\
 68134 &:= (((F((F(4))!))! - F(F(F(3!)))) + (C((-1) + F(8), 6))) \\
 68208 &:= -((8! - (02 \times C(F(8), 6)))) \\
 68257 &:= ((F((C(7, 5) + 2)) + 8!) - 6!) \\
 68364 &:= (((F((F(4))!) \times C(F(6), 3)) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68425 &:= (((5! - F(2))^{F(F(4))}) + (C(F(8), 6))) \\
 68439 &:= (((9 + C(F(F(3!)), F(4))) \times F(8)) + (F(6))!) \\
 68444 &:= ((4 \times (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 4) + F(F(8)))) + (6!)) \\
 68448 &:= ((C((8 + F(4)), (F(4))!) + F(F(8))) \times 6) \\
 68724 &:= (C(4!, 2) \times (F(F(7)) + (8 + F(6)))) \\
 68862 &:= (C((-2) + F(F(6)), 8) - (8! / 6)) \\
 68949 &:= (9! - (C(F(F((F(4))!)), 9) + F((8 - 6)))) \\
 68984 &:= ((C(4!, F(8)) \times F(9)) + (F(8) \times F(6))) \\
 68998 &:= -(((C(F(8), 9) - 9!) - ((8 \times 6)))) \\
 69434 &:= (((C(4!, 3) - F(4)) \times F(9)) + 6!) \\
 69498 &:= (C(-(F(8) - F(9)), F((F(4))!)) \times (9 \times 6)) \\
 69649 &:= ((9! + ((F(4))!))! - ((C(F(F(6)), 9) + F(F(6)))) \\
 69694 &:= ((4! + 9!) - (C(F(F(6)), 9) - (6!)) \\
 69734 &:= (((F(C((F(4))!, 3)) - F(F(7))) \times 9) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 69743 &:= ((3!! - F(F(F(4)))) \times (F(7) + (C(9, 6)))) \\
 69745 &:= ((5 \times F(F(F((F(4))!)))) - (-C(F(7), 9) \times F(F(6)))) \\
 69784 &:= (C(((F(4))! + (F(8))), (F(7) + 9)) - F(F(F(6)))) \\
 69996 &:= ((6! + F(F((9 - C(9, 9)))) \times 6) \\
 70542 &:= (C((-2) + F(F((F(4))!)), F((5 + 0!))) - (7!)) \\
 72144 &:= ((F((F(4))!))! + (C((4! - ((1 + 2))!), 7))) \\
 72244 &:= (((F(F(4)) + C(4!, 2))^2) - (7!)) \\
 72334 &:= (((C(4!, 3!) - F(3!)) / 2) + (7!)) \\
 72339 &:= ((F((9 \times F(3))) \times C(F(3!), 2)) - F(7)) \\
 72344 &:= ((F(4))! + ((C(4!, 3!) / 2) + 7!)) \\
 72346 &:= (F(6) - ((C(4!, 3!) / (-2)) - 7!)) \\
 72354 &:= -(((F(4))! - (5! \times (F(C(3!, 2)) - 7)))) \\
 72463 &:= ((3! - (F(C(6, 4)) / (-2))) \times F(F(7)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 72464 &:= (F(4!) - ((C(F(6), F(4)) \times (-2)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 72475 &:= (((5^7) - F(C((F(4))!, 2))) - (7!)) \\
 72538 &:= (C((F(8) + 3!), 5) - (2^{F(7)})) \\
 72744 &:= (((C(4!, 4) - F(F(7))) - F(2)) \times 7) \\
 72875 &:= (((5^7) - (C(F(8), 2) + 7!)) \\
 73333 &:= (-F(3!)) + ((3 \times F(C(F(3!), F(3)))) / F(7)) \\
 73342 &:= (F(2) + ((F(4) \times F(C(F(3!), F(3)))) / F(7)) \\
 73343 &:= (F(3) + ((F(4) \times F(C(F(3!), F(3)))) / F(7)) \\
 73346 &:= (-C(C(F(6), F(F(4))), 3) - (F(F(F(3!))) \times (-7))) \\
 73373 &:= ((F(F(3!)) + (C(F(7), 3))) \times (3! + F(F(7)))) \\
 73388 &:= ((F(F(8)) - C((8 + 3), 3!)) \times 7) \\
 73416 &:= (F(F(6)) \times (1 + (C((F(4))!, F(3)) \times F(F(7)))) \\
 73433 &:= ((F(C(3!, F(3))) \times ((F(4) + F(3))!)) + F(F(7))) \\
 73435 &:= (((5! \times F(C(3!, 4))) + F(3)) + F(F(7))) \\
 73476 &:= (6 \times ((C(F(7), F((F(4))!)) + F(F(F(3!)))) + F(7)) \\
 73486 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - (C(8, F(4)) \times F(3!))) \times 7) \\
 73642 &:= ((2 \times (F((F(4))!))! - (F(C(6, 3)) + F(F(7)))) \\
 73643 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), F(4)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 3!) - F(7)) \\
 73663 &:= ((3! \times (F(F(F(6))) + C(F(F(6)), 3))) + 7) \\
 73723 &:= (((F(C(3!, 2)) + 7!) + F(F(3!))) \times F(7)) \\
 73725 &:= (F((5^2)) - (C(F(7), F(3!)) + F(7))) \\
 73745 &:= (F((5^{F(F(4))})) - ((C(F(7), F(3!)) - 7))) \\
 73773 &:= ((F(F(3!)) \times (7! - C(F(7), F(3!)))) - (7!)) \\
 73784 &:= (F((F(4))!) \times (F(F(8)) - ((C(F(7), 3!) + (7)))) \\
 73847 &:= -((((C(F(7), (F(4))!) - F(F(8))) \times F(3!)) - 7) \\
 73969 &:= (((9! - C(F(F(6)), 9)) - F(F(3!))) + (7!)) \\
 73989 &:= (((9! - C(F(8), 9)) - F(F(3))) + (7!)) \\
 73993 &:= -((C(F(F(3!)), 9) - ((9! + 3) + 7!)) \\
 73996 &:= -((C(F(F(6)), 9) - ((9! + 3) + 7!)) \\
 73998 &:= ((-((C(F(8), 9) - 9!) + F(3!)) + (7!)) \\
 74074 &:= ((F(F(F((F(4))!))) - C((F(7) + 0!), F(4))) \times 7) \\
 74244 &:= (C(4!, F(F(4))) \times ((2^{F(F(4))}) + F(7))) \\
 74365 &:= (-5) \times ((F(C(6, F(3))) \times (-4!)) - F(F(7))) \\
 74367 &:= (-F(7)) + (C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), (F(4))!) - F(F(7))) \\
 74374 &:= -((F((F(4))!) + (C(((7 - 3))!, 4) \times (-7))) \\
 74379 &:= ((C((9 + F(7)), 3!) - F(F(F(4)))) - F(F(7))) \\
 74404 &:= (F(F((F(4))!)) + ((0! + (C(4!, 4) \times 7))) \\
 74409 &:= (F(9) + ((0! - C(4!, 4)) \times (-7))) \\
 74416 &:= (F((F(6) + 1)) + (C(4!, 4) \times 7)) \\
 74434 &:= (-4) + ((F(3!) + C(4!, 4)) \times 7)
 \end{aligned}$$

- 74436 := (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (4 × (F(4) + 7!)))
 74437 := (F((7 + 3)) + (C(4!, 4) × 7))
 74472 := -((F(2) - (7 × (C(4!, 4) + F(7))))))
 74474 := (F(F(F(4))) + (7 × (C(4!, 4) + F(7))))
 74568 := (((8 × (C(6, 5))!) - 4!) × F(7))
 74612 := (- (F(2)) + C((1 + F(F(6))), (- ((4 - 7))!))
 74613 := C((3! + 16)), (F(4) + F(7)))
 74615 := (- (5) + (C((1 + F(F(6))), (F(4))!) + 7))
 74632 := (C((F(2) + F(F(3!))), 6) + ((F(4))! + F(7)))
 74634 := (C((4! - F(3)), 6) + (F(4) × 7))
 74644 := (C((4! - F(F(4))), 6) + (4! + 7))
 74648 := (((C(F(8), F(4)) × F(6)) + 4!) × 7)
 74653 := (((F(3) + 5!) × F(C(6, 4))) + F(F(7)))
 74662 := ((2 × (F(6))!) - (C(F(F(6)), 4) - 7))
 74668 := ((8! + (F(6))!) - (C(F(F(6)), 4) - F(7)))
 74673 := (- (((F(3))! + (C(F(7), F(6)))))) + C(F(F((F(4))!)), 7))
 74714 := (F((4! + 1)) - (C(F(7), F(F(4))) + F(F(7))))
 74737 := (((7! - 3!) + C(F(7), 4)) × F(7))
 74793 := ((3! + ((9 × C(7, 4)))) × F(F(7)))
 74838 := (- (8) + (C((F(F(3)) + (F(8))), (F(4))!) + F(F(7))))
 74862 := (C((- (2) + F(F(6))), 8) - ((- ((4 - 7))!))
 74941 := (F((1 + 4!)) - C(9, - ((4 - 7)))
 74969 := (F(- ((C(9, F(6)) - F(9)))) - (F((F(4))!) × 7))
 75314 := (F((4! + 1)) + (C(F(3!), 5) + F(F(7))))
 75327 := (C(7, 2) × ((3!! × 5) - F(7)))
 75348 := (F(8) × (C(4!, - ((3 - 5))) × F(7)))
 75684 := (F(4) × (C(8, 6) - (- (5) × 7!))
 75685 := (- (5) + (C((F(8) + (6)), 5) - 7!))
 75733 := (((C(3!, F(3)) × 7!) + 5!) + F(7))
 75744 := ((C((F(4))!, F(F(4))) × 7!) + F((5 + 7)))
 75754 := (((- (4) - 5!) + F(C(7, 5))) × 7)
 75947 := ((- (F(7)) - (F((F(4))!))!) + C(F(F((F((9 - 5))!))), 7))
 75961 := ((1 - (F(6))!) + C(F(F((F((9 - 5))!))), 7))
 75973 := ((C(F(F(3!)), 7) - (F((F((9 - 5))!))!) + F(7))
 75973 := (F(7) + (C(F(F((F(- ((5 - 9))!))!), 7) - (F(3!))!))
 75984 := ((4! - 8!) + C(F(F((F((9 - 5))!))), 7))
 75994 := - (((F((F(4))!))! - F(9)) - C(F(F((F((9 - 5))!))), 7))
 76335 := (C((5 × 3), F(3)) × (6! + 7))
 76337 := ((F((7 × F(3))) - (F(3!))!) + (C(F(F(6)), 7)))
 76438 := ((- (C(F(8), F(3!))) - F((F(4))!)) + ((6⁷)))
 76574 := - (((F(4))! - ((F(C(7, 5)) - (6)) × 7)))
 76585 := (5 × ((C(F(8), 5) + F(6)) - 7!))
 76673 := (((3!! - 7) - (F(6))!) + C(F(F(6)), 7))
 76741 := (F((1 + 4!)) + (C((7 + 6), 7)))
 76757 := (- (C(7, 5)) + ((7! - F(F(F(6)))) × (-F(7))))
 76847 := (((C(7, (F(4))!) × F(F(8))) - F(6)) + F(F(7)))
 76887 := (C(F(7), 8) + ((F(8) - (6)) × 7!))
 77308 := (F(8) + (C((- (0!) + F(F(3!))), 7) - F(F(7)))
 77323 := (F(C(3!, 2)) + ((F(F(F(3!))) + F(7)) × 7))
 77507 := (- (F(7)) + C((- (0!) + F((- (5) + F(7))))), 7))
 77514 := - (((F(4))! - C((- (1) + F((- (5) + F(7))))), 7))
 77642 := (C((- (2) + 4!), 6) - (F(F(7)) × (-F(7))))
 77664 := ((C(4!, F(F(6))) × 6) + ((7! × F(7))))
 77674 := (F(F(4)) × ((F(F(7)) + (F(6))!) - C(F(7), 7)))
 77676 := ((C(F(F(6)), 7) - (F(6))!) + C(F(7), 7))
 77714 := ((C(F(F((F(4))!))), 17) - 7) × F(7))
 77747 := ((F(F(7)) - (F(4))!) + (C((F(7) + 7)), F(7)))
 77774 := (F(F((F(4))!)) + (F(F(7)) + (C((F(7) + 7)), F(7))))
 77784 := (C(4!, (- (8) + F(7))) - (7! × (-7)))
 77944 := ((C(4!, F(4)) × (F(9) + 7)) - 7!))
 78133 := (F(3!) + (- ((C(3, 1) - 8)⁷))
 78184 := (F(4!) - (8 - C(18, 7)))
 78234 := - (((F(4))! - 3!!) - C(- ((F(2) - F(8))), 7))
 78235 := ((- (5) + 3!!) + C(- ((F(2) - F(8))), 7))
 78241 := ((1 + ((F(4))!))! + C(- ((F(2) - F(8))), 7))
 78242 := ((2 + ((F(4))!))! + C(- ((F(2) - F(8))), 7))
 78243 := ((3!! + F(4)) + C(- ((F(2) - F(8))), 7))
 78244 := ((C(4!, (F(4))!) / 2) + F(F(C(8, 7))))
 78248 := ((8 + ((F(4))!))! + C(- ((F(2) - F(8))), 7))
 78338 := (C(F((F(8)/3)), 3!) - (F(F(8)) × (-7))
 78364 := ((F(4))! + (- (C(6, 3) - 8!)) × F(7))
 78432 := ((2 × (F(3!))!) - (F(4!) / F(C(8, 7))))
 78448 := (C((F(8) + F((F(4))!)), 4!) - ((8! - F(7))))
 78475 := ((- ((5⁷)) + (F((F(4))!))!) + C(F(8), 7))
 78636 := (6 × ((3 × 6!) + F(F(C(8, 7))))
 78643 := ((- (3) + C(4!, F(F(6)))) - (F(F(8)) × (-7)))
 78644 := - (((F(F(4)) - C(4!, F(F(6)))) + (F(F(8)) × (-7)))
 78734 := - ((F(F(4)) × ((3!! + F(F(7))) - (C(8, 7))!))
 78736 := (((F(6))! - F(3)) × 7) - (C(F(8), F(7)))
 78737 := ((7 × (F(3!))!) - ((F(7) + C(F(8), F(7))))))

$$\begin{aligned}
 78743 &:= (((C(F(3!), 4) + F(F(7))) + F(F(8))) \times 7) \\
 78754 &:= ((C(((F(4)!) + (5)), 7) + 8) \times F(F(7))) \\
 78764 &:= (((F(F(4)) + (F(6)!) \times 7) - (C(F(8), F(7)))) \\
 78776 &:= ((F(6)!) + ((7! - F(F(7))) \times C(8, 7))) \\
 78785 &:= (((5 + 8!) \times 7) - C(F(8), F(7))) \\
 78813 &:= (F(F(3!)) \times (-C(F(-((1-8))), 8) - (7!))) \\
 78924 &:= (((F((F(4)!)!) \times 2) - C((F(9) - F(8)), 7)) \\
 78988 &:= -((C(F(8), 8) + ((F(9) + 8!) \times (-7))) \\
 79236 &:= (((F(6)!) - 3!) \times 2) + C(9, 7)) \\
 79602 &:= (C(20, F(6)) - F((-9) + F(7)!)!) \\
 79635 &:= ((5! \times 3!) - F((6!/C(9, 7))) \\
 79662 &:= (C((F(2) + F(F(6))), 6) + (9 + 7!)) \\
 79847 &:= ((7 \times C((4! - 8), 9)) - F(F(7))) \\
 79848 &:= ((8! \times F(F(4))) - C((F(8) - 9), 7)) \\
 79884 &:= (4 \times (8! - C(F(8), (9 + 7))) \\
 79889 &:= ((9! + F(F(8))) - ((C(F(8), 9) + (7))) \\
 79935 &:= (5 \times (F(F(F(3!))) - (-C(9, 9) - 7!)) \\
 79945 &:= ((-5!) + F((4! + C(9, 9))) + (7!)) \\
 80388 &:= (C((8 + F(8)), 3) \times (0! + F(8))) \\
 80428 &:= (-C(F(8), 2) + (F(F(4)) \times (-0! - 8!))) \\
 80497 &:= -((F(F(7)) - (C((9 \times F(4)), (0! + F(8)))))) \\
 80569 &:= (C((F(9) - 6), 5) - F((0! + F(8)))) \\
 80583 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((-C(8, 5) - 0!) + 8!)) \\
 80584 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (-C(8, (5 + 0!)) - 8!)) \\
 80668 &:= (8! + (C(F(6), 6) + (08!)) \\
 80725 &:= (-5) + C(27, (0! + F(8))) \\
 81432 &:= (C((-2) + F(F(3!))), (F((F(4)!) + 1)) - F(F(8))) \\
 82278 &:= ((F(8) \times C(F(7), 2) - (-2) \times 8!) \\
 82345 &:= (((-5) + C(F(F((F(4)!)!), F(3)))^2) + 8) \\
 82356 &:= (C((F(6) + 5), 3!) - (-2) \times 8!) \\
 82376 &:= (((6 \times C(F(7), 3!)) + F(2)) \times 8) \\
 82377 &:= ((C(F(7), 7) + F(F(3!))) - (-2) \times 8!) \\
 82448 &:= ((F(F(8)) - (C(4!, 4) \times 2)) \times (-8)) \\
 82458 &:= (((-C(F(8), 5) - ((F(4)!)!) \times (-2)) + 8!) \\
 82544 &:= ((C(4!, F(4)) - 5!) - (-2) \times 8!) \\
 82614 &:= (F(F(4)) \times (F((1 + C(6, 2))) + 8!)) \\
 82643 &:= -((F(F(3!)) - ((C(4!, F(F(6))) - (-2) \times 8!))) \\
 82664 &:= (C(4!, F(F(6))) + (((6 + 2)!) + 8!)) \\
 82864 &:= (F((F(4)!) \times ((F(F(6)) \times (-C(8, 2))) + F(F(8)))) \\
 82984 &:= (C(4!, F(8)) \times ((F(9) - F(2)) + 8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 83044 &:= ((C(F(8), 3!) - F((0! + 4!))) \times (-4)) \\
 83144 &:= ((C(4!, 4) - F(13)) \times 8) \\
 83302 &:= (2 \times (0! + (C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 8!)) \\
 83324 &:= (4! - (-2) \times (C(F(F(3!)), 3) + 8!)) \\
 83342 &:= (2 \times ((F((F(4)!)!) + (C(F(F(3!)), 3) + (F(8)))) \\
 83367 &:= (C(F(7), F(6)) - (-F(3) \times (3! + 8!)) \\
 83391 &:= ((F(19) - C(F(F(3!)), F(3))) \times F(8)) \\
 83449 &:= (((9! + C(F(F((F(4)!)!), F((F(4)!)!)) / 3!) - F(F(8))) \\
 83546 &:= (6! + ((C(4!, 5) + F(3)) + 8!)) \\
 83634 &:= ((-4) + (F(3!))!) + ((C(F(F(6)), 3!) - F(F(8)))) \\
 83636 &:= (((C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (F(6)!) - F(3)) - F(F(8))) \\
 83643 &:= (C((F(3!) + (F(4)!)!, 6) + ((F(3) \times 8!)) \\
 83646 &:= (((C(F(F(6)), (F(4)!) + (F(6)!) + F(3!)) - F(F(8))) \\
 83662 &:= (-2) + (6 \times (C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 8!)) \\
 83663 &:= -((F(F(3)) - (6 \times (C(F(F(6)), 3!) - 8!))) \\
 83664 &:= ((F(4)!) \times ((6! - C(F(6), 3)) \times F(8))) \\
 83774 &:= ((F(F(4))^{F(7)}) + (C((F(7) + 3!), 8))) \\
 83775 &:= (5! + (F(7) \times C((F(7) + F(3)), 8))) \\
 83958 &:= ((8! - 5!) + C((9 \times F(3)), 8)) \\
 84072 &:= (2 \times (C(F(7), (F(04)!) + 8!)) \\
 84078 &:= (8! + C(((7 - 0!) \times F(4)), 8)) \\
 84146 &:= ((F(C(6, 4)) \times ((1 + 4)!) + F(F(8))) \\
 84294 &:= (F(F((F(4)!)!) \times (-F(9) + (-2) \times C(4!, F(8)))) \\
 84376 &:= ((6! \times ((7 - F(3)))! - (C(4!, F(8)))) \\
 84423 &:= (((C(F(F(3!)), 2)^{F(F(4))}) + ((F(4) + 8!)) \\
 84424 &:= (((C(F(F((F(4)!)!), 2)^{F(F(4))}) + (4 + 8!)) \\
 84426 &:= (((C(F(F(6)), 2)^{F(F(4))}) + (F(4)!) + 8!) \\
 84428 &:= (((C(F(8), 2)^{F(F(4))}) + F((F(4)!)!) + 8!) \\
 84433 &:= (((F(C(3!, 3)) / (-F(4))) + F(4!)) + 8!) \\
 84434 &:= (((C(4!, 3!) - F(4!)) / F(F(4))) + 8!) \\
 84446 &:= ((C((F(F(6)) - F(F(4))), (F(4)!) + F(4!)) + F(F(8))) \\
 84542 &:= (2 \times (C(4!, 5) - F(-((F((F(4)!) - (F(8)))))) \\
 84544 &:= ((-((C(4!, F(4)) + 5!)) + F(4!)) + 8!) \\
 84565 &:= (-C((5! / F(6)), 5) + (F((F(4)!) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 84638 &:= ((-((C(F(8), 3) + 6!)) + F(4!)) + 8!) \\
 84641 &:= (F((1 + 4!)) - (C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - F(F(8))) \\
 84643 &:= ((F(3!))! + ((F(4!) - F(F(6))) - (C(4!, F(8)))) \\
 84664 &:= ((F(4!) + (F(6)!) - (C((6 \times 4), F(8)))) \\
 84669 &:= (((9! - 6!) - F(C(F(6), F(F(4)))) + 8!) \\
 84734 &:= ((43 \times C(F(7), (F(4)!)!) + F(F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 84745 &:= ((F(C(5, F(4))) - (7!)) \times (4 - F(8))) \\
 84786 &:= ((F(6) \times (F(F(8)) - C(F(7), (F(4)!))) + F(F(8))) \\
 84824 &:= (F(4!) + ((-2) + F(8)) \times C(4!, F(8))) \\
 84843 &:= ((F(F(3!))^{F(4)}) + C((F(8) - F(F(4))), 8)) \\
 84893 &:= ((3^9) + (C(F(8), (F(4)!)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 84944 &:= ((C(4!, 4) - F((9 - F(4)))) \times 8) \\
 84947 &:= (-F(7)) - (((F(4)!))! \times (-C(9, 4) - 8))) \\
 84984 &:= -((4! + ((-8) - F(9)) \times C(4!, F(8)))) \\
 85269 &:= ((9! - F(C(F(6), 2))) - (5! - 8!)) \\
 85446 &:= ((F(C(6, 4)) - (4)) \times (5! + F(8))) \\
 85483 &:= (-((3! \times C(F(8), 4))) + F((5 + F(8)))) \\
 85645 &:= ((C((5 \times 4), F(6)) - (5)) - 8!) \\
 85695 &:= (((5! + 9!) / F(C(6, 5))) + 8!) \\
 85877 &:= ((7! \times F(7)) + (C(F(8), 5) + 8)) \\
 86244 &:= (F(4!) + ((C(4!, 2) - 6!) + 8!)) \\
 86336 &:= (F(6) \times ((C(3!, F(3)) \times 6!) - 8)) \\
 86546 &:= (((-C(6, 4)) + 5!) \times 6!) + F(F(8))) \\
 86604 &:= (F(4!) - (C((0! + F(6)), 6) - 8!)) \\
 86638 &:= (-((C(F(8), F(3)) + 6!)) + (F(6) \times F(F(8)))) \\
 86647 &:= ((-F(7)) + F(4!)) - (C(F(6), 6) - 8!) \\
 86697 &:= ((F(7) \times C(9, F(6))) \times (6! + F(8))) \\
 86827 &:= (((F(C(7, 2)) \times 8) - 6!) - F(8)) \\
 86904 &:= (F((F(4)!)) \times ((0! - C(9, 6)) + F(F(8)))) \\
 86924 &:= -((F(C((F(4)!), 2)) + (F(9) - (F(6) \times F(F(8)))))) \\
 86967 &:= (C(F(7), F(6)) + ((9! / F(6)) + 8!)) \\
 86974 &:= (F(4!) + (C(F(7), (9 - 6)) + 8!)) \\
 87266 &:= ((6! - (-C(6, 2)) \times 7!) + F(F(8))) \\
 87327 &:= (((F(C(7, 2)) \times F(3!)) - F(F(7))) - 8) \\
 87334 &:= (C(C(F((F(4)!), F(3)), -(F(3) - (7)))) - F(F(8))) \\
 87386 &:= ((-((F(6) - C(F(8), F(3)))) \times F(F(7))) + 8!) \\
 87524 &:= (F((F(4)!)) - (-2) \times C((5 + F(7)), 8)) \\
 87532 &:= (2 \times (F(3!) + C((5 + F(7)), 8))) \\
 87573 &:= ((F(3!) \times F(C(7, 5))) + (F(7) - 8)) \\
 87574 &:= ((F(4)! - (F(C(7, 5)) \times (F(7) - F(8)))) \\
 87733 &:= (((F(C(3!, 3)) \times F(7)) - F(F(7))) + (F(8))) \\
 87744 &:= (F(4!) + (4! \times (C(F(7), 7) + 8))) \\
 87955 &:= (-5) \times (5! - F(C((9 + F(7)), F(8)))) \\
 87984 &:= (F(4!) + ((8! + 9) + C(F(7), 8))) \\
 88347 &:= (C(F(7), 4) - ((F(3!) + F(F(8))) \times (-8))) \\
 88445 &:= ((5! \times ((F(4)!))!) + (C(4!, F(8)) + F(8)))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 88543 &:= (C(3!, 4) + ((-5!) - F(F(8))) \times (-8)) \\
 88645 &:= (-5) \times ((C(F(F((F(4)!)), 6) / (-8)) - F(F(8))) \\
 88743 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), 4) \times F(7)) + (F(F(8)) - 8)) \\
 88847 &:= (C(F(7), F((F(4)!)) - ((F(F(8)) \times (-8)) + 8)) \\
 88948 &:= ((C((F(8) - F(4)), 9) + 8) + 8!) \\
 89328 &:= ((F(F(8)) + C((2 \times 3!), 9)) \times 8) \\
 89431 &:= (-1) + (C(F(3!), F(4)) \times F((9 + 8))) \\
 89433 &:= (F(F(3)) + (C(F(3!), F(4)) \times F((9 + 8)))) \\
 89434 &:= (F(F(4)) + (C(F(3!), F(4)) \times F((9 + 8)))) \\
 89453 &:= ((C(F(3!), 5) \times F((F((F(4)!)) + 9))) + (F(8))) \\
 89664 &:= (C(4!, F(F(6))) + (F(6) \times (9 + F(F(8)))) \\
 89864 &:= (C(4!, F(F(6))) - ((F(F(8)) + F(9)) \times (-8))) \\
 89975 &:= (5 \times (C(F(7), 9) + (9! / F(8)))) \\
 91436 &:= -(((F(C(F(6), F(3))) - F(4!)) + (1 - 9!)) \\
 91438 &:= -(((F(C(8, F(3))) - F(4!)) - (1 + 9!)) \\
 92323 &:= -((F((F(3!) + 2)) - C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92336 &:= ((F(F(6)) \times (-F(3))) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92344 &:= (-F((F(4) \times F(4))) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92346 &:= ((F(6) \times (-4)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92347 &:= ((-7) - 4!) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92354 &:= -((4! - C(((5! / 3!) - F(2)), 9)) \\
 92357 &:= (-C(7, 5) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92362 &:= ((-2) \times F(6)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92363 &:= ((3! - F(F(6))) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92365 &:= ((-5) - F(6)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92366 &:= (-((6 + 6)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92371 &:= (-((1 \times 7)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92372 &:= ((F(2) - 7) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92373 &:= ((F(3) - 7) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92376 &:= -((F((F(F(6)) / 7)) - C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92377 &:= (-C(7, 7) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92379 &:= (F((9 - 7)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92383 &:= (-((3 - 8)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92384 &:= ((F(4)! + (C((F(8) - F(C(3, 2))), 9))) \\
 92393 &:= ((3! + 9) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92427 &:= ((7^2) + C((F(F((F(4)!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92433 &:= (F((F(3) + F(3!))) + C((F(F((F(4)!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92442 &:= ((2^{(F(4)!)} + C((F(F((F(4)!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92448 &:= ((-8) + F((4! + C(4, 2)))) / 9) \\
 92673 &:= (((3! \times C(F(7), 6)) + F(2)) \times 9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 92724 &:= ((F(4!) \times 2) - (C(7, 2) - 9)) \\
 92743 &:= ((F(3) \times F(4!)) + C(7, (F(2)^9!))) \\
 92744 &:= (C(4!, F(4)) + (7! \times (2 \times 9))) \\
 92807 &:= -((F(7) \times (0! - (C(F(8), 2) \times F(9)))))) \\
 93024 &:= ((F(4)!) \times C(20, (3! + 9))) \\
 93244 &:= (F(F(4)) \times ((C(4, 2)^{3!}) - F(9))) \\
 93288 &:= (8 \times (F(F(8)) + C(F((F(2) + 3!)), 9))) \\
 93449 &:= (((F(9) \times F(4!)) - C(4!, F(3!))) / 9) \\
 93646 &:= (((F(F(6)) + (C(4!, 6))) \times (-F(3))) + 9!) \\
 93653 &:= ((F(3!)^5) - (F(C(6, 3)) \times (-9))) \\
 93776 &:= ((6 \times F(F(7))) + C((F(7) + 3!), 9)) \\
 93864 &:= -((((F(4)!)! - ((F(6)!) + (C(F(8), -((3 - 9))))))) \\
 94334 &:= ((C(4!, 3!) - (F(3)!)!) + (4! + F(9))) \\
 94344 &:= ((C(4!, (F(4)!) - (F(3)!)!) + (F(F(4)) \times F(9))) \\
 94356 &:= ((F(F(F(6))) - C((5 + 3!), (F(4)!)!)) \times 9) \\
 94368 &:= (8! + (C(F(F(6)), 3!) + (4! \times (-9))) \\
 94374 &:= (-((F(4)!) + (C(F(7), 3!) \times F(-((4! - F(9)))))) \\
 94375 &:= (-5) + (C(F(7), 3!) \times F(-((4! - F(9)))))) \\
 94388 &:= (-((F(F(8)) + F(F(8)))) + C(F(F(3!)), -((F(F(4)) - 9))) \\
 94418 &:= (-((C(8, 1)^4)) + (F(F(F((F(4)!)!)) \times 9)) \\
 94593 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), (F((9 - 5)!)! + (F((F(4)!)!))! + 9) \\
 94633 &:= (C(F(F(3!)), 3!) + (((F(6)!) + 49))) \\
 94638 &:= ((C(F(8), 3!) + (F(6)!) + ((F(4)!) \times 9)) \\
 94664 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!)! + (C(F(F(6)), 6) + ((F(4)!)! / 9))) \\
 94668 &:= (-F(8)) \times (-C(F(6), 6) + ((F((F(4)!)!)! / (-9))) \\
 94686 &:= ((F(6)!) + ((C(F(8), 6) + (F(4) \times F(9)))))) \\
 94743 &:= (((C(F(3!), F(F(4))) \times 7!) - F(4!)) - 9) \\
 95664 &:= ((F((F(4)!)!)! + ((C(F(F(6)), 6) + (5! \times 9)))) \\
 96336 &:= ((C(F(F(6)), 3) + F(3!)) \times (F(6) \times 9)) \\
 96464 &:= -((((F(4)!)! + C(F(F(6)), F(4))) - (F(F(F(6))) \times 9)) \\
 96564 &:= (-((C(4!, F(6)) + (5))) + F((F(F(6)) + 9))) \\
 96695 &:= ((5^{F((9-6)!)} - C(F(F(6)), 9)) \\
 96734 &:= (((4!)^3 \times C(7, 6)) - F(9)) \\
 96774 &:= (-((4! + C(F(7), 7))) + (F(F(F(6))) \times 9)) \\
 96798 &:= ((F(F(8)) \times 9) - C(F(7), (-((6 - 9)!)!)) \\
 97417 &:= ((7! - 1) + C(((F(4)!)! + F(7)), 9)) \\
 97418 &:= (((8 - 1)!) + C(((F(4)!)! + F(7)), 9)) \\
 97794 &:= -((((F(4)!)! + (-9) \times F(C(7, -((7 - 9)))))) \\
 97854 &:= ((F(F((F(4)!)!)) + 5!) \times (-F(8) - C(F(7), 9))) \\
 97866 &:= (-6!) - ((F(6) + F(F(C(8, 7)))) \times (-9)) \\
 98214 &:= (-C((4! + 1), 2)) + (F(F(8)) \times 9) \\
 98332 &:= (-2) - ((-C(3!, 3) + F(F(8))) \times (-9)) \\
 98347 &:= (F(7) - (C((F(4)!)!, 3) - F(F(8))) \times 9) \\
 98553 &:= (-C(3!, 5) + ((5 + F(F(8))) \times 9)) \\
 98634 &:= (((C(4, 3) \times 6!) + F(8)) \times F(9)) \\
 99124 &:= (F(C((F(4)!)!, 2)) + (F(F(-((1 - 9)))) \times 9)) \\
 99143 &:= (F(C(3!, F(4))) + C(19, 9)) \\
 99333 &:= ((C(F(F(3!)), 3!) - F(-((3! - F(9)))) + 9!) \\
 99335 &:= (F((5^{F(3)})) + C((F(3!) + 9), 9)) \\
 99484 &:= ((C(((F(4)!) + (F(8))), F(4)) \times F(9)) + F(9))
 \end{aligned}$$

3.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **binomial coefficient type selfie numbers using square-root** in reverse order of digits. The work is up to six digits. This section is divided in two parts. One when the results are in symmetrical and/or consecutive way in blocks of 10. The second representations are for the rest of numbers.

3.4.1 Symmetric and Consecutive

$$\begin{aligned}
 12650 &:= 0 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) & 12654 &:= 4 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) \\
 12651 &:= 1 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) & 12655 &:= 5 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) \\
 12652 &:= 2 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) & 12656 &:= 6 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) \\
 12653 &:= 3 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right) & 12657 &:= 7 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$12658 := 8 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right)$$

$$12659 := 9 + C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, 21\right)$$

$$48720 := 0 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48721 := 1 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48722 := 2 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48723 := 3 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48724 := 4 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48725 := 5 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48726 := 6 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48727 := 7 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48728 := 8 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48729 := 9 + (-F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48930 := 0 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48931 := 1 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48932 := 2 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48933 := 3 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48934 := 4 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48935 := 5 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48936 := 6 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48937 := 7 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48938 := 8 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$48939 := 9 + F(F(-F(3) + 9)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4})$$

$$49980 := 0 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49981 := 1 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49982 := 2 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49983 := 3 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49984 := 4 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49985 := 5 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49986 := 6 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49987 := 7 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49988 := 8 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$49989 := 9 + F(8) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4)$$

$$54720 := 0 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54721 := 1 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54722 := 2 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54723 := 3 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54724 := 4 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54725 := 5 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54726 := 6 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54727 := 7 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54728 := 8 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54729 := 9 + (-2 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54730 := 0 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54731 := 1 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54732 := 2 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54733 := 3 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54734 := 4 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54735 := 5 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54736 := 6 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54737 := 7 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54738 := 8 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54739 := 9 + F(F(3)) \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times 5$$

$$54740 := 0 + (\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54741 := 1 + (\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54742 := 2 + (\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54743 := 3 + (\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54744 := 4 + (\sqrt{4} + F(C(7, \sqrt{4}))) \times 5$$

$$54745 := 5 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54746 := 6 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54747 := 7 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54748 := 8 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54749 := 9 + \left(\sqrt{4} + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54760 := 0 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54761 := 1 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54762 := 2 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54763 := 3 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54764 := 4 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54765 := 5 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54766 := 6 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54767 := 7 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54768 := 8 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$54769 := 9 + \left(6 + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \times 5$$

$$98280 := 0 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98281 := 1 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98282 := 2 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98283 := 3 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98284 := 4 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98285 := 5 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98286 := 6 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98287 := 7 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98288 := 8 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$98289 := 9 + C\left(C(8, 2), 8 - \sqrt{9}\right)$$

3.5 Symmetric and Nonconsecutive

$$33605 := 50 + F(6)! - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33616 := 61 + F(6)! - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33627 := 72 + F(6)! - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33638 := 83 + F(6)! - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33649 := 94 + F(6)! - F(C(3!, 3))$$

$$33650 := 05 + F(6)! - F(C(3!, 3))$$

3.5.1 Non Symmetric Representations

$$969 := C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(6))\right), \sqrt{9}\right)$$

$$1869 := F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + F(6)\right)\right) \times F(C(8, 1))$$

$$1974 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times F(C((7+9), 1))\right)$$

$$2574 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times C\left(F(7), \sqrt{5^2}\right)\right)$$

$$2594 := F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 9\right)\right) + C(5, 2)$$

$$3984 := F(4) \times \left(C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) - F(3)\right)$$

$$3985 := \left(-5\right) + \left(C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3\right)$$

$$3989 := \left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right)\right) - F(F(3))\right)$$

$$3996 := \left(\left(C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}\right) + F(\sqrt{9})\right) \times 3\right)$$

$$4767 := \left(F(F(7)) - (6)\right) \times C\left(7, \sqrt{4}\right)$$

$$4843 := \left(-F(3) + C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8))\right), 4\right)\right)$$

$$4844 := \left(-F(\sqrt{4}) + C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8))\right), 4\right)\right)$$

$$4895 := F\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \times F((8 + F(4)))$$

$$5984 := -\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - C(F(8), (9 - 5))\right)\right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6569 &:= \left(\sqrt{9}^{F(C(6,5))} + F(6) \right) & 09724 &:= \left(F((F(4)^2)) \times C(F(7), \sqrt{9+0}) \right) \\
 6748 &:= \left(C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times (F(F(7)) + F(6)) \right) & 10943 &:= \left(-C(3, \sqrt{4}) + F(F((9-01))) \right) \\
 8589 &:= \left(C(-((\sqrt{9}-F(8))), 5) + (F(8)) \right) & 10956 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + C(5, \sqrt{C(9,01)}) \right) \\
 9261 &:= \left(C((1+6), 2)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) & 10966 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + C(6, \sqrt{C(9,01)}) \right) \\
 9616 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + (-1) \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \right) & 11969 &:= \left((9 \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9})) - C(1, 1) \right) \\
 9657 &:= \left(-(C(F(7), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) & 12276 &:= \left(C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{7+2}) + F(21) \right) \\
 9688 &:= \left((C(F(8), 8) / F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) & 12486 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + C((F(8) + F(\sqrt{4})), (2+1)) \right) \\
 9724 &:= \left(F((F(4)^2)) \times C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) \right) & 12579 &:= \left(-(\sqrt{9}) + (F(F(7)) \times (F(C(5,2)) - 1)) \right) \\
 01297 &:= \left(C(F(7), (\sqrt{9}+2)) + 10 \right) & 12649 &:= \left(-(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - C((4+F(F(6))), 21)) \right) \\
 01298 &:= \left(C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) - \sqrt{2^{10}} \right) & 12849 &:= \left(C((F(\sqrt{9})^4), 8) - (21) \right) \\
 01384 &:= \left(-(F(\sqrt{4}) - ((C(F(8), 3) + F(10)))) \right) & 13529 &:= \left((F(\sqrt{9}) \times F((2 \times C(5,3))) - 1) \right) \\
 01869 &:= \left(F((\sqrt{9} + F(6))) \times F((C(8,1) + 0)) \right) & 13564 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((C(F(F(6)), 5) / 3) - 1) \right) \\
 01947 &:= \left(C((7 \times \sqrt{4}), 9) - F(10) \right) & 13966 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) / F(3))) + 1 \right) \\
 01969 &:= \left(C((\sqrt{9} \times F(6)), \sqrt{9}) - F(10) \right) & 13986 &:= \left(F(F(6)) \times ((C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) / F(3)) + 1) \right) \\
 01974 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times F((C((7+9), 1) + 0)) \right) & 14401 &:= \left((C(10, F(4))^{\sqrt{4}} + 1) \right) \\
 02574 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times C(F(7), (5 + (2 \times 0))) \right) & 14629 &:= \left((F(\sqrt{9}) \times C((F(2) + F(F(6))), 4)) - 1 \right) \\
 02594 &:= \left(F((\sqrt{4} \times 9)) + (C(5,2) + 0) \right) & 14949 &:= \left(C(((F(9) / \sqrt{4}) + 9), 4) - 1 \right) \\
 03984 &:= \left(F(4) \times (C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) - F((3+0))) \right) & 14998 &:= \left(((F(8)^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \times F(9)) + C(4,1) \right) \\
 03985 &:= \left(-(5) - (C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times (-3+0)) \right) & 15502 &:= \left(C(20,5) - \sqrt{5-1} \right) \\
 03989 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times C(F(8), \sqrt{9})) - F(F((3+0))) \right) & 15547 &:= \left(-(C(F(7), \sqrt{4}) - ((5^{5+1}))) \right) \\
 03996 &:= \left((C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) + F(\sqrt{9})) \times (3+0) \right) & 16398 &:= \left(((F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{9}) / F(3)) - F(F(C(6,1))) \right) \\
 04767 &:= \left((F(F(7)) - (6)) \times C(7, \sqrt{4+0}) \right) & 16976 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times (-C(7, \sqrt{9}))) + F((F(F(6)) + 1)) \right) \\
 04895 &:= \left(F(C(5, \sqrt{9})) \times F((8 + F((4+0)))) \right) & 17475 &:= \left((5 \times F(F(7))) \times (\sqrt{4} + F(C(7,1))) \right) \\
 05984 &:= \left(-(F(\sqrt{4}) - (C(F(8), ((9-5) + 0)))) \right) & 17596 &:= \left((C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \times 5) + F(F((7+1))) \right) \\
 06435 &:= \left(C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4+60}) \right) & 17694 &:= \left((-4) + F((F(F(\sqrt{9})) + (F(F(6)))))) - F(C(7,1)) \right) \\
 06748 &:= \left(C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times (F(F(7)) + F((6+0))) \right) & 17797 &:= \left((C(F(7), F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F(7))) - F((F(7) + 1)) \right) \\
 09261 &:= \left(C((1+6), 2)^{\sqrt{9+0}} \right) & 17946 &:= \left(F((F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}))) + (F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(C(7,1)))) \right) \\
 09616 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) + (-1) \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9+0}) \right) & 17948 &:= \left((C(F(8), 4) \times \sqrt{9}) - C(7,1) \right) \\
 09657 &:= \left(-(C(F(7), 5) + F(F(F(6)))) - F(\sqrt{9+0}) \right) & 18797 &:= \left((C(F(7), F(\sqrt{9})) \times (F(F(7)) + 8)) - 1 \right) \\
 09688 &:= \left((C(F(8), 8) / F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{9+0}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 18946 &:= \left(C(6, F(4))^{\sqrt{9}} + F(F(C(8,1))) \right) \\
 19397 &:= \left(C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) - (3^9) \right) \times (-1) \\
 19447 &:= C\left(F(7) + (4), \sqrt{49}\right) - 1 \\
 19448 &:= C\left(F(8) - (4), \sqrt{49 \times 1}\right) \\
 19449 &:= C\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4}, \sqrt{49}\right) + 1 \\
 19594 &:= \left(F(4)^9 - F\left(C(5, \sqrt{9}) + 1\right) \right) \\
 19665 &:= C\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}}, F(6)\right) / F((9+1)) \\
 19694 &:= \left((F(4)^9) + F(6) + \sqrt{C(9,1)} \right) \\
 19739 &:= \left(C(9,3) \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - 1 \\
 19773 &:= \left(F(3) + (7) \right) \times \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{C(9,1)}} \right) \\
 19894 &:= \left(F(4)^9 + C\left(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})\right) + 1 \right) \\
 19916 &:= \left(F(F((6+1))) + \sqrt{9}^{C(9,1)} \right) \\
 19917 &:= \left(F(F(7)) - (-1) - \left(\sqrt{9}^{C(9,1)} \right) \right) \\
 20289 &:= \left(\sqrt{C(9,8)} \times (F(20) - 2) \right) \\
 20348 &:= C\left(F(8), \left(\sqrt{4} + 3\right)\right) - F(02) \\
 20349 &:= C\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9 \times 4}\right)\right), (3+02)\right) \\
 21878 &:= \left(F(F(8)) - (7) \right) \times \sqrt{C(8,1)/2} \\
 21884 &:= \left(4 - F(F(8)) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{C(8,1)/2} \right) \\
 21889 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(F(8)) - F(C(8,1)/2) \right) \\
 21898 &:= \left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{C(8,1)/2} \\
 23679 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - (-7) \times F(C(6,3)) \right) / 2 \\
 23948 &:= \left((-C(F(8),4) - F(\sqrt{9})) \times (F(3) \times (-2)) \right) \\
 24446 &:= \left(F\left(C\left(F(6), \sqrt{4}\right)\right) / F((F(4) + (4))) \right) - F(2) \\
 24448 &:= \left(F\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) / F((F(4) + (4))) \right) + F(2) \\
 24467 &:= \left(F(F(7)) \times C\left(C(6,4), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) + 2 \\
 24496 &:= F(6) \times C\left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4}\right), 4\right) + 2 \\
 26334 &:= C\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F((3+3)))\right), (6 - F(2))\right) \\
 26466 &:= \left(6 \times \left(C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}\right) \times F(F(6)) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 26484 &:= \left((-F(4)) + F\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) / (6 \times 2)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 26486 &:= \left(F(F(6)) + F\left(C\left(8, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) / (6 \times 2) \\
 26897 &:= -\left(\left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - C(F(8), 6) / 2 \right) \\
 26899 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(F\left(\left(9 - F(\sqrt{9})\right)\right)\right) - C(F(8), 6) / 2 \right) \right) \\
 26975 &:= (-5) \times \left(C\left(F(7), F(\sqrt{9})\right) + F(F(F(6))) / (-2) \right) \\
 27456 &:= F(6) \times C\left(F\left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4}\right)\right), 7\right) \times 2 \\
 27598 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times 5 + F(C(F(7), F(2))) \right) \\
 27696 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(6)) - F(F(7)) \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 27698 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(6)) - F(F(7)) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 27846 &:= F(F(6)) \times \left(-4 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{7+2}\right) \right) \\
 27896 &:= \left(C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(8) - F((7+2)) \right) \\
 27959 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 5\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(7)) - F(2) \right) \\
 27961 &:= \left(C\left(16, F(\sqrt{9})\right) \times F(F(7)) + F(2) \right) \\
 27962 &:= \left(C\left(2 + F(6), \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(7)) + 2 \right) \\
 27966 &:= (-6) \times \left(\left(-C\left(6, \sqrt{9}\right) \right) \times F(F(7)) - F(2) \right) \\
 28426 &:= -\left(C\left(F(F(6)) + F(2), \sqrt{4}\right) - F((F(8) + 2)) \right) \\
 28448 &:= -C(F(8), F(F(4))) + F(F(F(4))) + F(F(8) + 2) \\
 28596 &:= -\left(C\left(F(6), \sqrt{9}\right) + (5) \right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 28684 &:= F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(8)\right)\right) + C((6 + F(8)), F(2)) \\
 28748 &:= F\left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + C((-7) + F(8), 2) \\
 28943 &:= C\left(F((3+4)), \sqrt{9}\right) + F((F(8) + 2)) \\
 29376 &:= \left((F(F(6)) \times F(F(7))) + 3 \right) \times \sqrt{C(9,2)} \\
 29696 &:= \left(F(6)^{\sqrt{9}} \times C\left(F(6), \sqrt{9}\right) + 2 \right) \\
 29925 &:= \left(5 \times C\left(F\left(\left(2^{\sqrt{9}}\right)\right), (F(9)/2)\right) \right) \\
 31698 &:= \left(F(F(8)) \times \sqrt{9} - C((F(F(6)) - 1), 3) \right) \\
 32298 &:= \left(-F(8) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - C(22,3) \right) \right) \\
 32843 &:= \left(C\left(3, \sqrt{4}\right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + (2+3) \\
 32844 &:= \left(C\left(F(4), \sqrt{4}\right) \times F(F(8)) \right) + (2 \times 3) \\
 32928 &:= \left(\left(C(8,2)^{\sqrt{9}} / 2 \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 33466 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times 3 - F(3) \right) \\
 33646 &:= C\left(\left(F(F(6)) + \sqrt{4}\right), (F(6) - 3) - 3\right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 33648 &:= \left(C \left(\left(F(8) + \sqrt{4} \right), 6 \right) - 3 \right) / 3 \\
 33649 &:= C \left(\left(\left(F(9) / \sqrt{4} \right) + (6) \right), (F(3) + 3) \right) \\
 33797 &:= \left(F(7) \times C \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(7) \right), 3 \right) \right) - 3 \\
 34584 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) - C(\sqrt{5^4}, 3) \right) \right) \\
 34749 &:= \left(9 \times F(4) \right) \times C \left(F(7), \sqrt{4^3} \right) \\
 34884 &:= \left(C \left(- \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - F(8) \right) \right), (8 - F(4)) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 35988 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \times 5 \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 35992 &:= \left(\left(- \left((F(2) - F(9)) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) + F(C(5, 3)) \right) \\
 36432 &:= \left(C(23, \sqrt{4}) \times F((6 \times F(3))) \right) \\
 36642 &:= \left(2 \times \left(F \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) + F(C(6, F(3))) \right) \right) \\
 36789 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times \left((F(F(8)) - (F(7))) + C(F(F(6)), 3) \right) \right) \\
 36964 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C(6, 3) \right) \right) \\
 36984 &:= \left(4 \times \left(\left(F(8)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - C(6, F(3)) \right) \right) \\
 37796 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \times (C(F(7), 7) + F(3)) \right) \\
 37986 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C \left(F \left(\left(F(8) / \sqrt{9} \right) \right), 7 \right) \right) \times 3 \right) \\
 38445 &:= \left(F \left(F \left(\left(5 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times C((F(4) + 8), 3) \right) \\
 38464 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left((C(F(F(6)), F(4)) - F(F(8))) \times (-F(3)) \right) \right) \\
 38696 &:= \left(C \left(C(6, \sqrt{9}), 6 \right) - (8^{F(3)}) \right) \\
 38962 &:= \left((F(2) + F(F(6))) \times C \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(8)) \right), 3 \right) \right) \\
 39248 &:= \left(\left(C(8, \sqrt{4}) \times (-2) \right) + (F(9)^3) \right) \\
 39379 &:= - \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{9} - C(F(7), F(3)) \right) - (F(9)^3) \right) \right) \\
 39424 &:= \left(C(4^2, \sqrt{4}) + (F(9)^3) \right) \\
 39447 &:= \left(\left(C(F(7), F(4)) / \sqrt{4} \right) + (F(9)^3) \right) \\
 39457 &:= \left(C \left((F(7) + (5)), \sqrt{4} \right) + (F(9)^3) \right) \\
 39586 &:= \left(\left(C((F(6) + F(8)), 5) + \sqrt{9} \right) / 3 \right) \\
 39588 &:= \left(\left(C((8 + F(8)), 5) / \sqrt{9} \right) + 3 \right) \\
 39672 &:= \left(- (F(2) + F(F(7))) \times C \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right), F(3) \right) \right) \\
 39689 &:= \left(\left(9 \times F(8) \right) \times C \left(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) - F(F(3)) \\
 39843 &:= \left(F(F((3 + 4))) \times C \left(\left(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right), F(3) \right) \right) \\
 39897 &:= \left(C(F(7), - \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - 8 \right) \right)) \times (F(9) - 3) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 39898 &:= \left(\left((F(8) + 9) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \right) - F(3) \right) \\
 39937 &:= \left(\left(C(F(7), F(3)) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9})^9 \right) \right) + F(F(3)) \right) \\
 39984 &:= \left(C \left((- (4) + F(8)), \sqrt{9} \right) + (F(9)^3) \right) \\
 39986 &:= \left(\left(F(F(6)) \times \left(C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times F(9) \right) \right) + F(3) \right) \\
 40656 &:= \left((C(F(F(6)), 5) - F(F(6))) \times \sqrt{04} \right) \\
 40858 &:= \left((C(F(8), 5) + (80)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 41895 &:= \left(\left(5 + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times C(F(8), (1 \times 4)) \right) \\
 42438 &:= \left(\left((C(F(8), F(3)) - (4)^2) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 42496 &:= \left(\left(C \left(\left(F(6) \times \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) - 2 \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 42584 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) - \left(C(5^2, \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 42874 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (C(7, (8/2))^{F(4)}) \right) \right) \\
 43262 &:= \left(- (2) + \left((C(F(F(6)), 2) - F(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 43263 &:= \left(\left((- (F(3)) + C(F(F(6)), 2))^{F(3)} - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 43264 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} - C(F(6 + 2), F(3)) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} \\
 43448 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - C \left(\left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}} \right), 3 \right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 43669 &:= \left(- \left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left((F(F(F(6))) - C(F(6), F(3))) \times 4 \right) \right) \\
 43748 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times 4) - C(7 + F(3), \sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43759 &:= \left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) + C(5 + F(7), (F(3))^{F(4)}) \right) \\
 43798 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(F(8)) \times F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + (7) \right) \times F \left(C(3, \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 43844 &:= \left(- \left((4^4) \right) + \left(C(F(8), F(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 43867 &:= - \left(\left(F((7 + 6)) - \left(C(F(8), F(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 43891 &:= \left((- (1) + F(9)) \times C(F(8), 3) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 43892 &:= - \left(\left((F(2) - F(9)) \times C(F(8), 3) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 43894 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(9) \right) \times (-C(F(8), 3)) \right) + 4 \right) \\
 43896 &:= \left((- (6) \times F(9)) + \left(C(F(8), F(3))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 43897 &:= \left(- (7) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times (C(8, F(3))^{F(4)}) \right) \right) \\
 44087 &:= - \left(\left(F(7) - \left(C(F(8), \sqrt{04})^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \right) \\
 44096 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{04}} - 4 \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 44098 &:= \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{04}} - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 44264 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + C\left(2^4, \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \right) \\
 44265 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C((F(F(6)) + 2), 4) - \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 44267 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) \times C\left(F(F(6)) - F(2), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) - F(4) \right) \\
 44285 &:= \left(5 \times \left(C((F(8) + 2), 4) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 44466 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) + C\left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}\right), 4\right) \right) \times F(4) \right) \\
 44468 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + C\left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4}\right), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44521 &:= \left((1 + C((2 \times 5), 4))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \\
 44624 &:= \left(\left(F(F((4 \times 2))) + C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44626 &:= \left(\left((-C(F(F(6)), 2) - F(F(F(6)))) \times (-4) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 44628 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) + F(2)) + C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 44684 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(F(8)) + \sqrt{C(6, 4)^4} \right) \right) \\
 44736 &:= \left(\left((F(6)^{F(3)}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times C\left(F(4), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 44946 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}\right) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right)^{\sqrt{4}} + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 44987 &:= \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left(C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times F\left(F(4)^{\sqrt{4}}\right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 45389 &:= \left((F(9) \times (C(F(8), 3) + (5))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 46158 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F(8), \sqrt{5-1}\right) - F((6 \times 4)) \right) \right) \\
 46189 &:= \left(C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(8)\right), (1 + F(6))\right) / \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 46248 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{4}\right), 2\right) - F((6 \times 4)) \right) \right) \\
 46279 &:= \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} + C(7, 2)\right)\right) - F((F(6) + F(4))) \right) \\
 46417 &:= \left(\sqrt{C(7, 1)^4 + F((6 \times 4))} \right) \\
 46425 &:= \left(\left(F(C(5, 2)) + \sqrt{4} \right) + F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 46434 &:= \left(C\left(4 \times 3, \sqrt{4}\right) + F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 46447 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F(7), \sqrt{4}\right) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) + F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 46466 &:= \left((6^6) - C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(6))\right), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 46488 &:= \left(C\left(8 + 8, \sqrt{4}\right) + F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 46494 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F(4) \times \sqrt{9}\right), 4\right) + F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 46583 &:= \left((F((3 \times 8)) + (5)) + C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 46596 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(\sqrt{9})\right), 5\right) + F(F(6)) \right) \times 4 \right) \\
 46626 &:= \left(-\left(\left(C(F(6), 2) - ((6^6)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \\
 46655 &:= \left((C(5, 5) + (6^6)) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 46678 &:= \left((F(C(8, 7)) + ((6^6))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 46868 &:= \left(C(F(8), 6) - (86^{\sqrt{4}}) \right) \\
 46928 &:= \left(C\left(8 \times 2, \sqrt{9}\right) + F((6 \times 4)) \right) \\
 46986 &:= \left(\left(F(6) + F\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) \right) + F(C(6, 4)) \right) \\
 46998 &:= \left(F\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + (9 \times C(F(6), 4)) \right) \\
 47268 &:= \left((-8) + C(F(F(6)), 2) \right) \times \left(F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47336 &:= \left(\left((F(C(6, 3)) - 3) \times 7 + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \\
 47346 &:= \left((F(C(6, 4)) - 3) \times C\left(F(7), \sqrt{4}\right) \right) \\
 47353 &:= \left((F((F(3) \times C(5, 3))) \times 7) - \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47354 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times C(5, 3)\right)\right) \times 7 \right) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47356 &:= \left((F(C(C(6, 5), 3)) \times 7) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47359 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(5, 3)\right)\right) \times 7 \right) + 4 \right) \\
 47361 &:= \left(((1 + F(C(6, 3))) \times 7) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47362 &:= \left((F(2) + F(C(6, 3))) \times \sqrt{\sqrt{7^4}} \right) \\
 47363 &:= \left(((F(F(3)) + (F(C(6, 3)))) \times 7) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47364 &:= \left(\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + (F(C(6, 3))) \right) \times 7 \right) + \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47367 &:= \left(((7 \times F(C(6, 3))) + F(7)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47369 &:= \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times F(6)\right)\right) + C((F(3) \times 7), 4) \right) \\
 47488 &:= \left((C((8 + F(8)), 4) - (7)) \times \sqrt{4} \right) \\
 47496 &:= \left(-(6) + \left(C(9, 4) \times F\left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{4}\right)\right) \right) \right) \\
 47646 &:= \left(((C(F(F(6)), 4) \times F(6)) - F(F(7))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47648 &:= \left(((C(F(8), 4) \times F(6)) - F(F(7))) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47698 &:= \left(F\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9}\right)\right) + C((F(6) + F(7)), F(4)) \right) \\
 47766 &:= \left(((-C(F(6), 6)) + F(F(7))) \times F(F(7)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \\
 47854 &:= \left(-(C((F(4) \times 5), 8)) + \left(F(F(7))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) \\
 47896 &:= \left(F(6) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + C(F(C(8, 7)), 4) \right) \right) \\
 47988 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + \left(C\left(8, \sqrt{9}\right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$48277 := - \left(\left(F(F(7)) - \left((F(F(7)) - 2) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$48279 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(7)) \right) \times \left(F(2) - C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$$

$$48387 := - \left(\left(F(F(7)) - C(F(8) - 3, (8 + F(\sqrt{4}))) \right) \right)$$

$$48464 := \left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}) \right) \times F(F((F(8)/F(4)))) \right)$$

$$48715 := \left(-5 - \left((1 - F(F(7))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$$

$$48719 := - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - \left((1 - F(F(7))) \times \left(-C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$48794 := \left(-4 \times F(9) - \left(F(F(7)) \times \left(-C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$48925 := \left(-5 + \left(F(F(-(2-9))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right)$$

$$48928 := \left(C(F(8), 2) \times F((F(9) - F(8))) - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$48929 := - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{9})) - \left(F(F(-(2-9))) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$48972 := (-2 + F(F(7))) \times \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$49278 := F(8) + \left(F(C(7, 2) \times 9) / \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$49396 := \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3) \right) \times F((9+4)) \right)$$

$$49476 := \left(\left(F(F(6)) - F(F(7) + \sqrt{4}) \right) \times \left(-C(9, F(4)) \right) \right)$$

$$49678 := \left(F(F(8)) / (-F(7)) \times \left(-C(F(6), \sqrt{9}) + F(4) \right) \right)$$

$$49686 := \left(6 \times \left(C(8+6, F(\sqrt{9}))^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right)$$

$$49725 := \left(\left(-C(5, 2) + F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - 4 \right)$$

$$49726 := \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), 2) + F(7) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(4) \right)$$

$$49728 := \left(\left(C(F(8), 2) + F(7) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$49862 := \left(F(F((F(2) + (6)))) \times \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) + 4 \right) \right)$$

$$49885 := \left(5 \times \left(F(F(8)) - C(F(8) - F(\sqrt{9}), F(4)) \right) \right)$$

$$49887 := \left(F(F(7)) + 8 \right) \times \left(C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) - F(4) \right)$$

$$49938 := \left(-F(8) \times \left(F(3) - C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4) \right) \right)$$

$$49967 := \left(-F(7) + \left(F(F(6)) \times C(F(9)/F(\sqrt{9}), 4) \right) \right)$$

$$52684 := \left(\sqrt{4} \times (8 + C((F(F(6)) + F(2)), 5)) \right)$$

$$52968 := \left(\left(F(C(8, 6)) - \sqrt{9} \right) / (F(2) + 5) \right)$$

$$53497 := \left(\left(F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} - C((4 \times 3), 5) \right)$$

$$54258 := \left(\left(C(F(8), (5 + F(2))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) - 5 \right)$$

$$54259 := \left(C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), (2 + 4)) - 5 \right)$$

$$54268 := \left(C(F(8), 6) + F(2) + \sqrt{4+5} \right)$$

$$54296 := \left(C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{C(9, 2)}) + \sqrt{4^5} \right)$$

$$54297 := \left(\left(F(F(7)) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F(C((2+4), 5)) \right)$$

$$54647 := \left(-C(F(7), \sqrt{4}) - \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \times (-5) \right) \right)$$

$$54705 := \left(\left(-5 + F(C(07, \sqrt{4})) \right) \times 5 \right)$$

$$54753 := \left(-F(3) + \left(\left(5 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) \times 5 \right) \right)$$

$$54754 := - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left(\left(5 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) \times 5 \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54759 := \left(F(9) - \left(\left(-5 \times F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) + 5 \right) \right)$$

$$54794 := \left(\left(4^{\sqrt{9}} - \left(F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \times (-5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$54796 := \left(F(F(6)) - \left(\left(9 + F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) \right) \times (-5) \right) \right)$$

$$54874 := \left(F(\sqrt{4} + F(7)) + C(F(8), (F(4) \times 5)) \right)$$

$$56259 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(C(5, 2)) \right) \times F((F(F(6)) - 5)) \right)$$

$$56448 := \left(\left(84^{\sqrt{4}} \times F(C(6, 5)) \right) \right)$$

$$56927 := \left(\left(C(F(7), F(2))^{\sqrt{9}} - \left(F(F(F(6))) \times (-5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$56975 := \left(-5 \times \left(F(F(7)) - C\left(-\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(6))\right), 5\right) \right) \right)$$

$$57684 := \left(C(\sqrt{4} + F(8), F(F(6))) \times (F(F(7)) - 5) \right)$$

$$57855 := \left(5 \times \left(\sqrt{5^8} + F(C(7, 5)) \right) \right)$$

$$57966 := \left(6 \times \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) - C(F(7), 5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$58993 := \left(\left((3^9) \times \sqrt{9} - C(8, 5) \right) \right)$$

$$58994 := - \left(\left(F(F(\sqrt{4} + 9)) - \left(C(9, 8^5) \right) \right) \right)$$

$$59054 := \left(\left(F(4) \right)^{C(5, \sqrt{09})} + 5 \right)$$

$$59259 := \left(C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 2) + (9^5) \right)$$

$$59374 := \left(C(\sqrt{4} \times F(7), F(3)) + (9^5) \right)$$

$$59469 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}) \right) + (9^5) \right)$$

$$59876 := \left(F(F(F(6))) + \left(F(F(7)) \times C(F(8), \sqrt{9-5}) \right) \right)$$

$$59974 := - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (7 \times C((9+9), 5)) \right) \right)$$

$$59979 := \left(\sqrt{9} + (7 \times C((9+9), 5)) \right)$$

$$59997 := \left(7 \times \left(\sqrt{9} + C((9+9), 5) \right) \right)$$

$$63669 := \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - F(F(F(6))) \right) + C((F(F(6)) + F(F(3))), 6) \right)$$

$$63696 := \left(F(6) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{9} - C(F(F(6)), 3) \right) \times (-6) \right) \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 63848 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (C(F(8), 3) \times (-6)) \right) \right) \\
 63978 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) - 3) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 63979 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{C(9,7)} + F(9) \right)^3 - F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 63995 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - (C(9,3)) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 64345 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) - C((F(3)^4), F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 64396 &:= - \left(\left(C\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9} \right), 3 \right) - (4^{F(6)}) \right) \right) \\
 64467 &:= \left(F(7) \times \left(- \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), 4) + \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 64636 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times (-F(F(3)))) + \left(C\left(\left(F(F(6)) - \sqrt{4} \right), F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 64758 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) - (C(5 + F(7), \sqrt{4})) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 64774 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) \times F(F(7)) \right) \times (C(F(7), F(4)) - F(6)) \right) \\
 64926 &:= \left(- (F(C(6,2))) + \left(F(\sqrt{9})^{\sqrt{4} \times F(6)} \right) \right) \\
 64956 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - C\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9} \right), F(4) \right) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 65466 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 6) - C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 5 \right), 6 \right) \right) \\
 65547 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F(7) \times \sqrt{4} \right), 5 \right) - F((5 + F(6))) \right) \\
 65674 &:= - \left(\left(\sqrt{4} - (F(C(C(7,6), 5) \times 6)) \right) \right) \\
 65679 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + (F(C(C(7,6), 5) \times 6)) \right) \\
 65697 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(7 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times C(6,5) \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \\
 65739 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times ((F(3) \times F(C(7,5))) + F(F(6))) \right) \\
 65754 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{4} + (5) \right) \right) + (F(C(7,5))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 65774 &:= \left(C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F(7) \right), C(7,5) \right) - (6) \right) \\
 65796 &:= \left(\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) + F(C(7,5)) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 65799 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) - (C\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times F(7) \right), 5 \right) + F(F(6))) \right) \right) \\
 66146 &:= F(C(6,4)) + \sqrt{16^{F(6)}} \\
 66957 &:= \left(C(F(7), 5) + \left(\left(F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times (-6) \right) \right) \\
 66996 &:= \left(\left(C\left((F(F(6)) - 9), \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 67829 &:= - \left(\left(F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - (2 \times (C(F(8), F(7)) / 6)) \right) \right) \\
 67834 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times (F(3) + (C(F(8), F(7)) / 6)) \right) \\
 67848 &:= \left(8 \times \left(F\left(- \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - (F(8)) \right) \right) \right) + C(F(7), 6) \right) \right) \\
 67938 &:= \left(\left(F(F(8)) + F\left(\left(C\left(3, \sqrt{9} \right) + F(7) \right) \right) \right) \times 6 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 68679 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \times 7 \right), F(6) \right) + (F(F(8)) \times 6) \right) \\
 69564 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(-(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(6)) \right), 5 \right) - F(9) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 69896 &:= \left(\left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(\left(\sqrt{C(9,8)} \right)^9 \right) \right) \times (-F(6)) \right) \\
 69978 &:= \left(\left((F(F(8)) + (C(F(7), 9))) + F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \times 6 \right) \\
 70844 &:= \left(4 \times F\left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C(8,07)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 72774 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(F(7)) \right) \times (C(F(7), 2) + F(F(7))) \right) \\
 73395 &:= \left(\left(C\left(\left(5 \times \sqrt{9} \right), F(3) \right) \times 3 \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) \\
 73461 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(1 + C\left(F(6), \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) - F(3) \right) / 7 \right) \\
 73695 &:= \left(F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - (C(F(F(6)), F(-((3-7)))) \right) \\
 74368 &:= \left(8 \times \left(\left(C(F(F(6)), 3) - \sqrt{4} \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 74384 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + (C((8 \times 3), 4) \times 7) \right) \\
 74389 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + C((8 \times 3), 4) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 74465 &:= \left(F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^{F(6)}}} \right) - C((4 \times 4), F(7)) \right) \\
 74466 &:= \left(\left((-F(6)) \times C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + \sqrt{4} \right) \times (-7) \right) \\
 74614 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + C((1 + F(F(6))), (F(4) + F(7))) \right) \\
 74618 &:= \left(\left(C((F(8) + 1), 6) - \sqrt{4} \right) + (7) \right) \\
 74626 &:= \left(C\left((F(F(6)) + F(2)), (F(6) - \sqrt{4}) \right) + (F(7)) \right) \\
 74628 &:= \left(\left(C((F(8) + F(2)), 6) + \sqrt{4} \right) + F(7) \right) \\
 74695 &:= \left(F\left(\left(5^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \right) - C((F(6) + F(4)), 7) \right) \\
 74846 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F(F(6)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right), (8 - \sqrt{4}) \right) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 74947 &:= \left(- \left(C\left(F(7), \sqrt{4} \right) + F((9 + F(4)) + F(7)) \right) \right) \\
 75248 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F(8), \sqrt{4} \right) + F(25) \right) + F(7) \right) \\
 75795 &:= \left(\left(- \left(C\left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times F(F(7)) \right) + (5^7) \right) \\
 76379 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + ((-C(7,3)) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 7 \right) \\
 76412 &:= \left(- \left(C\left(21, \sqrt{4} \right) - (F(F(F(6))) \times (-7)) \right) \right) \\
 76447 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - 4 \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76473 &:= \left(- (F(3)) + \left(\left(F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \\
 76474 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - \left(\left(F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) - F(F(6)) \right) \times 7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 76484 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} + F(F(8)) \right) + (4^{C(F(6),7)}) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 76564 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) + \left(F\left(F\left(F\left(C\left(6, 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F\left(6 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76569 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} + \left(F\left(F\left(F\left(C\left(6, 5 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F\left(6 \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76579 &:= \left(-\left(F\left(\sqrt{C\left(9, 7 \right)} \right) \right) + \left(\left(-5 \right) + F\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) \\
 76945 &:= \left(F\left(C\left(5, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(-6 \right) \times F\left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 76947 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F\left(7 \right) \times \sqrt{4} \right), F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(F\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 77289 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) + C\left(\left(F\left(8 \right) - F\left(2 \right) \right), F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) - F\left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 77486 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right) - C\left(\left(F\left(8 \right) - F\left(\sqrt{4} \right) \right), F\left(7 \right) \right) - \left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 77519 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) - C\left(\left(-1 \right) + F\left(\left(-5 \right) + F\left(7 \right) \right) \right), F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 77636 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), \sqrt{F\left(3 \right) \times F\left(6 \right)} \right) - \left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(7 \right) \right) \\
 77798 &:= \left(\left(C\left(F\left(8 \right), \sqrt{9+7} \right) \times F\left(7 \right) \right) - \left(7 \right) \right) \\
 77892 &:= \left(\left(\left(2 + \sqrt{C\left(9, 8 \right)} \right)^7 \right) - F\left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 77948 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(F\left(8 \right), 4 \right) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(7 \right) \right) \\
 79499 &:= \left(\left(\left(9 + F\left(9 \right) \right)^{F\left(4 \right)} - F\left(\sqrt{C\left(9, 7 \right)} \right) \right) \right) \\
 79685 &:= \left(F\left(\sqrt{\sqrt{5^8}} \right) + \left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \times F\left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 79847 &:= \left(\left(7 \times C\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times 8 \right), 9 \right) \right) - F\left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \\
 81396 &:= \left(C\left(\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), \left(3 + 1 \right) \right) \times F\left(8 \right) \right) \\
 82689 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(\left(F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) - \left(F\left(C\left(6, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 83647 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(7 \right) \right) \times \left(C\left(\sqrt{F\left(4 \right)^6}, F\left(3 \right) \right) + 8 \right) \right) \\
 83895 &:= \left(\left(5 + \left(\sqrt{9} \times C\left(F\left(8 \right), 3 \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(8 \right) \right) \\
 84368 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) - \sqrt{C\left(6, 3 \right)^4} \right) \times 8 \right) \\
 84645 &:= \left(-\left(5 \right) \times \left(\sqrt{4} - \left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), 4 \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84654 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{4} \right) + \left(-5 \right) \times \left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), 4 \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84655 &:= \left(\sqrt{5 \times 5} \times \left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), 4 \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84672 &:= \left(F\left(-\left(\left(F\left(2 \right) - F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times \left(C\left(F\left(6 \right), \sqrt{4} \right) \times F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 84968 &:= \left(-\left(8 \right) \times \left(C\left(-\left(\left(F\left(6 \right) - F\left(9 \right) \right) \right), \sqrt{4} \right) - F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 84984 &:= \left(\left(F\left(4 \right) - C\left(\left(8 \times \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) \right) \times \left(-8 \right) \right) \\
 85848 &:= \left(\left(\left(C\left(F\left(8 \right), \sqrt{4} \right) - F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) \times \left(-8 \right) \right) \\
 85966 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(C\left(F\left(6 \right), 6 \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) - \left(5 \right) \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 85967 &:= \left(7 \times \left(\left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + \left(5 \right) \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 86634 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - \left(-F\left(3 \right) \right) \times \left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), 6 \right) - F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86639 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(-F\left(3 \right) \right) \times \left(C\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right), 6 \right) - F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86938 &:= \left(-\left(\left(C\left(F\left(8 \right), F\left(3 \right) \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(-F\left(6 \right) \right) \times F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 86958 &:= \left(\left(F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \times \left(-C\left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) + F\left(\left(6 + F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87477 &:= \left(\left(\left(-F\left(7 \right) \right) + F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \right) \times 7 \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \\
 87514 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times \left(-1 \right) + C\left(\left(5 + F\left(7 \right) \right), 8 \right) \right) \\
 87516 &:= \left(F\left(\sqrt{F\left(6 \right) + 1} \right) \times C\left(\left(5 + F\left(7 \right) \right), 8 \right) \right) \\
 87547 &:= \left(\left(F\left(C\left(7, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) \times \left(-5 \right) + F\left(7 \right) \right) - \left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \\
 87799 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) + \left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{C\left(9, 7 \right)} + F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) \times \left(-F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87953 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\left(F\left(3 \right) \times C\left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(7 \right) \right) + 8 \right) \\
 87963 &:= \left(\left(\left(F\left(3 \right) + F\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(7 \right) \right) - 8 \right) \\
 87964 &:= \left(-\left(\sqrt{4}\right) - \left(\left(F\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(-F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) - \left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 87969 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} - \left(\left(F\left(C\left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times \left(-F\left(7 \right) \right) \right) - \left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 88464 &:= \left(\left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times C\left(F\left(6 \right), F\left(4 \right) \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \times 8 \right) \right) \\
 88898 &:= \left(C\left(F\left(8 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) - \left(F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \times \left(-\sqrt{8 \times 8} \right) \right) \right) \\
 89248 &:= \left(8 \times \left(C\left(F\left(\left(4 \times 2 \right) \right), F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89296 &:= \left(F\left(6 \right) \times \left(\left(\sqrt{C\left(9, 2 \right)}^{\sqrt{9}} + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89686 &:= -\left(\left(F\left(F\left(F\left(6 \right) \right) \right) - \left(C\left(F\left(8 \right), 6 \right) + F\left(\left(\sqrt{9} \times 8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89856 &:= \left(F\left(6 \right) \times \left(C\left(\left(5 + 8 \right), \sqrt{9} \right) + F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 89986 &:= \left(\left(6 \times F\left(F\left(8 \right) \right) \right) + C\left(\left(F\left(9 \right) / F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right), 8 \right) \right) \\
 91125 &:= \left(C\left(C\left(5, 2 \right), \left(1 + 1 \right) \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) \\
 92376 &:= \left(C\left(\left(6 + F\left(7 \right) \right), \left(3^2 \right) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 92379 &:= \left(F\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) + \left(C\left(\left(\left(7 \times 3 \right) - 2 \right), 9 \right) \right) \right) \\
 92732 &:= \left(\left(-2 \right) + F\left(\left(3 + C\left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \\
 92733 &:= \left(F\left(3 \right) \times F\left(\left(3 + C\left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) - \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 92734 &:= \left(\left(\sqrt{4} \times F\left(\left(3 + C\left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) - F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 92736 &:= \left(\left(6 \times F\left(\left(3 + C\left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 92739 &:= \left(\left(F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \times F\left(\left(3 + C\left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) + \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 92744 &:= \left(\left(4 + F\left(\left(F\left(4 \right) + \left(C\left(7, 2 \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \times F\left(\sqrt{9} \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 92928 &:= \left((C(F(8), 2) - F(9))^2 \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 93294 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} \times ((C(9, 2)^3 - 9) \right) \\
 93987 &:= \left(\left((F(F(7)) - C(8, \sqrt{9}))^{F(3)} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 94597 &:= \left((F(F(7)) \times C((F(9) - (5)), \sqrt{4})) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 94647 &:= \left(-(7) \times \left(-(\sqrt{4}) \times F(C(6, F(4))) + 9 \right) \right) \\
 94668 &:= \left((8 + 6) \times (F(C(6, F(4))) - \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 94864 &:= \left((F(4) + F(6)) \times C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \\
 94962 &:= \left(C((-2) + F(F(6))), 9) + F(\sqrt{4} \times 9) \right) \\
 94988 &:= \left(-(F(F(8))) + \left(F(C(8, F(\sqrt{9}))) / F(4) - \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 94996 &:= \left((C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(9 \times \sqrt{4})) \times F(9) \right) \\
 96498 &:= \left((C(8, \sqrt{9}) \times 4) - F(F(F(6))) \right) \times (-9) \\
 96624 &:= \left((F(4)^2) \times (F(F(F(6))) - C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 96695 &:= 5^{F(\sqrt{9})+6} - C(F(F(6)), 9) \\
 96796 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) \times 9) + \left(-(C(F(7), 6)) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 96798 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times 9) - C(F(7), (F(6) - F(\sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 96878 &:= \left(F(F(8)) - \left(-(7) \times (F(F(8)) + C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \\
 97494 &:= \left((F((F(4) \times 9) / \sqrt{4}) - (C(F(7), 9)) \right) \\
 97589 &:= \left((\sqrt{9} \times (8^5)) - C(F(7), 9) \right) \\
 97696 &:= \left((C(F(F(6)), 9) + (F(F(F(6))) / (-F(7))) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97947 &:= \left((F(C(7, \sqrt{4})) - (9 \times 7)) \times 9 \right) \\
 97956 &:= \left((F(F(F(6))) - (F(C(5, \sqrt{9})) + (7))) \times 9 \right) \\
 97969 &:= \left(((C(9, F(6)) \times F(9)) + (7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 97979 &:= \left((C((F(9) - F(7)), 9) + (7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97981 &:= \left((C(F((1 \times 8)), 9) + F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97982 &:= \left(F(2) + (C(F(8), 9) + F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97983 &:= \left(F(3) + (C(F(8), 9) + F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97984 &:= \left(F(4) + (C(F(8), 9) + F(7)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97986 &:= \left((F(F(6)) + ((C(F(8), 9) + (7))) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 97988 &:= \left((F(8) + (C(F(8), 9) + F(7))) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98209 &:= \left(F(\sqrt{C(9, 02)} + F(8)) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98246 &:= \left(C(C(F(6), \sqrt{4}), (2 + F(8))) - F(9) \right) \\
 98264 &:= \left(\sqrt{4} + ((-C(F(6), 2)) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \\
 98267 &:= \left(-(F(7) - C(C(F(6), 2), (8 - \sqrt{9}))) \right) \\
 98278 &:= \left(C((F(8) + (7)), (2 + F(8))) - F(\sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98349 &:= \left(-C((9 + \sqrt{4}), 3) + (F(F(8)) \times 9) \right) \\
 98427 &:= \left(-(C(F(7), 2)) + (F(\sqrt{4}) - F(F(8))) \times (-9) \right) \\
 98458 &:= \left((F(F(8)) \times (5 + 4)) - C(8, \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98547 &:= \left(C(F(7), \sqrt{4}) + ((-5) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \\
 98663 &:= \left((C(\sqrt{3^6}, 6) - F(8)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98665 &:= \left(-(5) + (C((F(F(6)) + (6)), F(8)) / \sqrt{9}) \right) \\
 98669 &:= \left((-\sqrt{9}) + C((F(F(6)) + (6)), F(8)) / \sqrt{9} \right) \\
 98679 &:= \left(C(-((F(\sqrt{9}) - (F(7)))) , F(6)) + (F(F(8)) \times 9) \right) \\
 98919 &:= \left((C((9 + 1), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(8))) \times 9 \right) \\
 98969 &:= \left(C((9 + 6), \sqrt{9}) + (F(F(8)) \times 9) \right) \\
 99437 &:= \left(-(F(7) - (C(3^{F(4)}, \sqrt{9}) \times F(9))) \right) \\
 99445 &:= \left(-(5) + (C((F(4)^{F(4)}, \sqrt{9}) \times F(9)) \right) \\
 99449 &:= \left((C((9 \times F(4)), F(4)) \times F(9)) - F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 99465 &:= \left(5 \times (C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4}) + (\sqrt{9^9})) \right) \\
 99649 &:= \left(((C(9, 4) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 9) + F(F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 99846 &:= \left(C(F(F(6)), F(4)) + ((F(F(8)) \times 9) + F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 99888 &:= \left(8 \times (F(F(8)) + C((F(8) + F(F(\sqrt{9}))), \sqrt{9})) \right) \\
 99957 &:= \left(F(F(7)) \times ((5 \times C(9, \sqrt{9})) + 9) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

3.6 Factorial and Square-Root Together

In this case, only few results are given. Not all the 5-digits numbers possibilities are included. The rest numbers shall be given later on.

3.6.1 Symmetric Representations

$$3990 := 0 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3991 := 1 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3992 := 2 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3993 := 3 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3994 := 4 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3995 := 5 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3996 := 6 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3997 := 7 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3998 := 8 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$3999 := 9 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), \sqrt{9}\right) \times 3$$

$$9690 := 0 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9691 := 1 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9692 := 2 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9693 := 3 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9694 := 4 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9695 := 5 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9696 := 6 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9697 := 7 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9698 := 8 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$9699 := 9 + C\left(F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right), F(6)\right) / F\left(F\left(\left(\sqrt{9}\right)!\right)\right)$$

$$04430 := 0 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04431 := 1 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04432 := 2 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04433 := 3 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04434 := 4 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04435 := 5 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04436 := 6 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04437 := 7 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04438 := 8 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$04439 := 9 - F\left(C\left(3!, \sqrt{4}\right)\right) + (F(4)! + 0)!$$

$$06370 := 0 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06371 := 1 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06372 := 2 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06373 := 3 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06374 := 4 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06375 := 5 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06376 := 6 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06377 := 7 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06378 := 8 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06379 := 9 + 7! + C\left(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06650 := 0 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06651 := 1 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06652 := 2 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06653 := 3 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06654 := 4 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06655 := 5 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06656 := 6 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06657 := 7 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06658 := 8 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$06659 := 9 + 5 \times C\left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(6) + 0!}\right)$$

$$07980 := 0 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7 - 0!)$$

$$07981 := 1 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7 - 0!)$$

$$07982 := 2 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7 - 0!)$$

$$07983 := 3 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7 - 0!)$$

$$07984 := 4 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7 - 0!)$$

$$07985 := 5 + C\left(F(8), \sqrt{9}\right) \times (7 - 0!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{07986} &:= 6 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times (7-0!) & \mathbf{37986} &:= 6 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) \\
 \mathbf{07987} &:= 7 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times (7-0!) & \mathbf{37987} &:= 7 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) \\
 \mathbf{07988} &:= 8 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times (7-0!) & \mathbf{37988} &:= 8 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) \\
 \mathbf{07989} &:= 9 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times (7-0!) & \mathbf{37989} &:= 9 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{23790} &:= 0 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38430} &:= 0 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23791} &:= 1 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38431} &:= 1 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23792} &:= 2 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38432} &:= 2 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23793} &:= 3 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38433} &:= 3 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23794} &:= 4 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38434} &:= 4 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23795} &:= 5 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38435} &:= 5 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23796} &:= 6 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38436} &:= 6 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23797} &:= 7 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38437} &:= 7 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23798} &:= 8 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38438} &:= 8 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \mathbf{23799} &:= 9 + \sqrt{9} \times F(7) \times F(C(3!, 2)) & \mathbf{38439} &:= 9 + F(C(3!, \sqrt{4})) \times F(8) \times 3 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{27930} &:= 0 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39180} &:= 0 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27931} &:= 1 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39181} &:= 1 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27932} &:= 2 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39182} &:= 2 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27933} &:= 3 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39183} &:= 3 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27934} &:= 4 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39184} &:= 4 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27935} &:= 5 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39185} &:= 5 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27936} &:= 6 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39186} &:= 6 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27937} &:= 7 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39187} &:= 7 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27938} &:= 8 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39188} &:= 8 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{27939} &:= 9 + C(F(F(3!)), \sqrt{9}) \times C(7, 2) & \mathbf{39189} &:= 9 - C(F(8) - 1, \sqrt{9}) + F(3)! \\
 \\
 \mathbf{37980} &:= 0 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) & \mathbf{39390} &:= 0 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{37981} &:= 1 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) & \mathbf{39391} &:= 1 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{37982} &:= 2 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) & \mathbf{39392} &:= 2 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{37983} &:= 3 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) & \mathbf{39393} &:= 3 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{37984} &:= 4 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) & \mathbf{39394} &:= 4 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)! \\
 \mathbf{37985} &:= 5 + (-8! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!))), 7)) / F(3) & \mathbf{39395} &:= 5 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)!
 \end{aligned}$$

$$39396 := 6 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)!$$

$$39397 := 7 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)!$$

$$39398 := 8 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)!$$

$$39399 := 9 - (\sqrt{9})!! - C(F(F(3!)), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(3)!$$

$$40530 := 0 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40531 := 1 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40532 := 2 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40533 := 3 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40534 := 4 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40535 := 5 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40536 := 6 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40537 := 7 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40538 := 8 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$40539 := 9 + F(3)! + C(F(F(5+0!)), \sqrt{4})$$

$$41990 := 0 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41991 := 1 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41992 := 2 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41993 := 3 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41994 := 4 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41995 := 5 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41996 := 6 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41997 := 7 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41998 := 8 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$41999 := 9 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9}!)), 9) / (1 + F(4)!))$$

$$42980 := 0 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42981 := 1 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42982 := 2 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42983 := 3 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42984 := 4 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42985 := 5 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42986 := 6 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42987 := 7 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42988 := 8 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$42989 := 9 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) \times 2 + F(F(4)!)$$

$$43980 := 0 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43981 := 1 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43982 := 2 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43983 := 3 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43984 := 4 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43985 := 5 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43986 := 6 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43987 := 7 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43988 := 8 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$43989 := 9 + 8! + (\sqrt{9})! \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$49840 := 0 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49841 := 1 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49842 := 2 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49843 := 3 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49844 := 4 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49845 := 5 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49846 := 6 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49847 := 7 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49848 := 8 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$49849 := 9 + (F(4)!! - 8) \times C(F((\sqrt{9}!), 4)$$

$$54390 := 0 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54391 := 1 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54392 := 2 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54393 := 3 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54394 := 4 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54395 := 5 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54396 := 6 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54397 := 7 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54398 := 8 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$54399 := 9 + (\sqrt{9})! + C(F(F(3!)), F(4)!) + 5!$$

$$64490 := 0 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64491 := 1 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64492 := 2 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64493 := 3 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64494 := 4 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64495 := 5 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64496 := 6 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64497 := 7 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64498 := 8 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$64499 := 9 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), F(4)!) - F(4)!! + F(F(F(6)))$$

$$75690 := 0 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75691 := 1 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75692 := 2 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75693 := 3 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75694 := 4 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75695 := 5 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75696 := 6 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75697 := 7 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75698 := 8 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75699 := 9 + C(\sqrt{\sqrt{9^6}}, 5) - 7!$$

$$75960 := 0 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75961 := 1 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75962 := 2 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75963 := 3 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75964 := 4 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75965 := 5 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75966 := 6 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75967 := 7 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75968 := 8 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$75969 := 9 - F(6)! + C(F(\sqrt{9} + 5), 7)$$

$$94710 := 0 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94711 := 1 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94712 := 2 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94713 := 3 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94714 := 4 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94715 := 5 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94716 := 6 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94717 := 7 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94718 := 8 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

$$94719 := 9 + (1 + F(7)) \times F(C(F(4!), \sqrt{9}))$$

3.6.2 Non Symmetric Representations

$$444 := ((F(4)!)! - (C(4!, \sqrt{4})))$$

$$792 := C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7)$$

$$924 := C(((4)!) / 2, (\sqrt{9})!)$$

$$0341 := \sqrt{1 + C(F(F(F(4)!)), 3! + 0!)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 0399 &:= \left(C \left((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9} \right)^{F(3)} - (0)! \right) \\
 0495 &:= \left(F \left(C \left(5, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \times (F((F(4))!) + (0)!) \right) \\
 0496 &:= \left(C \left(\left(6 + (\sqrt{9})! \right), 4 \right) + (0)! \right) \\
 0748 &:= \left(C \left(8, \sqrt{4} \right) + ((7 - (0)!)!) \right) \\
 0792 &:= C \left(\left(2 \times (\sqrt{9})! \right), (7 + 0) \right) \\
 0843 &:= \left(F \left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F(F((8 - (0)!)!)) \right) \\
 0923 &:= \left(C \left(((3)! \times 2), (\sqrt{9})! \right) - (0)! \right) \\
 0924 &:= C \left(4!/2, (\sqrt{9+0})! \right) \\
 1157 &:= F(7) \times F \left(\sqrt{5! + C(1,1)} \right) \\
 1279 &:= - \left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) - (C(F(7), F((2+1)!)!)) \right) \right) \\
 1339 &:= \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) + (C(F(F(3)!), 3) + 1) \right) \\
 1369 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{9})! + F(F(F(6))) \right) / F(C(3,1)!) \right) \\
 1464 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (6)!) + (C(4,1)!) \right) \\
 1469 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \times C(F(6), 4) \right) - 1 \right) \\
 1792 &:= \left(\left(2^{F((\sqrt{9})!)} \right) \times C(7, 1) \right) \\
 1899 &:= \left(\left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right)! / F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right) - F(C(8,1)) \right) \\
 2444 &:= \left(4 \times \left(F(\sqrt{4}) + F(C((F(4))!, 2)) \right) \right) \\
 2484 &:= \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) + 8 \right) \times C((4)!, 2) \right) \\
 2689 &:= \left(F \left(F(\sqrt{9}) \right) - ((8)! / (-C(6,2))) \right) \\
 2696 &:= \left(F(6) - \left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right)! / (-C(6,2)) \right) \right) \\
 2729 &:= \left(\left(C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 2 \right) \times F(7) \right) - F(2) \right) \\
 2796 &:= \left(\left(6 + (\sqrt{9})! \right) \times F(C(F(7), F(2))) \right) \\
 2945 &:= \left(- (5) \times \left(F(F((F(4))!) - F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2))) \right) \right) \\
 3449 &:= \left(\left(F \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right) / \sqrt{4} \right) - (C((4)!, 3)) \right) \\
 3464 &:= \left((\sqrt{4} \times (6)!) + C((4)!, 3) \right) \\
 3879 &:= \left(\sqrt{9} \times (C(F(7), 8) + (3)!) \right) \\
 3998 &:= \left(\left(C \left(F(8), \sqrt{9} \right) \times \sqrt{9} \right) + F((3)!) \right) \\
 4296 &:= 6! \times \sqrt{C(9,2)} - 4! \\
 4389 &:= \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \times \left(C(F(8), F(3)) - F(\sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 4391 &:= \left(F(19) + C \left(F(F((3)!)!, \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \\
 4431 &:= \left(\left(1 + C \left(F(F((3)!)!, \sqrt{4}) \right) \right) \times F(F((F(4))!)! \right) \\
 4754 &:= \left(\left((\sqrt{4} + (5))! \right) - (C(F(7), F(4))) \right) \\
 4839 &:= \left(- \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) + C \left(- \left(F(F(3)) - F(8) \right) \right), 4 \right) \\
 4848 &:= \left(\left(C \left(F(8), \sqrt{4} \right) - 8 \right) \times (4)! \right) \\
 4961 &:= \left(F(F(F((1 \times 6))) - C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 4 \right) \right) \\
 4962 &:= \left((F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) - C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 4 \right) \right) \\
 4963 &:= \left((F(3) + F(F(F(6)))) - C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 4 \right) \right) \\
 4965 &:= \left((5)! + C \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right), 4 \right) \right) \\
 4969 &:= \left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) + F(F(F(6))) \right) - C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 4 \right) \right) \\
 4999 &:= \left(C \left(\left((\sqrt{9})! + 9 \right), (\sqrt{9})! \right) - (F(4)!) \right) \\
 5739 &:= \left(\left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \times ((3)!) \right) - C(7, 5) \right) \\
 5865 &:= -5! + C \left(F(F(6)), \sqrt{F(8)-5} \right) \\
 6429 &:= \left(C \left(C \left((\sqrt{9})!, 2 \right), F((F(4))!) \right) - 6 \right) \\
 6433 &:= - \left(\left(F(3) - C \left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{4} \right), F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6434 &:= - \left(\left(F(\sqrt{4}) - C \left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{4} \right), F(6) \right) \right) \right) \\
 6443 &:= \left(F((3)!) + C \left(C \left((F(4))!, \sqrt{4} \right), F(6) \right) \right) \\
 6495 &:= \left(\left(- (5) \times F \left(C \left((\sqrt{9})!, F(4) \right) \right) \right) + (F(6)!) \right) \\
 6793 &:= \left(\left(F \left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) + 7 \right) + F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 6933 &:= \left(F(C((3)!, 3)) + \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \times F(F(6)) \right) \right) \\
 7739 &:= \left(\left(C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), (3)! \right) / 7 \right) - F(7) \right) \\
 7849 &:= \left(C \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right), 4 \right) - (- (8) \times F(F(7))) \right) \\
 7993 &:= \left(\left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right)^{\sqrt{9}} \right) - (7) \right) \\
 8922 &:= \left(- \left(C \left(((2+2)!, \sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \\
 8943 &:= \left(F(F((3)!) + \left(- \left(C \left((4)!, \sqrt{9} \right) + F(F(8)) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9044 &:= C(F(F(F(4))!), F(4)!) / (\sqrt{09})! \\
 9317 &:= \left(7 \times \left(1 + C \left(F(F((3)!)!, \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9324 &:= \left(- (C((4)!, 2) + ((3)!)! \times F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right) \\
 9349 &:= \left(F \left(\left(9 \times \sqrt{4} \right) \right) + F \left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9403 &:= \left(C \left(F(F((3)!)!, ((0)! + (4))) - F \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9406 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - C \left(((0)! + F(F((F(4))!)!)), \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \\
 9476 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(7 \times C \left(F(F((F(4))!)!, F(\sqrt{9})) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9593 &:= \left(\left(F \left(C \left((3)!, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) / (-5) \right) + F \left(F \left(F \left((\sqrt{9})! \right) \right) \right) \right) \\
 9645 &:= \left(((5)! \times (4)!) + F \left(C \left(6, \sqrt{9} \right) \right) \right) \\
 9684 &:= \left((C(F(F((F(4))!)!, 8) / F(F(6))) - (\sqrt{9})! \right) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 9685 &:= \left(- (5) + \left(C(F(8), F(6)) / F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \right) \right) \\
 9689 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), 8) - (F(F(6)))) / F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \right) \right) \\
 9806 &:= \left(F(F(F(6))) - \left(C(-((0)! - F(8)), \sqrt{9}) \right) \right) \\
 00682 &:= 2 \times \sqrt{C(F(8), F(6) - 0!) + 0!} \\
 00792 &:= C\left(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, ((7 - (0)!) - (0)!) \right) \\
 00923 &:= \left(C((3)! \times 2), (\sqrt{9})! \right) - (00)! \\
 02443 &:= \left(\left(F(C(3)!, \sqrt{4}) \times 4 \right) + (2 + (0)!) \right) \\
 02941 &:= \left(\left(14 \times C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) \right) + (0)! \right) \\
 04391 &:= \left(F(19) - \left(C(F(F((3)!), \sqrt{4}) \times (- (0)!) \right) \right) \\
 04432 &:= \left((2 \times F((3)!)) \times \left(C(4)!, \sqrt{4} \right) + (0)! \right) \\
 04733 &:= \left(\left(C(F((3)!), F(3)) \times \left(F(7)^{\sqrt{4}} \right) \right) + (0)! \right) \\
 04831 &:= \left(((1 + (3)!))! - \left(C(F(8), \sqrt{4}) - (0)! \right) \right) \\
 05401 &:= \left(\left(C(10, \sqrt{4}) \times (5)! \right) + (0)! \right) \\
 05961 &:= \left(- \left((\sqrt{16})! \right) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (5 - (0)!) \right) \\
 05962 &:= \left((- (2) - F(F(6))) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (5 - (0)!) \right) \\
 05971 &:= \left((- (1) - F(7)) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (5 - (0)!) \right) \\
 05972 &:= \left(- ((F(2) \times F(7))) + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), (5 - (0)!) \right) \\
 05991 &:= \left(\sqrt{1 \times 9}! + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), 5 - 0! \right) \\
 06291 &:= \left((- (1) + C(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) \right) \times F(F((F(6) - (0)!))) \\
 06432 &:= \left(- (2) + \left(C(C(3)!, \sqrt{4}), F(6) \right) - (0)! \right) \\
 06433 &:= \left(- (3) + \left(C(C(3)!, \sqrt{4}), F(6) \right) + (0)! \right) \\
 07333 &:= F(C(3!, 3)) + \left(F(3!) \times \sqrt{7! + 0!} \right) \\
 08922 &:= \left(- \left(C((2 + 2)!, \sqrt{9}) \right) + F(F((8 + 0))) \right) \\
 08923 &:= - \left(\left(C((F(3) + 2)!, \sqrt{9}) - F(F(8)) \right) - (0)! \right) \\
 09043 &:= C(F(F(3)!), F(4)!) / (\sqrt{09})! - 0! \\
 09723 &:= \left(\left(F((3^2)) \times C(F(7), \sqrt{9}) \right) - (0)! \right) \\
 10961 &:= \left(F(F(F((1 \times 6)))) + C((\sqrt{9})!, ((0)! + 1)) \right) \\
 11592 &:= \left(F(\left((F(2) + \sqrt{9}) \right)!) / C((5 - 1), 1) \right) \\
 13451 &:= \sqrt{1 + 5!} + F(F(4)!) / C(3, 1) \\
 15981 &:= \left(\left((- ((1 - 8)!) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \right) - C(5, 1) \right) \\
 15991 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 + (\sqrt{9})!) \right)! + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \right) + C(5, 1) \right) \\
 16392 &:= 2^{(\sqrt{9})! + F(3)} + F(C(6, 1)) \\
 17942 &:= F(-2 + 4!) - F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(C(7, 1))) \\
 19292 &:= \left(\left(2 + C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) \right) \times 91 \right) \\
 19362 &:= \left(- (F((2 \times F(6)))) + C(F(F((3)!), ((\sqrt{9})! - 1)) \right) \\
 19381 &:= \left(\left(C((- (1) + F(8)), (3)!) / F(\sqrt{9}) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 19382 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(C(F(8), F((3)!)) / F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \right) + 1 \right) \right) \\
 19413 &:= (3!! - 1) \times \left(4! + \sqrt{C(9, 1)} \right) \\
 19482 &:= \left(C((2 + F(8)), F(4)) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) + 1) \right) \\
 19951 &:= \left(\left(15 \times C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!), \sqrt{9}) \right) + 1 \right) \\
 19962 &:= 2 \times \left(F(F(6))^{\sqrt{9}} + \sqrt{C(9, 1)!} \right) \\
 19971 &:= \left(((1 + 7)!) - C(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)), ((\sqrt{9})! - 1) \right) \\
 20343 &:= \left(C(F(F((3)!), (\sqrt{4} + 3)) - ((0)! + 2) \right) \\
 23343 &:= \left(C(3)!, \sqrt{4} \right) + \left(((3)!)^3 / 2 \right) \\
 23751 &:= C(\sqrt{1 + 5!} \times 7, F(3) + 2) \\
 23941 &:= \left(\left(C((- (1) + F(F((F(4)!))), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F((3)!)) \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 23942 &:= \left(\left(C((- (F(2) + F(F((F(4)!))), \sqrt{9}) \times F(F((3)!)) \right) + 2 \right) \\
 25391 &:= \left(\left((1 + (\sqrt{9})!) \right)! + (C(F(F((3)!), 5) + 2) \right) \\
 26933 &:= \left(\left(F((3)!) + F(C(3)!, \sqrt{9}) \right) + ((F(6)!) / 2) \right) \\
 27992 &:= \left(2 \times \left(\left(F(C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)) \right) \times 2 \right) \right) \\
 29242 &:= \left(\left(C((- (2) + F(F((F(4)!))), 2)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + F(2) \right) \\
 29243 &:= \left(\left(C(\left(F(F((3)!) - \sqrt{4} \right), 2)^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) + 2 \right) \\
 29362 &:= \left(F((2 + F(F(6)))) + \left(((3)!)! - C((\sqrt{9})!, 2) \right) \right) \\
 29402 &:= \left(\left((F(((2 + (0)!)!))! - F(F(F((F(4)!)))) \right) + C(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) \right) \\
 29652 &:= \left(\left(((2 + 5)!) + C(F(F(6)), (\sqrt{9})!) \right) / 2 \right) \\
 29791 &:= \left(\left(\left((1 + \sqrt{9}) \right)! + 7 \right)^{C(\sqrt{9}, F(2))} \right) \\
 29833 &:= \left((C(F((3)!), 3) \times F(8)) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!) + 2) \right) \\
 29982 &:= \left(\left((- (2) - F(F(8))) + \left(F((\sqrt{9})!) \right) + F(C((\sqrt{9})!, 2) \right) \right) \\
 32922 &:= \left(F((2 + 2)) \times \left(C(F((\sqrt{9})!), 2) + F(F(F((3)!))) \right) \right) \\
 33891 &:= - \left(\left(\left((1 + \sqrt{9}) \right)! - (C(F(8), F((3)!)) / (3)!) \right) \right) \\
 33921 &:= \left(\left(C(F(F(((1 + 2)!)!), F((\sqrt{9})!)) / (3)!) + (3)! \right) \right) \\
 33923 &:= \left(F((3)!) + \left(C(F(2^{\sqrt{9}}), F((3)!) / (3)!) \right) \right) \\
 33992 &:= \left(F(\left((F(2) + \sqrt{9}) \right)!) - (C((F(9) / F(3)), (3)!) \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$34092 := \left((2 \times F(F(\sqrt{9}!)) + (0)!) \right) - C(F(F(F(4)!)), 3)$$

$$34292 := \left((-F(2)) - F(\sqrt{9}!) \right) + C((-2) + (4)!, (3)!))$$

$$34741 := F((-1) + (4)!) + \left(C(F(7), \sqrt{4})^{F(3)} \right)$$

$$34792 := 2^{F(\sqrt{9})+F(7)} + C(4!, 3)$$

$$35931 := \left(C(13, \sqrt{9}!) - 5 \right) \times F(F(3)!))$$

$$35951 := \left(-1 - C((-5) + F(F(\sqrt{9}!))), 5 \right) - F((3)!))$$

$$37923 := - \left(C(F(F(3)!), 2) + \sqrt{9^7} \right) - F((3)!))$$

$$37962 := \left(C(F(F(2) + (6))), F(\sqrt{9}!) \right) + ((7)!) \times (3)!$$

$$37982 := \left((-2) + C(F(8), F(\sqrt{9})) \times F(F(7)) \right) - F(F(F(3)!)))$$

$$38492 := - \left(C(2 \times F(\sqrt{9}!), 4) + (-((8)!) + F((3)!) \right)$$

$$38823 := C(F(F(3)!), \sqrt{2 \times 8}) + F(F(8)) \times 3$$

$$38982 := \left(-2 - C(F(8), \sqrt{9}) - (8)! \right) + (3)!$$

$$39032 := \left(-F(2) - C(F((3)! + (0)!), F(\sqrt{9}!)) \right) - F((3)!))$$

$$39033 := \left(F((3)!) - C(F((3)! + (0)!), \sqrt{9} + F(3)) \right)$$

$$39871 := \left(-1 + ((7)! - C(8, \sqrt{9})) \times F((3)!) \right)$$

$$39942 := \left((2 \times 4)! - C(F(9) - \sqrt{9}!, F(3)) \right)$$

$$40043 := \left(F((3)!) - C((4)!, ((0)! + (0)!)) + F(\sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$40491 := C(19, \sqrt{4}) + F((F(04)!)!)$$

$$40661 := \sqrt{1 + C(F(F(6)), F(6) - 0!)} + F(F(4)!)!$$

$$40692 := \left(2 \times (-\sqrt{9}) + C(F(F(6)), ((0)! + (4)!) \right)$$

$$40923 := \left(F(C((3)!, 2)) + F(\sqrt{9}!) \right) - ((0)! + (F(4)!))$$

$$41343 := \left(C(3!, \sqrt{4}) - ((3)! + 1) \right) + F((4)!))$$

$$42492 := \left((-2) \times \sqrt{9}! \right) + C((4)!, (F(2) + (4)!))$$

$$42941 := C(-1 + F(F(F(4)!)), \sqrt{9}!) + F((-2) + F(F(F(4)!))))$$

$$42942 := \left(-2 + (F(F(F(F(4)!))) - C(F(F(\sqrt{9}!)), 2)) \times 4 \right)$$

$$42961 := \left((-1 + C(F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9}!)))^2 \right) - ((F(4)!)!)$$

$$43891 := (F(19) + (8)!) - F(C(3!, \sqrt{4}))$$

$$44103 := \left(C(F(F(3)!), ((0)! + 1)) \sqrt{4} \right) + F(4)$$

$$44352 := C(\sqrt{F(2) + 5!}, 3!) \times 4! \times 4$$

$$45442 := -2 + F(4!) - C(\sqrt{4! + 5!}, F(4)!))$$

$$45443 := -F(F(3)) + F(4!) - C(\sqrt{4! + 5!}, F(4)!))$$

$$45911 := - \left(C(11, \sqrt{9}!) - 5 \right) - F((4)!))$$

$$45913 := \left(F(((3+1)!) - C(\sqrt{9} \times 5), F(4)) \right)$$

$$45962 := - \left(C(F(F(2) + (6)), \sqrt{9}) + (5)! \right) - F((4)!))$$

$$46092 := - \left(C((F(2) + \sqrt{9})!, ((0)! + F(F(6)))) \right) - F((4)!))$$

$$46313 := \left(F(((3+1)!) - C(3 + F(6), \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$46932 := C(F(2) + 3!, F(\sqrt{9})) + 6^{F(4)!}$$

$$47292 := C(2 \times \sqrt{9}!, \sqrt{2+7}!) + F(4!)$$

$$47443 := \left(((3)! / \sqrt{4}) + F((4)!) \right) + C(F(7), 4)$$

$$47542 := \left(C(24, 5) + (7)! - \sqrt{4} \right)$$

$$47661 := \left(F(\sqrt{16}!) + 6 \right) + C(F(7), F((F(4)!)!)))$$

$$47933 := C(F(F(3)!), 3) + \left(F(\sqrt{9}) + F(F(7)) + F((4)!) \right)$$

$$47971 := F(17) + \sqrt{C(9, 7)} + F(4!)$$

$$48391 := \left(-1 + C(\sqrt{9} \times F((3)!), F(8)) + F((4)!) \right)$$

$$48932 := \left((2 \times (3)!) \times F(9) - C(8, \sqrt{4}) \right)$$

$$49223 := \left(-(((3)! + F(2))! + F(2)) + C(F(F(\sqrt{9}!)), (F(4)!)! \right)$$

$$49333 := \left(C(3^3, (3)!) / \sqrt{9}! \right) - \sqrt{4}$$

$$49392 := \left(2 \times (C(9, 3)^{\sqrt{9}}) / (4)! \right)$$

$$49631 := \left(F(1 + F(F(3)!)) \right) - C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) \times (-4)!$$

$$49942 := \left(-2 + C(F(F(F(4)!)), \sqrt{9}!) - (\sqrt{9}!) \times ((F(4)!)! \right)$$

$$53481 := \left(C(1 + F(8), \sqrt{4})^{F(3)} \right) + (5)!$$

$$53992 := \left((F(2) - C(\sqrt{9}!, \sqrt{9})) \times (-F((3)!) \right) - (5)!$$

$$54382 := \left(C((F(2) \times F(8)), (3)!) - \sqrt{4} \right) + (5)!$$

$$54641 := F(14) + C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{4+5}!)$$

$$54961 := C(1 + F(F(6)), F(\sqrt{9})) - (F(F(F(F(4)!))) \times (-5)!$$

$$54982 := \left(-2 + C(F(8), \sqrt{9}!) \right) + ((F(4)!) \times (5)!))$$

$$55392 := \left(F(2 \times F(\sqrt{9}!)) \times C(F(3)!, 5) \right) + (5)!$$

$$58692 := \left(2 \times (F(\sqrt{9}!) - F(F(6))) \right) - C(8, 5)$$

$$59913 := \left(3 \times (-((1-9)!) - C(F(F(\sqrt{9}!)), 5) \right)$$

$$62592 := \left(2 \times C(F(F(\sqrt{9}!)), 5) + (F(2) + F(F(F(6)))) \right)$$

$$62991 := \left(C((-1) + F(F(\sqrt{9}!))), F(\sqrt{9}!) / 2 \right) + 6$$

$$63972 := \left((2 - C(F(7), \sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(3)!)) \right) \times 6$$

$$64923 := - \left(F(C((3)!, 2)) + \sqrt{9} - (4^{F(6)}) \right)$$

$$66933 := \left(-3 + (C(F(F(3)!), F(\sqrt{9})) + F(F(F(6)))) \times 6 \right)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 66942 &:= \left((F(2) + (C(F(F((F(4)!)), F(\sqrt{9}))) + F(F(F(6)))) \right) \times 6) \\
 67391 &:= (-1) + \left(((\sqrt{9})! \times F(F(F(3)!))) + C(F(7), 6) \right) \\
 69391 &:= (F(19) + (C(F(F(3)!), (\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F(6)))) \\
 73433 &:= \left((F(C(3!), F(3))) \times ((\sqrt{4} + 3)!) + F(F(7)) \right) \\
 73962 &:= \left((-2) \times C(F(F(6)), \sqrt{9}) - (F(F(F(3)!)) \times (-7)) \right) \\
 73972 &:= (C(2 \times F(7), F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) + (F(3)^{F(7)})) \\
 74691 &:= (C((1 + F(F((\sqrt{9})!))), 6) + ((F(4)! \times F(7))) \\
 77952 &:= (2^5) \times \left(((\sqrt{9})!)! + C(F(7), 7) \right) \\
 78192 &:= (F(((F(2) + \sqrt{9})!)) + (C(18, 7))) \\
 79313 &:= (F((3)!))! + (C((-1) + F(F(3)!), (\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(7))) \\
 79323 &:= \left(((F(3)!))! \times 2 - (C(F(F(3)!), \sqrt{9}) - F(7)) \right) \\
 79422 &:= \left((C(((2+2)!), 4) + ((\sqrt{9})!)! \right) \times 7) \\
 79602 &:= C(20, F(6)) - F((\sqrt{9+7})!) \\
 79661 &:= \left((C((1 + F(F(6))), 6) + F((\sqrt{9})!)) + ((7)!) \right) \\
 79922 &:= 2 + 2 \times (F((\sqrt{9})!)! - (\sqrt{C(9, 7)}))! \\
 79923 &:= (F(3)!))! \times 2 + \sqrt{9} - (\sqrt{C(9, 7)}!) \\
 82921 &:= (C(F(F((1+2)!)), (\sqrt{9})!) + (F((2 + F(8)))) \\
 84423 &:= \left((C(F(F(3)!), 2)^{\sqrt{4}} + ((F(4) + (8)!)) \right) \\
 84542 &:= \left(2 \times (C((4!), 5) - F(F(-((F(\sqrt{4}) - 8)))) \right) \\
 84692 &:= \left(2 \times ((F(\sqrt{9}) + (F(6)!)) + (C((4!), F(8)))) \right) \\
 84971 &:= (-1) - \left((C(F(7), (\sqrt{9})!) - F((4)!)) - (8)! \right) \\
 84972 &:= (-F(2)) \times \left((C(F(7), (\sqrt{9})!) - F((4)!)) - (8)! \right) \\
 87992 &:= \left(((-2) - F(C((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}))) \times (-F(7)) + (F(8)) \right) \\
 88492 &:= (C((2 \times (\sqrt{9})!), (F(4)!)) + (F(F(8)) \times 8))
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 89232 &:= \left((-2) + C(F(F((3)!), 2)) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \right) \times 8) \\
 90592 &:= (-2) - (C(9, 5) \times ((0)! - ((\sqrt{9})!))) \\
 92381 &:= \sqrt{1+8} + C(F(F(3!)) - 2, 9) \\
 92382 &:= \sqrt{2 \times 8} + C(F(F(3!)) - 2, 9) \\
 92391 &:= (F((1 + (\sqrt{9})!)) + C((F(F(3!)) - 2), 9)) \\
 92631 &:= (1 + (F(F(3!)) \times C(F(F(6)), 2))) \times F(F((\sqrt{9})!)) \\
 93332 &:= (2 \times ((3)!)^3) + C(3!, \sqrt{9}) \\
 93723 &:= (F(((F(3) + 2)!)) - (-7) \times F(C(3!, \sqrt{9}))) \\
 93862 &:= \left((-2) + (F(6)!)) + (C(F(8), (3)!)) - ((\sqrt{9})!)! \right) \\
 94043 &:= \left((-((F(3)!))! - F(F(((F(4)! + (0)!))) + (C(4!, (\sqrt{9})!))) \right) \\
 94232 &:= \left(2 \times (C(F(3!), 2) + F((4)!)) + ((\sqrt{9})!)! \right) \\
 94333 &:= (F(C(3!), 3) + (F(3)! \times F((4! - \sqrt{9})))) \\
 94582 &:= (-2) + (8)! + C(F((5 + F(4))), (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 96423 &:= (C((F(F(3!)) + 2), 4) + (F(F(F(6))) \times F((\sqrt{9})!))) \\
 97342 &:= (-2) + \left(((C(4, 3))! \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})} \right) \\
 97343 &:= - \left((F(F(3)) - ((C(4, 3))! \times F(7))^{F(\sqrt{9})}) \right) \\
 99123 &:= (F(C(3!), 2) - 1) - (F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!))) \times (-9)) \\
 99133 &:= (F(C(3!), F(3)) + ((1 + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) \times 9)) \\
 99233 &:= \left((F(F(3!)) \times C(3!, 2))^{F(\sqrt{9})} + F((\sqrt{9})!) \right) \\
 99343 &:= \left((((3)!))! \times C((4!), F(3)) - F(9) \right) / F(\sqrt{9}) \\
 99382 &:= \left((-2) + C(F(8) + (3!), \sqrt{9}) \right) \times F(9) \\
 99412 &:= \left(2 \times (C((-1) + F(F((F(4)!))), (\sqrt{9})!) + F(F(F((\sqrt{9})!)))) \right) \\
 99433 &:= (F(C(3!), 3) + (F((4)! - F(9)) \times F(\sqrt{9})))
 \end{aligned}$$

4 Summary: Selfie Numbers

The author studied different ways of expressing numbers in such a way that both sides of the expressions are with same digits. One side is with number, and another side is an expression formed by same digits with some operations. These types of numbers we call **selfie numbers**. Some times they are called as **wild narcissistic numbers** [2, 3, 4]. Friedmann [6, 7, 8, 9] also made some study in this direction. These numbers are represented by their own digits by use of certain operations. Following subsections give different ways of writing **selfie numbers**. Examples of selfie numbers are with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, **Quadratic numbers**, **Cubic numbers**, etc. In two variables, we obtained selfie numbers with **binomial coefficients**, **S-gonal numbers**, **centered polygonal numbers**, etc. The other way of writing **selfie numbers** is by use of **permutable powers**, where **bases** and **exponents** are of same digits. See the subsection below with some examples.

4.1 Permutable Powers

Below are some examples of **permutable power selfie numbers**. By **permutable powers**, we understand that bases and exponents are of same digits with different permutations. Some times we may call them as **flexible power selfie numbers**.

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{1} &:= 1^1 & \mathbf{3529} &:= -3^3 + 5^5 + 2^9 - 9^2 \\
 \mathbf{23} &:= -2^2 + 3^3 & \mathbf{4316} &:= 4^6 + 3^1 + 1^4 + 6^3 \\
 \mathbf{1239} &:= 1^2 + 2^9 - 3^1 + 9^3 & \mathbf{4355} &:= 4^5 + 3^4 + 5^3 + 5^5 \\
 \mathbf{1364} &:= 1^6 + 3^1 + 6^4 + 4^3 & \mathbf{39339} &:= -3^3 + 9^3 + 3^9 + 3^9 - 9^3 \\
 \mathbf{1654} &:= -1^6 + 6^1 + 5^4 + 4^5 & \mathbf{46350} &:= -4^3 + 6^6 - 3^5 + 5^0 + 0^4 \\
 \mathbf{1837} &:= 1^8 - 8^1 + 3^7 - 7^3 & \mathbf{46360} &:= 4^0 + 6^6 - 3^4 - 6^3 + 0^6 \\
 \mathbf{2137} &:= -2^1 + 1^3 + 3^7 - 7^2 & \mathbf{397612} &:= 3^2 + 9^1 + 7^6 + 6^7 + 1^9 + 2^3 \\
 \mathbf{2173} &:= -2^3 + 1^2 - 7^1 + 3^7 & \mathbf{423858} &:= 4^3 + 2^8 + 3^4 + 8^2 + 5^8 + 8^5 \\
 \mathbf{2537} &:= 2^5 - 5^2 + 3^7 + 7^3 & \mathbf{637395} &:= 6^5 + 3^3 + 7^3 + 3^9 + 9^6 + 5^7 \\
 \mathbf{3125} &:= -3^2 + 1^1 + 2^3 + 5^5 & \mathbf{758014} &:= 7^7 + 5^1 + 8^0 + 0^5 + 1^4 - 4^8 \\
 \mathbf{3275} &:= -3^3 + 2^7 + 7^2 + 5^5 & \mathbf{778530} &:= 7^7 + 7^3 + 8^5 - 5^7 + 3^0 + 0^8 \\
 \mathbf{3435} &:= 3^3 + 4^4 + 3^3 + 5^5 & \mathbf{804637} &:= 8^0 + 0^4 - 4^8 + 6^6 - 3^3 + 7^7
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{15647982} &:= 1^5 - 5^9 + 6^2 + 4^4 + 7^7 - 9^1 + 8^8 + 2^6 \\
 \mathbf{17946238} &:= 1^6 + 7^8 + 9^4 + 4^2 + 6^9 + 2^3 + 3^1 + 8^7 \\
 \mathbf{57396108} &:= -5^6 + 7^9 + 3^5 + 9^3 + 6^7 + 1^1 + 0^0 + 8^8 \\
 \mathbf{134287690} &:= 1^2 + 3^8 + 4^7 + 2^4 + 8^9 + 7^3 + 6^6 + 9^0 + 0^1 \\
 \mathbf{387945261} &:= 3^3 + 8^2 + 7^6 + 9^9 + 4^7 + 5^8 + 2^4 + 6^1 + 1^5 \\
 \mathbf{392876054} &:= 3^0 + 9^9 - 2^2 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 + 0^3 - 5^4 + 4^6 \\
 \mathbf{392876540} &:= -3^0 + 9^9 - 2^4 - 8^5 + 7^8 - 6^7 - 5^3 + 4^6 + 0^2
 \end{aligned}$$

More details can be seen in author's work [25].

4.2 Basic Operations

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** by use of **basic operations**. See below some examples in both orders:

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{13825} &:= 1 + (3 \times 8)^{-2+5} &= ((5-2) \times 8)^3 + 1 \\
 \mathbf{14641} &:= (1+4+6)^4 \times 1 &= (1+4+6)^4 \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{15552} &:= (1^5+5)^5 \times 2 &= 2 \times (6^5+5) \times 1 \\
 \mathbf{16377} &:= (1+6-3)^7 - 7 &= -7 + (7-3)^{6+1} \\
 \mathbf{23328} &:= (2 \times 3^3)^2 \times 8 &= (8-2)^{3+3}/2 \\
 \mathbf{116565} &:= (-1+16) \times (-5+6^5) = 5 \times (3 \times 6^{6-1} - 1) \\
 \mathbf{131072} &:= (1+3)^{1+0+7} \times 2 &= 2^{(7+0-1) \times 3-1} \\
 \mathbf{147419} &:= -1 + (4^7 - 4) \times 1 \times 9 &= 9 \times (1 \times 4^7 - 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{147429} &:= 1 + (4^7 - 4/2) \times 9 &= 9 \times (2 + 4^7 - 4 - 1)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{147491} &:= 1 \times (4^7 + 4) \times 9 - 1 = 1 \times 9 \times (4^7 + 4) - 1 \\ \mathbf{156252} &:= 1 \times 5^6 \times 2 \times 5 + 2 = 2 \times (5^{2 \times 6 - 5} + 1) \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and in reverse order of digits:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{656250} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 0 = 0 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656251} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 1 = 1 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656252} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 2 = 2 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656253} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 3 = 3 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656254} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 4 = 4 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656255} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 5 = 5 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656256} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 6 = 6 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656257} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 7 = 7 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656258} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 8 = 8 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6 \\ \mathbf{656259} &:= 6 \times 5^6 \times (2 + 5) + 9 = 9 + (5 + 2) \times 6 \times 5^6. \end{aligned}$$

This is the only work done by author up to 7-digits numbers. For details [34].

4.3 Factorial

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **factorial**. See below some examples:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{145} &:= 1! + 4! + 5! & \mathbf{361469} &:= 3! - 6! - 1! + 4! - 6! + 9! \\ \mathbf{733} &:= 7 + 3!! + 3! & \mathbf{363239} &:= 36 + 323 + 9! \\ \mathbf{1463} &:= -1! + 4! + 6! + 3!! & \mathbf{363269} &:= 363 + 26 + 9! \\ \mathbf{5177} &:= 5! + 17 + 7! & \mathbf{364292} &:= 3!! + 6! - 4! - 2! + 9! - 2! \\ \mathbf{10077} &:= -1! - 0! - 0! + 7! + 7! & \mathbf{397584} &:= -3!! + 9! - 7! + 5! + 8! + 4! \\ \mathbf{40585} &:= 4! + 0! + 5! + 8! + 5! & \mathbf{398173} &:= 3! + 9! + 8! + 1! - 7! + 3! \\ \mathbf{80518} &:= 8! - 0! - 5! - 1! + 8! & \mathbf{403199} &:= 40319 + 9! \\ \mathbf{317489} &:= -3! - 1! - 7! - 4! - 8! + 9! & \mathbf{408937} &:= -4! + 0! + 8! + 9! + 3!! + 7! \\ \mathbf{352797} &:= -3! + 5 - 2! - 7! + 9! - 7! & \mathbf{715799} &:= -7! - 1! + 5! - 7! + 9! + 9! \\ \mathbf{357592} &:= -3! - 5! - 7! - 5! + 9! - 2! & \mathbf{720599} &:= -7! - 2! + 0! - 5! + 9! + 9! \\ \mathbf{357941} &:= 3! + 5! - 7! + 9! - 4! - 1! \end{aligned}$$

The above numbers are in **digit's order** and are only with positive and negative coefficients. Below are consecutive sequence values in both ways:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{35280} &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 0 = 0 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ \mathbf{35281} &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 1 = 1 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ \mathbf{35282} &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 2 = 2 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ \mathbf{35283} &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 3 = 3 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ \mathbf{35284} &:= -3!! \times (5 + 2) + 8! + 4 = 4 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 35285 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 5 = 5 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35286 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 6 = 6 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35287 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 7 = 7 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35288 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 8 = 8 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \\ 35289 &:= -3!! \times (5+2) + 8! + 9 = 9 + 8! - (2 \times 5 - 3)! \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [31, 32].

4.4 Square-Root

This subsection brings **selfie numbers** with use of **square-root**. See below some examples in both orders, i.e., in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$\begin{aligned} 1764 &:= 1 \times (7 \times 6)^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 2378 &:= -23 + \sqrt{7^8} \\ 19454 &:= 19 \times 4^5 - \sqrt{4} \\ 19459 &:= 19 \times 4^5 + \sqrt{9} \\ 19684 &:= 1 + \sqrt{9\sqrt{\sqrt{6^8}/4}} \\ 839793 &:= (-8 + (-3+9)^7 + \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \\ 839795 &:= -8 + (-3+9)^7 \times \sqrt{9} - 5 \\ 839804 &:= (-8 + (3-9)^8 + 0) / \sqrt{4} \\ 839816 &:= (8 + (3-9)^8) / \sqrt{\sqrt{16}} \\ 995544 &:= ((9 + \sqrt{9})^5 + 54) \times 4 \\ 999916 &:= -9 \times 9 - \sqrt{9} + (9+1)^6 \\ 999976 &:= -\sqrt{9} \times 9 + \sqrt{9} + (\sqrt{9}+7)^6 \\ 64 &:= \sqrt{4^6} \end{aligned}$	$\begin{aligned} 1024 &:= \sqrt{\sqrt{4^{20}} \times 1} \\ 1296 &:= 6^{\sqrt{9+2-1}} \\ 2189 &:= \sqrt{9^{8-1}} + 2 \\ 3867 &:= (-7 + \sqrt{6^8}) \times 3 \\ 9375 &:= \sqrt{5^{7+3} \times 9} \\ 12289 &:= \sqrt{9} \times 8^{2 \times 2} + 1 \\ 19693 &:= 3^9 + 6 + \sqrt{9} + 1 \\ 42436 &:= (6 \times 34 + 2)^{\sqrt{4}} \\ 59051 &:= \sqrt{-1+5} + 0 + 9^5 \\ 999901 &:= (10^{9-\sqrt{9}}) - 99 \\ 999991 &:= (1^9 + 99)^{\sqrt{9}} - 9 \end{aligned}$
--	---

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details refer author's work [16, 18].

4.5 Factorial and Square-Root

Below are some examples with **factorial** and **square-root** written in both ways, i.e., in digit's order and its reverse

$$\begin{aligned} 936 &:= (\sqrt{9})!^3 + 6! &= 6! + (3!)^{\sqrt{9}} \\ 1296 &:= \sqrt{(1+2)!^9} / 6 &= 6^{(\sqrt{9}+2-1)} \\ 2896 &:= 2 \times (8 + (\sqrt{9})!! + 6!) &= (6! + (\sqrt{9})!! + 8) \times 2 \\ 331779 &:= 3 + (31-7)^{\sqrt{7+9}} &= \sqrt{9} + (7 \times 7 - 1)^3 \times 3 \\ 342995 &:= (3^4 - 2 - 9)^{\sqrt{9}} - 5 &= -5 + (-9 + 9^2 - \sqrt{4})^3 \\ 759375 &:= (-7 + 59 - 37)^5 &= (5 + 7 + 3)^{\sqrt{9-5+7}} \end{aligned}$$

$$759381 := 7 + (5 \times \sqrt{9})^{-3+8} - 1 = -1 + (8 \times 3 - 9)^5 + 7.$$

$$5040 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 0 = 0 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5041 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 1 = 1 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5042 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 2 = 2 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5043 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 3 = 3 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5044 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 4 = 4 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5045 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 5 = 5 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5046 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 6 = 6 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5047 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 7 = 7 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5048 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 8 = 8 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

$$5049 := (5 + 0 + \sqrt{4})! + 9 = 9 + (\sqrt{4} + 0 + 5)!$$

The following examples are in **digit's order** and its **reverse** separately:

$$120 := ((1 + 2)! - 0)!$$

$$127 := -1 + 2^7$$

$$1673 := -1 - 6 + 7!/3$$

$$1679 := 1 + (-6 + 7)/\sqrt{9}$$

$$1680 := (1 + 6)!/\sqrt{8 + 0!}$$

$$38970 := -3!! + 8! - 9 \times 70$$

$$38986 := -3 + 8! - \sqrt{(\sqrt{9} + 8)^6}$$

$$40310 := (\sqrt{4^{03}})! - 10$$

$$90894 := -(\sqrt{9})! + ((0! + 8)! + (\sqrt{9})!!)/4$$

$$91560 := ((\sqrt{9})! + 1)! + 5! \times (6! + 0!)$$

$$25 := 5^2$$

$$64 := \sqrt{4^6}$$

$$289 := (9 + 8)^2$$

$$3894 := (\sqrt{4} + \sqrt{(\sqrt{9})!^8}) \times 3$$

$$4957 := 7! - 59 - 4!$$

$$6992 := 2^9 + 9 \times 6!$$

$$26493 := (2 + 6)! - 4!^{\sqrt{9}} - 3$$

$$30792 := 3! \times ((0 + 7)! + 92)$$

$$54476 := (5! + 4!^4 - 7!)/6$$

$$75989 := \sqrt{9} \times (8 - (\sqrt{9})!!) + 5^7$$

First column numbers are in **digit's order** and second columns are in **reverse order of digits**. For details refer author's work [16, 18, 21].

4.6 Fibonacci Sequence

Fibonacci sequence numbers are well known in literature. This sequence is defined as

$$F(0) = 0, \quad F(1) = 1, \quad F(n+1) = F(n) + F(n-1), \quad n \geq 1.$$

Below are examples of **selfie numbers** by use of **Fibonacci sequence values**. This we have done in different situations, such as using $F(\cdot)$ and $F(F(\cdot))$ in separate works. See below examples:

$$143 := -1 + F(4 \times 3) = F(3 \times 4) - 1$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{986} &:= F(9) \times (F(8) + F(6)) &= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 \mathbf{1178} &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) &= F(8) + F(7) \times F(11) \\
 \mathbf{2585} &:= F(2) + F(5 + 8 + 5) &= F(5 + 8 + 5) + F(2) \\
 \mathbf{12819} &:= 1 + F(2 \times (8 - 1)) \times F(9) &= F(9) \times F((-1 + 8) \times 2) + 1 \\
 \mathbf{24297} &:= F(2 \times 4) \times F(2 + 9) \times F(7) &= F(7) \times F(9 + 2) \times F(4 \times 2) \\
 \mathbf{39394} &:= -3 + 93 + F(9)^{F(4)} &= (-4 + F(9)) \times 3 + F(9)^3 \\
 \mathbf{74997} &:= -7 \times 4 + F(9 + 9 + 7) &= F(7 + 9 + 9) - 4 \times 7 \\
 \mathbf{87937} &:= -8 + F(7) \times F(9 \times 3 - 7) &= F(7) \times F(3 \times 9 - 7) - 8 \\
 \mathbf{98703} &:= 9 \times (F(8) + F(7 \times 03)) &= (F(3 \times 07) + F(8)) \times 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{34} &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & \mathbf{36} &:= 6^{F(3)} \\
 \mathbf{233} &:= F(F(-2 + 3 \times 3)) & \mathbf{143} &:= F(3 \times 4) - 1 \\
 \mathbf{630} &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & \mathbf{231} &:= F(13) - 2 \\
 \mathbf{1178} &:= F(11) \times F(7) + F(8) & \mathbf{377} &:= F(-7 + 7 \times 3) \\
 \mathbf{2079} &:= (-2 + F(F(07))) \times 9 & \mathbf{986} &:= (F(6) + F(8)) \times F(9) \\
 \mathbf{4864} &:= F(F(4))^8 \times (F(F(6)) - F(F(4))) & \mathbf{1165} &:= 5 \times F(F(6 \times 1 + 1)) \\
 \mathbf{8759} &:= -F(9 - 5)^7 + F(F(8)) & \mathbf{1596} &:= F(F(6) + 9) - F(F(F(5 - 1))) \\
 \mathbf{8849} &:= -9 \times F(F(F(F(F(4)))) - 8) + F(F(8)) & \mathbf{2592} &:= F(2 \times 9) + F(5 + F(2)) \\
 \mathbf{9349} &:= -F(F(9)/F(F(4))) + F(F(F(-3 + 9))) & \mathbf{9756} &:= F(F(F(6))) - 5 \times 7 \times F(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{834660} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 0 = 0 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834661} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 1 = 1 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834662} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 2 = 2 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834663} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 3 = 3 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834664} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 4 = 4 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834665} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 5 = 5 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834666} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 6 = 6 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834667} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 7 = 7 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834668} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 8 = 8 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)) \\
 \mathbf{834669} &:= (F(8 \times 3) \times F(4) + 6) \times 6 + 9 = 9 + 6 \times (6 + F(4) \times F(3 \times 8)).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{21960} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 0 = 0 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21961} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 1 = 1 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21962} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 2 = 2 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21963} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 3 = 3 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21964} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 4 = 4 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21965} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 5 = 5 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21966} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 6 = 6 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2 \\
 \mathbf{21967} &:= 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 7 = 7 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\mathbf{21968} := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 8 = 8 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2$$

$$\mathbf{21969} := 2 \times 1 \times (F(9) + F(F(F(6)))) + 9 = 9 + (F(F(F(6))) + F(9)) \times 1 \times 2.$$

First three blocks are in both ways. In the last block the first column values are in **digit's order** and the second columns values are in **reverse order of digits**. For more details see author's [28, 29].

4.7 Triangular Numbers

Triangular numbers are very much famous in the literature of mathematics. The general formula to write these numbers is given by

$$T(n) = 1 + 2 + 3 + \dots = \frac{n+1}{2} = C(n+1, 2).$$

The examples given in above subsections are with **factorial, square-root, Fibonacci sequence** numbers, etc. Still, one can have similar kind of results using **Triangular numbers**. See below some examples:

$$\mathbf{1069} := T(10) - T(6) + T(T(9))$$

$$\mathbf{1081} := T(1 + T(08 + 1))$$

$$\mathbf{2887} := T(T(T(T(2)))) + T(T(8) + T(8)) + T(7)$$

$$\mathbf{4965} := T(-4 + 9) + T(-T(6) + T(T(5)))$$

$$\mathbf{4999} := 49 + T(99)$$

$$\mathbf{99545} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 5$$

$$\mathbf{99546} := T(9) + T(9) \times T(T(T(5) - 4)) + 6.$$

$$\mathbf{874} := T(T(T(4))) - T(T(7) + 8)$$

$$\mathbf{0105} := 50 + T(10)$$

$$\mathbf{1155} := -T(T(5)) + T(51 - 1)$$

$$\mathbf{1224} := T(T(T(4)) - T(T(2))) - 2 + 1$$

$$\mathbf{2418} := T(81) - T(42)$$

$$\mathbf{99632} := 2 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9)$$

$$\mathbf{99633} := 3 + (3 + T(T(6) + T(9))) \times T(9).$$

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\mathbf{2210} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 0 = 0 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2211} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 1 = 1 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2212} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 2 = 2 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2213} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 3 = 3 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2214} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 4 = 4 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2215} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 5 = 5 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2216} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 6 = 6 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2217} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 7 = 7 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2218} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 8 = 8 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2))))$$

$$\mathbf{2219} := T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))) - 1 + 9 = 9 - 1 + T(T(T(T(T(T(2))))/T(T(T(2)))).$$

For more details see author's work [26].

4.8 Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Numbers

This subsection brings numbers where we can write them in terms of both Fibonacci Sequence and Triangular Numbers at the same time. See below some examples,

$$\begin{aligned}
 \mathbf{34} &:= F(3 \times F(4)) & \mathbf{34} &:= F(F(4)^{F(3)}) \\
 &:= -T(T(3)) + T(T(4)) & &:= T(T(4)) - T(T(3)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{63} &:= F(F(6)) \times 3 & \mathbf{63} &:= 3 \times F(F(6)) \\
 &:= T(6) \times 3 & &:= 3 \times T(6) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{630} &:= F(F(6)) \times 30 & \mathbf{168} &:= F(8) \times F(6) \times 1 \\
 &:= T(6) \times 30 & &:= 8 \times T(6 \times 1) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{693} &:= F(F(6)) \times (F(9) - F(F(3))) & \mathbf{231} &:= F(13) - 2 \\
 &:= (T(T(6)) \times (9/3)) & &:= T(T(1 \times 3 \times 2)) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1575} &:= F(F(1 + 5)) \times 75 & \mathbf{0376} &:= F(F(F(6)) - 7) - F(F(3 + 0)) \\
 &:= T(1 + 5) \times 75 & &:= T(T(6) + 7) - 30 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{1995} &:= F(-1 + 9) \times 95 & \mathbf{0702} &:= (2 + 0!) \times (F(F(7)) + 0!) \\
 &:= 19 \times T(9 + 5) & &:= 2 \times T(-0! + T(7) - 0!) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{2016} &:= F((2 + 0!)!)/(-1 + F(F(6))) & \mathbf{0748} &:= F(8) + F(4)!! + 7 + 0 \\
 &:= T(T(2) \times T(0 \times 1 + 6)) & &:= T(T(8)) + T(T(4)) + T(7) - 0! \\
 \\
 \mathbf{3584} &:= (F(3) + 5) \times 8^{F(4)} & \mathbf{2796} &:= (F(F(6)) - 9) \times F(F(7) \times F(2)) \\
 &:= -T(T(3)) + 5 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(4))) & &:= T(6) + T((9 + T(7)) \times 2) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{4410} &:= F(F(F(4)!))^{F(F(4))} \times 10 & \mathbf{4182} &:= F(2) + F(F(8) + 1 - F(4)) \\
 &:= T(4! - 4) \times T(T(T(1 + 0!))) & &:= T(T(T(T(2)) + 8 - 1)) - 4 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{9244} &:= F(9)^2 \times F(F(4)!) - 4 & \mathbf{5994} &:= F(4)! \times 9 \times (-9 + 5!) \\
 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 4 & &:= T(4 \times 9) \times T(9)/5 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{9248} &:= F(9)^{-2+4} \times 8 & \mathbf{7896} &:= F(6) \times 987 \\
 &:= (9 - T(2)) \times T(T(T(4))) + 9 & &:= T(-6 + T(9) + 8) \times 7 \\
 \\
 \mathbf{9586} &:= -F(9) \times 5 \times 8 + F(F(F(6))) & \mathbf{9248} &:= F(8)^{F(4)} - F(-2 + 9) \\
 &:= T(9) \times T(T(5)) + T(T(-8 + T(6))) & &:= 8 + T(T(T(4))) \times (-T(2) + 9) \\
 \\
 \mathbf{9837} &:= 98^{F(3)} + F(F(7)) & \mathbf{9586} &:= F(F(F(6))) - 8 \times 5 \times F(9) \\
 &:= 9 \times (T(T(8)) + T(T(3)) + T(T(7))) & &:= T(T(T(6) - 8)) + T(T(5)) \times T(9)
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 7560 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 0 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 0 \\
 7561 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 1 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 1 \\
 7562 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 2 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 2 \\
 7563 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 3 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 3 \\
 7564 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 4 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 4 \\
 7565 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 5 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 5 \\
 7566 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 6 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 6 \\
 7567 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 7 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 7 \\
 7568 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 8 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 8 \\
 7569 &:= 7! + 5! \times F(F(6)) + 9 = 7! + 5! \times T(6) + 9
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 6480 &:= 0 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 0 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6481 &:= 1 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 1 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6482 &:= 2 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 2 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6483 &:= 3 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 3 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6484 &:= 4 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 4 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6485 &:= 5 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 5 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6486 &:= 6 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 6 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6487 &:= 7 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 7 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6488 &:= 8 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 8 + T(8)/4 \times 6! \\
 6489 &:= 9 + (8 + F(F(F(4)))) \times 6! = 9 + T(8)/4 \times 6!
 \end{aligned}$$

In both the cases, the first column is on digit's order and second column is in reverse order of digits. For more details refer author's work [29].

4.9 Binomial Coefficients

Binomial coefficients are well known in literature. They are given by

$$C(m, r) = \frac{m!}{r! \times (m-r)!}, \quad m \geq r \geq 0, \quad m, r \in \mathbb{N}.$$

In above subsections, we gave examples of selfie numbers with **Fibonacci sequence**, **Triangular numbers**, etc. Still, one can have similar kind results using **binomial coefficients**. See below some examples written in **both ways, digit's order and reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned}
 6435 &:= C(C(6, 4), 3+5) = C(5 \times 3, \sqrt{4}+6) \\
 15504 &:= C(15+5, 0!+4) = C(4 \times 05, 5 \times 1) \\
 42504 &:= C(4!, \sqrt{2 \times 50/4}) = C(4!, -05+24) \\
 54264 &:= C(5+4^2, C(6, 4)) = C(4!-6/2, (\sqrt{4}+5)!) \\
 74613 &:= C(7 \times 4-6, 1 \times 3!) = C(3!+16, (-4+7)!).
 \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 12650 &:= C(-1+26, 5-0!) & 28 &:= C(8, 2) \\
 12870 &:= C(1 \times 2 \times 8, 7+0!) & 792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7) \\
 14950 &:= C(-1+4!+\sqrt{9}, 5-0!) & 924 &:= C(4!/2, (\sqrt{9})!) \\
 18564 &:= C(18, (5-6+4)!) & 2024 &:= C(4!, 2+(0 \times 2)!) \\
 19448 &:= C(19-\sqrt{4}, \sqrt{4}+8) & 4845 &:= C(5 \times 4, 8-4) \\
 26334 &:= C(2+C(6, 3), 3+\sqrt{4}) & 00378 &:= C(C(8, \sqrt{7-3}), 0!+0!) \\
 43758 &:= C(4!-3!, 7-5+8) & 00792 &:= C(2 \times (\sqrt{9})!, 7-0!-0!) \\
 53130 &:= C(5^{3-1}, 3!-0!). & 00924 &:= C(4!/2, \sqrt{9} \times (0!+0!)).
 \end{aligned}$$

Consecutive sequential representations:

$$\begin{aligned} 25920 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 0 \\ 25921 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 1 \\ 25922 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 2 \\ 25923 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 3 \\ 25924 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 4 \\ 25925 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 5 \\ 25926 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 6 \\ 25927 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 7 \\ 25928 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 8 \\ 25929 &:= (-2+5)!! \times C(9,2) + 9. \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned} 98280 &:= 0 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98281 &:= 1 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98282 &:= 2 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98283 &:= 3 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98284 &:= 4 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98285 &:= 5 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98286 &:= 6 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98287 &:= 7 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98288 &:= 8 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}) \\ 98289 &:= 9 + C(C(8,2), 8 - \sqrt{9}). \end{aligned}$$

For more details refer author's work [27].

4.10 S-gonal numbers

The formula for **S-gonal numbers** is given by

$$P(n, s) := \frac{n(n-1)(s-2)}{2} + n, \quad s > 2.$$

This subsection brings some examples of selfie numbrs using **S-gonal numbers**. These examples are in **digit's order** and in **reverse order of digits**:

$$\begin{aligned} 4992 &:= P(4!, 9 + 9 + 2) & 8967 &:= 7 \times P(P(6, \sqrt{9}), 8) \\ 7744 &:= (P(7, 7) - 4!)^{\sqrt{4}} & 9504 &:= 4! \times P(\sqrt{0! + 5!}, 9) \\ 7896 &:= 7 \times P(8 \times \sqrt{9}, 6) & 9744 &:= 4! \times P(4 \times 7, \sqrt{9}) \\ 65485 &:= -P(6, 5) + \sqrt{4} \times 8^5 & 49281 &:= 1 \times 8! + P(29, 4!) \\ 65943 &:= P(6, 5) \times ((\sqrt{9})!^4 - 3) & 49548 &:= -8! - P(4!, 5) + 9!/4 \\ 67977 &:= (6 + 7) \times (P(9, 7) + 7!) & 50424 &:= 4! \times P(-2 + 4!, \sqrt{0! + 5!}) \\ 72495 &:= -P(7 + 2, 4) + 9!/5 & 52895 &:= (5 + P(9, 8))^2 - 5 \\ 83544 &:= \sqrt{P(8, 3)} \times (5! - \sqrt{4})^{\sqrt{4}}. & 53995 &:= (5! - P(9, \sqrt{9})) \times 3!! - 5. \end{aligned}$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$\begin{aligned} 86640 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 0 & 86644 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 4 \\ 86641 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 1 & 86645 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 5 \\ 86642 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 2 & 86646 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 6 \\ 86643 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 3 & 86647 &:= P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 7 \end{aligned}$$

$$86648 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 8$$

$$86649 := P(8, 6) \times (6! + \sqrt{4}) + 9.$$

$$5640 := 0 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5641 := 1 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5642 := 2 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5643 := 3 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5644 := 4 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5645 := 5 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5646 := 6 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5647 := 7 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5648 := 8 + P(4!, 6) \times 5$$

$$5649 := 9 + P(4!, 6) \times 5.$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

4.11 Centered Polygonal Numbers

The formula for **centered polygonal numbers** is given by

$$K(n, t) := \frac{tn(n-1)}{2} + 1, \quad t > 2.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **centered polygonal numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$$2883 := K(2 \times 8, 8) \times 3$$

$$2888 := K(2 + 8, 8) \times 8$$

$$3640 := K(3!, 6) \times 40$$

$$14939 := -1 + (K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 3) \times 9$$

$$14959 := (-1 + K(4!, (\sqrt{9})!) + 5) \times 9$$

$$15144 := K(15, (-1 + 4)!) \times 4!$$

$$15347 := (-1 + 5)! \times 3!! - K(4!, 7)$$

$$15399 := K(1 \times 5!/3!, 9) \times 9$$

$$00938 := K(\sqrt{K(8, 3)}, (\sqrt{9})!) \times (0! + 0!)$$

$$01051 := K(15, 0!0)$$

$$01199 := K(9, \sqrt{9}) \times (1 + 10)$$

$$59938 := K(8, 3!) + (\sqrt{9})!! + 9^5$$

$$62424 := 4! \times K(2 + 4!, 2 + 6)$$

$$63384 := 4! + (K(8, 3) + 3) \times 6!$$

$$63744 := 4! \times (K(4!, 7) + 3 + 6!)$$

$$63973 := K(3! + 7, 9) \times K(3!, 6).$$

The consecutive sequential examples are given by

$$99360 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 0 = 0 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99361 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 1 = 1 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99362 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 2 = 2 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99363 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 3 = 3 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99364 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 4 = 4 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99365 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 5 = 5 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99366 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 6 = 6 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99367 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 7 = 7 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99368 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 8 = 8 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}$$

$$99369 := K((\sqrt{9})!, \sqrt{9}) \times 3 \times 6! + 9 = 9 + 6! \times K(3!, \sqrt{9}) \times \sqrt{9}.$$

For more details refer author's work [22].

4.12 Quadratic-Type Selfies

The formula for **quadratic numbers** is given by

$$Q(n) := n^2, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **quadratic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

<p>48 := $-Q(4) + Q(8)$ 81 := $Q(8 + 1)$ 128 := $1 \times 2 \times Q(8)$ 292 := $Q(Q(Q(2))) + 9 \times Q(2)$ 322 := $Q(Q(3) \times 2) - 2$ 1036 := $10^3 + Q(6)$ 1125 := $Q(11 + Q(2)) \times 5$ 1729 := $1 \times 7 \times (Q(Q(Q(2))) - 9)$ 9843 := $(Q(-9 + Q(8)) + Q(Q(4))) \times 3$ 10025 := $100^2 + Q(5)$ 10384 := $(-1 + Q(Q(03))) \times 8 \times Q(4)$ 99378 := $9 \times (Q(93) + Q(Q(7))) - 8$</p>	<p>49 := $Q(-9 + Q(4))$ 89 := $Q(9) + 8$ 224 := $(Q(4) - 2) \times Q(Q(2))$ 275 := $Q(5) \times (7 + Q(2))$ 736 := $Q(Q(6) - Q(3)) + 7$ 0107 := $7 + Q(010)$ 0231 := $-Q(13) + Q(20)$ 1257 := $7 + Q(Q(5)) \times 2 \times 1$ 2239 := $-Q(9) + Q(3 \times Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(2))$ 08136 := $Q(6) + Q(Q(3) + 1 + 80)$ 99712 := $Q(Q(2)) \times 1 \times (Q(79) - 9)$ 37293 := $-3 + (Q(Q(9)) - Q(Q(2)) - Q(Q(7))) \times Q(3)$.</p>
--	---

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

12680 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 0 = 0 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12681 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 1 = 1 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12682 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 2 = 2 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12683 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 3 = 3 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12684 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 4 = 4 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12685 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 5 = 5 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12686 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 6 = 6 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12687 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 7 = 7 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12688 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 8 = 8 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$
12689 := $(Q(1 + Q(Q(2))) + Q(Q(6))) \times 8 + 9 = 9 + 8 \times (Q(Q(6)) + Q(Q(Q(2)) + 1))$

For more details refer author's work [30].

4.13 Cubic-Type Selfies

The formula for **cubic numbers** is given by

$$C(n) := n^3, n > 0, n \in N.$$

Below are some examples of selfie numbers with **cubic-type selfie numbers**. These are in **digit's order** and **inreverse order of digits**:

$125 := 1^2 \times C(5)$	$512 := C(2 + 1 + 5)$
$522 := 5 \times 2 + C(C(2))$	$991 := (C(1 + 9) - 9)$
$991 := -9 + C(9 + 1)$	$0235 := 5 \times (C(3) + 20)$
$1371 := (1 + 3) \times C(7) - 1$	$0263 := C(3) + C(6) + 20$
$1715 := 1 \times C(7) \times 1 \times 5$	$1735 := 5 \times (3 + C(7) + 1)$
$2587 := -C(2) + 5 \times (C(8) + 7)$	$5974 := -4 + 7 \times (C(9) + C(5))$
$9945 := C(9) + 9 \times 4^5$	$00157 := -C(7) + 5 \times 100$
$10125 := (10 - 1)^2 \times C(5)$	$01928 := 8 \times (C(C(2)) + C(9) - C(10))$
$16444 := C(16) \times 4 + C(4) - 4$	$45194 := -4 + C(9) \times (1 + C(5) - C(4))$
$30375 := C(30) + C(3 + 7 + 5)$	$99535 := 5 \times (C(C(3)) + C(5) + 99)$
$99873 := C(9) \times (9 + C(8)/(7 - 3))$	

First column values are in **digit's order** and the second column values are in **reverse order of digits**. In consecutive sequential values we have:

$$\begin{aligned}
 22950 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 0 = 0 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22951 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 1 = 1 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22952 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 2 = 2 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22953 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 3 = 3 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22954 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 4 = 4 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22955 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 5 = 5 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22956 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 6 = 6 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22957 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 7 = 7 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22958 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 8 = 8 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2))) \\
 22959 &:= (-2 + C(C(2))) \times 9 \times 5 + 9 = 9 + 5 \times 9 \times (-2 + C(C(2)))
 \end{aligned}$$

Remark 4.1. The notation $C(., .)$ in two variables represent **binomial coefficients**, while the $C(.)$ in single variable represent **cubic numbers**.

For more details refer author's work [30].

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